

FORWARD – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

WP2 _ Nine regional diagnoses and joint strategy for OR R&I ecosystem performance

Report _ Final version

Project Acronym	FORWARD
Project name	Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions
Grant agreement n°	824550
Project type	Coordination and Support action
Start date - End Date	01/01/2019 - 31/12/2021
Workpackage	WP2
Responsible partner	Nexa
Delivery date	2020/03/24

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550

Introduction

In a time of global competition, collaboration has become an imperative. Sharing resources and efforts, exchanging knowledge and know-how, foster capacities and distinctive innovations that allow organizations and territories to survive and thrive. For the 9 outermost regions (OR), connection is vital. Because of their limited size, they lack the critical mass of talents and resources crucial to build competitive advantages. This in turn hinders their capacity to attract the needed resources, which flow to, and concentrate in, a few well-endowed European hubs. To counteract this self-reinforcing, exclusion mechanism that affects their research, innovation, and economic dynamics, OR must tackle their relational isolation. They need to connect to the major European networks and hubs, which will increase their visibility, attractiveness and capacities.

In that respect, the framework programmes (FP) for research and innovation represent a major opportunity. Since the first edition in 1984, these funding instruments have been thought as levers to stimulate competitiveness and address the innovation gap between the European Union and the United States, through the coordination of dispersed national research and innovation efforts and resources-pooling (Breschi and al. 2003). Establishing transnational scientific networks was also seen as a way to accelerate the EU integration through the creation of an “internal market in research” (Makkonen et al. 2015) that would ease the diffusion of knowledge and stimulate spillovers through increased mobility and collaboration between research teams. This will was materialized in 2000 with the creation of the European Research Area which established a unified research system and encouraged the creation of strong transnational networks to address major challenges (Roediger et al. 2007), sustained by the FP. Throughout the years, the functions of the programmes were progressively extended to become the major planning instrument of the European Commission for research and innovation.

Considering their growing strategic and financial importance (from 3,8 billion euros for FP1 to 77 bn for Horizon 2020), framework programmes have given rise to a dynamic research field. These studies have underlined the force of cumulative advantages that result in the creation of dominant, “oligarchic” networks or clubs (Lepori et al. 2015) which concentrate most of the projects, and determined the main characteristics of (un)successful organizations, in terms of size, research orientation, scientific excellence...

Though the participation of lagging behind regions has been analyzed in depth (Makkonen et al. 2015; Pontikakis et al. 2018), Outermost regions remain a blind spot. Collective representations, reflected in the article 349 of the Treaty on European Union, point out the inherent, structural characteristics of these territories, that would inhibit the participation to collaborative, competitive, calls for projects: small ecosystems, with limited and fragmented research and innovation capacities; physical isolation and lack of integration in the networks; specific challenges and research topics, largely ignored by the calls for projects of the FP, etc.. Such determinist “handicap rhetoric” naturalizes the obstacles to H2020, homogenizes highly singular territories and neglects their ongoing realizations and exceptional potential.

The Forward project offers an opportunity to question these representations. What is the actual performance of Outermost Regions in terms of FP participation? How do they compare to other European Regions? Are they isolated from the networks that dominate the scene? Do the participation determinants identified by the literature apply to Outermost Regions? Do they face specific challenges? What are the similarities and differences between the outermost regions? How do they compare to each other in terms of organization and participation to FP? Do they share the same assets and weaknesses?

The lack of precise diagnostic is also a limit to the effectiveness of the policies implemented by regional and European authorities. In line with the ongoing discussions on Horizon Europe and future cohesion policies, Outermost regions need to identify the precise obstacles that limit their integration and the most adapted levers to support their ambition.

This collective ambition is not only defensive but proactive: transform their singularities, often reduced to constraints that ought to be minimized and neutralized, into strategic opportunities that can feed the development of competitive advantages and the prosperity of each region, but also benefit the E.U as a whole. Their exceptional physical, natural and sociocultural characteristics constitute major research fields and opportunities to connect to the rest of the world. Assessing the assets, consolidating the existing expertise and widening cooperation with both European and regional actors thus constitute an imperative to accelerate their transition toward a resilient and inclusive knowledge-economy.

To address these issues, WP2 was designed and implemented into four phases.

First, the development of a common methodology for the diagnosis of ORs performance, based on critical principles : a review of the literature on FP participation, the use of social sciences standards for the analysis, the drawing of conclusions and recommendations based on evidences and not only on perceptions, the comparison among OR and with other EU regions, the involvement of local quadruple helix to co-design regional action plan.

Delivered to partners at the beginning of month 4, the methodology is detailed in Section I of the present document.

In the second phase, each region performed its regional census and diagnosis. Under the responsibility of a regional delegate, each region started their regional census through data collection from online database (Cordis, H2020 dashboard, Eurostats, SCIMAGO institutions ranking, JRC ESIF viewer), database processed by Nexa (ECORDA, H2020 ranking, ETER, etc.), regional database and regional stakeholders' interviews. All the data were combined in two mapping tools ("RDI mapping" and "FP participation") and a performance dashboard ("Regional figures") by regional delegates. On this basis, each region first produced a state of play of its participation in FP. Then, they analyzed the contribution of the four main factors - networks connection, research and innovation ecosystem performance, organization's characteristics and individual capacities and motives - on their FP performance. From there, OR were invited to construct, involving their local community, a regional diagnosis that builds consensus among the community on the main evidence-based obstacles and then draw

impact-driven action plan with levers and solutions to effectively increase regional participation in FP.

Regional diagnosis drafted by each OR are detailed in the section "Regional diagnosis" of the document. The mapping tools and performance dashboards of all regions are available in Annex I. A quality report on the nine regional diagnoses is also included to this document, available in Annex II.

Third, to facilitate peer-learning processes among OR and increase knowledge about FP performance of other similar EU regions, Nexa conducted a comparative offering a global overview of the OR participation in FP, identifying the common and specific regional features, striking facts, successes and experiences and suggesting recommendations to allow regions to actualize their regional diagnoses.

Capitalizing on all the work done at this stage, the members of the steering committee organized a mutual learning event in order to (i) share knowledge and experiences accumulated during the production of the diagnoses, (ii) discuss and debate on the results of the comparative analysis and (iii) prepare orientations for the joint strategy for OR that will improve, promote and support their R&I ecosystem in the participation in the Framework programmes.

A mutual learning report was delivered during month 11 and a summary is available in Annex III of the present document.

Finally, a joint strategy was drawn to present common vision, mission and values for OR's to improve, promote and support their R&I ecosystem in the participation of the EU Framework programme. Following a co-creation process the strategy proposes orientations to improve activities which will be undertaken in WP3 (thematic working groups), WP4 (capacity building and training), WP5 (networking actions), WP6 (connecting research and policy making).

The joint strategy is detailed in the third section of this report.

Table of contents

A COMMON METHODOLOGY FOR OR ECOSYSTEMS DIAGNOSIS PART I

NINE REGIONAL DIAGNOSES PART II

JOINT STRATEGY PART III

ANNEXES PART IV

PART I
A COMMON METHODOLOGY FOR OR
ECOSYSTEMS DIAGNOSIS

Methodology guidelines table

INTRODUCTION	12
I - STATE OF PLAY OF PARTICIPATION	13
1) Data collection.....	13
2) Evolution of regional participation.....	14
3) Participation to the different programmes and funding schemes	14
4) Thematic distribution.....	15
5) Stakeholders mapping.....	15
6) Participation profile	16
7) Regional collaboration.....	16
II - ANALYSIS OF PARTICIPATION DETERMINANTS	17
A - NETWORK ANALYSIS	17
1) Global connectivity.....	18
2) Thematic connectivity	19
3) Relative position.....	19
4) Third countries participation	19
B - REGIONAL INNOVATION SYSTEM	20
1) Regional innovation system performance (Azores, Canary Islands and Madeira)	22
2) Regional innovation system performance (French OR).....	23
3) Regional research performance	23
4) Private sector implication.....	23
5) RIS3 priorities.....	24
6) Public policies.....	25
C - REGIONAL ORGANIZATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS	26
1) Review of higher education and research organizations' participation determinants	26
2) Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions	28
3) Analysis of institutional strategies.....	28
4) Analysis of Support Services.....	29
D - ANALYSIS OF PARTICIPATION DETERMINANTS AT INDIVIDUAL LEVEL	29
1) Patterns of success and failure.....	29
2) Analysis of self-selection determinants.....	30
III - COLLECTIVE CONSTRUCTION OF REGIONAL DIAGNOSIS AND ACTION PLAN	31
A - PRELIMINARY DIAGNOSIS	31
B - COLLECTIVE REPRESENTATIONS QUESTIONING (SURVEY)	31
C - PARTICIPATIVE APPROACH FOR DIAGNOSIS REFINING AND IDENTIFICATION OF OBSTACLES AND LEVERS TO H2020	32
D - REGIONAL DIAGNOSIS AND ACTIONS PLAN ELABORATION	36
METHODOLOGY TOOLS	37

Introduction

The proposed methodology was thought to be:

- Science based: during the proposal drafting and at the very beginning of the project, Nexa conducted a review of the scientific literature on participation in FP, research & Innovation eco-systems and public policies. Using this information, Nexa built a skeleton of the analysis based on four axes corresponding to the four main determinants : connection to major networks, regional innovation system structure and performance, regional organizations' characteristics, individual profiles and motives
- Progressive: partners were supported in the preparation and implementation of regional diagnosis with step by step guidelines, three excel tools, interview and workshop protocols, and information resources (detailed in the annex) as well as a continuous assistance by Nexa.
- Flexible: the level of analysis was adapted according to the resources mobilized by partners.
- Quantitative and qualitative: partners combined data analysis with interviews and workshops that strongly associated their regional community
- Factual and symbolic: partners collected and analyzed figures and facts, and at the same time question the mental representations of local stakeholders that play a major role in the development of regional innovation systems.
- Collective and individual: all regions applied the same approach and mobilized the same tools to analyze their systems. The templates and results were shared among regions through google drive and treated by Nexa to build a comparative analysis.
- Regionalized: each region was invited to designate a regional delegate and create a working group (WG) which brings together the different partners involved in the project. This group freely determined its organization, the specific roles of the different partners and its workplan, in compliance with the methodology and deadlines defined in the present guidelines. Each group designated a delegate who acted as interface between Nexa and the rest of the partners.

I - State of play of participation

The first objective of the WP2 is to describe the reality and diversity of Outermost Regions stakeholders' participation in the framework programmes: how does the participation evolve throughout the programs? What is the relative performance of each region compared to other OR and European regions? What are the most represented stakeholders and themes? What types of instruments do regional actors mobilize, etc.

1) Data collection

For this purpose, partners are first invited to collect data on FP7, H2020 and other E.U instruments proposals, projects and funding. The inclusion of FP7 is motivated by the necessity to constitute a larger sample and to decipher recent evolutions.

The data collected will be incorporated in a dedicated excel tool: [“FP participation”](#), and more specifically in the first two spreadsheets :

- [“FP-1 Projects table”](#) gathers general information on the projects: title, abstract, scientific domain, RIS3 priority, budget and consortium constitution, etc.
- [“FP-2 Other EU projects”](#) : compile information on regional involvement in other EU funding instrument

Following the workshop organized during the kick-off meeting, the option of an exhaustive mapping of proposals has been removed. The observation of submission activity is thus restricted to the global number of proposals.

To complete these tables, partners can mobilize the following databases:

- [CORDIS](#), the European Commission data base that compile the results of EU research and innovation framework programmes
- The [H2020 dashboard](#), that proposes an interactive consultation of data on H2020 projects
- ECORDA : this internal EU database compile proposals and evaluations. Though direct access and consultation is limited to the Commission staff members, national contact points and programme committee members can provide extractions of anonymized, non-sensible data.

They can also contact local research institutions; regional authorities and FP support offices that may provide useful information, especially on other EU instruments such as Life or Best.

The results of each analysis (2 to 8) will be indicated in a specific tool, designed the most essential regional data that will be used to establish the diagnostic and comparative analysis : [“Forward Regional Figures”](#). To ease the analysis, a specific spreadsheet [“RF-1 Participation data”](#) has been designed to centralize data for analyses on FP participation.

2) Evolution of regional participation

The data collected in step 1 will first be mobilized to assess the evolution of the regional participation in FP and compare to other European and Outermost regions.

To that end, partners are invited to complete the two first categories of the “[RF-1 Participation data](#)”: “Global performance” which presents general indicators and “EU Contribution” which measures the funding obtained by regional stakeholders and their relative weight in the GDP.

3) Participation to the different programmes and funding schemes

Observing the types of FP programmes and funding schemes mobilized by stakeholders give helpful insight on the nature of the activities implemented in the regions.

To map the use of the different FP instruments, partners can filter the data collected in the “[FP-1 FP Projects table](#)” by « Pillar of Specific Programmes of the FP » (P7) and “Funding scheme” (S7).

The total number of projects for each programme and funding scheme will then be indicated in the “[RF-1 Participation data](#)” spreadsheet. This information may be used to determine the distribution of the participation and underline the most frequently used instruments.

Besides FP, the EU offers support through instruments such as INTERREG Europe, Life, and dedicated agencies like EASME and COSME, that may intervene in the research and innovation fields of expertise of the OR (ex. biodiversity conservation, blue economy, marine spatial planning). Analyzing the regional mobilization of such competitive instruments will provide useful qualitative information on:

- the regional themes which benefits from an external recognition
- the regional stakeholders who may be in capacity to engage in FP projects
- partners and networks that may be mobilized to develop FP projects
- potential substitution effect vis à vis FP, whereby regional stakeholders would concentrate their efforts on sources of funding perceived as less competitive
- eventual specific blocking points, inherent to FP, identified by recurrent failures of individuals who mobilizes regularly these sources of funding

To determine the regional orientation toward FP and other funding, partners can :

- specify the relative share of the different funding instruments, including FP
- produce a ratio between H2020 and other EU competitive funding.

4) Thematic distribution

One of the key objectives of the Forward project is to evaluate the research and innovation assets and priorities of each region. Mapping the domains in which regional stakeholders successfully participate in FP provides an indication of the fields of expertise. It also facilitates the identification of common areas of interests between two or more outermost regions, which could be explored to increase cooperation.

To construct such thematic distribution, partners can filter the [FP-1 FP projects table](#) spreadsheet per scientific domain. For each of them, partners will be able to precise the number of participations and amount of funding collected; and to determine their respective share. The treated data will then be incorporated in the “[RF-1 Participation data](#)” “thematic analysis” section, to realize an overview of the most active domains.

The thematic distribution of FP participation can also contribute to the implementation and evaluation of the smart specialization strategy (RIS3), by comparing regional thematic priorities and the successful FP domains. The data collected in [FP-1 FP projects table](#) can also be sorted by RIS3 priorities to allow partners to list the different priorities active in H2020 and specify the share of H2020 active RIS3 priorities.

5) Stakeholders mapping

Determining the type of organizations active in H2020, and their relative importance in the regional participation, can reveal salient facts about the under or over-representation of certain categories of stakeholders which highlight specific strengths or weaknesses.

To that end, partners will filter the [FP-1 FP projects table](#) according to the “organization type” – higher education institution, private companies, public sector, research organizations, etc. These information will be compiled in the “Organization types” section of [RF-1 Participation data](#)”.

The distribution of participation is another useful item to measure the territorial mobilization around FP (for instance, a highly concentrated participation around a small number of very active stakeholders). To do so, partners are first invited to filter [FP-1 FP projects table](#) by the “name of the partner” and to determine the total number of participations of each organization, as well as their relative weight.

The figures for the top 3 organizations will then be included in the “[RF-1 Participation data](#)” “stakeholders mapping” section. Regions can also determine the share of 20% most successful organizations in the total number of participations, to evaluate the concentration of participation.

The same procedure will be repeated with individuals to fine-tune the analysis in the "Concentration of participation at individual level" sub-section.

6) Participation profile

Partners' role in FP projects can be used as an indicator of their relative influence in the networks they are part of.

To measure this participation, [FP-1 FP projects table](#) mentions the status of the organization in the consortium (FP-1.29) : coordinator, partner, third party... FP-1.30 indicates whether the organization acts as a Work Package (WP) leader or not.

This information can be filtered to determine the number and share of projects in which regional organizations acted as a coordinator and WP leader. Results will be reported in the [“RF-1 Participation data”](#) “Participation profile” section.

7) Regional collaboration

The Forward projects aims at reinforcing the collaboration among outermost regions as well as connections with neighboring countries.

To establish a diagnostic of the existing collaborations, regions are invited to extract from [FP-1 FP projects table](#) the projects which mobilize partners from another OR, and those who implicate neighboring third countries.

They can then determine the number and share of projects which include a partner from another OR or third country. Partners are also invited to indicate the top-3 outermost regions and countries with which they share the greatest number of projects. These data will be compiled in [“RF-1 Participation data”](#) "Regional collaboration" section.

Analysis of participation determinants

Besides quantifying and qualifying the participation of Outermost Regions in Framework Programmes, the Forward project aims at identifying the underlying factors that explain this situation. The workplan specifically mentions a mapping of the “*obstacles and challenges*”, especially in terms of connectivity deficit, which will be “*objectivized and prioritized in order to identify the most critical obstacles for each region as well as common barriers*”.

To identify such obstacles, we have conducted a preliminary literature review on the determinants to FP participation. These scientific publications conclude that the latter cannot be explained by scientific excellence alone, but rather results from complex, intertwined factors, which operate at four different levels:

- At the European level, strong cumulative mechanisms lead to the concentration of participation in a restricted number of operators and networks, and to the parallel exclusion of minor competitors. For instance, 152 of the 1300 European higher education institutions account for 70% of the financed projects; while 50% of these institutions remain excluded from H2020 (Lepori et al. 2014)
- At the regional level, the structure and performance of the research and innovation system as well as the policies conducted (incl. smart specialization strategy) strongly affect the capacity of stakeholders build capacities, reach critical masses and connect to these dominant networks
- The internal characteristics of candidate organizations – size, orientation, resources, past participation and strategy – also influence their capacity and will to engage and succeed in FP.
- At the individual level, the implication first depends on a preliminary decision to apply or not to the programmes, which may be induced by a lack of knowledge, confidence or interest. Applicant’s success is then influenced by their inner characteristics (experience, international connection, reputation, etc.) and strategy.

As mentioned in the introduction, no analysis of the determinants of Outermost regions’ stakeholders participation in the framework programmes has yet been undergone. The Forward project will thus contribute to this dynamic field of research, by testing the applicability of the identified factors in these territories and by a strong qualitative, field-approach that questions the organizations and individuals’ profile.

A - Network analysis

In a 2017 working paper, Simen G. Enger from the University of Oslo, points out the critical importance of “*persistent oligarchic networks that would appear to constitute clubs, closed to those less fortunate*”, which participate frequently in the FP and concentrate success. At the opposite end of the spectrum “*newcomers to European research, seeking funding*

without well-developed networks and with no prior experience, are likely to fail” (Enger 2017).

Considering the influence of networks, the integration of Outermost Regions or their relational isolation thus constitute a critical determinant to their participation. To that end, each region is invited to scrutinize:

- its absolute connectivity to the dominant networks, measured by the number of participations in FP
- the integration of regional stakeholders in the major thematic networks, that dominate the competition
- the relative position of regional stakeholders inside each network.

This analysis will be conducted with the help of five databases:

- [CORDIS](#)
- The H2020 organizations’ ranking list established by Nexa
- [Horizon 2020 dashboard](#)
- [SCIMAGO Institutions ranking](#)

Results will be compiled in the [“Forward Regional Figures](#), RF-2 Networks analysis section.

1) Global connectivity

The first objective is to determine the actual capacity of regional stakeholders to integrate the major “clubs” that dominate the FP scene, as well as the global position of the region.

On a regional scale, partners are invited to extract from the [FP-1 FP projects table](#) the list of all the European organizations implicated in the projects. They will then specify for each of these organizations their position in the H2020 participation ranking list. Thanks to these data, each region will be able to determine the average rank of its partners.

To deepen the analysis, we need to consider the “quality” of the most frequent partners. This could be determined by:

- Ranking the partner organizations according to the intensity of the relation with the region (measured by the number of common projects)
- Defining the top 10 partner organizations and their respective number of participation in H2020
- Identifying among this top 10, the number of partners with more than 50 projects;
- Repeating the same approach for institutions with more than 100 projects

2) Thematic connectivity

The same approach can be duplicated to assess the relative position of regional organizations vis à vis the great thematic networks: absence of connection, juxtaposition (connection via a common partner), integration. Being part of one these networks would attest the existence of a comparative advantage in the field. To conduct this analysis, each region will:

- Extract from the [FP-1 FP projects table](#) the scientific domains which present the higher number of H2020 participation, by filtering work programmes (H2020-A.17)
- Establish for each work programme the list of partner institutions
- Determine the average ranking of these partners and the average number of projects
- Check whether these partners belong to the top 10, 15, 20 participating institutions of the corresponding work programme in the H2020 dashboard

3) Relative position

The role of organizations in H2020 projects reflect to a certain extent their relative position in the networks ; acting as a coordinator attests from the capability of an organization to identify and bring together partners, who will recognize its influence and value proposition.

Using the analysis on “participation profile” conducted in the “state of play” (I.6), each region will identify the scientific domains or RIS3 priorities in which local organizations have coordinate one or more H2020 projects.

The same exercise can be repeated with the WP leader function.

4) Third countries participation

Analyzing the research and innovation relation between each outermost region and the major neighboring third countries can provide useful information on their capacity to connect and position themselves as recognized partners. To examine these collaborations, two sources of information can be used: the Interreg programmes (MAC; Caraïbes, Océan Indien) and the H2020 dashboard.

Each region is invited to compile a list of strong research and innovation content projects implemented with the help of their Interreg programmes in the spreadsheet “[RDI-11 Collaboration with TC](#)” of “[RDI mapping](#)”. This list can be established with the help of managing authorities.

In parallel, the [FP-1 FP projects table](#) allows regions to estimate number of projects which bring together partners from the two territories. By comparing this list with the H2020 dashboard maps, determine the share of projects that include partners from the OR in the total number of participation of the neighboring country. This analysis will give an insight on the level of integration of the two ecosystems and on the preferential orientations of third

countries. This approach can be replicated at the work programme scale to characterize the connections, determine fields of cooperation and identify potential partners.

B - Regional innovation system

The ability to connect to the institutions and networks that dominate the FP scene, is itself affected by the openness and performance of the regional innovation system. Local organizations are indeed grounded in a territory which influences their capacities, resources, reputation and strategies. The “innovation leader” regions determined by the Regional Innovation Scoreboard also appear to concentrate the most successful and influencing institutions in FP, while modest innovation regions remain modest recipients of FP funds (Amoroso et al. 2017). FP participation and performance of the regional system thus constitutes a feedback loop, where limited regional capabilities reduce the access to exterior resources, capacities and networks, that could feed the creation of a competitive advantage...

The analysis of each outermost regional innovation system will be carried out through 4 steps :

- a census of the components and relations that constitute the system
- an evaluation of its performance, through the recent years and in comparison to other European regions
- a specific focus on the priorities and value chains defined in the smart specialization strategy
- an outlook on research and innovation public policies, and potential synergies between structural funds and framework programmes.

Mapping the regional innovation system

The regional innovation systems approach aims at understanding the processes that determine the capacity of a territory to produce knowledge and turn it into new, successful solutions. The system can be defined as:

- *“all important economic, social, political, organizational, and other factors that influence the development, diffusion, and use of innovations”* (Edquist 1997)
- *“the network of institutions in the public and private sectors whose activities and interactions initiate, import, modify and diffuse new technologies »* (Freeman 1987)
- *“the landscape of research and technology-developing, innovation facilitating institutions, including their regulations”* (Kulhman. 2001)
- *“interacting knowledge exploration and exploitation subsystems linked to global, national and other regional innovation systems for commercializing new knowledge”* (Cooke, 2004)

Though diverse, these definitions insist on the necessity to adopt a global, complex approach that considers:

- the variety of local resources : natural, human, material, financial as well as symbolic (knowledge and know-how, representations, etc.)
- their usage and transformation by interdependent organizations that produce, diffuse and exploit knowledge : universities, research centers, intermediaries, economic stakeholders, users...
- how the relationship between these organizations give rise to social institutions, which in turns influence the representations and actions of stakeholders and the way they mobilize resources.

To understand how the system works, a census will be conducted on regional resources and organizations, according to the "[RDI mapping](#)" tool developed by Nexa. The data collected and incorporated into this tool will serve for analysis as well as to emphasize Outermost Regions research and innovation capacities and initiatives through the creation of a common web portal (WP8)

The first spreadsheet of the "[RDI mapping](#)" : [RDI-1 Regional Profile](#) gathers general information on the regional natural, human and economic resources. To complete it, partners can mobilize the [Eurostat](#) database, as well as regional databases managed by statistics offices, observatories and public bodies.

The second and third spreadsheets, [RDI-2 Research Cap](#) and [RDI-3 Research Cap](#), is dedicated to a comprehensive census of regional research capabilities, specified at the organization and research group levels. Such census will bring out the resources (workforce, infrastructures, equipment, etc.), scientific activities and collaborations. To gather this information, partners are invited to mobilize their regional community to draw a list of the research groups operating in each institution, and identify the person in charge who could help fill or confirm the needed data.

The fourth spreadsheet, [RDI-4 education](#) focuses on higher education training (Master and PhD). Like the census of research capabilities, data collection will be realized through the mobilization of regional higher education institutions.

The fifth spreadsheet [RDI-5 Innovation capabilities](#), compiles information on research and technology organizations (RTO), which act as an interface between knowledge producers and users: clusters, technology transfer centers, incubators and support services for innovators, maker spaces, etc. The identification of these stakeholders can rely on the participation of universities, chambers of commerce and public bodies or structural funds managing authorities. Each organization will bear the responsibility to fill a questionnaire, extracted from the spreadsheet.

The sixth spreadsheet, [RDI-6 Inn. Entrepreneurship](#), aims at illustrating significant entrepreneurial and social innovation projects. Considering the multiplicity of initiatives in each region, this census is by no means exhaustive; it is designed to illustrate the smart specialization priorities of the region. The identification of such projects can be done through

the mobilization of intermediaries with an extensive knowledge of the business sectors, for instance chambers of commerce, regional development / innovation agencies, clusters...

Finally, each region will select 5 flagship initiatives, based on their scientific excellence, their contribution to the regional development, etc. The related information will be compiled in [RDI-7 Flagship initiatives](#) and used to create the future web portal.

1) Regional innovation system performance (Azores, Canary Islands and Madeira)

To assess the performance of regional innovation systems and facilitate interregional comparisons, the European Union uses a Regional Innovation Scoreboard, adapted from the methodology and indicators designed by the OECD. This tool aggregates data on several domains which influence or reveal innovation capabilities, such as human resource, scientific excellence, openness, R&D expenditure, intellectual assets or economic impact.

These indicators have been compiled in the ["Forward Regional Figures" "RF-3 R.I. Scoreboard"](#) spreadsheet. To fill the template, partners can turn to Eurostat's [regional statistics portal](#) and [selection of regional data](#).

Raw data have been normalized by Eurostat to establish a 0 to 1 score. Through the consultation of the successive editions of the Regional Innovation Scoreboard (available on the Forward google drive), partners can also analyze the evolution of the different regional indicators from 2007 to 2017, to identify encouraging or alarming dynamics.

Each region will then be invited to compare the latest available indicators vis à vis other European regions. Thanks to the Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2017 database, each region can calculate the average score of their national-state homologues and other European regions. This approach will allow each region to identify the indicators that necessitate a specific attention to catch up and raise the performance of the regional innovation system.

Eurostat aggregates these data to calculate the "Regional Innovation Index", used to benchmark regions and define categories according to their performance ("leader, follower, moderate, modest"). Such index constitutes an opportunity to fine-tune the regional comparison through :

- the evaluation of the amount of H2020 funding obtained by regions which present a comparable regional innovation index, through the use of the ["synergy tool"](#) developed by the JRC during the Stairway to Excellence project. The ranking will help each region compare to others and identify similar rated regions which participate much more to Horizon 2020. These regions could provide useful study cases to understand the performance difference and the underlying mechanisms
- the evaluation of the average regional innovation index of regions which obtain close amount from their H2020 participation
- the identification of regions which present close innovation index and/or close participation results to determine their profile.

2) Regional innovation system performance (French OR)

Contrary to the Azores, Canary Islands and Madeira, the French Outermost Regions are considered by Eurostat a Nuts 3 unit. As a consequence, the data presented in the Regional Innovation Scoreboard remain aggregated in an irrelevant category “départements d’outre-mer” which prevents individualized analysis.

To determine if the pertinent information can be extracted for each region, Nexa will get in touch with the authors of the Regional Innovation Scoreboard, from the Maastricht Economic and Social Research Institute on Innovation and Technology – MERIT.

If the data were to be unavailable, Nexa would propose an individualized methodological support to calculate approximate value for the indicators listed in the scoreboard.

3) Regional research performance

Research institutions are a key component of RDI ecosystem. In H2020, they represent 54% of total participation and get 64% of the EU net contribution. To assess the performance of regional research system and allow inter-regional comparison a set of indicators has been designed and included in the ["Forward Regional Figures"](#) under the [RF-4 Research syst. analysis](#) spreadsheet.

Through the exploitation of the data collected in [RDI-2 Research Cap](#) and [RDI-3 Research Cap](#) spreadsheets of the “[RDI mapping](#)”, regional partners will:

- define their research system profile, expressed by the total number of higher education institutions, research organizations, research groups, and researchers ;
- evaluate the relative attractiveness of their research system through the share of foreign researchers active in the region
- determine the level of economic research outcomes through the number of spin off creations and international patents owned by research institutions
- analyze scientific excellence through the number of publications and international co-publications

4) Private sector implication

The implication of the business sector in research and development expenditures constitutes a major signal of the regional system performance (Pontikakis et al.2018). It illustrates the capacity of the latter to give rise to new innovative firms, transform existing business and mobilize private savings to develop risky activities, which attests a confident, future-oriented state of mind.

Examining the evolution of private R&D expenditures can thus provide useful information on the dynamics of the regional system. Portuguese and Spanish partners can compare the public and private R&D growth rates to underline the implication of private

stakeholders. French OR can mobilize data on the “credit d’impôt recherche” to estimate the recent tendencies.

5) RIS3 priorities

Since 2014, Outermost Regions have been designing and implementing their respective smart specialization strategy which aims at concentrating regional resources on a limited number of innovation priorities to reach a critical mass and build competitive advantage that will contribute to the transformation of the economy and the development of new, diversified sources of prosperity and jobs. In line with the coming 2020-2016 programming, some outermost regions are currently engaging the evaluation and evolution of their strategy. If the Forward project is not specifically dedicated to RIS3, studying the priorities previously defined presents a major interest to:

- map the fields of interest common to several outermost regions to detect potential cooperation opportunities and support the creation of interregional working groups and value chains (in line with the WP3 objectives)
- identify European regions which have selected close priorities to evaluate the competitive position of the outermost regions, learn from their experience and potentially establish new networks and partnerships, that could lead to new FP projects.
- scrutinize the resources, capabilities and realizations of each RIS3 priority and their performance in terms of FP participation to support the evaluation process.

To pursue this analysis, partners are invited to

- 1) Setup a working group with the people in charge of the implementation and monitoring system as well as RIS3 priority referents. This working group will capitalize on available information and collected data to complete the [“RDI-8 RIS3 priorities”](#) spreadsheet of the ["RDI mapping file"](#).
- 2) Actualize the mapping of regional stakeholders and value chains elaborated during the construction of the RIS3 with the help of the data collected in the previous task
- 3) Mobilize regional authorities and ERDF managing authorities to identify the instruments and funds dedicated to the priorities from 2014 to 2020.
- 4) Specify the number of FP projects in each RIS3 priority, with the help of the [FP-1 FP projects table](#)
- 5) Associate higher education and research institutions, RTO, clusters and chambers of commerce, to map realizations in each RIS3 priority: collaborative projects, publications, patents, RD services, etc. These indicators will be used to measure the intensity of the relations between regional stakeholders, which attests from the development of an “entrepreneurial discovery” process.

- 6) If available, specify the number of jobs in, and the turnover generated by each RIS3 priority. Such data will be used to evaluate their respective economic weight and impact.
- 7) Rank the priorities according to 3 criteria : the completeness of the value chain and the existence of critical mass of stakeholders (point 2), the intensity of relations (5) and possibly their contribution to economic development (point 6)
- 8) Determine among the top-ranked RIS3 priorities, the most active in terms of FP participation and well-connected to the major networks identified in II.A. This analysis will highlight regional competitive advantages.
- 9) Connect to the [Eyes@RIS3](#) tool developed by the JRC to identify regions that share the same priorities.

6) Public policies

The last field of analysis of the innovation system is dedicated to the public policies implemented to reinforce the regional capacity to produce knowledge and transform into innovations. The objectives are twofold: encourage mutual learning between outermost regions through a comprehensive overview of the orientations and instruments; and study the synergies between cohesion policy, sustained by European Structural and Investment Funds, and the participation in FP.

Though they face close conditions and challenges and are all engage in the smart specialization process, outermost regions have few occasions to exchange on their respective research and innovation policies. To facilitate interregional learning and comparisons, a specific template “[RDI-9 Existing Policies](#)” has been elaborated in [the RDI mapping file](#) to gather information on the objectives and actions engaged by regional authorities to develop their innovation system and reinforce the participation in H2020. Another template « [RDI-10 Existing tools](#) » from [the RDI mapping file](#) will map the intervention instruments for research and innovation in the ERDF programme 2014-2020. This document can be filled thanks to the “ESIF viewer” tool developed by the JRC <http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/esif-viewer>, and by the mobilization of the regional managing authority.

For Outermost regions, which benefit from the cohesion policy, synergy of funding is a matter of fundamental importance. This concept designates the strategic use and coordination of available funding sources to support the sustained development of the regional innovation system and maximize “the impact of public investment” (Elena Perez et al. 2014), for instance by mobilizing ERDF to support infrastructure and capacity building, international mobility and networking activities that will increase the chance of FP participation. To evaluate the actual synergies between ERDF and H2020 in each territory, we propose to apply the methodology developed by Pontikakis et al. in their 2018 JRC Technical Report : “*Mobilising European Structural Funds and Investment Funds and Horizon 2020 in support of innovation in less developed regions*” This method relies on 3 successive steps :

- 1) Determine the H2020 funding intensity, which measures the amount of H2020 funding obtained each year by regional stakeholders, divided by the number of inhabitants to neutralize the size factor
- 2) Specify the amount dedicated to research and innovation intervention instruments from 2014 to 2020 ; and determine the average amount per year and inhabitant
- 3) Divide the H2020 funding intensity by the ERDF funding intensity. According to Pontikakis and al., a more than 1 ratio demonstrates the existence of a leverage effect.

To complement this approach, we suggest partners to engage in a qualitative analysis of the use of ERDF with policy makers and managing authorities : are the instruments oriented toward H2020 participation? how does the synergy materialize ? how do they influence the strategies of regional stakeholders ? do they generate substitution effects through the availability of less competitive source of funding? (Enger et Castellacci. 2016)

C - Regional organizational characteristics

If the FP participation of outermost regions organizations may be influenced by network effects and the innovation system they evolve in, their very nature and characteristics can also be determinant. To evaluate the impact of the resources and strategies of institutions, we propose to conduct a fourfold analysis :

- Determine the local research and higher education institutions characteristics vis à vis the main influential factors identified by the literature on FP participation. This step will confirm or infirm the applicability of these factors in the region, and highlight organizational characteristics associated to (non) participation
- Evaluate the influence of higher education institutions' governance and strategy on the participation in FP
- Examine the profile of non-academic institutions, which constitute a notable share of the stakeholders involved in FP in outermost regions, to underline their motives, good practices and keys of the success.
- Analyse the impact of support services

1) Review of higher education and research organizations' participation determinants

According to the literature on FP participation, the inner characteristics of candidate organizations influence their chance of success, through 5 main determinants.

First, the size of the institution. According to a study realized in 2014 on the 1300 higher education institutions of the EU, participation to H2020 is proportional to the size of organization and those with less than 500 full time equivalent academic staff demonstrate a limited participation in the FP (Lepori et al. 2014). This size effect is linked to the necessity to reach a critical mass of researchers to develop excellent research. The concentration of talents

attracts exterior researchers eager to find a favorable environment to conduct their scientific activities and professional carriers. A large number of researchers also contribute to the diversification of scientific efforts and the integration of networks, that can reinforce the participation in FP. Finally, the economies of scale favor the creation of dedicated H2020 administrative support services that allow researchers to focus on their scientific activity and the development of proposals.

Secondly, the orientation : those which concentrate more resources to research show a higher rate of success than organizations which privilege teaching. This “research intensity” can be measured by the ratio between the number of PhD students and the number over undergraduates (Enger, 2017).

Thirdly, scientific excellence. Though many question the contribution of FP to the production of world-class scientific results, the scientific activity of an institution is of tremendous importance. Two indicators may be used to estimate this effort: the scientific productivity (measured by the number of publication per full time equivalent) and the impact (determined by the average number of publications’ citation). Due to the rising importance of bibliometrics, these factors now largely condition teams and institutions’ reputation. And reputation has been for long considered a strong determinant in FP participation : according to the “Matthew effect”, prestigious institutions are more likely to access to competitive funding which will, in return, increase their capacity to develop a sustained scientific activity and reputation, that will reinforce the chances of participation (Geuna, 1996). In FP, institutions which enjoy a good reputation present higher participation records thanks to their implication in networks.

Fourthly, the degree of international openness. More integrated units and institutions, which develop large-scale cooperations will also enjoy a greater participation rate. Openness can be estimated by the number of international co-publications, the share of foreign PhD or the number of foreign researchers.

Finally, prior participation. Because of the both collaborative and competitive nature of FP, newcomers face large entry costs that reduce the probability of success; contrary to regular players who benefit from learning effects. To enter the most competitive networks, newcomers shall demonstrate an outstanding value proposition to convince coordinators to retain their candidature over well known, less risky potential partners. The second effect stems from the administrative complexity of FP project development and management, which can dissuade new comers who will support the costs with little perspective of success. Access to resources and FP are interdependent: over the years and participations, institutions develop capacities and accumulate resources which contribute to their competitive advantage, reputation and capacity to integrate the most competitive networks. At the opposite end of the spectrum, weakly endowed institutions face difficulty to participate to FP and risk to find themselves locked in a negative spiral of cumulative disadvantages: the lack of projects deprives them of the material and social resources that could have supported the development of their capacity and reputation...

2) Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions

According to the article 349 of the Treaty on European Union, outermost regions suffer from two structural handicaps that hinder their competitiveness: small size and isolation. Such handicaps are in line with the factors identified by the literature. It thus appears relevant to determine whether regional higher education and research institutions present characteristic that could negatively impact their participation.

To that end, the template [RDI-2 Research cap \(1\)](#) of the [RDI mapping](#) encapsulates the determinants found in the literature and described before. To fill this document, partners can mobilize data produced by the research institutions themselves (notably for their monitoring and evaluation process), national organisms or ministry (for instance the Observatoire des Sciences et des Technologies in France) and consult European database like [ETER](#) and [SCIMAGO](#)

The collected data will help underline the salient facts about these institutions : their size, orientation, internationalization and scientific excellence. These characteristics will be put in line with their performance in FP measured by the submission rate, number of financed project, success rate as well as their rank in terms of H2020 participation. To feed the diagnosis, partners can also investigate the implication of these institutions in other EU competitive funding. Finally, with the help of the CORDIS and ETER databases, they will be able to determine the profile and characteristics of institutions which present close participation results in FP.

3) Analysis of institutional strategies

This section aims first of all at questioning the governance of research institutions, and in particular the interest in Horizon 2020: what is the program's place in the organisation strategy? Have specific objectives been defined in relation to FP programmes participation?...

A comparative analysis between participating and non-participating research institutions will reveal notable characteristics, such as a deliberate and strategic choice to orient the organisation toward other research funding schemes.

On the other hand, the CORDIS analysis reveals the relatively strong weight in outermost regions of other participating structures such as public bodies, agencies or "SMEs". Analysing these organisations' internal policy is a topic of interest to understand the drivers that led them to engage in FP programmes and the benefits they derive from this activity and collect good practices that could inspire other organizations.

To carry out these analyses, partners will conduct interviews with governance representatives of the targeted organizations (specific Interview protocols are provided in Annexes 1 and 2). To allow for meaningful analysis, it is important that partners interview a maximum of the targeted organisations.

4) Analysis of Support Services

The existence of dedicated FP support services providing assistance to local stakeholders in the building, management and reporting of projects is an asset to increase regional participation in FP programmes. It reduces the entry costs to Horizon 2020 and allows participants to focus on scientific aspects of the proposal development cycle. It also reflects local stakeholder's commitment to increase participation to FP and thus strengthen the integration of their region in the European Research Area.

To support mutual learning within the Forward consortium, the "[FP-7 Support Services](#)" template, in [FP Participation](#) aims at describing the service supports in place in the regions (objectives, activities and services, achievements and results). In order to fill out this template, partners can contact regional support services representatives. Beyond the description, partners are invited to question FP facilitators about difficulties revealed in their daily practice alongside project leaders and collect good practices.

D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

Most studies on FP participation focus on network, systemic or organizational determinants and privileges quantitative analysis based on large databases like CORDIS and ECORDA. Yet, the sum of individuals' profiles and strategies can exercise a major influence on the regional performance taken as a whole. Taking advantage of the small size of OR innovation systems, Forward thus proposes to investigate the factors that influence individual researcher's implication and success, through 2 qualitative, interview-based, analyses. The first will point out the regularities and common traits found within highly successful individuals and the characteristics of unsuccessful candidates, to hypothesize patterns of success and failure. The second one will be dedicated to the self-selection phenomenon "*whereby either very weak participants, or very strong ones, who can tap on alternative funding sources*", *choose not to participate*" (Pontikakis et al. 2018).

1) Patterns of success and failure

Partners are first invited to constitute two groups of scientific and technical leaders of FP proposals:

- Participant Group, composed of the maximum number of regional participants to FP programmes (ideally all)
- Candidate Group, composed of a large panel of unsuccessful H2020 candidates representing at least 5% of their RDI community, with a minimum of 10 regional participants.

The members of each group will then be interviewed (specific interview protocols are provided in annexes 3 & 4) to identify potential common traits among them, related to their profiles in terms of scientific activity, international mobility, knowledge of the FP... The most common traits of each group members will then be tested on the other group members to highlight discriminating factors.

The partners are invited to collect the elements resulting from these interviews in the template [FP-4 Keys to success](#) and [FP-5 Failure factors](#) from FP Participation file.

2) Analysis of self-selection determinants

If the literature regularly addresses the self-selection issue at the organizational level, the Forward project represents a unique opportunity to question the phenomenon at the individual level. To that end, partners are expected to constitute a panel of FP non-applying researchers representing at least 5% of their global R&I community, and a minimum of 10 individuals.

Partners will then conduct interview (a protocol is provided in annex 5) to identify the determinants of self-selection, along four types of causes :

- the lack of knowledge on the opportunities offered by FP
- the perception of one's own abilities
- the lack of interest for a programme
- the lack of resources and support

Partners are invited to input the elements resulting from these interviews in the template [FP-3 Self-Selection Determinants](#) from the FP Participation file.

Collective construction of regional diagnosis and action plan

Through the previous stages of the methodology, partners have acquired in-depth knowledge of regional actors' participation in FP and a broad and precise understanding of strengths and weaknesses impacting the participation.

The challenge is now to aggregate results and salient facts of the analysis in order to build a territorial diagnosis and to involve regional stakeholders to question their representations about the regional participation to FP Programmes, in particular, their perceptions of determinant factors explaining the relative performance.

These elements will allow each region to collectively build a territorial action plan to remove obstacles to H2020 and increase FP participation.

A - Preliminary diagnosis

To share and refine the results of the work carried out at part 1 and 2, partners from the working group will gather in order to produce a preliminary diagnosis. This report will depict the state of the regional participation and highlight the explanatory factors of the performance.

This document, along with the completed mapping tools will be uploaded on the Forward Google Drive shared space (> FORWARD > WP2 > Ressources and data bases for WP2) for transmission to Nexa. (For calendar deadlines, please refer to Annex 11)

B - Collective representations questioning (survey)

OR R&I community members often depict FP programmes as too complicated, competitive and unsuited to local situations and realities. These prejudices generate a lack of ambition and involvement. Though poorly studied and often underestimated, beliefs and fears constitute powerful obstacles to H2020 access; overcoming them can be energy and time consuming, particularly when building participative territorial actions plan.

Therefore, the involvement of a large and diverse panel of members of the R&I community through survey represents the opportunity to map and assess representations on FP participation and explanatory factors. Such survey will test a potential gap between the collective representations and the facts characterized in the analysis.

To that end, partners will first determine the type and number of actors to be questioned, according to their community characteristics (diversity and size). To ensure significant participation and generate significant results, partners have to elaborate an efficient dissemination and stakeholder's involvement strategy. The diffusion of the surveys also represents an opportunity to promote the Forward project within the regional community and therefore should be developed in accordance with the WP8 communication strategy

The survey will be common to all regions to allow the comparison of collective representations and highlight regional similarities and differences.

Once the surveys are completed, partners will produce a synthesis which presents the overall analysis of the survey and its main outcomes, in particular widespread beliefs and convictions. These representations will be put in relation with the data and facts identified during parts I and II, through the production of a dedicated table. This table will emphasize the congruence or, on the contrary, the divergence between the collective representations and the factual elements. For example :

"90% of the respondents think that OR's organizations cannot participate in FP Programmes // Our University participates in X projects."

C - Participative approach for diagnosis refining and identification of obstacles and levers to H2020

Mobilising a broad panel of the regional stakeholders in a participative setting is essential to objectivize hypotheses, adopt new ambitions, develop strategies and prioritize actions to increase participation to H2020.

To that end, partners are invited to conduct one or several workshops using collective intelligence tools. The number of workshops depends on the number of factors and obstacles to be addressed. In terms of methodology, the workshops will follow a 3 step approach - share of the diagnosis - identification of major obstacles - definition of levers - by using the problem/solution tree logical framework. This tool helps find solutions by mapping out the anatomy of cause and effect of an issue.

1) Using problem and solution trees :

When organised in a way that alternates large/small group work sessions, the logical framework based on Problem/solution trees allows to benefit from the collective intelligence of a large number of people while giving to each participant the opportunity to express his/her point of view.

This analysis technique relies on 2 participative tools: problem and solution trees.

The problem tree maps the causes and effects of a specific issue, allowing a more accurate description and in-depth analysis of the problem and a better understanding of its consequences.

It is based on a tree-like image where :

- the main problem is written on the tree's trunk
- the roots symbolises the causes and sub-causes
- the branches symbolizes the effects or consequences

Once completed, the problem tree represents a summary picture of the existing situation. It can be pre-filled by workshops' organizers in order to facilitate the diagnosis. It can also be completed during a collective session, where participants depict causes and effects on post-it notes, in a cause-and-effect logic. *The heart of the exercise is the discussion, debate and dialogue that is generated as factors are arranged and re-arranged, often forming subdividing roots and branches (like a Mind map). [It is important to] take time to allow people to explain their feelings and reasoning, and record related ideas and points that come up on separate flip chart paper under titles such as solutions, concerns and decisions¹.*

The solutions tree transforms negative situations identified in the problem tree into solutions and actions to tackle the challenges identified. A similar picture is used with :

- in the center : the priority replacing the central problem
- above : strategic orientations replacing effects
- below : strategic objectives and operational actions replacing causes

¹ <https://www.odi.org/resources/docs/6461.pdf>

2) Organisation of workshops

Getting ready for the workshop

To guarantee the success of the workshops, partners in charge of the organisation must be well prepared. They are invited to read carefully the following guidelines and the detailed annex 6 on workshops' protocol. They can also find more information about organizing workshops and leading creative meetings thanks to the following link: <https://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents>. French-speaking partners can refer to [Nexa collective intelligence toolbox](#).

a) Preparing workshops tools

Partners will first elaborate a presentation of the preliminary regional diagnosis and the surveys' results. This presentation includes a comparison between salient facts analysed in part 1 and 2 (on FP participation and determinants) and representations identified through the surveys. This presentation will be shared with participants at the very beginning of the workshops.

Partners will then extract elements from this diagnosis to pre-fill a set of problem trees, selecting major issues/central problems that need to be treated during the workshops.

Partners also prepare printed versions of all the elements.

b) Selecting and recruiting participants

In order to have sufficient number of participants and a broad panel of profiles, characterizing the R&I community, Partners invite between 15 to 25 participants, ideally according to the following distribution:

PROFIL		Number	%
Researchers	a. Successful participants in H2020	3	30%
	b. Not successful participants in H2020	3	
	c. Not participating to H2020 (when we believe they could)	3	
Representatives of Research and innovation organisations governance	a. Research institutions representatives	3	25%
	b. Innovation support organization	3	
Institutions financing research and innovation	a. Regional authority representatives in charge of Research and Innovation	2	15%
	b. State representatives in the region in charge of Research and Innovation	2	
Private Companies	a. Companies participating to H2020	2	15%
	b. Companies not participating in H2020 (when we believe they could)	2	
Support structures	a. European offices/Department, supporting proposal writing of H2020 projects	2	15%
		25	100%

c) Conducting the workshops

A detailed agenda to prepare and conduct the workshops is provided in annex 10

3) Production of workshops' deliverables

To ensure to capitalize on all the qualitative data produced by R&I stakeholders, partners are in charge of producing the following deliverables, compiled in a report :

- workshops' datasheets (date, list of organizing partners, list of participants, ...)
- a regional diagnosis expanded and refined by the participants
- refined problem trees and complete solution trees
- a list of orientation and ideas for actions plan to increase FP participation

These deliverables are shared with Nexa (Please refer to annex 11 for deadlines).

D - Regional diagnosis and actions plan elaboration

Based on the preliminary diagnosis and on the workshops' report, partners will produce the final version of their regional diagnosis and draw a territorial strategic plan to increase regional participation to FP Programme.

The strategic plan includes detailed actions with general and specific objectives, organizations in charge, targets, indicators of implementation and results, timeline (using the template provided later)

These documents are transmitted to Nexa in order to elaborate the inter-regional analysis and to prepare the mutual learning event. (Please refer to annex 11 for deadlines).

METHODOLOGY TOOLS

CALENDAR AND DELIVERABLES

Deadlines	Deliverables
31 st of March 2019	Final methodology approved by the partners
15th of April	Names and contact's details of the regional delegate and the members of the working group
31 st of May 2019	All partners deliver the results of top-down analysis composed of the preliminary diagnosis and the completed mapping tools to Nexa
30 ^{s^t} of June 2019	All partners deliver Report on workshops
31 nd of July 2019	All partners deliver the Final regional diagnosis and strategic plan
10 th of September 2019	Nexa delivers the Comparative regional analyses to all partner
24 th , 25 th , 26 th of September 2019	Mutual Learning Event co-animated by FRCT and Nexa, preparing the joint strategy
31 st of October 2019	FRCT delivers the Joint-Strategy for OR R&I Ecosystems performance to all partners

EXCEL TOOLS

1. RDI Mapping
2. FP Participation
3. Regional Figures

TABLE OF ANNEXES

- Annex 1: Interviews Protocol _ Research organisation Strategies
- Annex 2: Interviews Protocol _ Other participating organisations
- Annex 3: Interviews Protocol _ Keys to Success
- Annex 4: Interviews Protocol _ Failor Factors
- Annex 5: Interviews Protocol _ Self-Selection determinants
- Annex 6: Workshops Protocol
- Annex 7: Problem-Solution tree Poster
- Annex 8: Template for the preliminary diagnosis*
- Annex 9: Template for reports on surveys and workshops*
- Annex 10: Template for the Regional Diagnosis and strategic plan*
- Annex 11: Calendar deadlines

PART II

NINE REGIONAL DIAGNOSES

REGIONAL DIAGNOSES TABLE

The present section contains the nine regional diagnosis reports in the alphabetical order: Azores, Canary islands, French Guiana, Guadeloupe, La Réunion, Madeira, Martinique, Mayotte and Saint Martin.

To respect WP2 deadlines, each region had to provide, by November 29th, four completed documents:

- three excel files (FP participation; RDI Mapping; Regional figures)
- one regional report covering the different sections described in the methodology.

On December 11th, the SC validated the integration, into deliverable 2.2, of 5 diagnoses which complied to the objectives of WP2. Four regions were asked to complete their analysis: Guadeloupe, Guyane, Mayotte and St Martin. The 4 regions were to deliver the actualized diagnoses by January 30th and all of the documents were finally received on March 13th.

The SC took the decision to integrate the 9 regional diagnoses in the DEL 2.2 received independently from the quality at the only restrictive condition that it is written in English. A report presenting the completeness of the analysis with respect to the methodology is presented in Annex II.

Azores

Governo dos Açores

FORWARD – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems:

Azores

21/11/2019 (RV)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

under grant agreement No 824550

Title of the document	FORWARD, Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems: Azores
Information of the WP	WP2. Task 2.1
Partner responsible	FRCT
Author	Lina Silveira, Luz Paramio, Gisela Nascimento
Collaborative partners	UAc; CCIA; NEXA
Co-authors	Célia Amaral (UAc); Eduardo Braga (CCIA); Phillippe Holstein (NEXA); Evelyne Tarnus (NEXA)
Version	2.0

The information included in this report do not bind the collaborated entities or any other entity that had contributed to its realization.

SUMMARY

This document is the Executive Summary of the Azores Regional Diagnosis and Strategic Plan that occurred under the WP2 Diagnostics of OR's R&I ecosystems from "FORWARD project – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions" (GA N° 824550/952727405). The management team of the Azores Regional Fund for Science and Technology (FRCT) produced this report with the supervision of NEXA (WP2 leader) following the FORWARD WP2 work plan. The WP2 works started on the third month of the project (M3 - March 2019) with the Task2.2 on Mapping of OR's R&I ecosystem and are foreseen to finish with a co-creation of the Joint strategy for ORs R&I ecosystem performance (in M10 - October 2019).

The Regional Diagnosis is the culmination of the work developed during the WP2 which includes three excel tools, namely, Framework Program participation (FP participation); Research, Development and Innovation Mapping (RDI Mapping) and FORWARD Regional Figures. These three tables gathered R&I information from the region participation in European financed programs (FP7; H2020 and other financed projects) including all the interconnected data regarding the Research and Innovation Regional Ecosystem (RIRE) in order to highlight the explanatory factors of performance in the Azores.

This process of analysis covered three stages:

1. **State of play of participation** - based in data collection - quantitative and qualitative data - namely regarding the evolution of regional participation in FP and other European financed projects in R&I;
2. **Analysis of participation determinants** - crossing information and go in to more details regarding the Network analysis; Regional innovation system; Regional organizational characteristics; Analysis of participation determinants at individual level – this implied the conduction of in-person interviews. At this stage we do comparative analysis between participating and non-participating research institutions through Interviews with researchers, public representatives/organizations and private sector representatives with relevance in the R&I Azorean ecosystem;
3. **Collective construction of regional diagnosis and action plan** - a comprehensive connection of data that allowed us to interpret the collected information, and on the other hand promoted a

direct contact with the R&I key players in the region, through participative actions, namely using surveys and a workshop for a bottom up regional analysis.

This completed mapping allowed Azores Region to have a clear landscape of the current conditions regarding the R&I regional ecosystem as the capabilities, profile, network, areas of research, and opportunities. This WP created the opportunity to identify and connect local stakeholders of the R&I. This approach included interviews, surveys and a workshop opening the discussion of ideas, exchange of experiences and needs and understanding expectations regarding the R&I financing program, as H2020 framework and projects is reaching its end and a future regional strategy for Horizon Europe is needed. These inputs provide useful information to FORWARD consortium to advance with more robust and realistic strategies for the regional R&I ecosystem. The direct contact with the local stakeholders gives better conditions to design an action plan that reflects the reality of the regional stakeholders and may contribute in a more realistic way to the promotion and empowerment of the R&I ecosystem of the Azores and ultimately the OR's.

The implementation of these tools of mapping have strengthened the conversation and open new horizons regarding the vision of what the R&I ecosystem can become, defining a new background for the future Horizon Europe. From the exchanges that took place between regional stakeholders, in the context of the activities of the WP2, several ideas have arisen, as well as a strong joint conscience of what are the present conditions, as well as opportunities. Ideas/needs that as the creation of a Regional Contact Point, a regional database that can work as an interface, as the creation of B2B tools, between regional and international stakeholders, has been pointed out as levers from promoting the Azorean participation in framework projects, as well as promoting the capacity building, network and internationalization of the R&I ecosystem. As also, the idea/need to create a public support organization that can help with the identification and the elaboration of proposals, in order to promote the increase of successful applications to FP projects and calls.

The WP2 implementation in the region has help to set common goals and reach common innovative proposals that were born from an awareness of who is part of the R&I ecosystem network, and how we can collaborate, as an added value of a cooperation at a multilevel and multisector level. The small ecosystem can work in favor of the region, since it facilitates the implementation of measures and reach agreements. This was also one of the conclusions of the stakeholders during the participation of the initiatives on the WP2 context. A positive and

constructive perspective that can use our added value of a resilient living lab to strengthen the R&I ecosystem.

This analysis bears in mind the need to have a regional strategy and a strong alignment with all sectors involved at the knowledge value chain, in order to promote the participation and contribute to a more competitive OR's ecosystem, using to the fullest the opportunities that are foreseen to arise in the future framework program Horizon Europe, in 2021. By combining the regional mapping and diagnose of the 9 OR's we will able to create a joint strategy for the OR's to address common challenges and showcase the opportunities that they can offer to the European and international R&I ecosystem. The OR's can demonstrate the added value of their competitive advantage in the context of the EU and contribute to shape the future of the EU regional R&I ecosystem.

The conclusions and recommendations presented in the Azores Regional Diagnosis result from the integration of the work from the three partners (FRCT, UAC; CCIA) and the consultation of the regional quadruple helix: public, private and academic stakeholder's by an interactive process.

INTRODUCTION

The Azores Regional participation in the projects under the 7th Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development, from 2007 to 2013, register's 11 programs participation and growing positively in to the following Framework Programme, from 2014 to 2020, Horizon 2020 with a participation in 28 projects. Despite this very positive increase of the Azores region participation in the framework programs there is still a long way to go forward when we compare the regional participation with the national context, (1% of the total participation – table 3).

The diagnose reveled the lack and/or the dispersion of information regarding the framework programs, therefore the main challenge was to find and gather up to date information's on projects, especially on budgeted allocated per region/organization. Also some of the information's were very difficult to access, demanding almost a search one by one and extensive Grant Agreements reading. It was also difficult to access some Grant Agreements in order to compile the demanded information. The goal on this phase, having in to mind raising the capacity to access more financed projects, is to be able to continue to follow up on the information, regarding the R&I ecosystem and it's interaction with funded projects. Information as projects applied, areas of interest, skills needed to produce a successful project or manage are essential to apply the proper policies and put in to place the needed tools. This shows the need to focus the regional information in a Regional Contact Point, in order to collect, treat and make it available to all interested in the OR's and EU R&I ecosystem and specially for putting in to place adjusted incentives and target politics adapted to the regional reality.

The analysis process revealed a lack of alignment between the quadruple helices' in the ecosystem of investigation and innovation. This was the main problem highlighted by the replies in the survey, interviews and confirmed by the participants of the workshop conducted in the region with the R&I stakeholders. This shows the need to create measures to promote a more fruitful connection between the four helices of the R&I ecosystem. This can be attained through several measures that ultimately promotes a more effective link and understanding of the different stakeholders of the R&I ecosystem, namely their capacities, needs and goals. One measure that can tackle this challenge can be the creation of a platform, either formal or informal, that offers the regional stakeholders of the R&I ecosystem a context to exchange and develop project ideas, as well as keeping them on the loop regarding the new market trends. Also measure's that help regional

stakeholders, especially from the private sector, to be aware of the regional research capabilities, promoting their collaboration. The low number of private companies, at a regional level, that participate in FP projects reveals the need of a better approach in order to show the advantages for the private companies to participate in H2020 programs. This may also reveal a lack of capacity building linked to a lack of knowledge regarding the available calls that may be of their interest.

Therefore it was identified the need to concentrate and disseminate in a more effective, broader and accessible way the political incentives and programs available to support innovative projects, as well as available financed projects, and access to trainings. A capacity building plan should be put in to place to address the needs of skills to tackle the low level of successful applications, and applications in general, in the region (table 5). This plan should start with FORWARD but be a strategy that live beyond that project life time, as medium, long term plan, to target specific sectors of the R&I ecosystem and provide training on specific needs and skills that were identified during the diagnoses. A plan that include capacities and training from the “roots” (what is H2020 and who is it for; communication and networking skills; who is how in the European Union: institutions) to specialized trainings (how to write a successful application for H2020; how to build a consortium). This plan should take in to account different levels of needs, but having as a target a common level of knowledge to “equip” the entire regional R&I ecosystem, at the level of human resources, initiatives, policies, tools, infrastructures, etc. This strategy could contribute to leverage of the all ecosystem of Innovation and Research regionally, involving the quadruple helix, with special incidence to the society. Having as successful examples in this regard the Macaronighth event.

The local action plan should take in to account the reality of a disperse territory, since the geographical reality of the Azores presents a bigger challenge to reach all stakeholders, as an archipelagos with nine islands. This is a condition that Azores has always to take in to account when designing and implementing an action plan and define strategies to comply with this reality. One of the solutions can be using digital solutions, promoting online meetings, using social media and other digital platforms available. The use of digital and innovative platform for training, networking and engaging can work as bridges to overcome the physical constrains inherent to Azores permanent conditions, at regional level, but also nationally, between OR's, at EU level and internationally.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology followed was based in a transversal, per peer, co-creation type, that allowed a better connection and alignment with the intervenient of the R&I ecosystem in the region, taking in to account that the region has a small ecosystem, this was used in our favor, as it allowed a better and deeper approach to the ecosystem.

The methodology of the WP2 mapping of the R&I in the Azores was approached regarding 3 levels:

1. Identify challenges and present conditions;
2. Analyse future opportunities at a multilevel and multisectorial level;
3. Define an action plan for the Azorean R&I ecosystem for future FP, in order to create a common OR's strategy and vision.

Regionally we started by setting up a Regional Working Groups that gathered the regional partners of the project (FRCT;CCIA;UAc) in order co-create and align the work procedures, namely to define a common methodology, share the tasks and set deadlines. The work was divided mainly in two categories:

- 1) Search, gather and interpret data;

Collect and insert qualitative and quantitative information in the tables and create connections in order to interpret the data;

- 2) Consult directly the R&I regional stakeholders.

Launch an online survey, conduct in person interviews and organize a workshop regionally, with representatives of the R&I ecosystem. This close contact with regional R&I stakeholder's, trough different actions allowed to mobilize, promote, exchange ideas and diagnose challenges. This conscience of the state of play allowed us to have a better view of the needs and levers of the ecosystem in order to find adjusted solutions, develop strategies and prioritize actions. This actions was also a first opportunity to raise awareness regarding the H2020 opportunities to the R&I ecosystem. A first step that contributes to the goal of the project, to increasing the Azorean participation in the framework programs.

Regional working groups

The regional Working Group (WG) was an organization suggested by the WPL and in the Azores included the 3 regional partners that integrate the FORWARD consortium: Regional Fund for Science and Technology, as group leader, the University of the Azores and the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Azores, as delegates

As a first step, FRCT designed a work plan, dividing the work load of the WP2 within partners, in alignment with the plan set by the WP2 leader, NEXA, from Reunion Island. This plan was sent by FRCT for approval to the regional delegates that gave their inputs and finalized in coordination with FRCT resulted in an approved final common work plan. The overall goal was to divide the work taking in to account each organization target public, therefore the University was in charge of collection and analysis of all the information targeting the research and high education sector and the CCIA was in charge of the collection and analysis of the data related to the regional private sector. The results of CCIA and UAc collection were sent to the WG leader, as the responsible to gather the data in to one single document that represents the result of the regional analysis.

The WG organized several in-person and online meetings between the regional delegates, and sent as well regular emails following the development of the work and to share the point of situation, questions and challenges regarding the collection and analysis of the data. The FRCT project manager was always available by email, skype and phone for any question regarding the development of the work or any additional questions, working as an interface with the WPL. The FRCT remained in constant contact with NEXA, as the WP2L, conducting online meetings and keeping in contact by email, skype and google drive for exchanging and sharing of documents.

Tables

FRCT, as the regional leader, started to send a regional timetable to the Azorean partners with distribution of WP2 works, with the definition of the different stages of the tables sent by the WPL. This tables were completed under the orientations of the WP2 guidelines that helped to better understand the kind of work required, the sources and the objectives in each stage, clear deadlines and protocol.

To obtain these information's we had to combine several sources, from internal available information in our organizations, to public data available in public websites and through our IP. This was also made in several levels, from the regional level, through the government organizations data, to other organizations, as SREA – Regional statistics from the Azores and IDIA- Investigação, Desenvolvimento e Inovação in the Azores, to national data centers, as PORDATA (Base de Dados Portugal Contemporâneo) and reaching out to the National Contact Point, as well as European sources, such as CORDIS, ECORDA and EUROSTAT. Only by combining information from this several levels, we managed to construct a table with the most information possible.

The collection of the data for the tables regarding the projects in R&I in Azores, was conducted accordingly to WP2 guidelines and collected by FRCT in one single document in order to comply with the following objectives:

- 1) Establish a state of play of the Azorean participation in FP, through the analysis of available data;
- 2) Explore the main factors that can give an accurate image of the regional innovation system structure and performance, regional organizations' characteristics, in order to analyze the participation determinants and collectively construct a regional diagnosis and elaborate an action plan.

The methodology applied to the WP2 work, regarding the tables, was:

- Collect relevant data, from regional, national and international sources (governmental bodies, regional partners). As the National Contact Point, CORDIS; IDIA-SG (Investigação, Desenvolvimento e Inovação Açores -Sistema Gestão); INE (National Institute for Statistics); SREA (Serviço Regional de Estatística dos Açores);
- Engage in direct contact with stakeholders through in person interviews, conducted by the regional partners (FRCT; UAc and CCIA) - to the private; public and academic sectors in the region – based on a common list agreed between the regional delegates;
- Launch an open survey with questions directed to the regional stakeholders that are part of the R&I ecosystem through the platforms from the delegates and the partners of the delegates;

- Gather relevant stakeholders of the R&I ecosystem in a single Workshop – this created an opportunity for the regional partners of FORWARD project to present the preliminary results of the WP2 work to the interested stakeholder's. This was also an opportunity for stakeholder's to discuss, in a transversal, multilevel, and multisector way, the common challenges and opportunities identified by the data and the survey.

The key words that constitute a back bone of the methodology applied regionally for the WP2 works are:

Alignment: develop the work engaging the WPL, the regional delegates and the key representatives of the R&I ecosystem in the Azores, as an overall collection of information in a homogeny way, with continuous communication;

Flexible: the data, quantitative and qualitative, was not all accessible; therefore, the level of analysis had to be adapted according to the resources, despite the coordinated efforts of the regional delegation and the WPL;

Regionalized, collective and individual: the same approach was implemented, by defining from the beginning the type of approach that was expected, and mobilize in a coordinated way the regional entities, as well as the needed tools to obtain data. The templates and results were shared frequently between regional partners and the WPL for a combination of collective and individual analysis of the data and always taking in to account our regional reality and limitations.

Survey

Regarding the survey, the adjustment, translation, online publication and management of the platform was under FRCT responsibility, as WG leader, with the regional delegate's participation. The regional partners of the project used their sources, namely partner organizations, to disseminate the survey link to the stakeholder's from the regional R&I ecosystem. For example, it was published on FRCT website, sent out on CCIA's newsletter to their partners and were disseminated through UAC's research centers directors. FRCT managed the income of the information and adjust it to the intended propose.

It was a challenge to engage participants in this activity - despite the efforts from the regional partners from FORWARD and our associated partners. Therefore, we only had 38 replies from a

period of one month, from M6 to M7. The profile of the 38 participants is the following: 30% researchers, 27, 8% public officers; 19,4% representatives from the private sector (11,1% managers of a private companies and 8,3% workers from private companies).

The explanation regarding the lack of participation can only be explained in theoretical hypotheses: either the fail was on the side of the organizers, maybe the platforms to reach the R&I ecosystem was not clear or persuasive enough to pass the purpose of their participation. Another explanation can be on the side of the ecosystem players, explained by their lack of interest in this kind of tool or it can't be explained on the side of the stakeholders, by the feeling of being *over consulted* on European projects - due to Azores being a small ecosystem it is usually the same organizations/people that are solicited to participate in this kind of initiatives contributing to the lack of motivation in this kind of consultation in which they do not foresee any direct, immediate result.

Regarding the results obtained, the stakeholders that participated in the survey revealed the needs and impressions, as well as the widespread beliefs and convictions, regarding the framework projects. This allowed us to evaluate their knowledge of the regional ecosystem and its global context and compare it with the factual data.

The reply to the question regarding knowledge/perception of the level of Horizon 2020 programs that included Azores as partners (as beneficiary; coordinators) revealed a low level of knowledge regarding the H2020 in the region. Less than half of the replies (47%) indicated the answer that correspond to reality – that the region is engaged in the range of 10 to 50 H2020 projects. We even had 8% of participants replying that they believed that Azores do not participate in H2020 programs.

Despite the less positive vision from the survey repliers on the Azores participation in H2020 projects in general, when we change the element of comparison, with other European regions, the perception changes. According to the answers given by the participants in the survey, the perception/knowledge regarding the Azores participation in H2020 projects, compared to the average of European Outermost Regions (OR), is that it's "in the average" (39%), "high" (24%), "very high" (5%). With a total of 68% replies (gathering the percentage of the 3 replies mentioned before) pointed to a very positive image regarding the Azores in the context of other OR's.

Regarding the determinant factor of the participation of the Azores in the framework programs on Research & Innovation, the “Connection with successful H2020 networks” and “Using other FP as a leverage to build capacities to access H2020 programs” are mentioned as the most influential determinants by the majority of the replies.

The survey also revealed that the private sector is still not recognized as an equal partner in terms of importance in the promotion of the Azorean R&I ecosystem, since the “Private investment in the R&I sector” was classified as “somehow influent” or “does not influence” by the majority of the repliers. This reveals that there is still work to be done to show the advantages to engage the private sector in the R&I ecosystem in the region as a key step for the promotion of the ecosystem as an all. Regarding this matter, the “Scientific excellence” and the “Dimension of the regional organizations” were mentioned as influent factors for the Research & Innovation ecosystem in the Azores to participate in framework programs. This showcases the importance that is given to the promotion of science but also reveals the conscience and limitations felt by the small/limited size of regional organizations, as a downside that affects the participation of the Azorean organizations in FP program.

Interviews

Regarding the in-person interviews the responsibility for conducting this stage of the work were distributed by the regional delegates that integrate the WG (CCIA; UAc; FRCT), taking in to account the target audience required by each table (FP3; FP4;FP5;FP6;FP7), and to be compiled by the regional leader - FRCT. The interviews guideline sent by the WPL (NEXA) were followed and the questions were translated, adapted to Portuguese language, and distributed as a form, in table format, to the regional delegates for final updates.

The FRCT created a preliminary list with proposed names of regional stakeholders representatives of the regional R&I ecosystem, with a minimum number of participants by areas to be target by each delegate. FRCT submitted for approval the list of the regional delegates. Each regional delegate worked this list of representatives to be interviewed and sent to the regional group leader for final inputs that resulted in to a common approved list. After these stages of confirmation and adjustment's the model passed by a test period within the regional partners organization. After this trial period the delegates started the interviews to the partners identified in the common list.

The results of the interviews were sent to the FORWARD manager in FRCT that compiled the information in to one single file.

Workshop

The Workshop was designed in order to include representatives from the four helices of the R&I from the regional ecosystem, as a micro-representation of the regional ecosystem. The list of participants was created in partnership with all the regional delegates, in order to select and integrate all the relevant stakeholders. The Workshop gathered 25 participants and gave inputs on how to build a regional action plan for the regional R&I. A bottom up process, from contacting the intervenient of the ecosystem and confronting them with the compiled data from the surveys and in-person interviews. The profile of the group was the following; from these 25 participants we had 8 participants from Research organizations & Universities, 6 participants in representation of the Private sector and 11 participants from Public organizations.

The workshop occurred on the 24.06.2019, in São Miguel Island, in Ponta Delgada city. The methodology followed within the groups was to choose a secretary (to take notes) and a facilitator (moderate and summarize ideas) per group. All the facilitators had the same memo. The presentation of the results was presented to the group by all the participants of the group by turns.

Problem Tree exercise

The organizers started by presenting the preliminary results to the overall group and formed 4 subgroups (mixing the private; public and researchers) and a printed Problem tree, completed, to

The Problem Tree table was completed with information that resulted from the answers obtained on the survey and in-person interviews that took place between May and June 2019. The compilation and selection of the information was made by the regional delegates of the project (CCIA; UAc and FRCT), by mutual agreement during an in person meeting.

The central problem that was identified was: “Lack of strategic alignment of the quadruple helix of the innovation and research ecosystem” - with the reference to causes and effects that surrounded this problematic identified by the regional stakeholders on the surveys and interviews.

each group. The group composition was selected previously, based on the enrolled list of participants, in order to include representatives from different sectors.

Figure1 – Problem Tree used during workshop in Azores for the R&I stakeholders

The group had as a first task to discuss within their group the Problem Tree and suggest alternatives, in case they have any comments or disagreed with the identified problem, as well as the causes and effects mentioned. The four sub-groups all agreed with the identified problem and the overall tree construction presented, as a conclusion of the survey and interviews, previously conducted.

Solution Tree exercise

After analyzing the Problem Tree it was given to each group a blank table for the creation of a Solution Tree, in order to each group define a goal, as well as identify the leverage and the associated impact surrounding this identified goal. The identified goal was “A capacity strategy to involve the quadruple helix” – this goal was decided by mutual agreement between the 4 groups, after their individual presentation. It was combined in to one exercise the several reflections done in the 4 sub-groups. As leverage it was highlighted the training and capacity building on H2020, networking and knowlage transfer activities, public suport services for applications, a better engagment of the private sector with research, promotion of innovation culture, etc. As impact from this leverage actions with the goal in to mind, it was pointed questions related to credibility, increase the available data, promote the H2020 application, internationalization actions, etc.

Figure 2 – Solution Tree used during workshop in Azores for the R&I stakeholders

Actions Plan

Based on these first two reflections done with the two tools given by the WPL – the Problem Tree and The Solution Tree – the groups had two other tasks. Turn this first analysis if the problem and solution and turn it in to a SWOT analysis, were they analyzed the Strengths, the Weakness, of the “Opportunities and Treats of the Azorean R&I ecosystem in the H2020 program-framework”.

As strengths, the participants identified: the endogenous resources – living labs; the geographical position; political autonomy; university in the region – with several competences and international attractiveness; new generation of more qualified human resources; small dimension of the R&I ecosystem – allows better links and network.

As opportunities in the Azores it was pointed the emerging new areas: energy; biodiversity; sustainability; tourism; the Azores geostrategic position in the EU and OR's – Atlantic bridge; the new framework programs with more attention to OR's – budget allocated to R&I; the politics on Smart specialization – RIS3; the Forward project – OR's network; the access to differentiated markets – Third countries.

As weaknesses, the participants highlighted the lack of alignment of the R&I – no cooperation culture; no capacitation and training activities in H2020 in the region; private sector is conservative - not very open to innovation & research – with limited dimension; limited RIS3; territorial fragmentation – 9 islands; missing the support to apply and manage projects – no information or specialized human resources in organizations.

Finally, as treats it was pointed the EU competition/Globalization, the Brexit consequences to the EU budget; the different characteristics and maturity of the R&I ecosystem in OR's – jeopardize the strength of our alignment; Potential (damaging) competition between OR's future framework program opportunities; Dependency on transports – outermost position; Projects with no impact – affects credibility.

These SWOT analysis served to transform the subsequent analysis in to actions and the group constructed an action plan that will be explained in more detail head in this analysis. However this was the process, the methodology created to do a step by step creation of conscience regarding the reality and analyzing all the different angles for a complete action plan.

Communication

In terms of communication, the FRCT created an image for the event and the detailed program, based on the Guidelines of WP2. The invitations, with program, for the event were sent out to a defined list of participants and the confirmations were managed by FRCT. The regional partners (UAc and CCIA) worked with FRCT in the dissemination and communication of the event, in the

network media (email, facebook; linked in; twitter, etc) and the media (journalists). This helped to create awareness regarding the importance of the project and the event. The FRCT also had the human resources support from CCA and UAc during the workshop, helping with the registration and material distribution and managing the work of the groups.

I State of play of participation

The first objective of the WP2 is to describe the reality and diversity of the Outermost Regions R&I ecosystem namely through the participation in the framework programs, therefore and for the sake of comparison and evolution the analyzed is made not only based on information regarding the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation but all the data that can illustrate and explain the research and innovation ecosystem in the Azores.

It was gathered information regarding the number of framework programs that the Azores has participated, from FP7 to H2020, to other information regarding the characteristics, performance and implication of other direct and indirect factors related to the R&I ecosystem. Also the testimonial of the key actors of the R&I ecosystem in the region granted us a most complete information to put in to place a plan with a target, clear and focused actions having as a main the goal the promotion of the region participation, with success, in funded projects, specifically on the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

Regarding other EU financed projects that Azores participate and that contributes to the Research and Innovation in the region, we have reunited information on 82 EU financed projects that are/were implemented in the region. It was taken in to account projects since 2013 to the present year, from INTERREG projects to LIFE projects. The main challenge regarding the collection of these information's was to access more detailed information, namely regarding the distribution of the budgeted.

The obstacles that were encountered, during the process of data collection, just reinforced the idea that we need to have more/better regional data that concentrates all the information regarding regional projects. These information's could support more informed political decisions in order to obtain a greater efficiency in the use of EU funding but also to keep track on the possible stakeholders and areas of interest and trends that are immerging in the R&I ecosystem. This can be essential to track the regional trends, identify potential partners for future consortium's and cross information's regarding work developed or being developed in certain scientific areas of interest. This knowledge can contribute to improve our competitiveness and alignment at a regional, national and global level. Due to the geographical reality of the Azores, as an archipelagos, composed with 9 islands, really requires to put in place a adjusted plan in order to

potentiate regional synergies. This synergies can help to put in to place the implementation the actions adjusted to the reality of the FP participation landscape and extend the life of the projects, in terms of results and legacy, beyond its financing period, contributing to the potentiation of their results.

1) Evolution of regional participation identified

From 2007 to 2013, on the context of PF7 the Azores registered 11 participations in projects, that had a bugged for the region of 41 288 680 euros. From the framework project (FP) of FP7 ((2007-2013) to the H2020 (2014-2020) there was a positive evolution, since that in the context of the H2020 Azores increased their participation from 11 projects to 28 projects, that is translated in to a 147 938 331 euros for the Azores until now, and there is still one year to go to close the FP. The Azorean H2020 per capita per year is 148 and the competitive funds are 5,45 €, a number that taking the OR's in to account is quite good, however we should analyze the numbers having as a reference the national (see figure) reality as well as European. At a European level, *vis à vis* NUTS 2 regions, Azores is at number 148 in a rank of a total of 274 NUTS 2 regions. Despite this very positive increase of participation of the Azores region in the FP there is still a long way to go FORWARD when we compare the regional participation with the national context, (1% of the total participation – figure 3), as well as it's added value in the context of the R&I ecosystem.

Figure 3 – H2020 programs distribution per region in Portugal (data from NCP)

2) Participation in the different programmes and funding schemes

If we analyze the EU financed projects in the region in the area of R&I we realize that the H2020 is still behind INTERREGGE projects that in total have 108 projects (counting with the 2nd call of Interreg MAC 2014-2020) compared to the 28 ongoing H2020 projects. Just the Interreg Mac projects surpass the H2020 by 75 projects.

Figure 4 – H2020 vs other EU financed programs (in FP2 table)

This difference in numbers may have to do with the success rate and not only the number of submitted projects, since in total we have 121 submitted projects with just 28 successfully approved, that means we only manage to have a 21% success rate. At a national level the success rate is around 15% (data from National Contact Point¹), since the number of proposals is much higher, as in Excellence in science that has a total number of submissions (according to data from the National Contact Point from 2014 to 2018) of 3663 submissions.

¹ https://www.gppq.fct.pt/h2020/participacao_pt.php

Although the level of success in Azores low comparing to the EU level (of almost 30% - National contact point data), it's in a good position at a national level. Less summited projects however better success rates. This can reflect the high capacity that Azores can still explore and develop in order to increase its approval rate. The high level of competition requires a better level of support, a need reinforced, by the key players of the R&I ecosystem that participated in the surveys, interviews and also in the workshop in the region.

Global Success Rate of H2020 in Azores

Figure 5 – Global Success rate of H2020 in Azores – comparison between approved and non-approved projects.

3) Thematic distribution

Regarding the analysis of FP7 and H2020 framework programs participation, the conclusion reach is that the larger number of FP7 programs in the region are under the Cooperation pillar, as the H2020 programs in Azores are under Pillar III, Societal Challenges. Both FP7 and H2020 have more projects under the scientific domains analysis of LS8-Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Biology, with 5 and 7 projects respectively. In H2020 these represents 33% of the total projects, with an amount of EU contribution from this scientific domain of 1981 365,00 euros, that represents 38% of the total of the EU contribution for the total of EU H2020 bugged to the region. The second most represented scientific domain is PE10 – Earth System Science, with 23% of share of total contribution for the scientific domain areas in H2020 for Azores (6 projects), although that in terms of EU budged it only represents 14,6% in the scientific domain.

In third place, the most represented scientific domain is SG3- The Social World, Diversity, Population, with 5 projects in H2020, that corresponds to 19% of the scientific domains representation in the total of H2020 projects in the region, and it corresponds to 11% (605 662,00 euros) of the total budget for H2020 in Azores.

Figure 6 – Scientific areas distribution: H2020 vs other EU financed projects in R&I areas

The participation in INTERREG programs (Europe; Atlantic; MAC) overcomes largely the number of H2020 programs, with 66 INTERREG programs approved. In terms of scientific area, the other projects are mainly in the scientific area defined as LS8 - Evolutionary, Population and Environmental Biology. This is also the scientific area with more projects on H2020 programs, with 29 projects dedicated to Evolutionary, Population and Environmental Biology that corresponds to 35% of all the other programs list. The second scientific area with more projects, with 13 in total, is the SH2 - Institutions, Values, Beliefs and Behavior. This area includes sociology, social anthropology, political science, law, and communication, social studies of science and technology projects. With projects as the SIMPLIMAC dedicated to improve public efficiency through administrative simplification or PI ESPECIAL that implement an interactive platforms for special education. This may show the importance of linking the implementation of projects with cohesion policies, taking in to account the social reality of the Outermost regions, namely the goal to

promote the creation of jobs, promote social inclusion and address the current macroeconomic imbalance and the external deficit.

4) Stakeholders mapping (type of stakeholders)

The organization with the most FP projects in the Seventh European Framework Programme for Research and technological development (2007-2013) was University of the Azores, with 55% of the projects successfully approved in Azores, followed by EDA, the electricity company of the Azores, with private-public managing. In the Horizon 2020, the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020), that reality changed and FRCT became the organization with more FP projects, with 45% of the projects, in the Azores, changing the lead from academia to a public organization. And in second place IMAR, as a research organization, with 32% of the projects. Azores University dropped its participation in the H2020 projects to 14%. Azores, accordingly to the analyses of WP2, have participation on H2020 is concentrated on a limited number of stakeholders. This may be a result of the lack of information and limited access to information regarding H2020 to the R&I ecosystem.

The role Azores have, as region, in the framework program is mainly as partner, although having the lead on Work Packages on most FP projects. Azores took the lead mainly in projects that are related to the Sea and Fisheries, as NetBiome-CSA (H2020), Move, Mystic Sea's and MarSP. Despite Azores have a lower rate of coordination role in H2020 project that does not repeat itself in other financed projects in the area of research and innovation. This may come across as lack of confidence or capacity of taking the lead in the network context in FP, since it's not clearly lack of capacity either experience, especially in the cases of institutions that have a concentration of projects, as IMAR, FRCT and UAc. This concentration on a limited number of stakeholders can be a source of vulnerability, if such institutions face a crisis or suddenly changes its policy. Therefore it's important to promote and empower other organizations trough training, capacitation and promoting the H2020 advantages for innovation to widespread the participation by regional stakeholders.

In the analysis of the FP2 table (other projects) is possible to find a wider range of stakeholders, taking part I to projects, as representatives of higher education and research centers, such as IAMA, Fundação Gaspar Furtuoso, etc, to private sector, with Fundo de Maneio and Boa Fruta, to public services as Regional Directory for Energy, or the Regional Direction for European Affairs.

When we look into organizations outside the national sphere, regarding type of organization that participate with the Azores in FP projects we can realize that most of our network is composed of Research Organizations (224 REC - FP-1 table) and High education establishments (191 HES - FP-1 table).

Figure 7. Foreign organizations, outside Portugal, that are involved in FP projects with Azores

5) International connections and network

The top ten organizations that are involved in FP projects with the Azores are *The Natural Environment Research Council*, from United Kingdom, with 8 projects in total, followed by a Greek organization in the area of marine research with 7 projects. In third place in the ranking there are 2 other organizations, involved in 6 other projects, one from Netherlands, in the area of Sea, another a University from Norway. There are also 5 other organizations with that are in 5 other projects, from countries as Spain, France, for example and finally there are 5 other organizations with 4 FP projects with Azorean partners, from France, Norway, UK, Netherlands and Italy. This shows a great variety of nationality and organizations, which also demonstrates that we do not focus on certain organizations and countries, namely OR's.

Figure 8. Network: Ranking of top organizations involved in FP projects with Azores

Another analysis was the level of influence that this top 10 organizations have in the H2020 network. By analyzing the amount of projects that these organizations are involved we realize that at least 7 out of the 14 that are included in the top 10 (since there are in the top 10 organizations that have the same amount of project numbers with Azores, therefore they are 14), so 50%, have between 80 to 478 projects. And 4 of them, 29%, have more than 100 projects. So big players that can open up other opportunities and can contribute to the development of capacities and exchange of good practice due to their large experience in H2020.

RANKING	PARTNERS ON H2020 PROJECTS WITH THE AZORES	NUMBER OF PROJECTS	NATIONALITY
*1	Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)	81	United Kingdom
2	Universitetet i Bergen	105	Norway
3	Universite Pierre et Marie curie - paris 6	89	France
5	United Kingdom Research and Innovation	231	United Kingdom
6	Wageningen University	152	Netherlands
7	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	478	Italy

Table 1. Network: Ranking of top organizations involved with Azores in H2020 projects (2014-2019).

Another comparison was at the level of ¹MAC, a new program INTERREG V-A Spain-Portugal MAC Cooperation Programme (Madeira-Azores-Canarias). This is important to highlight since it involves strategic neighboring countries, namely two OR's, Madeira and Canary Islands and the neighboring countries, concentrated in Africa, as Cape Verde (Portuguese speaking), Senegal and Mauritania.

INTERREG V-A Spain-Portugal MAC Cooperation Programme - Azores				
Framework	Call	Number projects	Projects with Third countries	Participation rate of third countries
2007-2013	1st CALL	23	0	0%
2007-2013	2nd CALL	0	0	0%
2007-2013	3rd CALL	0	0	0%
2014-2020	1st CALL	32	23	72%
2014-2020	2nd CALL	42	36	86%
	TOTAL	97	59	61%

Table 2. Network: Ranking percentage of Third countries involved with Azores in Interreg Mac projects (from 2007 to 2020)

Only from 20014 on the participation of the Azores is visible and the relation with third countries have intensified in the last years, especially with Cape Verde that is present in every project (23 project with 23 Cape Verde participation; 36 projects with 36 participation). A valuable partners, especially because the official language is also Portuguese and because it's also an archipelago, as Açores, being an equivalent territory to share projects and experiences at a geographical, environmental and social level.

¹ <http://www.mac-interreg.org/> On 3 June 2015, the European Commission approved the new INTERREG V-A España-Portugal MAC Cooperation Programme (Madeira-Azores-Canarias) 2014-2020 with a budget of EUR 130 million (85% financed by the European Regional Development Fund-ERDF). On 17 October 2017, the EC approved an increase in the programme's funding, with a total budget of almost EUR 149 million (126'5 million ERDF).

INTERREG V-A Spain-Portugal MAC Cooperation Programme - Azores					
FP	CALL	NUMBER PROJECTS AZORES AND THIRD COUNTRIES	Cape Verde	Senegal	Mauritania
2007-2013	1. ^a CALL	0	0	0	0
2007-2013	2. ^a CALL	0	0	0	0
2007-2013	3. ^a CALL	0	0	0	0
2014-2020	1. ^a CALL	23	23	8	7
2014-2020	2. ^a CALL	36	36	14	9
	TOTAL	59	59	22	16

Table 2. Network analysis of the Third countries involved with Azores in Interreg Mac projects (from 2007 to 2020)

6) Regional collaboration (with other Outermost Regions & Third Countries)

Another conclusion that we can reach by analyzing the involvement of OR's in framework programs is that more than one OR's in FP7 project is still low, registering 27% of projects, and only 21% of more than one OR's per project in H2020 projects. This may mean that from one framework program to the following the OR's have lowered their successful number of approved projects that included more than one OR.

Figure 9. Network: Top 10 nationalities from organizations that are involved with the Azores in FP projects.

The analysis revealed that partners that are in the projects we are involved in, H2020 and others, do not reflected the advantage of our geostrategic position, neither our connection with OR'S.

In other hand the Interreg MAC in this regard is the main tool of third countries interaction at EU financed projects that Azores use in order to promote the privileged relations with Macaronesia countries. This may be explained by the specific projects in this regard and lower competitive required, as well as the better structured network in this geographical context.

We have a total of 726 foreign organizations that participated with Azores in FP projects. By analyzing these organizations nationality and intensity of participation we conclude that the 10 top nationalities of the organizations, outside the national sphere, that participate in the framework projects with Azores as partners are the Italy, with 76 organizations participating with Azores, followed by United Kingdom, with 71 organizations and Germany, with 59 organizations in total. Also we can highlight that the only third country in the top 10 is Norway, with an expressive number of 32 organizations, largely ahead of our fellow member state Greece (23) and Belgium (27), for example.

II Analysis of participation determinants

A- Network analysis

1 Global network

Analyzing the global network we have looked in to the size of the stakeholders in framework projects, with focus on the partners with 100 or more projects, so we could have an idea of the reach and experience of the project partners engaged with the Azores. We conclude that the Azores has 8 organization's that are partners between 50 to 100 FP projects. These 8 organizations have in average 5 projects with the Azores.

Figure 10. Network analysis: organizations with more than 50 projects that are in H2020 projects with the Azores

The network of partners that Azores is involved in FP participation only includes 3 partners with more than 100 projects. These 3 partners are organizations with focus on science and research: as *Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC)*, from Spain; the *UK Research*

and Innovation, a British organization that works in partnership with universities, research organizations, businesses, charities, and government; and thirdly Universitetet i Bergen, a Norway internationally recognized research University.

However Azores only includes 8 relatively experienced organizations relations in our H2020 projects (with more than 50 projects), those major partners are important to access major networks and other partners and be included in future projects.

Another matter to analyze regarding the network is thematic in which our partners are engaged in and their preponderance and experience in projects in this thematic areas in H2020 projects. By analyzing the thematic that these partners are involved and the number of partner by thematic we can acknowledge the reach of these thematic that we are involved in, as the larger the number of partners per thematic stronger the network in that are. On this regards the thematic related to are the **Physical science and engineering (PE1;P9;P10)**¹ is the one that concentrate the larger amount of partners on H2020 with Azores, followed by **Life sciences (LS7; LS8)**². In third place, the smallest amount of partners, are concentrated in Social science and humanities³.

Figure 11 on Organization with projects with Azores and their number of projects, as well as total number of organizations per thematic (area-discipline in footnote)

¹ PE1: Mathematical foundations; PE9: Universe sciences; PE10: Earth system science

² LS7: Diagnostic tools, therapies and public health; LS8: Evolutionary, population and environmental biology

³ SH3: Environment and society; SH4: The Human Mind and its complexity; SH5: Cultures and cultural production

Larger the amount of partner that are integrated in a thematic the stronger the network, therefore the thematic of physical science and engineering is the one with a larger network available through projects that Azores is already engaged in.

1 Third countries participation

In terms of Third countries participation we still do not see reflected the full use of the advantages of the geostrategic positioning of the Azores and other advantages that involve the CPLP countries or the countries in which we have stronger connections due to our diaspora. By counting, the number of organizations from third countries included in the consortium that we are a part of Norwegian (27 projects) and Switzerland (12) are leading the rank. Countries, to whom we have favored relations compared to other European regions, as United States of America and Canada (with an extensive and influent Azorean diaspora) only are accounted for 6 and 7 projects, respectively. A low number compared to the leading countries and also to other third countries that are quite in ahead, as Iceland with 14 projects (mainly in the area of energy) and Turkey with 10 projects.

Other countries as Cabo Verde, with the same official language and similar geographical conditions (being an archipelago) we only account two projects in H2020. We integrate also projects with strong third countries in the international sphere, as China, Russia and South Africa, but one in one project for each.

B - Regional innovation system

2 Mapping the regional innovation system

As it was mentioned in the Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2012, “Innovation is a key factor determining productivity growth. Understanding the sources and patterns of innovative activity in the economy is fundamental to develop better policies.” In Azores the data related to regional innovation performance, namely in research and private sector is still little and not easy to compile, since it’s disperse and not always available.

3 Regional innovation system performance

The information available to properly build a Regional Innovation Mapping was scarce, nevertheless, we found several enterprises that had participated in some programs and some started some level of innovation. The gathered information revealed the Azores as being far from the mainland's percentage of participation on FP projects. This unwillingness of businesses to participate was explained, during the workshop session organized in Azores, by the R&I stakeholders, as being easier and faster to apply for a regional programs.

With the information (forecasted) available for 2019 the R&D expenditures in the private sector as percentage of GDP is 0,02, and the same expenditures in the public sector the percentage of GDP is 0,27. The public sector investment for this year is higher, reflecting the difference between public and private sectors participation in FP projects. Also in 2019, the EPO patent applications per billion GDP* value is 1.28, which may be considered a good indicator compared with the most developed region of Portugal (Lisbon 1.59). To reinforce the difference between the two regions and also to validate the previous information as a good indicator, the European Trademark applications per billion GDP* value for Azores is, also for 2019, 1.26 and Lisbon has 6.83

	"2011" - score relative to EU 2011	"2017" - score relative to EU 2011	"2017" - score relative to EU 2017	Performance group
Norte	79,1	81,7	79,6	Moderate +
Algarve	63,5	54,9	53,5	Moderate -
Centro	84,2	87,2	85,0	Moderate +
Lisboa	98,2	90,6	88,2	Moderate +
Alentejo	70,0	70,2	68,4	Moderate
RA Açores	53,4	54,2	52,9	Moderate -
RA Madeira	55,2	56,4	55,0	Moderate -

Fonte: Regional Innovation Scoreboard, 2017.

Table 3. Position of the Portuguese regions in the Regional Innovation Scoreboard

The position of the Azores in the Regional innovation scoreboard is in the bottom at a national level. A disadvantaged position, even below the RA Madeira, fellow Outermost Region. Being qualified as "- moderate", less then moderated performer in the national overall score.

4 Regional Research Performance

There are 12 research groups in University of the Azores, the only high education institution in the region, since 2015 to the present year. In terms of regional research performance little is to say in

terms of data fluctuation, since the numbers have been quite stable since 2015 to 2019 (the available data that we have accessed through UAc), presenting the same number of PhD students, with average number of 15 doctoral graduates per year. As it has the same average number of foreign post docs (3) during the same period.

Regarding the number of scientific publications (indexed within Elsevier's scopes on all field), has dropped slightly in 2018, from 225 in the year 2017 to 210 publications in the year of 2018. In 2019 we just accounted 70 publications to the moment. From the total of publications a percentage of 49% are from co-publications with national partners and 62% are from co-publications with international partners (including partners from EU countries). From these international co-publications, almost half are from European partners (49%). These may point us to the fact that the University of the Azores has a good international network that may be a good network to promote to foster financed projects and that could empower the region capacity to reach international networks and key partners internationally for key project. A potentiality that possibly is not being used to its full potentiality, since this do not reflect on the number of FP that the UAc is currently included.

5 Private sector implication

The R&D expenditure in the business sector as percentage of GDP is 0,02, despite this information, we lack information to do a more thorough. We do not have information's regarding the non-R&D innovation expenditures of SMEs as percentage of total turnover and we have scarce information regarding innovation activities in SME and impacts, namely in employment. The implication of the private sector in the R&I is not measurable at the moment due to little information available. Nevertheless it's important to stress that this information is fundamental to better understand the added value in R&I in the private sector, as it was mentioned in the Solution Tree (as a leverage) during the workshop organized in the region, as a conclusion, by the R&I stakeholder's. The analysis of the PO in relation to the Azores concluded that there is a weak articulation of the companies with the actors of the scientific and technological system which does not potentiates an environment of innovation and development of new products, processes and services. Therefore, there is a need to articulate initiatives that promote greater investment in particular in the business fabric to promote the articulation of the scientific system with companies, especially in the areas of intelligent specialization, such as in agriculture or tourism.

6 RIS3 priorities

Smart specialization is a strategic approach to economic development through targeted support to Research and Innovation (R&I) as part of the future Cohesion Policy's contribution to the Europe 2020 jobs and growth agenda. This process Azores choose an approach through its main traditional sector: Agriculture, livestock and agroindustry; Fisheries and Sea, and Tourism.

In the context of the smart specialization strategy the project RIS3_Net, MAC/5.11 A/075, was approved by the Management committee of the INTERREG MAC 2014-2020 Cooperation program, meeting in Funchal, Madeira, on November 8, 2016, has a duration of 26 months and aims to promote inter-regional cooperation For the smart growth of the MAC space regions.

RIS3_Net aims to develop an institutional cooperation and a common governance system strategy, directed to the institutions responsible for planning, implementing and monitoring the smart specialization strategies on the MAC Regions, also taking into account the potential of including the third countries. This project will allow increasing the common knowledge of the RIS3 strategies of the participating regions

This S3 approach is the basis for a structural investments as part of the cohesion policy contribution to the objectives of the Europe 2020 strategy. Although this strategy is having positive results in terms of other financed projects, as the Operational Programs (FEDER & FSE)* there is a lack of alignment in terms of thematic between the H2020 and smart specialization areas defined by RIS3 in Azores. The defined RIS3 are not reflected in the majority of the projects we are included. This demonstrates the need for revising and reflecting on the priorities expressed by the R&I stakeholders. The RIS3 need to be realigned with the H2020 in order to be more competitive in the access of the financing, promote areas of interests from the R&I ecosystem and reach a broader international network. In terms of percentage, in terms of H2020 (on FP1), 61% (23 projects in 38 H2020) of the projects that Azores are involved on do not correspond to Azores smart specialization area, even in the F2 regarding other projects, as INTERREG and Call for proposals, 55% (45 projects in 82 in total) do not correspond to the defined Smart specialization areas for the Azores. This lack of specialization has missed the mark to showcase the differentiation of OR's, however many OP projects have been implemented on this context with great success, as you can see by the approved projects and investments illustrated in the table on Figure 14.

Operational Program 2020 Azores (FEDER e FSE)	Approved projects (total costs approved) (€)	Eligible investment of approved operations in execution
Açores	53.154.052,82	31.423.685,95
Alentejo	20.106.625,20	5.667.951,20
Algarve	3.780.749,22	1.852.999,92
Centro	42.022.711,94	12.227.545,52
Lisboa	5.510.025,65	1.051.655,61
Madeira (10)	23.049.247,14	6.756.249,67
Norte	84.176.745,89	17.815.788,10

Figure 4 – Operational Programs approved in Portugal and budgeted

7 Public policies

The total ESIF dedicated to R&I registered is 186,000,000, with a total ESIF dedicated to R&I per year per capita of 108,98. The total of H2020 per capita per year is still 4,23 euros. This is translated in to a ratio between (Total H2020 per capita per year) and (Total ESIF dedicated to R&I per capita per year) of 0,04.

The public policies tools in practice in the regions highlighted are PACT; *Agenda de Inovação* and *Competir +*, grants that has Public and private research labs, Researchers from public institution and Private sector as target public, respectively. These programs orientate and mobilize instruments of support for the R&I ecosystem,

PACT is a call dedicated to detect and finance research projects / Innovation projects with regional interest and/or relating to RIS3 priorities. A policy that promotes the participation in H2020 through evaluation of criteria on the impacts of the project include the perspective of competitive projects submission, however this criteria is not mandatory.

Agenda de Inovação as also the aim to develop international research collaborations in RIS3 priorities through ingoing and outgoing, short and long term mobility (from 6 to 24 months). Promoting not only the strategic areas defined and the region as it promotes the widening of researchers network. This tool can be used to prepare collaboration aiming at H2020 consortium building. Since this is a recent policy the aim is also to have in to mind the preparation for the Horizon Europe framework program.

Competir + is a public policy more directed to the private sector for the 2014-2020 period and it has three main objectives:

1-Increase the productivity and value of investment projects, giving greater emphasis to the component of "best investment", when compared with "more investment", as well as the positioning of business activity in competitive markets;

2-development of competitive factors associated with knowledge, culture and creativity, through innovation;

3-Intensifying the participation of regional companies in globalization, reflecting resources towards the production of tradable goods and services and rebalancing threats and opportunities. Compensate regional companies of additional costs resulting from the pursuit of economic activities in an outermost region.

As existing RDI policies we mentioned, that encourage mutual learning between outermost regions through a comprehensive overview of the orientations and instruments mobilized by the partners (WP2 and WP6), study the synergies between the cohesion policy, sustained by European Structural and Investment Funds, and the participation to the FP (WP2), the two following policy framework:

1. Pro Scientia Plan

The Regional Government, through the Regional Directorate for Science and Technology, has opened two calls under Pro-Scientia for the allocation of support to initiatives and projects aimed at the dissemination of scientific and technological culture, providing an overall funding of 40 thousand euros. One of the calls is specifically aimed at supporting projects, initiatives, campaigns or challenges under the "Citizen Science" initiative. It intends to foster the active participation of social actors in scientific research processes and in the collaborative construction of knowledge, while aligning research results with the expectations, needs and challenges of the society. In turn, the other call is focused on the creation of Science and Technology contents in multimedia format for dissemination in the media with a view to increasing the scientific and technological literacy of citizens. It intends to encourage the creation of contents in multimedia format as well as to promote informal learning contexts. These calls, which run until September 30 2019 (ongoing), intend to contribute to the implementation of the Action Plan for Scientific and Technological Culture of the Azores (PACCTO Azores). Its measures and operational actions are intended to reach the entire Azorean society, thus creating conditions for greater involvement of all citizens in search of innovative solutions to the challenges of today's world.

Pro Scientia Plan has as objectives:

- (Create) Value through the following action, first of all empower the entities in the Scientific and technological system in the Azores (SCTA) and value its activities and secondly promote activities of research, innovation development and innovation in the entrepreneurship context;
- (Foster and reinforce) Cooperation through the following actions: reinforce the cooperation and knowledge transfer in technologies incentive the creation and partnership with the exterior;
- (Promote) Update through improving accessibility and conditions used in the development of technology of information & communication
- (Promote, support, stimulate, incentive) Qualification through the following action: improve accessibility and conditions used in the development of technology of information & communication

2. Research and innovation strategy for the intelligent specialization of the autonomous Region of the Azores – RIS3 AZORES

The development process of the RIS3 Azores was defined as referring to the necessary selection of priorities, which allow the region to focus its investments on a limited set of options, taking into consideration the Competitive advantages and international expertise. As a basis for the construction of the aforementioned priority selection process, a preliminary definition of comprehensive thematic areas was made, the selection of which was supported in aspects such as existing assets, regional policy priorities, or the potential of these sectors in terms of economic development and job creation in the autonomous region of the Azores:

-Agriculture, livestock and agroindustry;

-Fisheries and sea;

-Tourism.

These thematic areas were explored in different ways in the development of the RIS3 Azores. It was intended that, in each case, the vision allowed guiding the elaboration of the subsequent strategic definition levels, allowing to collect clues about the way to go and motivate reflections around the strategy to be adopted. At the moment these areas are being revised since the framework conditions have changed at regional, EU and international level therefore its being analyses and restructured.

As it was mentioned in the paragraph regarding the RIS3 (and illustrated by a table), the PO Açores 2020 European funds, managed by the regional authorities are aligned with the Smart Specialization Strategies RIS3, however when it comes to externally managed funds, as the H2020 the areas go beyond the regional managed funds.

C- Regional organizational characteristics

In terms of economic situation the Azores have a global value of 3731 million of euros and a GDP per capita (€) of 15 898 (ratio from 2015 to 2018 data), with a R&I intensity of 0, 7 in percentage of the GDP. With a H2020 budgeted per capita per year of 21, 9.

The support services available in Azores region, despite its variety of approach and organic and goals, have a strong participation of public support/participation. This may constrain the type of processes and network that can be built by this organizations that is meant to support. With most of the regional organizations having strong public participation, it may format the goals and mission and this may have an impact on the perspective and result of the innovation and research developed. Therefore it's important that the public support may not gain characteristics of nurturing, since it's fundamental to build a resilient and competitive R&I ecosystem. The public support should exist as a beginning but not as an end in order to promote a stronger and diverse R&I ecosystem.

1 Review of higher education and research organizations' participation determinants

The Azores has the advantage of having one high education organization in the Region as well as 12 research groups operating in the region. From the 9 islands, three of them has facilities from the University (São Miguel island, as headquarter, Faial island, Terceira island), as well as research groups operating. This allows not only to fix the young population and researcher in the region, and its islands, as well as gain attractiveness and critical mass and infrastructures for external researchers and students. With 70% of the population between the age of 15 to 64 year old (Population within 15<age<64 of 171030 in a total of 243862 - 2017), with a total Marine area of 23663 km² and an Exclusive economic zone of 930 687 km², the Azores have unique characteristics that set them apart from other EU Regions and within the Outermost Regions giving the perfect conditions to gain competitive advantage that can be promoted through scientific research combined with innovative approached, methods and products.

From the analysis to the results of interviews and questionnaires to researchers from the University of the Azores, the main conclusions are:

- a) A vast majority of respondents point out as the main causes for low participation rates not having sufficient knowledge about the FP programs and the fact they seemed to be designed to favor the greatest European research institutions;
- b) Despite these considerations, Azorean researchers consider that they have the conditions to integrate international consortia, taking into account the lines of research in which they work, as well as the academic qualifications they possess. However, the fact that they do not integrate international networks is also a condition. to the unsuccessful participation in FP program calls;
- c) The easy access to less competitive and less demanding regional funding resources also contributes as a factor to a low participation of regional researchers in European project proposals;
- d) Despite a certain distance from European funding opportunities, the Azorean researchers consider that is important to strengthen their participation on it through a concerted strategy to this end, which should be developed by all players of the regional research and innovation system.

2 Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions

University of the Azores plays a fundamental role in education and research in the region, thus contributing to professional qualification, scientific innovation, social improvement and intercultural awareness. The University of the Azores integrates three *campus* located on the islands of São Miguel, Terceira and Faial, and comprises university and polytechnic organic units. Its organic is based on a logic of departments and schools, which are units intended for the continued realization of teaching and research. Its teaching, research, services and cultural extension activities cover the most diverse areas of Exact and Technological Sciences, Natural and Environmental Sciences, Medical and Health Sciences, Agrarian Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities.

As a result of its framework and regional, national and international priorities, the University of the Azores is currently focusing on differentiating areas of training and research, such as the sea, including fisheries and aquaculture, and natural hazards such as volcanology and seismology, climatology and meteorology. Other areas are also relevant to de UAc strategy, such as biodiversity, biotechnology and biomedicine, agriculture and livestock, geological and energy resources, economics and marketing, sociology and geography, pedagogy and psychology,

language and communication, history and philosophy, archeology, political science. In what concerns the new technologies, the most relevant areas are information and communication technologies and technologies of materials.

As far as research is structured, the University of the Azores has 10 FCT accredited research groups, namely 2 research institutes, 8 research centers and two internal research centers. In the most recent evaluation carried out by FCT, 4 of the research groups were rated *excellent* and the remainder mentioned *very good*.

3 Analysis of institutional strategies

The strategy of the University of the Azores for the coming years includes concrete measures to support the research sector in order to promote the recognition and excellence of the work that researchers carry out in the various scientific areas in which they work. For this purpose, in 2017 the Science and Technology Service was created to support scientific research, technology transfer and innovation. The operational objectives of the service include:

1. Diffusion of relevant information, in particular on calls, notices and other science and technology initiatives;
2. Give support to proposals submissions, services, scholarship and other C&T initiatives, in articulation with UA organic units, other research units, other public or private research institutions, C&T management entities and funding agencies;
3. Provide support to financial and material report of projects, services, scholarships and other C&T initiatives,

4 Analyses of Support Services

- University of the Azores

The research support services at the University of the Azores is currently centered on the Science and Technology Service. In addition to the services already provided by that structure, it is intended in short term to strengthen the capacity of its staff in order to improve the participation rates of researchers from the University of the Azores in European programs, in close collaboration with other regional and regional structures with S&T competences.

Parks for science and technology

- NONAGON and TERINOV

Other support services mentioned in the RDI Mapping FORWARD mapping are NONAGON and TERINOV. Both are associations with public participation, parks for science and technology. These organizations have entrepreneurs; technology-based viable SME's, researchers and public in general as target public. These organizations provide conditions for sustained growth, supported by innovation, technology, entrepreneurship and, consequently, valuing products, companies and Azorean organizations. These parks for science and technology foster the development of new leadership paradigms and promote the catalyze of innovation and creativity; Trough the promotion of the interaction between companies, R&D organizations and public entities, support the promotion and establishment of regional, national and international partnerships. These are places of innovation as the foundation for business competitiveness that contribute to attract and retain new talents, being a fundamental issue in regions as the Outermost Regions. These organizations are platform for cooperation between the business fabric and local and regional entities, such as the University of the Azores, institutions of I&D and public bodies. Through the services and support they provided are designed to increase the competitiveness of local and regional companies through the development and dissemination of a culture of innovation and creativity.

As enabling and available technology & machinery we can highlight that TERINOV provides two wards of research and development laboratories for the agro-food industry and biotechnology, and a laboratory for innovation in dairy products. A support service that invest in agriculture innovation in the area, joining private sector with research, supporting simultaneously one of the Smart specialization strategies (RIS3) areas signalized in the region by the Azorean government.

Public support services

- Regional Fund for Science and Technology (FRCT)

FRCT is a public body that was created with the objective of coordinating and manage the financial resources available for scientific research and technological development from Regional, European and International programmes. The target public of FRCT incitiatives are researchers; private and public sector and society. The FRCT mission is to promote the Science and Technology System of the Azores (SCTA) R&D+I, through the following actions:

- Funding of Research Grants & Fellowship;

- Promoting the participation of other SCTA entities in international programs and projects;
- Providing support to the SCTA in the preparation of project proposals;
- Participating in R&D+I projects under external financing programmes.

- Instituto de Inovação Tecnológica dos Açores – INOVA

INOVA is a Research and Technology Organization association, with public participation, in the area of agriculture. INOVA targets public the private sector and it's support services are focused in technological development, technology transfer, the provision of specialized services and quality support to the regional industry and promoting applied research. It's a technological infrastructure of reference in the regional context, with increased strategic importance and necessary to the development of the Azorean business fabric and economy. Once again the support services area focused on Smart Specialization areas defined by the region.

- Laboratório Regional de Engenharia Civil –LREC

The LREC is a Public entity, the Regional Laboratory of Civil Engineering is a public institution that provides services in various areas of Civil engineering. Among the services provided are the studies, opinions and essays. LREC has a laboratory of materials, chemistry and is also equipped with all the technology that allows to gauge, measure and correct all parts that are part of any engineering work and contributes to guarantees that the materials that constitute it have the necessary quality contributing to the longevity of any construction. LREC has a annual trainings plan, that includes trainings in several innovative areas, such as passive houses, energy efficiency in general, as well as renewable energy applied to engineering, on financed projects and meteorological instrumentation. LREC also implements partnerships, supports publications and thesis in the context of innovation and technologies in Engineering.

- Sociedade de Desenvolvimento Empresarial dos Açores

SDEA, *Sociedade de Desenvolvimento Empresarial dos Açores* (Society for Private sector development in the Azores), EPER, conceives and executes policies to stimulate business development, aiming to strengthen the competitiveness and productivity of Azorean companies, as well as to promote innovation and entrepreneurship.

SDEA is a public body that has the following tasks, just to mention a few: (a) propose and promote measures to reduce context costs in order to simplify and streamline investment processes; (b)

Contribute to new measures in the field of incentive policy, including financial incentive schemes for investment and the functioning of regional enterprises; (c) Carry out the monitoring of the incentive policy and evaluate its results; (d) Support information for sectoral policy measures in order to promote employment and support vocational training; e) Fostering entrepreneurship and innovation, boosting measures leading to the creation of new businesses with innovative potential and added value, and the economic valuation of knowledge; (h) Promote the enlargement of the regional export base; i) to conceive and promote the image of the Azores brand abroad globally, with a view to promoting exports, internationalization and attracting investments; j) intervene in the management of business areas and parks aimed at the installation of companies, namely to promote dynamics of innovation, technological-based entrepreneurship, business aggregation and logistic synergy; k) to streamline the publication and dissemination of specialized information of a corporate scope; u) To promote programs to promote and incentivize the entrepreneurship in the region, as: "Network of Business incubators of the Azores; Regional Entrepreneurship Competition"; Vale Incubation Azores; Program of support Digital Azores; Employing my business program; Program for Azorean Network of Mentors; Financial support for digital services: Vale PME Digital Azores and Vale programming, etc.

Chamber of Commerce

- Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Azores (CCIA),

The CCIA was created in 1979 and it acts as an “umbrella” of the 3 Azorean Chambers of Commerce, that represent the secondary and tertiary sectors. This structure of business associations of the Azores unifies the existence of 3 centennial chambers of Commerce, increasing their capacity for intervention and the recognition in their geographical areas of influence. The CCIA's main intervention areas are:

- Social-economic partner;
- Promotion of the region and its products/services;
- Liaison between businesses and innovation/knowledge centres;
- It's has been an important partner for the Regional Government and other organizations;
- Through its affiliates it renders a wide scope of businesses services and support.

Management authorities for the support services

- Direção Regional do Planeamento e Fundos Estruturais

This public body is under the authority of the Vice-Presidency of the Regional Government of the Azores, Employment, Entrepreneurship and Competitiveness, of the Regional Government of the Azores. The Regional Directorate for Planning and Structural Funds it's an Innovative entrepreneurship support services that manages the RIS3-NET plan, supports entrepreneurs, SME; Citizens in general; Associations; NGO 's. It's the operative service, at a regional level, responsible for preparing and monitoring the implementation of the Regional plan (financed projects by the Region and structural funds - FEDER e FSE), namely the Operational Plan of the Açores, as well as implementing interventions with community support and conducting studies of socioeconomic nature.

- Direção Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (DRCT)

Is a governmental body under the authority of the Regional Secretary for Sea, Science and Technology. The Regional Directorate for Science and Technology is an innovative entrepreneurship support services or programs that is also responsible for managing the RIS3-NET plan. It's public target includes: research center's and businesses; associations ; NGO's; private sector and public in general. This Regional Directorate has the mandate to settle regional policy in the fields of science and technology, as well as coordinating and developing the actions necessary for its implementation. Its main lines of action focus on supporting scientific research programs and projects, experimental development and technological innovation and modernization, promoting infrastructure to support research activities Scientific and technological development and dissemination of science and technology, and in encouraging the qualification of human resources and the specialized training and dissemination of science and technology. Knowledge creation and its transfer to the economic fabric are key factors for the sustainable development of the Azores. The challenge to be launched by researchers is towards a culture of innovation, based on the transfer of knowledge and technology and the promotion of value-added areas. Strengthening the establishment of knowledge partnerships and the articulation between the entities of the scientific and technological system of the Azores (SCTA) and the socio-economic fabric, and between research, innovation and entrepreneurship, in order to reinforce the cooperation between research center's and businesses, encompassing and strengthening each link

in the innovation chain, from fundamental research to technological transfer. As well as supporting scientific research programs and projects, experimental development and technological innovation and modernization; establishment of knowledge partnerships and the articulation between the entities of the scientific and technological system of the Azores (SCTA) and the socio-economic fabric, and between research, innovation and entrepreneurship; encompassing and strengthening each link in the innovation chain, from fundamental research to technological transfer; develop and manage European financed programs - from H2020 to INTERREGS; grant fellowships to researchers, especially in RIS3 areas.

D- Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

Most studies on FP participation focus on network, systemic or organizational determinants and privileges quantitative analysis based on large databases like CORDIS and ECORDA. Yet, the sum of individuals' profiles and strategies can exercise a major influence on the regional performance taken as a whole. Taking advantage of the small size of OR innovation systems, Forward thus proposes to investigate the factors that influence individual researcher's implication and success, namely through qualitative interview-based analyses. The first points out the regularities and common traits found within highly successful individuals and the characteristics of unsuccessful candidates, to hypothesize patterns of success and failure. The regional partners conducted the interviews to representatives of organizations that participated in an H2020 competition. Including public organizations as Regional Fund for Science and Technology, The Regional Direction for Energy, as well as innovation centers, as Nonagon, high education and research organizations as University of the Azores and CCMMG, IITA-A (Institute of Research and Agronomic Technologies and Environment) and private companies as Fundo de Maneio etc.

1 Patterns of success and failure

In terms of keys success patterns that stand out in the interviews and other direct interactions with R&I stakeholders, we have identified characteristic's that may determine the success of a project application, namely the academic profile. Applicants that have a phd are participants that shared success cases indicated that they had more successful cases. Also many of this participants with success cases have had international mobility experiences or/and national. This also can be a factor that contribute to the large majority of them had previews experiences with other project submissions. Regarding the role in this applications, most of the participants had an early stage participation in the process and were in charge of writing major key points of the project, either they played major impact on the conceptualization of the proposal from the early stage of the process. This reveals the recognition, on the part of the partners, of the value of the contribution that regional partners from the Azores R&I ecosystem can bring to the table. However, despite their qualifications and experience, most of them are not enrolled in the European Commission as experts and we lack project coordination's.

The most common traits in terms of profile of the participants of the failure cases is that the level of involvement in the project. Most of them indicated that they had a major role in the core group who conceptualise the proposal, however the level of experience of the participants in its majority is low, due to the number of projects they have worked up until then and their inexistent mobility at a professional level or mainly national.

2 Analysis of self-selection determinants

In the self-selection determinates that resulted from one on one interviews with researchers, the most of the participants indicate as a motive to do not participate in H2020 projects the lack of network that allow them to penetrate this competitive environment, considered by many as reserved to large organizations despite all agree on the importance of strengthen relations with high level research organization's outside Europe. The solution that most of the researchers that participated in the interviews presented was to resource to less competitive funds to finance their research, since most of them consider that the amount of time used to apply to H2020 programs, with scars changes of financing, not justify the investment of time and human resources. Despite most participants agree that the FP funds are a priority for their organization they point as obstacles for H2020 participation the fact that H2020 is focus in areas that have immediate economic or utility results (as Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research and the bioeconomy; emerging technologies; leadership in enabling and industrial technologies, etc) which is not the case in the of humanities or fundamental science, therefore researchers do not think their research is contemplated in the H2020 calls. The perspective presented is that the lack of organizational support, lack of time and resources, as well as excessive academic work (and related), lack of framing / representation and interest on specific fundamental research fields (as for History and Heritage) are a block to participation in H2020 programs. The participants also expressed a lack of skills that block the capacity for leveling up to the competitive, as for example the requested level of English or specialized human resources to support with the writing of proposals, to the managing of the process.

III Analysis of the representations

A- Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders (analysis of interviews; analysis of survey)

The conduction of interviews and survey during the mapping and diagnosis process represented an opportunity to map and assess representations on FP participation and explanatory factors that are in the roots of the beliefs and fears regarding the H2020 participation and constitute powerful obstacles that OR's should address in order to promote an increases of participation regionally

As main obstacles to the participation in H2020 the participants indicated in the surveys and interviews were that there was a high level of competitiveness in H2020 projects; also the matter of time, since it's time consuming to do a search for calls or consortium partner's, as well as write and submit a proposal, with no warranties of success.

Also another matter that was stress was the bureaucracy and the fact that the distance keep us away from the decision centres and therefore takes us away the chance to lobby per sectors and connect with successful networks that influence from the time the call is still in its planning phase. Another question that was raised that is important to stress in this context, is the low level of funding for the ORs research teams compared to the funds allocated to mainland research groups. The RIS3 was also mentioned, pointing out that it needs to be analyses and implement with a more comprehensive view of the it's applicability. This point *soundbites* in the lack of connection that we can identify between the scientific area of the projects in the Azores and it's RIS3 areas, regarding FP projects (FP-1) and other projects (FP-2).

Participants pinpointed obstacles in the area of qualifications and capacities: some participants indicated that there is a lack of qualified human resources with experience and the knowledge in European affairs and in European projects. Additionally they identified the need for more capacity building actions on writing proposals, managing the project, and financial managing, as well as lack of leadership skills and communication. Finally it was highlighted the absence of public support to administrative support to submit proposals for H2020, since internally there isn't, as it was mentioned, human resources with the experience and capability to do it.

On the other hand, as levers of H2020 participation it was mentioned the fact that it promotes research studies by allowing the fostering for the publications and academic of great importance for the execution of researcher work. Another lever identified, in regards of research, is the possibility to integrate different researcher's background in to one project, promoting inter connection between scientific areas and promote stronger and wider networks. Another lever mentioned is the simple rules and the possibility to do bigger projects with high impact due to the larger budget of each project. Finally yet importantly, it mentioned as a lever the clear definition of strategic areas for the ORs (RIS3) and H2020 as a promoter to strengthen the research and innovation in the ORs.

Following the discussion promoted during the workshop, piggybacking in the resume of the conclusions taken from the survey and interviews they identified based on the Trees dynamic the group filled in a SWOT analysis table regarding the conditions of the R&I ecosystem. This tool intended to promote a strategic planning to help identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to R&I ecosystem and identify points of competitive advantage and obstacles. The regional stakeholders did the followed analysis having in to mind the R&I Azorean ecosystem:

STRENGTHS: Endogenous resources – living labs; Geographical position; Political autonomy ; University in the region – with several competences and international attractiveness ; New generation of more qualified human resources; Small dimension of the R&I ecosystem – allows better links and network.

WEAKNESSES: Lack of alignment of the R&I – no cooperation culture; No capacitation and training activities in H2020 in the region; Private sector is conservative - not very open to innovation & research – with limited dimension; Limited RIS3; Territorial fragmentation – 9 islands; Missing the support to apply and manage projects – no information or specialized human resources in organizations.

OPPORTUNITIES: Emerging new areas: energy; biodiversity; sustainability; tourism; Azores geostrategic position in the EU and OR's – Atlantic bridge; New framework programs with more attention to OR's – budget allocated to R&I; Politics on Smart specialization – RIS3; Forward project – OR's network; Access to differentiated markets – Third countries.

TREATS: EU competition/Globalization; The Brexit consequences to the EU budgeted; The different characteristics and maturity of the R&I ecosystem in OR's – jeopardize the strength of our

alignment ; Potential (damaging) competition between OR's future framework program opportunities ; Dependency on transports – outermost position; Projects with no impact – affects credibility

IV Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation

A - Major obstacles

On the 24th of June 2019 was conducted a Workshop dedicated to the quadruple helix, under the following name: FORWARD: Promoting participation in European funding programs in the innovation and research ecosystem, in São Miguel island, in Ponta Delgada city. The activated had 27 participants: 12 from representatives from high education institutions and researchers, 11 representatives from public sector, officers that work at a technical level and representatives from support organizations, as well as 4 representatives of the private sector. In the context of this workshop we presented several dynamics that served as an exercise to reflect, analyze and present solutions and actions towards the promotion of the participation of the I&R ecosystem in the H2020 and in future framework programs (as Horizon Europe), namely: the Problem Tree; the Solution Tree; SWOT tools; construction of an action plan.

Firstly it was presented a completed Problem Tree, as a result of the compilation and resume of the answers obtained from the key player of the quadruple helix of the Innovation and Research (I&R) ecosystem on the surveys (sent by link by the three regional partners of FORWARD) and the interviews (conducted in-person). This information was obtained during the month of May and June 2019 on the context of FORWARD project and it was compiled and selected in cooperation with the regional partners of FORWARD project (CCIA; UAc e FRCT).

The central problem that was highlighted by the majority of the participants regarding the Innovation and Research (I&R) ecosystem in the Azores was the “Lack of strategic alignment of the quadruple helix of the innovation and research ecosystem”. From this central problem we analyzed two axes: the causes, in the roots; the effects, in the branches.

The indicated causes of the problem regarding the Azorean I&R ecosystem are: bureaucratic limitations; inexistence of sectorial lobbies; aversion to risk and change; Reduced dimension of companies; low cooperation culture; scarce qualified technical resources for the managing of

financed project; outermost region condition; lack of knowledge and interest of the potential beneficiaries of H2020 financed projects

The effects mentioned in the Problem Tree regarding the I&R regional ecosystem are: low participation; Weak human resources in the organizations; Difficulties in attaining excellence; Low competitiveness; Reduced capacity for internationalization; Weak network at an European and International level; Lack of innovative dynamics; Low capacity of adding value.

B Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP

The preliminary actions plan results from the several tools of intervention and diagnosis that were put in to place regionally and that allowed us to have a clearer view

The analysis of the preliminary diagnosis that resulted in the table's completion, the interviews and survey results were analyzed during the FORWARD workshop which reunited a group of stakeholders from the R&I ecosystem of the Azores. This day dedicated to the exchange of impressions, needs and recognition of opportunities and competitive advantages that Azores uphold served as the base to create a common action Plan that resulted in the following proposed actions:

- Create Regional Contact Points, dedicated to the support of present and future competitions and to the capacity building of the organizations and its teams in order to promote more and better skills to access successfully the approval of submitted projects;
- Focus on Capacity building needs, namely on financing programs and proposal writing – that should be provided by organizations dedicated to H2020 support;
- Workshop and other networking, ideas development platforms that could help in the promotion and engagement of the R&I ecosystem – including EC programs and success cases/studies;
- Promote education for creativity in schools and universities to invest in future generations and change the conservative culture, identified by stakeholders, that by avoiding change also may impeach innovation at the level of research, entrepreneurship and public politics;

- Identify and empower the value chain, by valuing our differentiation products, services and overall conditions – at a regional level and in the OR's context;
- Establish clusters and thematic groups, in order to reinforce R&I networks and share information;
- Adjust the Smart Specialization areas in order to correspond to the interests that the Azorean stakeholders show in the projects they apply and the present differentiation conditions, and also adjusted to the future opportunities for Horizon Europe;
- Mobilize a collaborative and international strategy for FP competitions, already promoting networks and aligning interests for the future competitions.

Canary islands

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems

Canary Islands

31st October 2019

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No

824550

Summary	4
Introduction	8
Evolution of the participation of Canary Islands partners in FP7 and H2020	9
Methodology	17
I - State of play of participation	19
1) Evolution of regional participation	19
2) Participation to the different programmes and funding schemes.....	24
3) Thematic distribution	25
4) Stakeholders mapping	37
5) Participation profile.....	38
6) Regional collaboration (with other Outermost Regions & Third Countries).....	39
II - Analysis of participation determinants.....	41
A - Network analysis.....	42
1) Global connectivity	42
2) Thematic connectivity.....	44
3) Relative position	47
4) Third countries participation.....	50
B - Regional innovation system	51
1) Mapping the regional innovation system	53
2) Regional research performance.....	67
3) Private sector implication.....	69
4) RIS3 priorities	70
5) Public policies	72
C - Regional organisational characteristics	74
1) Review of higher education and research organisations' participation determinants	74
2) Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions.....	77
3) Analysis of institutional strategies	78
4) Analysis of Support Services	80
D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level.....	83
1) Patterns of success and failure	83
2) Analysis of self-selection determinants	87
III - Analysis of the representations	89
1) Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders (analysis of interviews; analysis of survey).....	89
2) Analysis of the concordance or gaps between survey results and the data.....	92
IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation	93
A - Major obstacles	93
B - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP	104

General objective:..... 104
Specific objectives: 104

Summary

The Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems of the Canary Islands report has been composed by the Canary Islands Institute of Technology (ITC), in collaboration with the Canary Islands Agency for Research, Innovation and Information Society (ACIISI), which coordinates the project, and the rest of the Canarian partners: University of La Laguna (ULL), University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands (PLOCAN), Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC) and Consulta Europa (CE).

Throughout the report, the participation of the Canary Islands in the Seventh Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development (FP7) (2007-2013) and Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (H2020) (2014-2020), both from the European Union, is analysed. Some key determinants are reviewed to conclude with a diagnosis of the situation and the proposal of an action plan that allows for the adoption of specific measures that prepare the Canary Islands to more successfully approach participation and funds return in the next research and innovation framework programme, Horizon Europe.

In said diagnosis of the situation, the starting point is the analysis of the Canary Islands' R&I system, which presents a series of weaknesses that could be considered structural, where the effort in terms of research and regional development is low and below the European and Spanish averages. The Canary Islands is the second Autonomous Community with the lowest intensity of spending in R&I (0,50% compared to the national 1,21%, data from 2017).

The previous indicator, together with others such as the total corporate R&I expenditure in the Canary Islands, which is lower than in the rest of the country (15,45% compared to 54,96%, respectively, for 2017), positions the regional innovation system of the Canary Islands significantly behind the Spanish and EU averages, so it is necessary to implement new plans and actions that will allow for the modification of the current situation with the purpose of progressively bringing the Canary Islands closer to the national average first and, subsequently, to the European average.

The conclusion reached from the analysed data is that the evolution of the Canary Islands in these two programmes (FP7 and H2020) has been positive, as the number of project proposals has almost doubled, going from 365 to 614, although the success rate has decreased

by two points for H2020, going from 21% to 19%. The total of approved Projects in FP7 were 77, and in H2020, up until the elaboration of this study, 117

For the scrutinised period, the Total funding awarded to regional partners amounts to 25.449.495,68€ for FP7 and to 40.398.794,91€ for H2020. A positive evolution in the obtaining of European funding can be observed, even though the return rate is lower for H2020, which, with almost double the funded projects, barely obtains a third more of the funding.

The most relevant themes in number of approved projects for both programmes are part of the Physical Sciences and Engineering scientific domain and they are: PE10 Earth System Science, with 34 projects in total, and PE9 Universe Science, with 29 projects.

The previous themes together with LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, and Molecular and Biosystems Engineering receive a sum of 33.603.643€, which represents almost 50% of the total funding received by both programmes.

The types of organisation that concentrate the majority of FP projects are: Higher education establishments (HES), Research organisations (REC) and Public sector (PUB), the standouts in number of projects being the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (HES) with 48 projects, Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (REC) with 31 projects, and the Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (PUB) with 28 projects.

It should be noted that out of all the Canary Islands' funded projects, 14% of them, that is, 28 projects, are coordinated by a local institution.

Regarding the RIS3 priorities that frame the H2020 projects, the following stand out: Social and economic valorisation of specialised R&D with 42 projects, Green growth and sustainability with 25, Digital agenda with 17, European Mid-Atlantic with 5 and Smart and sustainable leadership in tourism with 4.

The collaboration between outermost regions is low, as only 2 FP7 projects and 7 H2020 projects include partners from other regions.

The participation of neighbouring third countries is incidental in both programmes and it is limited to two countries: Cape Verde and Senegal.

The capacity of regional stakeholders to get involved with the main organisations that take part of framework programmes is positive, although it could be improved. The Canary Islands participates in 19 FP7 projects along with 3 of the Top 10 centres in the European ranking which hold the first, sixth and eighth positions in said ranking. The Canary Islands

also participates in 60 H2020 projects with 5 of the best in said ranking, holding the first, second, sixth, seventh and eighth positions.

The Research Capabilities of the region are mainly found in the two public universities that together have 91% of the research groups (434 groups) and 93% of researchers (3.631 researchers). Other smaller public research centres (IAC, PLOCAN and ITC) are included, and, among them, the IAC is the most prominent with a first-class research excellence award, 38 research groups and 200 researchers, apart from being the most attractive centre for foreigners, receiving 71% of the total.

In terms of the participation of FORWARD partners in these two programmes, the most prominent is the ULPGC with 282 proposals, followed by the ULL with 187 and IAC with 183.

The review of the available data to appraise in what ways the following four determinants influence participation and success produces the following conclusions:

The size of the institution, albeit an important indicator, does not seem to be a determining factor in the Canary Islands regarding participation in FP, as the ULL, the first regional institution, with more research groups and researchers, is actually the second institution in number of submitted proposals and the fifth in approved projects.

Orientation does not seem to be a determining factor either in the success rate in FP programmes for both Canarian universities, as the ULPGC, with a lower PhD/ undergraduate ratio than ULL, achieves a much higher success rate (17% ULPGC and 7% ULL).

Concerning scientific excellence, it should be noted that the ULL has a significantly greater number of scientific publications when compared with the second and third institutions in this ranking (ULPGC e IAC), confirming as well that this determinant does not affect participation and success rates.

The degree of international openness of the three main research institutions reveals that the institution with greater international openness and a higher Average number of foreign post docs per year is the ULL, followed by the ULPGC and IAC. This seems to indicate that this determinant does not condition participation and success rates either.

Finally, if we analyse the **success rate** of FP7 and H2020 participation for Canarian institutions, it can be observed that the smaller research institutions have a higher success rate in projects awarded (34% ITC and 22% PLOCAN) followed by the ULPGC (17%), IAC (17%) and the ULL (10%).

Concurrently with the collection and analysis of the previously presented data, a series of interviews and a survey were conducted in order to identify the determinants of self-selection, the main determinants (obstacles) that influence the Canary Islands' participation according to local stakeholders. These obstacles are:

- 1) Lack of technical and administrative support in proposal writing.
- 2) Difficulty to build partnerships and networking.
- 3) Small size of research groups and research centres.
- 4) Low participation of SMEs.
- 5) Lack of institutional support, public authorities support.

From this and the workshops' report, the Canary Islands partners produced the final version of the regional diagnosis and drew a territorial strategic plan to increase regional participation to FP Programme.

The strategic plan includes detailed actions with general and specific objectives, organisations in charge, targets, indicators of implementation and results.

The general objective is to redefine an appropriate public framework that allows the increase of the participation and return of the Canary Islands in European R&D programmes - Horizon Europe.

The Specific objectives are:

- 1) Promoting support and institutional engagement and networking.
- 2) Promoting a communication strategy raising awareness of the importance of the internationalisation of the R&I.
- 3) Reinforcing and supporting research teams and centres to develop proposals.
- 4) Increasing SME participation in R&D&I projects

Introduction

Framework Programmes have been the main financial tool for funding R&I within the European Union, supporting research and development activities covering almost all scientific disciplines.

As indicated on the Spanish website for the EU Research and Innovation Programme, Framework Programmes for Research and Technological Development developed in the EU have contributed to the increase of competitiveness and to the growth and generation of knowledge in the different member states. However, results in participation considerably vary in different regions and that is why excellence should be identified and promoted independently of geographical location.

The Canary Islands' participation in these programmes leaves room for improvement, so we should make a collective effort to improve the current participation, approval and return ratios.

All of the Canarian R&I organisations and, especially, Forward project partners, are aware of the importance that active participation in these programmes has for the quality of the science and research developed in their institutions.

By means of the action plan developed at the end of this diagnosis report, we intend that a greater number of research groups increase their participation in EU programmes, not only to improve the experience and achieve better results, but also to help our researchers to progress.

To that end, the involvement of the Government of the Canary Islands and the rest of participants of the Canarian R&I system will be essential.

Evolution of the participation of Canary Islands partners in FP7 and H2020

A series of brief summaries on the evolution of some of the Project Partners in terms of participation in the EU Framework Programmes (FP7 and H2020) is included below:

1. University of La Laguna (ULL)

For the past years, the Vice-Rectorate for Research has been strongly committed to increasing the participation of the ULL research groups in international calls, with a special focus in the H2020 programme. Through this initiative, the collaboration with prestigious companies (both big and SMEs, such as Nokia or Neurogames) and international research centres (e.g. Fraunhofer Institute or Liverpool University) was reinforced. For instance, the Vice-rectorate team is currently focused on boosting collaborative projects, and has started to spread the knowledge of FP calls among researchers by thematic areas. Additional efforts helped us to get the EC-validated EURAXESS seal of excellence, and the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R), which focuses on an internationally recognised Open, Transparent and Merit-based recruitment strategy. Furthermore, the institutional strategy included for the first time specific measures in relation to the next FP Horizon Europe, training specialised personnel in infodays in Brussels, etc.

Despite the significant leap in participation experienced in the last year, it is quite clear that we must further improve both the level of participation and the quality of project proposals to reach better success rates. Fortunately, in 2018, and thanks to the financing of the FDCAN programme (Funds for Development at the Canary Islands), the International Projects Promotion Unit was created, with a specialised technical team to support researchers in project development and submission. Overall, these measures allowed us to more than double the number of project applications, as shown in the following table:

Table 1. Number of H2020 proposals

Number of H2020 proposals		
2017	2018	Increase
16	42	26

Source: ULL

However, the rise in participation has not yet been reflected in the success ratios, since the promotion unit activities started just one year and a half ago. The next figure shows the evolution of the ULL's participation in FP7, H2020 (excluding Erasmus + projects) and Directorates-General calls:

Figure 1. European projects granted

According to the data found in the “Horizon Dashboard” tool, the ULL is among the top three more successful institutions in fundraising in both the H2020 (2014-2020) and FP7 (2007- 2013) in the Canaries.

Table 2. Participation figures in the Canaries by institution (H2020)

Legal Name	Country	H2020 Net EU Contribution	H2020 Participations
Totaux		€ 42.436.520	168
INSTITUTO DE ASTROFISICA DE CANARIAS	Spain	€ 10.935.817	15
UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA	Spain	€ 7.892.914	26
UNIVERSIDAD DE LA LAGUNA	Spain	€ 5.258.781	9

Table 3. Participation data in the Canaries by institution (FP7)

Legal Name	Country	City	Participations	EU Contribution
Total			79	€ 21.456.764
UNIVERSIDAD DE LA LAGUNA	ES - Spain	LA LAGUNA TENERIFE	9	€ 5.861.437
UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA	ES - Spain	LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA	19	€ 4.952.253
INSTITUTO DE ASTROFISICA DE CANARIAS	ES - Spain	SAN CRISTOBAL DE LA LAGUNA	16	€ 4.876.995

2. University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC)

The ULPGC is committed to raising EU funds. 30 years after emerging as a University, and with the support of the Science and Technology Park of the ULPGC, the ULPGC has positioned itself prominently in the access to European funds.

The ULPGC has participated in EU projects since the III Framework Programme. But it has not been until FP7 that the increase has been notable, consolidating their performance in H2020, where the number of projects financed with respect to FP7 has been exceeded.

Figure 2. Number of EU projects (FP7, H2020, DG)

Coinciding with the launch of H2020, the Vice-Rectorate for Research of the ULPGC promoted in 2014 the European Projects Office (OPE). While managed by the Scientific and Technology Park Foundation of the ULPGC (FCPCT), the OPE was also supported thanks to the IMPERA project, that was submitted and received national funds from the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness of Spain. This project allowed the alignment of the ULPGC with national policies regarding Science and Technology, with the goal to “increase the participation of all the agents of the Spanish system in international projects and programmes; increase the economic return obtained by the Spanish entities derived from their participation in EU R&D projects; increase the leadership of Spanish entities in H2020 projects; support access to H2020 by Spanish entities without previous experience; and facilitate the fulfilment of the participation objectives established in the strategic internationalization plans of the beneficiary entities”.

The IMPERA project allowed the training and the specialisation of OPE Team members as EU Project Managers for fundraising and management of EU projects, as well as the establishing of a network of national and European contacts resulting from the participation in infodays and brokerage events. These actions have also lead to ULPGC visibility at a European Platforms level.

Although H2020 is the main source of EU Funds, ULPGC has an active participation in Directorates-General (DGs) of the UE, COST Actions, ERA-NETs or Joint Programming Initiatives. This contributes to expand the range of financial opportunities for the ULPGC Research Groups; their capacity to make their research visible, as well as the possibilities to establish relations with other reference Research Organisations at European and global level.

An analysis of ULPGC's participation in EU programmes confirms that strategic areas such as Marine Sciences, Blue Economy, and its related transversal areas, define very well the high potential of the ULPGC in these research disciplines.

Therefore, the commitment made by the ULPGC to launch its European Projects Office has fostered the participation with guarantees of its Research Groups in European and international research programmes; has positioned the ULPGC on the European map of excellence research and increased their performance in terms of success rates and economic return; and promoted synergies with researchers and companies located in the three continents.

The current ULPGC Research and Transfer Plan 2018-2020 includes a specific action to provide funds to enhance the mechanisms to support Research Groups in order to reduce the burden of management processes and support the proposals preparation process.

A remarkable milestone for the ULPGC has been the financing of its first ERC-StG in 2019, (ISOCAN project), to be developed during the next five years in the area of Archeobiology.

The ULPGC RESEARCH website (<https://www.research.ulpgc.es/>) collects all the information regarding the research done at the ULPGC (projects, news, events, videos) in their commitment to make them visible and available to the general public, with the aim to highlight the importance and benefits of S&T in our society.

3. Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands (PLOCAN)

PLOCAN was created in 2007 and in 2010 it started with its first staff recruitment and operational activities. PLOCAN continued with the infrastructures and the national and EU projects of the former ICCM (Canary Islands Marine Science Institute), and it also leveraged on the ICCM network of collaboration and project participation. With regard to FP programmes, PLOCAN continued with the observation activities in EU projects like CANIGO (4th FP), ANIMATE (5th FP), MERSEA (6th FP), EuroSITES (7th FP) and other projects related to marine technologies, such as AMASS (7th FP). Moreover, PLOCAN also

received the strong network and collaboration framework developed by the ICCM in the Macaronesian region and Interreg Projects such as MARES, MAXIMAR, etc....

With this background, in 2010, the EC launched the Ocean of Tomorrow joint programme and, in particular, a topic for Multiuse offshore Platforms. Being an innovative research infrastructure, with the aim to design, construct, equip and exploit an offshore platform, this was an excellent opportunity to participate as coordinators and highlight PLOCAN's role in Europe. PLOCAN presented the proposal for the TROPOS project and it was fortunately awarded, starting in 2011 and ending in 2014. This initial experience was key for the newly recruited staff to gain experience and organise internally, as well as for becoming better known externally.

With these two sources, and focusing on ocean observation, multiuse platforms and maritime technologies, PLOCAN has continued developing and promoting cooperation in EU R&D and increasing its research lines. A breakthrough in this strategy has been the integration and application of its Marine Test site to Marine renewable energies, mostly waves and offshore wind.

Figure 3. PLOCAN Active European FP Projects

- Focusing on PLOCAN's strategic plan objectives, e.g.:
 - Alignment with the Integrated Maritime Policy (Blue Growth, Sea basin strategies, etc.) → to support sustainable growth in the marine and maritime sectors as a whole
 - PLOCAN EU project objectives in FP7 and H2020 has been aligned with several RIS3 priorities (in which the H2020 projects are framed) → Marine Sciences and Technologies + Social and economic valorisation of specialised R&D

- Making a great effort to develop a strong stakeholder network based on PLOCAN's strategic and engagement plan
 - Partnerships and networking → International, European, national and regional connectivity
- Adapting and organising the institution internally → e.g. the development of a robust, effective and certified programme management system turned out to be essential and an integral management methodology was specifically created and successfully passed the ISO 9001:2008 certification in 2016
- Gaining expertise and applying best practices in proposal development (attending specific training and relying on technical and administrative support)
- Improving dissemination and communication strategies
- Learning by doing + continuous improvement

How resources have been mobilised

Based on specific needs and its mid-long-term strategy, PLOCAN mobilised the needed resources by means of:

- PLOCAN's own investment
- Infrastructure and services (national and European support)
- Direct Spanish and Canary Islands Government institutional support

How the connections with EU institutions have developed

- Attending EU specialised meetings and networking sessions
- Connection and solid network activities with national contact points and EU project and programme officers, etc...
- Partners in EU projects
- Others....

4. Canary Islands Institute of Technology (ITC)

The Canary Islands Institute of Technology (ITC) was founded in 1992 and began to apply to competitive European R&D&I calls in 1996. It has to be considered that ITC is not exactly a research centre in strict terms, but a public company (SME, owned by the Regional Government) acting as a multidisciplinary technology centre. In this sense, and although one of its corporate purposes is the development of R&D&I activities, ITC participates in most of the European calls as SME.

Furthermore, and in comparison to the other institutions carrying out R&D&I activities in the Canary Islands, ITC has a relatively small dimension, with (currently approx.) 140 people distributed among 9 departments which develop R&DI projects in the following emerging technological areas: renewable energies, water technologies, algae biotechnology, biomedical engineering, environmental analysis, and ICTs/Computing. (ITC, being a public SME, was particularly affected by the economic crisis: the number of researchers/scientists/engineers went down to below 90).

On the other hand, not all employed people at ITC (technical staff) are involved in R&D&I projects: some of them work in studies and services contracted with the local/regional administration or with companies. This means that all ITC departments have a relatively small critical mass to compete in European (and also national) R&D&I calls. Nevertheless, ITC has been quite successful in its applications:

- Since 1998, ITC has participated in approx. 150 European competitive EC co-funded projects
- Out of these 150 projects, 32 correspond to EC Framework programmes (4th FP: 2 project; 5th FP: 7 projects; 6th FP: 10 projects; 7th FP: 5 projects (worst period of the economic crisis); H2020: 8 projects (both figures, 150 and 32, are proportionally high if compared to other regional R&D&I institutions with a bigger dimension)
- The remaining projects correspond to INTERREG programmes (Atlantic Area, Macaronesian Region, Europe, etc.) and other European Programmes (Erasmus, etc.)
- The areas in which ITC has been more successful are those with the biggest critical mass, namely: renewable energies and water technologies (focused on innovative and sustainable solutions for islands and isolated areas) and business innovation (the traditional areas of ITC since its foundation)

Participation in competitive European R&D&I projects (and collaboration with European and international renowned partners) is a high priority for ITC. In this sense, EC FP calls represent an excellent opportunity to continue growing and acquiring R&D&I excellence, both in the traditional technological areas named above, but also especially in the new emerging technological ones (blue biotechnology, biomedical engineering, environmental analysis), which have been gaining relevance in the last years.

5. Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC)

The IAC has been participating in research and Innovation framework programmes since the mid-90's when the FP4 was published. Participation has been quite productive in the different Framework Programmes throughout this time.

International scientific and technological collaboration has always been a priority for the IAC. For that reason, the evolution of its participation in FPs has been progressive, since the starting instrumental projects to the most recent scientific ERC projects, bearing in mind the large scientific infrastructures, such as the European Solar Telescope. The IAC has relevant experience on EU funding and related policies as a result of our participation in committees, working groups, hearings, submission and review of proposals, management and coordination of funded projects, etc.

The communication and relationships established with the different EU bodies has been marked by the transparency and the straightforward access necessary to accomplish the financed projects, as well as by the contributions from the IAC that have been made in the definition and performance of the several work programmes. Some of our researchers have participated as evaluators for different specific programmes. We have been also involved as a National Contact Point (FP5 and FP6, Research Infrastructures and Marie Curie Actions). We usually attend info-days, hearings and other EU events, with oral contributions in some cases.

As the report already shows, an important amount of resources has been mobilised during FP7 and H2020 programmes, with an exceptional level of performance in terms of implementation and execution of the projects. The IAC has a consolidated experience in the management and coordination of EU projects, well recognised by our international scientific community.

Definitely, the European Framework programmes represent a great opportunity to foster the competitiveness and networking between partners. They have become an important pillar to project funding within the IAC and its collaborative scientific network.

Methodology

In the execution of the preliminary diagnosis of the R&I ecosystem in the Canary Islands corresponding to project FORWARD's WP2, representatives of all the Canary Islands partners participated and a regional delegate was designated and tasked with coordinating the different stages of the process.

Canary Islands: Forward partners WP2

- ACIISI (Antonio López, Javier Roo)
- ULL (Paloma Bernal, Rebeca Baz, Elizabeth Carrillo y Mar Borges)
- ULPGC (Almudena Suárez, Acerina Sosa)
- PLOCAN (Marimar Villagarcía, Silvia Martín)
- ITC (Alma Cruz⁽¹⁾, Lucía Dobarro, Dayana Martín, Carmina Santana, M. Antonella Pugliese, Avelino Yanes, Guillermo Martín)
- IAC (Anselmo Sosa, Alfredo García)
- Consulta Europa (Michelle Perello, José Benedicto)

(1) Regional delegate for WP2

The organisation of the work involved multiple online meetings for the review of the methodology provided by Nexa, criteria homogenisation, the collection of the required data, a survey and various interviews, a preliminary analysis of the data, two regional workshops, one in Tenerife and another in Gran Canaria, and the writing of a final diagnosis and action plan.

Figure 4. Work organisation

Source: FORWARD

In the first stage, data has been collected on FP7, H2020 and other EU instruments proposals, projects and funding.

The sources and databases employed in the development of this study are the following: information provided by FORWARD partners incorporated in the Excel tools provided in the guidelines, CORDIS, the H2020 dashboard and ECORDA. On a regional level, local research institutions, regional authorities and FP support offices have been contacted as well. On a state level, information provided by the CDTI (Centro para el Desarrollo Tecnológico Industrial, or Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology) has been consulted.

The collected data for the realisation of this study cover up until July 2019.

The main difficulties faced in the development of the project were:

- The requirement of very detailed and extensive information in each of the Excel spreadsheets of the methodology to be completed by each partner of the project.
- This implies seven partners providing large amounts of information, as well as collecting information from other awarded organisations.
- The information provided by partners was not always normalised (ex. H2020 Pillars, RIS3 domains...).
- The Excel spreadsheets provided do not allow filtering.
- Different data between ECORDA – CORDIS and data provided by the partners in terms of:
 - Number of FP7 / H2020 projects
 - EU contribution FP7 / H2020

Finally, it is important to point out that, throughout this document, FORWARD partners are referenced, which, for the Canary Islands, are: the Government of the Canary Islands (GOBCAN), through the Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Información (ACIISI, or Canary Islands Agency for Research, Innovation and Information Society), the University of La Laguna (ULL), the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC), Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias, S.A. (ITC, or the Canary Islands Institute of Technology), and Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (PLOCAN, or Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands). When FORWARD partners are referenced in this document, we are referring to the group as a whole.

I - State of play of participation

The first objective of this diagnosis is to describe the reality and diversity of the Canary Islands participation in the framework programmes.

1) Evolution of regional participation

The data collected in step 1 will first be mobilised to assess the evolution of the regional participation in FP and compare it to other European and Outermost regions.

To that end, two categories were completed: “Global performance”, which presents general indicators, and “EU Contribution”, which measures the funding obtained by regional stakeholders and their relative weight in the GDP.

The general objective set for the analysis of this topic is:

- *To describe the reality and diversity of the Canary Islands’ participation in the framework programmes for research and innovation (FP7 and H2020).*

The specific objectives are:

- *The evolution of the Canary Islands’ participation in the FP7 and H2020 programmes.*
- *The positioning of the Canary Islands compared to other European OR.*
- *Most represented organisations and themes in the Canary Islands*

The evolution of the participation of the Canary Islands in projects within the framework programmes for research and innovation (FP7 and H2020) between the years 2007 and 2019 has been very positive, as the number of proposals submitted to each programme has increased and, in the case of H2020, even doubled. However, the success rate for H2020 has decreased by two points.

The total number of project proposals with participation from the Canary Islands submitted to FP7 was 365, achieving a global success rate (funded projects / submitted proposals) of 21%.

Compared to this level of participation in FP7, the total number of project proposals with participation from the Canary Islands submitted to H2020 between the years 2014 and first trimester of 2019 was 614, achieving a global success rate (funded projects / submitted proposals) of 19%.

Regarding the positioning of the Canary Islands compared to other European OR, in the ECORDA graph below, our region, notably ahead, holds the first place in number of funded projects (See Figure 5). According to this source, the Canary Islands were awarded funding

for a total of 194 projects: 117 projects corresponding to the H2020 programme and 77 to the FP7 programme.

Figure 5. Number of FP7 and H2020 projects in the OR

Source: ECORDA

The second OR in the funded projects ranking is Madeira, with 54 projects (34 FP7 and 20 H2020 projects). The rest of the OR are considerably behind the Canary Islands.

The Canary Islands have obtained funding for 194 projects: 117 projects corresponding to the H2020 programme and 77 to the FP7 programme.

It should be noted that out of all the Canary Islands’ funded projects, 14% of them, that is, 28 projects, are coordinated by a local institution.

In regard to the Canarian Organisations with a higher rate of project participation in these programmes, public organisations are notably ahead of private ones. Among the first, the first places are held by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) with 48 projects (24 of them for H2020), the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC), with 31 projects (15 for H2020) and the Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (PLOCAN), with 29 projects (20 for H2020).

To get a better idea of the participation rate of private Canarian organisations in these programmes, the one with the most projects is LA PALMA RESEARCH CENTRE FOR FUTURE STUDIES SL, an organisation created in 2011 which takes part in 15 projects, 12 of them for H2020, and 3 in which they participate as coordinators.

Concerning the most common themes in which Canarian organisations participate within each programme, the two most relevant scientific domains¹ are:

PE10 Earth System Science with 34 projects and

PE9 Universe Science with 29 projects.

With respect to the total amount of EU contribution for each scientific domain both for FP7 and H2020, the most relevant scientific domains in the Canary Islands are:

PE9 Universe Science = 15.741.792€

PE10 Earth System Science = 9.466.916€

LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, and Molecular and Biosystems Engineering = 8.394.935€

These three scientific domains together obtain 33.603.643€, which represents almost a 50% of the total funding awarded for both programmes.

Regarding **RIS3 priorities** (5 in total) in which the H2020 projects are framed, the three main ones are:

- Social and economic valorisation of specialised R&D via thematic concentration (42 projects)
- Green Growth and Sustainability (25 projects)
- Digital Agenda (17 projects)

As is shown in Table 4, for the analysed period and according to the ECORDA source, the Total FP7 funding awarded to regional partners amounts, for the Canary Islands, to 25.449.495,68 €, while the Total H2020 funding awarded to regional partners amounts to 40.398.794,91€. Thus, generally speaking, a positive evolution for the obtaining of European funding for the Canary Islands can be observed, even though the return rate is lower for H2020, which, with almost double the funded projects, barely obtains a third more of the funding.

In regard to the **Total of other EU competitive funding awarded to regional partners**, and only taking into account the comparison with H2020, the awarded funding amounts to 9.658.901,69 €, less than a third of the funding awarded for H2020, which reflects the lower number of projects.

¹ The research fields are defined following the 2019 ERC evaluation panels and keywords.

Table 4. EU Contribution in FP7 and H2020

EU Contribution	FP7	H2020
Total FP7 funding awarded to regional partners	25.449.495,68	
Total H2020 funding awarded to regional partners		40.398.794,91
Total of other EU competitive funding awarded to regional partners	Data collected from 2014	9.658.901,69
Share of H2020 in the total EU funding	-	80.70%
Ratio between H2020 and other EU competitive funding	Data collected from 2014	4,18
H2020 funding as percentage of GDP		0,091
Average EU contribution per project	4.254.264,44	9.037.922,79
Average EU contribution to regional partner	322.145,51	348.265,
Average share of EU contribution awarded to regional partner	9.68 %	7.86 %

Source: ECORDA (H2020) and own work (FP7)

Canary Islands participation in other programmes that may be involved in the research and innovation fields

The participation of the Canary Islands in other European programmes is lower than their involvement in FP7 and H2020. In fact, there are only 40 projects accounted for, with the COSME programme funding most of them (7), followed by ERANET (6). We consider the list of analysed projects not exhaustive. The information has been provided by partners.

It should be pointed out that 7 of these 40 projects are coordinated by local institutions.

In relation to the RIS3 priorities of these other EU projects, the most relevant are:

- Green Growth and Sustainability (8 projects)
- Social and economic valorisation of specialised R&D via thematic concentration (7 projects)
- Marine Sciences and Technologies (7 projects)

Figure 6. Participation of outermost and European islands in H2020

Source: ECORDA

If we compare the Canary Islands’ participation in H2020 with that of the islands of the Outermost Regions and Europe, even though it is in third position, it is considerably behind the two Mediterranean islands that hold the first positions (Crete and Cyprus), both in the level of European funding obtained and in the number of projects submitted.

Regarding the award of European funding in H2020, even though it places third, ahead of all of the outermost islands and most European islands, it only amounts to 40.000.000€ compared to Crete and Cyprus, which obtain over 100.000.000€ and 160.000.000€, respectively. The comparison between the Canary Islands and Crete stands out because, even though both territories have a similar surface area (Crete, 8.000 km² / Canary Islands, 7.493 km²) and Crete has a significantly lower population (Crete’s population: 632.700 in 2017 / Canary Islands’ population: 2.128.685 in 2018), our region places notably lower than Crete, whose results, both in number of projects (271) and in funding, more than doubles those of the Canary Islands (124 projects).

This is because Crete has one of the largest Research Organizations in the country, the **Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas (FORTH)** <https://www.forth.gr/> and the largest Science and Technology Park of Crete (STEP-C) <http://www.stepc.gr/>. Thus, having a lower population, their innovation ratios are higher.

2) Participation to the different programmes and funding schemes

Regarding Participation to the different programmes, Table 5 classifies projects in which the Canary Islands takes part according to the five FP7 and H2020 programmes.

Table 5. Participation to specific programmes and objectives (H2020 and FP7)

Number of Projects	No.	%
Number of H2020 Excellent Science projects	34	37,0
Number of H2020 Industrial Leadership projects	29	31,5
Number of H2020 Societal Challenges projects	27	29,3
Number of H2020 Specific objective “Spreading excellence & widening participation”	0	0,0
Number of H2020 Specific objective “Science with and for society”	02	2,2
TOTAL	92	100,0
Number of Projects	No.	%
Number of FP7 Ideas projects	01	1,4
Number of FP7 Cooperation projects	32	46,4
Number of FP7 Capacities projects	20	29,0
Number of FP7 People projects	16	23,2
Number of FP7 JRC projects	0	0,0
TOTAL	69	100,0

Source: own work

The Canary Islands participate in just 4 of the different H2020 programmes, mainly in Excellent Science projects (34), and followed closely by Industrial Leadership projects (29) and Societal Challenges projects (27).

In the case of FP7 programmes, the Canary Islands participate in 4 of them, with the main one being Cooperation projects (32), which comprises almost half of the projects.

Table 6 classifies the Canary Islands` projects regarding the participation to the different funding schemes in FP7 and H2020.

Table 6. Participation to the different funding schemes and actions type (H2020 and FP7)

Number of Projects	No.	%
Number of H2020 Research & Innovation actions	42	36,2
Number of H2020 Innovation actions projects	17	14,7
Number of H2020 Coordination & support actions projects	29	25,0
Number of H2020 Grants of the European Research Council (ERC) to support frontier research	5	4,3

Number of H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions (MSCA)	13	11,2
Number of H2020 COFUND actions	3	2,6
Number of H2020 Procurement actions	0	0,0
Number of H2020 SME instrument	7	6,0
Number of H2020 Inducement Prize	0	0,0
Number of H2020 Recognition Prize	0	0,0
Number of H2020 Debt and equity facility	0	0,0
TOTAL	116	100
Number of Projects	No.	%
Number of FP7 Collaborative projects	28	42,6
Number of FP7 Networks of excellence	0	0,0
Number of FP7 Coordination and support actions	25	36,8
Number of FP7 Individual projects	0	0,0
Number of FP7 Support for training and career development of researchers	0	0,0
Number of FP7 Research for the benefit of specific groups – in particular SMEs	4	5,9
Number of FP7 Marie Curie grants	9	13,2
Number of FP7 ERC project	1	1,5
TOTAL	68	100,0

Source: own work

As can be observed, for H2020, 76% of the projects are framed within just three funding schemes: Research & Innovation actions (RIA), with 42 projects, Coordination & support actions projects (CSA), with 29, and Innovation actions projects (IA) with 17. For FP7, 79,4% of the projects correspond to two funding schemes: Collaborative projects (CP), with 28, and Coordination and support actions (CSA), with 25.

3) Thematic distribution

One of the key objectives of the Forward project is to evaluate the research and innovation assets and priorities of each region. Mapping the domains in which regional stakeholders successfully participate in FP provides an indication of the fields of expertise. It also facilitates the identification of common areas of interest between two or more Outermost Regions, which could be explored in order to increase cooperation.

To construct such thematic distribution, FORWARD partners were able to specify the number of participations, the scientific domains and amount of funding collected.

The **scientific domains** in which the Canary Islands obtain more FP7 and H2020 projects can be observed in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Thematic distribution on FP participation in Canary Islands

Source: own work

The number of projects included in the first 5 scientific domains is itemised next.

In FP7:

PE9 Universe Science = 16

PE10 Earth System Science = 13

PE8 Products and Process Engineering = 10

LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, Molecular and Biosystems Engineering = 11

PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering = 9

In H2020:

PE10 Earth System Science = 21

PE6 Computer Science and Informatics =15

PE9 Universe Science =13

PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering =11

LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, Molecular and Biosystems Engineering = 8

The joint thematic distribution in both programmes shows that the most relevant scientific domains in the Canary Islands are the following:

PE10 Earth System Science with 34 projects and **PE9** Universe Science with 28 projects.

In order to further explore the subthemes in the highlighted scientific domains, the abstracts and fixed keywords in FP7 and H2020 projects have been analysed in order to find out which subdomains comprise the greatest number of projects, reaching the following results:

PE10 Earth System Science.- Most important subdomains: Deep Ocean (5 projects), Marine Sciences (4) / Raw materials (4) / Mineral extraction (4) / Atlantic basin (3) / Water treatment (3).

PE9 Universe Science.- Most important subdomains : Astronomy/Astrophysics /Space (16 projects) / Solar Physics (12).

PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering.- Most important subdomains: Renewable energy (7).

LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, Molecular and Biosystems Engineering.- Most important subdomains: Aquaculture (11)/ Health (3) / Algae, microalgae (2).

PE6 Computer Science and Informatics.- Most important subdomains: Cloud (5) / Security (3) / Internet (3).

In turn, each Forward partner selected the most representative H2020 projects in said scientific domains and subdomains, leading to Table 7, included below.

Table 7. Scientific domain/subdomain and most representative H2020 projects

Scientific domain / Subdomain	Describe the specific activity /subfield	Most representative H2020 projects	FORWARD partner
<p>PE10 Earth System Science. Deep Ocean - 5 projects, Marine Sciences – 4 projects / Raw materials - 4 projects / Mineral extraction – 4 projects / Atlantic basin – 3 projects / Water treatment 3 - projects.</p>	<p>Supporting Statements as the Belem and Galway ones for the Atlantic are crucial for the Canary Islands, as they cover many of the priorities stated in this OR (e.g. ocean observation, food security, ocean renewables, etc.). Institutions such as PLOCAN are focused on participating in their support actions (e.g. via AANChOR, AORA, etc.). PLOCAN is also part of the EMSO ERIC and the projects being implemented within for the ocean observation (EMSODEV, EMSO-Link), always contributing to the strategic position and development of the Canary Islands archipelago in blue growth.</p>	<p>AANChOR: All AtlaNtic Cooperation for Ocean Research and innovation AORA-CSA: Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance Support Action Atlantos: Optimising and Enhancing the Integrated Atlantic Ocean Observing System EMSODEV: EMSO implementation and operation: DEvelopment of instrument module EMSO-Link: Implementation of the Strategy to Ensure the EMSO ERIC’s Long-term Sustainability ENVRI PLUS: Environmental Research Infrastructures Providing Shared Solutions for Science and Society EUMarineRobots: Marine robotics research infrastructure network OCEANSET: Support to the Realisation of the Ocean Energy Implementation Plan of the SET-Plan SYMBIOSIS: A Holistic Opto-Acoustic System for Monitoring Marine Biodiversities</p>	<p>PLOCAN</p>
	<p>Water management and sustainable use of water, are crucial for the Canary Islands. Research organisations, such as ITC, develop and use desalination technologies, purification, regeneration and circular economy. The ITC is also committed to cooperation with the regions of Macaronesia and West African countries, and supports the implementation of European and regional studies and projects in quality and governance of water.</p>	<p>MAGIC: Moving Towards Adaptive Governance in Complexity: Informing Nexus Security”</p>	<p>ITC</p>
<p>PE9 Universe Science.- Astronomy/Astrophysics /Space - 16 projects / Solar Physics – 12 projects.</p>	<p>Astronomy and Astrophysics are part of the Canary Islands RIS3 strategy, aiming to achieve major advances in the understanding of the laws that govern the origin and evolution of the various forms of matter/energy in the Universe. Addressing key problems on: very high energy phenomena in the Big Bang and around black holes, the genesis of cosmic</p>	<p>RADIOFOREGROUNDS: Ultimate modelling of Radio foregrounds: a key ingredient for cosmology OPTICON: Optical Infrared Coordination Network for Astronomy WHOLE SUN: The Whole Sun Project: Untangling the</p>	<p>IAC</p>

	<p>and gamma-rays, formation and evolution of galaxies, the life cycles of stars, physics under strong gravity fields, the physics of magnetic fields in the Sun, and the detection and characterisation of Earth-like planets in nearby stars. Research organisations, such as IAC, develop international cooperation and exploitation of an exceptional set of observational facilities to achieve leadership in key areas of astrophysics .Those key research lines are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solar Physics • Exoplanetary Systems and Solar System • Stellar and Interstellar Physics • Formation and Evolution of Galaxies • Cosmology and Astroparticles • Astrophysics instrumentation 	<p>complex physical mechanisms behind our eruptive star and its twins.</p> <p>PRE-EST: Preparatory Phase for the European Solar Telescope</p>	
<p>PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering. Renewable energy – 7 projects.</p>	<p>The Canary Islands are committed to being part of regional, national, European and International R&D&i networks. PLOCAN takes part in several of them, especially the ones that are related to the maritime sector in general and to renewables in particular. These contributions ensure the presence and positioning of the Canarian archipelago in the international and European consortiums that are planning future actions on the corresponding fields.</p>	<p>MARINERGI: Marine Renewable Energy Research Infrastructure</p> <p>MARINET2: Marine Renewable Infrastructure Network for Enhancing Technologies</p> <p>SWARMS: Smart and Networking UnderWater Robots in Cooperation Meshes</p>	PLOCAN
	<p>The Canary Islands are committed to the energy sustainable transition, positioning the Islands as a natural reference laboratory for the testing of energy saving and efficiency systems. Research organizations, such as ITC, develop strategies and technologies aimed at maximising the use of renewable energies, especially in island networks and remote areas, as well as developing regions in Africa through international cooperation projects.</p>	<p>TILOS: Technology Innovation for the Local Scale, Optimum Integration of Battery Energy Storage</p>	ITC
<p>LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, Molecular and Biosystems Engineering.-</p>	<p>Many cell types in living systems use electrical signalling to perform their physiological functions. Cells store and deploy electrical energy to, among others, communicate, release</p>	<p>Nanopdics: Optoelectrical Dynamics of Ion channel Activation in Calcium Nanodomains</p>	ULL

<p>Aquaculture - 11 projects / Health - 3 projects / Algae, microalgae 2 - projects.</p>	<p>hormones or neurotransmitters, grow and divide. Ion channels are intriguing proteins located that allow the controlled flow of specific ions (potassium, sodium, calcium, magnesium, chloride...) across cellular membranes. The amazing thing about ion channels is that their function can be studied in real time, using techniques like patch-clamp and fluorescence. Not surprisingly, malfunction of these proteins constitutes the common cause of many diseases, including epilepsy, migraine, muscular dystrophy, hypertension, etc. Due to their unquestionable physiopathological relevance, ion channels are nowadays one major pharmaceutical target.</p>		
<p>LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, Molecular and Biosystems Engineering. - Aquaculture - 11 projects / Health - 3 projects / Algae, microalgae 2 - projects.</p>	<p>The diversity of European cities and regions creates barriers for the demonstration of systemic food-related innovative approaches valuable in so different contexts. The objective of FoodE is to accelerate the growth of citizen-led City/Region food systems (CRFS) by bringing local initiatives across Europe together, as well as co-developing and disseminating a range of tools - co-designed with academia, citizens, and food system start-ups - to ensure that the most up-to-date cross-sectorial knowledge is applied. Start-ups will also provide an in-depth understanding of the needs of the key stakeholders, making resilient citizen-driven food systems happen. The key challenge is then to aggregate the most sustainable models of CRFS and enable co-creation of innovative pilot experiences, fostering the health and wellbeing of European citizens. This challenge will be tackled by setting a co-created mechanism, based on Citizen Science and Responsible Research and Innovation principles, where public authorities, citizens, business actors and non-profit organisations share ideas, tools, best practices and new models, supporting cities in becoming innovative food hubs.</p>	<p>FOOD-E: Food Systems in European Cities</p>	<p>ULL</p>
	<p>An analysis of ULPGC's participation in EU programmes confirms that strategic areas such as Marine Sciences, Blue Economy, and its related transversal areas, define very well the</p>	<p>ECOQUA: Research and Technology to enhance excellence in Aquaculture development under an</p>	<p>ULPGC</p>

	<p>high potential of the ULPGC in these research disciplines.</p> <p>In this sense, the ULPGC plays an active role in the development of the European Blue Economy, contributing to the Outermost Regional Sustainable Development.</p> <p>The following research projects deserve a special mention: research projects on increased animal performance during their life-cycle, new aquaculture species under climate change scenarios, genetic improvement, marine spatial planning and site selection, large-scale microalgae-based biorefinery of biostimulants, biopesticides and feed additives, in addition to biofertilizers and aquafeed, using only marine water and nutrients from wastewaters.</p> <p>ULPGC also offers its research facilities for other EU research institutions as well as for the aquaculture industry, from genetics to technology through pathology, physiology and nutrition, covering both established and new aquaculture species.</p>	<p>Ecosystem approach</p> <p>SABANA: Sustainable Algae Biorefinery for Agriculture aNd Aquaculture</p> <p>AQUAEXCEL2020: AQUAculture infrastructures for EXCELlence in European fish research towards 2020.</p> <p>AQUAIMPACT: Genomic and nutritional innovations for genetically superior farmed fish to improve efficiency in European aquaculture</p>	
SH6 social sciences and humanities/The study of the human past	<p>Advance in our knowledge on Neanderthals and their demise has been hampered by the fragmentary and inorganic nature of the archaeological record. At the same time, the sedimentary deposits from Neanderthal sites remain largely unexplored and conceal invaluable archaeological information at the microscopic and molecular scales. The main goal of PALEOCHAR is to identify archaeologically relevant microscopic and molecular residues preserved in sediments from Neanderthal sites.</p>	<p>PALEOCHAR: Tracking past human impact on islands by improving palaeoecological reconstructions with PalEnDNA analysis</p>	ULL
PE8- Physical Sciences and Engineering/Products and processes engineering	<p>The main objective of ENCORE is to increase the share of renovated stock in Europe and worldwide by providing effective and affordable BIM tools that cover the whole renovation life-cycle (from data collection to project execution, and commissioning/delivery). It will tackle energy efficiency and comfort parameters, involving all the actors in the process</p>	<p>ENCORE: ENergy aware BIM Cloud Platform in a COst-effective Building RENovation Context</p>	ULL

	(architecture studios, designers, constructors, tenants, or public administration), and facilitating information exchange among all the parties. To achieve this objective ENCORE proposes the creation of a system that integrates services for data acquisition and will also provide mechanisms for the dwellers or owners to validate the project, either on-site with Augmented/Mixed Reality solutions, or on-line. Then, ENCORE will automatically generate the work planning for the construction works, and will provide continuous monitoring of the energy consumption to ensure non-degradation of the renovation works.		
PE8 Products and process engineering: product design, process design and control, construction methods, civil engineering, energy systems, material engineering. Renewable energy	The Canary Islands are committed to the energy sustainable transition, positioning the Islands as a natural reference laboratory for the testing of energy saving and efficiency systems. Infrastructures, such as PLOCAN, develop strategies and ease technologies testing aimed at maximising the use of renewable energies (while ensuring that they are sustainable and competitive); this aspect of blue economy is very relevant in isolated electrical systems, as those found in islands and unconnected coastal zones.	ELICAN : Self-Installing Telescopic Substructure for Low-Cost Craneless Installation of Complete Offshore Wind Turbines. Deep Offshore 5MW Prototype WAVEPISTON : Competitive Wave Energy on Islands FLOTANT : Innovative, low cost, low weight and safe floating wind technology optimised for deep water wind sites PIVOTBUOY : An Advanced System for Cost-effective and Reliable Mooring, Connection, Installation & Operation of Floating Wind OCEANERA-NET : The coordination of national research activities of Member States and Associated States in the field of Ocean Energy (ERA-NET)	PLOCAN
LS8 Evolutionary, population and environmental biology	In the ad-hoc customisation of the RIS3 (Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialization) developed and approved for the Canary Islands, blue growth and marine energies play a fundamental role. PLOCAN has large expertise and know how in projects related to the coordination and supporting of Blue Growth at European and regional level (e.g. implementation of RIS3 Priorities in Blue Growth through Smart Blue and RIS3-NET projects), e.g. in biodiversity, ocean	BiodivERsA3 : Consolidating the European Research Area on biodiversity and ecosystem services COLUMBUS : Monitoring, Managing and Transferring Marine and Maritime Knowledge for Sustainable Blue Growth BiodivClim : Promoting and implementing joint programming to reinforce transnational research at the	PLOCAN

	renewables, etc. This is currently continued in view of the next EC framework 20121-2027.	crossroads between biodiversity and climate change	
SH2 Institutions, values, beliefs and behaviour: sociology, social anthropology, political science, law, communication, social studies of science and technology	Cooperation with other Outermost Regions (ORs) and even some Overseas Countries and Territories (OCTs) started in 2007 and it has been continuously maintained through different projects (e.g. knowledge transfer, capacity building, access to public funds, etc.), in order to improve common results and objective design, and implementing responsible research and innovation practices in its institutions, which are crucial topics for the Canary Islands. Infrastructures such as PLOCAN, foster this kind of initiatives and have participated as case study for enhancing its own processes, procedures and policies.	FORWARD : Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions GRRIP : Grounding RRI practices in research performing organizations	PLOCAN

Source: own work

Regarding themes by project funding, Figure 8 shows their relevance according to programme (FP7 and H2020).

Figure 8. Themes by project funding in the Canary Islands

Source: own work

If we analyse the **Total Amount of EU contribution for each scientific domain** for each programme, the following information is gathered:

FP7.- In this programme we find projects that are part of 11 different **scientific domains**. From these, we are highlighting the three most important ones, which, besides collecting more than half of the funding, also show a similar weight. In order, they are: **LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology**, with 23% of the total funding, **LS7 Applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics, Therapies and Public Health**, with 23%, and **PE9 Universe Science** with 22%.

H2020.- In this programme, we find projects that are part of 17 different **scientific domains**. However, just three of those scientific domains accumulate almost half of the funding: **PE9 Universe Science**, which gets 26% of the total funding, followed by **SH2**

Institutions, Values, Environment and Space, which receives 13% of funding. In the third position, **PE10 Earth System Science** appears, with 10% of funding.

If we analyse the **Total Amount of EU contribution for each scientific domain** jointly for FP7 and H2020, the most relevant scientific domains in the Canary Islands are:

PE9 Universe Science, with 15.741.792€, followed by **PE10 Earth System Science** with 9.466.916€, and in third place, **LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, and Molecular and Biosystems Engineering** with 8.394.935€.

These three scientific domains together receive 33.603.643€, which represents a little over 50% of the total funding received by both programmes.

In terms of the **RIS3 priorities** (5 in total) in which H2020 projects are framed, we find the following distribution:

- 1) Smart and sustainable leadership in tourism (4 projects)
- 2) Digital Agenda (17 projects)
- 3) European Mid-Atlantic Reference (5 projects)
- 4) Green Growth and Sustainability (25 projects)
- 5) Social and economic valorisation of specialised R&D via thematic concentration (42 projects)

As can be observed, the no. 5 RIS3 priority, “Social and economic valorisation of specialised R&D via thematic concentration”, is the one that comprises a greater number of projects (42) and, within this category, the following thematic lines can be noted:

- RIS3- Marine Sciences (19 projects)
- RIS3- Canarian R&I (17 projects)
- RIS3-Strengthening in astrophysics and space (14 projects)

The second most important RIS3 category is no. 4, “Green Growth and Sustainability”, which comprises 25 projects.

It should be noted that, even though the no. 1 RIS3 priority, “Smart and sustainable leadership in tourism”, should be one of the categories with the most number of projects in our region due to the importance of tourism as an economic activity and to the experience in this sector at an international level, it is, however, the one with the least H2020 projects (4). Said projects are: Urbanwaste, Vamos, WinWind y Yurakan, which were also included in priority no. 4.

Finally, below we find data from CDTI, the Spanish National Contact point for H2020, in which the themes and areas in which the Canary Islands participate in H2020 can be observed, as well as the relation of each with: the return in millions of euros and the percentage over the national total (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Canary Islands participation in H2020 by theme/area

Participación de Canarias en H2020 por temas/ áreas

Source: CDTI

The areas displayed in Figure 9 are listed below:

- BIO Food safety, agriculture, marine, bioeconomy
- CYS Science with and for society
- ENE Safe, clean and efficient energy
- ERC European Research Council
- ESP Space
- FET Emergent Future Technologies
- ICT Information and communications technology
- IIN Research Infraestructure
- MA Climate, environment, effic resources and raw materials
- MSC Marie Sklodowska-Curie
- NMBP Nanotec. advanced materials, biotec. advanced manufacturing
- PYM Innovation in SMEs
- SAL Health
- TRS Transport

From this, we can observe that the most important theme in terms of return is ERC (European Research Council, with 8,4), followed by IIN (Infraestructuras de Investigación, or Research infrastructures, with 5,3), BIO (Food safety, agriculture, marine, bioeconomy, with

4,6) and MA (Climate, environment, efficiency, resources and raw materials, with 4,4). However, the main theme, taking into account the percentage over the national total, belongs, by a considerable margin, to IIN (Infraestructuras de Investigación, with 6,1%).

4) Stakeholders mapping

For the analysis of the main stakeholders that manage FP7 and H2020 projects, the data provided by FORWARD partners has been taken as the baseline.

Concentration of participation at organisation level: The organisations that concentrate most of the FP projects are of the following kinds: **Higher education establishments (HES), Research organisations (REC) and Public sector (PUB)**, and they are:

- ULPGC / University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (HES) together with FULP-ULPGC (Fundación Universidad Las Palmas, Foundation of the University of Las Palmas) with 48 projects (43 ULPGC and 5 FULP-ULPGC)
- IAC / Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (REC) with 31 projects
- PLOCAN / Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (PUB) with 28 projects

With respect to institutions/research centres that in the Canary Islands represent 20% of the total number of successful FP projects, the institution that fulfils this requisite, both for FP7 and H2020, is the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, with 24 FP7 projects (31% of the projects) and 24 H2020 (20,5% of the projects).

Another institution that fulfils this condition, but only for FP7 projects, is the IAC, with 16 projects (21%).

Finally, in relation to the participation of private companies (PRC), the following stand out:

- ATOS Consulting Canarias, SA Unipersonal, with 14 H2020 projects.
- ITC, with 3 FP7 projects and 9 H2020 projects.
- LPRC (LA PALMA RESEARCH CENTRE FOR FUTURE STUDIES SL) with 12 H2020 projects.

Organisation types.- In terms of types and number of organisations that participate in FP and H2020 projects we can find:

1. In FP7:

- Higher education establishments (HES) = 2 (ULPGC and ULL)

- Research organisations (REC) = 3 (IAC, ICCM, Themis SL)
- Public sector (PUB) = 2 (PLOCAN and GOBCAN)
- Private companies (PRC) = 9
- SME participant to FP Projects participating in FP = 12

2. In H2020:

- Higher education establishments (HES) = 2 (ULPGC and ULL)
- Research organisations (REC) = 1 (IAC)
- Public sector (PUB) = 6 (PLOCAN, Government of the Canary Islands, Cabildo de Lanzarote, Cámara Oficial de Comercio de S/C de Tenerife, Cámara Oficial de Comercio de Gran Canaria, Ayto. S/C de Tenerife)
- Private companies (PRC) = 17
- SME participant to FP Projects participating in FP = 12

5) Participation profile

Partners' roles in FP projects can be employed as an indicator of their relative influence in the networks they are part of.

The FP Projects participants' profile can be of five kinds:

- **Coordinator,**
- **Mono- beneficiary;**
- **Project, Beneficiary (partner),**
- **Third Party,**
- **International Participants (Third country)**

Of all those profiles, the most numerous is "**Project, Beneficiary (partner)**".

The analysis of the "**Coordinator**" profile shows the following results: from the whole total of FP projects in the Canary Islands (194), 14,4% fit this profile, that is, in a total of **28 projects** regional organisations act as coordinators (8 FP7 projects and 20 H2020 projects).

The organisations that coordinate a greater number of FP7 projects are the IAC (3 projects) and PLOCAN (2 projects). For H2020, they are the Government of the Canary Islands (6 projects) and the IAC (3 projects).

In the analysis of the "**Mono-beneficiary**" profile, of the total FP projects (194), there are 19 in which Canarian organisations acted within this profile (9 FP7 projects and 10 H2020

projects). The organisations that have a greater number of projects that fit this profile are the IAC (5 FP7 projects and 4 H2020 projects), ITC, with 4 H2020 projects, and the Government of the Canary Islands, with 3 H2020 projects.

Regarding the **Third Party profile**, International Participants (Third country), it is irrelevant because it only amounts to 10 projects.

From the total number of projects and profiles, **the organisations with higher participation are:**

- ULPGC, with 48 participations (24 in FP7 and 24 in H2020)
- IAC, with 31 participations (16 in FP7 and 15 in H2020)
- PLOCAN, with 28 participations (2 of them as subcontracts), 09 in FP7 and 19 in H2020
- ULL, with 19 participations (10 in FP7 and 09 in H2020)
- ATOS Consulting Canarias, with 14 participations in H2020
- ITC, with 12 participations (03 in FP7 and 09 in H2020)
- LPRC, with 12 participations in H2020

In this ranking, we see that the first 4 organisations belong to the public sector and just these four encompass 126 projects, that is, 65% of the projects.

In the sixth and seventh positions, there are two organisations that belong to the private sector, but that together only represent 15% of the total number of projects.

Lastly, and concerning the number of projects in which regional organisations act as WP leaders, there are 26 for FP7 projects and 41 for H2020 projects.

6) Regional collaboration (with other Outermost Regions & Third Countries)

In this section, the level of collaboration between Outermost Regions in their participation in common FP7 and H2020 projects will be analysed, determining the number of projects in which more than one region takes part and those in which a neighbouring third country participates.

Table 8. Regional collaboration in FP7 and H2020

Regional collaboration	FP7	H2020
Number of projects involving at least a second partner from OR including Canary Islands	17	25

Number of projects involving at least a second partner from other OR	2	7
Number of projects including a neighbouring third country	1	3
Share of projects including at least a second partner from OR	22%	21,36%
Share of projects including a neighbouring third country	1,20%	2,50%
Top 5 OR	1	3
Top 5 third countries	0	2

Source: own work

If we take into account the aggregate data from the previous table, we find that from the 77 FP7 projects, a total of 17, that is, 22%, involve at least a second partner from other OR. However, of those, 15 are developed with partners from the Canary Islands and only 2 projects are developed with partners from other Outermost Regions: Azores, Guadalupe, Reunión, Martinica (the NetBiomecsa and Singular projects). From this, we can conclude that the level of collaboration between Outermost Regions is almost merely nominal and that there exists an average level of collaboration between partners from the Canary Islands.

For H2020, the level of collaboration is similar, given that from 117 projects, a total of 25, that is, 21,36%, involve at least a second partner from other OR, including the Canary Islands. From these 25 projects, 7 are developed with partners from other Outermost Regions. They are the following: Atlante, Biodiversa, Destinations, Forward, Macaronight, Soclim pact and Urbanwaste.

Concerning the number of projects that involve neighbouring third countries, it is incidental in both programmes (1,2% FP7 and 2,5% H2020), and it is limited to two countries: Cape Verde and Senegal.

For FP7: Cape Verde takes part in 1 project (Netbiomac)

For H2020: Cape Verde takes part in 3 projects (Aanchor, Triatlas and Macaronight) and Senegal in one (Triatlas).

Finally, among the Top 5 OR the following island territories stand out: Azores (5 projects), Réunion (4 projects) and Madeira (4 projects).

And in the Top 3 third countries: Cape Verde and Senegal.

II - Analysis of participation determinants

Besides quantifying and qualifying the participation of Outermost Regions in Framework Programmes, the Forward project aims at identifying the underlying factors that explain this situation. The workplan specifically mentions a mapping of the “*obstacles and challenges*”, especially in terms of connectivity deficit, which will be “*objectivised and prioritised in order to identify the most critical obstacles for each region as well as common barriers*”.

To identify such obstacles, we have conducted a preliminary literature review on the determinants to FP participation. These scientific publications conclude that the latter cannot be explained by scientific excellence alone, but rather results from complex, intertwined factors, which operate at four different levels:

- At the European level, strong cumulative mechanisms lead to the concentration of participation in a restricted number of operators and networks, and to the parallel exclusion of minor competitors. For instance, 152 of the 1300 European higher education institutions account for 70% of the financed projects; while 50% of these institutions remain excluded from H2020 (Lepori et al. 2014)
- At the regional level, the structure and performance of the research and innovation system as well as the policies conducted (incl. smart specialisation strategy) strongly affect the capacity of stakeholders’ build capacities, reach critical masses and connect to these dominant networks
- The internal characteristics of candidate organisations – size, orientation, resources, past participation and strategy – also influence their capacity and will to engage and succeed in FP.
- At the individual level, the implication first depends on a preliminary decision to apply or not to the programmes, which may be induced by a lack of knowledge, confidence or interest. Applicant’s success is then influenced by their inner characteristics (experience, international connection, reputation, etc.) and strategy.

No analysis of the determinants of Outermost regions’ stakeholders’ participation in the framework programmes has yet been performed. The Forward project will thus contribute to this dynamic field of research, by testing the applicability of the identified factors in these territories and by a strong qualitative, field-approach that questions the organisations and individuals’ profile.

A - Network analysis

In a 2017 working paper, Simen G. Enger from the University of Oslo, points out the critical importance of “*persistent oligarchic networks that would appear to constitute clubs, closed to those less fortunate*”, which participate frequently in the FP and concentrate success. At the opposite end of the spectrum, “*newcomers to European research, seeking funding without well-developed networks and with no prior experience, are likely to fail*” (Enger 2017).

Considering the influence of networks, the integration of Outermost Regions or their relational isolation thus constitute a critical determinant to their participation. To that end, the Canary Islands region has scrutinised:

- Its absolute connectivity to the dominant networks, measured by the number of participations in FP
- The integration of regional stakeholders in the major thematic networks, that dominate the competition
- The relative position of regional stakeholders inside each network.

The Canary Islands regional situation is described in each of the following subsections.

1) Global connectivity

The first objective is to determine the actual capacity of regional stakeholders to integrate within the major “clubs” that dominate the FP scene, as well as the global position of the region.

In order to evaluate the quality of the most frequent Canary Islands stakeholders in the participation in EU framework calls, we have requested FORWARD partners and other regional participating organisations to provide information of the stakeholders in each of their projects that are not from the Canary Islands. Said information was organised and compared with the ranking provided by CORDIS in the following ways:

In the first place, a list comprising the non-Canarian organisations provided by FORWARD partners was composed. From this list, comparing it with the information provided by CORDIS, it was determined that, in the FP7 programme, the Canary Islands had a total of two non-Canarian stakeholders with between 50 and 100 approved projects. This amount decreased to just one non-Canarian stakeholder in H2020 calls. Moreover, the number of non-Canarian stakeholders in our Top 10, with more than a hundred approved projects, was four, which increased to seven in H2020 calls.

Secondly, the Top 10 organisations, as reported by CORDIS, with between 50 and 100 projects were analysed in order to ascertain how many of them were stakeholders of the Canary Islands in FP7 and H2020. In this way, we found that one organisation from CORDIS' Top 10 with between 50 and 100 approved projects was a stakeholder of the Canary Islands in at least one project. This number increased to six stakeholders when H2020 calls were analysed. The same analysis was applied to the CORDIS Top 10 organisations with over 100 projects. From this, we concluded that in FP7 there were three organisations that shared at least one project with the Canary Islands, and the number increased to five for H2020 calls.

The capacity of regional stakeholders to get involved with the main organisations that take part of framework programmes is positive, although it could be improved. The Canary Islands participate in 19 FP7 projects along with 3 of the Top 10 centres in the European ranking which hold the first (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS), sixth (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche) and eighth (Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Forderung der Wissenschaften EV) positions in said ranking. The Canary Islands also participates in 60 H2020 projects with 5 of the best in said ranking, holding the first, second (Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V.), sixth, seventh (University College London) and eighth positions.

Table 9. Number of FP Projects that the Canary Islands share with other research centres and the position of these centres in the EU ranking

Research Centres	Number of H2020 project per organisations	Ranking	Number of FP7 Projects shared with the Canary Islands	Number of H2020 Projects shared with the Canary Islands
AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	293	14	12	14
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	925	1	7	9
MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV	408	8	7	7
HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH	41	290	7	4
UNIVERSITAET BREMEN	62	179	6	6
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	435	6	5	6
UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN	98	105	5	4
INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE RECHERCHE POUR L'EXPLOITATION DE LA MER	45	268	5	9
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI ASTROFISICA	36	340	5	5
UNIVERSIDAD DE OVIEDO	14	880	5	2

Source: own work

2) Thematic connectivity

Assessing the relative position of regional organisations in the great thematic networks allows us to know the existence of a comparative advantage in the different fields. To conduct this analysis, we used a similar approach as in the global connectivity one. Said information was organised and compared with the ranking provided by CORDIS in the following ways:

In the first place, we extracted the scientific domains which present the higher number of H2020 participation. The five scientific domains with a major number of projects shared with non-Canary stakeholders are:

PE10 Earth System Science = 21

PE6 Computer Science and Informatics =15

PE9 Universe Science =13

PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering =11

LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, Molecular and Biosystems Engineering = 8

Secondly, we established the list of partner institutions for each scientific domain. In Table 10, we show the top 5 partners in each scientific domain. From this table we can extract that FEDERATION EUROPEENNE DES GEOLOGUES is the partner with which we share a greater number of projects in a certain area (Earth System Science).

Table 10. Top 5 of non-Canarian partners that share projects in each thematic area

	No. of Projects
PE6 Computer Science and Informatics	
FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V.	4
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	2
COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES	2
FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER	2
AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	2
PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering	
Wavec Offshore Renewables - Centro de Energia Offshore Associacao	3
FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V.	2
COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES	2
INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE RECHERCHE POUR L'EXPLOITATION DE LA MER	2
DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	2
PE9 Universe Science	
MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV	5

ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI ASTROFISICA	5
AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	4
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	4
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	3
PE10 Earth System Science	
FEDERATION EUROPEENNE DES GEOLOGUES	9
INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE RECHERCHE POUR L'EXPLOITATION DE LA MER	5
MINPOL GMBH	5
GEOLOSKI ZAVOD SLOVENIJE	5
MISKOLCI EGYETEM	4
LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, Molecular and Biosystems Engineering	
INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE RECHERCHE POUR L'EXPLOITATION DE LA MER	3
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	3
AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	2
STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	2
HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH	2

Source: own work

Thirdly, we checked whether these partners belong to the top 10, 15, 20 of participating institutions of the corresponding scientific domain in the H2020 dashboard.

According to Table 11, the Canary Islands have a network of partners that are better positioned in the Universe Science (PE9) area: eight out of ten non-Canarian partners that share projects within this area are part of the CORDIS Top 10, while the other two are in the Top 20 (See Table 11). Most of these non-Canarian partners also research within other areas, except for MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV, which shares five projects with Canary Islands partners in this area.

Conversely, and in spite of the Earth System Science (PE10) area having a greater number of projects in which non-Canarian partners participate, it is also the area with the lowest number of well-positioned partners in the CORDIS ranking: four of them are in the Top 10 and one in the Top 20 (See Table 11).

Regarding the Computer Science and Informatics (PE6) and Systems and Communication Engineering (PE7) areas, their degree of connectivity with non-Canarian partners well-positioned in the ranking is relative: each area comprises four partners each in the Top 10, with three of them being the same centre. In terms of the Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, Molecular and Biosystems Engineering (LS9) area, it also shows a relative connectivity with well-positioned partners, of which only one, The University of Edinburgh, exclusively researches in this area with Canarian partners

Table 11 Non-Canarian partners' ranking in CORDIS according to thematic area

Name of the organisation	PE6 Computer Science and Informatics	PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering	PE9 Universe Science	PE10 Earth System Science	LS9 Applied Life Science, Biotechnology, Molecular and Biosystems Engineering	Ranking CORDIS	Total projects shared
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE			4	2	1	1	7
FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V.	4	2	1	2		2	9
THE CHANCELLOR MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE			1			3	1
AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS			4	2	2	4	8
THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	1	1	1			5	3
COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES	2	2	2			6	6
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE		1	1		2	7	4
KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET					1	8	1
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	2		3	2		9	7
ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE		1				14	1
The University of Edinburgh				1	1	16	2
MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV			5			17	5
DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET		2			2	18	4
Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy	1					19	1
POLITECNICO DI MILANO	1		1			20	2

Source: own work

3) Relative position

Based on Figure 10, Physical sciences and engineering is the area which has more accepted projects coordinated by Canary Islands' organisations in FP7 projects. In this area, the main scientific domain is PE9 Universe Sciences, within which all projects are led by the Instituto Canario de Astrofísica (IAC). The area corresponding to Life sciences has 6 projects, most of them related with LS7 Applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics, Therapies and Public Health. Social Sciences and Humanities have 3 projects, all of them related with SH1 Individuals, Markets and Organisations.

According to Figure 11, Physical sciences and engineering is still the area which has more accepted projects, a total of 20 coordinated by some Canary Islands' organisation in H2020. Once again, most of them are related with PE9 Universe Sciences (10) and led by the Instituto Canario de Astrofísica (IAC). Social Sciences and Humanities have increased the number of projects, from 3 to 12. SH2 Institutions, Values, Environment and Space are the scientific domains that have the most accepted projects (5). Two of them are led by the Canary Islands Government, two by local institutions and one by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. Life Sciences has 9 accepted projects, most of them related with LS7 Applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics, Therapies and Public Health (3) and led by the Canary Islands Government (2) and the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (1).

Figure 10. Number of projects coordinated by Canary Islands Regions in FP7 filtered by their respective scientific domains.

Source: on work

Figure 11. Number of projects coordinated by Canary Islands Regions in H2020 filtered by their respective scientific domains.

Source: on work

4) Third countries participation

Analysing the research and innovation relation between each outermost region and the major neighbouring third countries can provide useful information on their capacity to connect and position themselves as recognised partners. To examine these collaborations, two sources of information can be used: the Interreg programmes (MAC; Caraïbes, Océan Indien) and the H2020 dashboard.

In order to know the capacity of the Canary Islands as a preferential stakeholder in participation for the framework projects FP7 and H2020, we have analysed, firstly, the information provided by Forward partners of the Canary Islands regarding third countries' participation in projects together with our region in the Interreg MAC programme.

From this analysis, it is inferred that there are three neighbouring countries that take part in this programme along with some Canarian partner. Specifically, Cape Verde has 10 projects of this kind in common with the Canary Islands; Senegal has 4 and Mauritania 5.

Secondly, the participation of these three countries (Cape Verde, Senegal and Mauritania) in FP7 and H2020 calls is analysed in order to subsequently determine the number of projects shared with the Canary Islands.

From said analysis, we gather that Cape Verde shared 1 FP7 project of the approved 9 the country has and 2 of the 11 H2020 projects. In the case of Senegal, of their 49 FP7 framework programmes, none were shared with the Canary Islands, while of their 48 approved H2020 projects, they shared 1. Finally, with Mauritania, the Canary Islands did not share any of their approved projects, which were one in FP7 and another in H2020.

Another Canary Islands neighbour is Morocco. This country cannot participate in Interreg MAC, but it participates in European framework programmes. Of the 131 Morocco FP7 funded projects, none are shared with Canary Islands. The same goes for H2020, within which Morocco has 70 funded projects.

In addition to this, we wanted to characterise the connections between the Canary Islands and their neighbours in terms of fields of cooperation. According to the information given by the partners and the FP7 Funded Projects (EC), the FP7 project shared between the Canary Islands and Cape Verde coincides with one of the most frequent topics of interest in this country, the environment. In the H2020 programme, the shared topics are focused on the Atlantic Ocean and on sustainable management of land and waters to secure healthy food. But there is no information regarding topics from the H2020 Dashboard filtered by country so no comparison can be made. Moreover, we could not compare the most frequent H2020 topics

between Senegal and the Canary Islands in their shared projects either. The same goes for Morocco, although there is no project shared between the two regions.

B - Regional innovation system

The Canary Islands R&I system presents a series of weaknesses that could be considered structural, where the effort in terms of research and regional development is low and below the European and Spanish average. The Canary Islands is the second Autonomous Community with the lowest intensity of spending in R&I (0,50% compared to the national 1,21%, data from 2017).

Figure 12. R&I Expenditure (% over PIB). 2017

Source: INE (National Statistics Institute), Statistics in R&I activities

Moreover, R&I activities are mainly supported by the public sector, with very low R&I corporate levels (both in investments and human resources); the total corporate R&I expenditure in the Canary Islands is lower than in the rest of the country (15,45% compared to 54,96%, respectively, for 2017).

This is all caused, to a large extent, by the weakness of the Canarian production system, characterised by a greater number of SMEs and micro-SMEs with very low research capabilities and mostly specialised in labour-intensive service sectors and with very little added value.

In addition, there is also little interaction between businesses and research centres and universities, thus generating low levels of technological transfer (patents, licences, spin-off, etc.) and a reduced innovation intensity in innovating businesses, which, in the Canary Islands amounts to 0,18, compared to the national 0,89 (data from 2016).

The previously noted main indicators position the regional innovation system of the Canary Islands significantly behind the Spanish and EU averages, so it is necessary to implement new plans and actions that will allow for the modification of the current situation with the purpose of progressively bringing the Canary Islands closer to the national average first and, subsequently, to the European average.

Despite the noted weaknesses in terms of R&I, the Canary Islands Science, Technology and Innovation System shows some strengths, such as the existence of a significant research potential based on the capacity of the human resources in La Laguna and Las Palmas de Gran Canaria universities and other research centres in fields of excellence, namely astrophysics, marine sciences, renewable energies, biotechnology, biomedicine, ICTs, microelectronics, neuroscience, nanotechnology and advanced materials, among others, some of which are framed within the Key Enabling Technologies (KET). These R&I fields, correspond, to a greater and lesser degree, with those identified as priorities within the Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3) in the Canary Islands: astrophysics and space, marine-maritime sciences, biotechnology and biomedicine related to biodiversity and tropical diseases.

In order to create a solid base of knowledge in the boundary between science and technology, R&I capabilities in universities, public centres and organisations in the Canary Islands need to approach the challenges of society and allow for future scientific-technological developments. The critical mass needs to increase and the scattering of research groups needs to be corrected so as to extend the impact of R&I results in key areas for smart

specialisation, ensuring the promotion of interregional collaboration between research groups as well as between these groups and the production systems.

On the other hand, the innovation system in the Canary Islands entails great difficulties for the expansion of the processes of knowledge transfer, notably due to the presence of an economic structure with reduced possibilities of absorption, the rare private involvement in R&I activities, the low technological demand, as well as the insufficient levels of innovation.

In this context, it is necessary to, on the one hand, consolidate some of the region's strengths, promoting the technological and scientific equipment and infrastructures that allow to overcome the structural problems present and, on the other hand, encourage the creation of R&I projects, both public and private, that favour, not only corporate innovation, but also the transfer of technology and the cooperation between businesses and public research centres. In the same way, the access to funding for innovative projects has to be improved and the incorporation of new research personnel to universities and public research centres promoted.

The previous objectives have to be carried out emphasising those specialisation fields in which the Canary Islands have competitive advantage, which stem from the conjunction of geographic characteristics with local capabilities in research and innovation, such as: the knowledge and exploration of the sky (astrophysics) and the oceans (oceanography), biodiversity (biotechnology), tourism, development and export of technologies in the field of renewable energies and water treatment, activities related to the maritime-marine sector, service platform to Africa, etc. which are included in RIS3.

1) Mapping the regional innovation system

The regional innovation systems approach aims at understanding the processes that determine the capacity of a territory to produce knowledge and turn it into new, successful solutions. To gather general information on the regional natural, human and economic resources, partners employed the [Eurostat](#) database, as well as regional databases managed by statistics offices, observatories and public bodies.

Regional profile

In 2018, the Canary Islands had a total population of 2.127.685 and a Population density of 286 pop./km². While the population aged between 20 and 64 amounted to 1.375.865 people, those younger than 20 amounted to 420.290, and those older than 64 amounted to 331.530 people. The birth and death rates in 2017 were very similar (7.45 people/birth and 7.2 people/death).

The total surface area adds up to 7.446,95 km², 3.012,37 km² of which are protected. Moreover, the total Marine area adds up to 490.337 km²; 455.397 km² of those are an Exclusive economic zone and 17.147 km² represent the protected marine area.

In terms of Macroeconomic data, the global value has risen every year between 2000 and 2017, except during the years 2008-2015, which corresponds to an important economic crisis period. Something similar happened with the GDP index per capita, between 2008 and 2015. In 2017 this index increased up to 44.502,73€. The GDP Ratio vs. EU mean in percentage, reached its maximum before the economic crisis, between 2006 and 2007 (0,39%), but after this period it decreased to 0,34%, the same value obtained in 2001.

The amount of exports of goods and services reached its maximum in 2018 (3.711,07 M€), taking into account the period between 2000 and 2018. Import of goods and services also reached their maximum in 2018 (17.375,93 M€), taking into account the same period. The employment rate reached its maximum before the economic crisis, 62,3% in 2007. After this, it decreased up until 2013, when it started to increase reaching 57,4% in 2018. Conversely, the unemployment rate reached around 20,1% at that time, doubling the 2007 rate, 10,5%. The service sector was the first economic sector, encompassing 87,78% of total employment in the region. It is also the sector with an added gross value: 35.281.559 employers and 124.501 associated companies. Other sectors (Agriculture, forestry and fishing; Industry; Energy; and Construction) were less important in terms of these indexes.

In terms of the region's export activities in 2018, Europe was the main partner for Special codes (mainly: supplies to ships and aircraft); Machinery, apparatus and mechanical devices, parts for these machines; and Fruits and edible fruits. For Mineral fuels, mineral oils and products of their distillation, and bituminous materials, the main partners were America and Europe.

Regional research capabilities

For a comprehensive census of the Canary Islands regional research capabilities, specified at the organisation and research group levels, partners mobilised their regional community to draw a list of the research groups operating in each institution. The analysis of the reported data helps us understand the characteristics of higher education and research institutions in Canary Islands.

In the table below the main information concerning research institutions, groups and researchers of the FORWARD partners in the region is collected, taking into consideration the number of researchers expressed by "head count" (number of people).

Table 12. Main research indicators

Name of Research institution	Number of the research group	Number of researchers	Average number of foreign post docs per year	Average number of doctoral graduates per year	Average number of PhD students	Share of foreign PhD students of total
ULPGC	115	1717	18	162	397	13,16%
ULL	319	1914	8	124	956	11,95%
IAC	38	200	62	13	66	30,00%
ITC	9	84				
PLOCAN	N/A	N/A				
Total	479	3.915	88	299	1.419	

Source: own work

As can be observed, the Research Capabilities of the region are mainly gathered in the two public universities (ULL y ULPGC), which together comprise 91% of research groups and 93% of researchers. Other public research centres are included (ITC, IAC y PLOCAN), with fewer research activities, although, it should be noted that IAC, with a first-class research excellence award, has 38 research groups and a great number of researchers (200).

The institution with a greater number of research groups and researchers in the region is the ULL, which comprises 66,5% and 49% of the total. It is followed by the ULPC with 24% of groups and 44% of researchers.

However, if we analyse the **average number of foreign post docs per year** in the region, the IAC is the most attractive centre for foreigners, with a greater number of them (62) compared to the two universities, which together do not reach half of that number (26). Thus, the IAC receives 71% of foreign post docs annually.

Even though the **average number of doctoral graduates per year** is similar in both public universities (162 ULPGC and 124 ULL), the **average number of PhD students** at ULL (956) is more than double than those at ULPGC (397).

Concerning the **share of foreign PhD students of the total**, it is once again superior for IAC compared to the two public universities, reaching 30%.

The data referring to the number of FP7 and H2020 projects submitted by FORWARD partners, the number of projects awarded, and the total EC contribution awarded to H2020 projects is collected in the table below.

Table 13. Number of projects and total EC contribution awarded to H2020 projects

Name of Research Institution	Number of FP7 projects submitted	Number of FP7 projects awarded	Number of H2020 projects submitted	Number of H2020 projects awarded	Total EC contribution awarded to H2020 projects
ULPGC	107	24	175	24	7.199.024,3
ULL	57	9	130	9	5.235.966,9
IAC	74	16	109	15	10.935.816,5
PLOCAN	10	9	75	19	3.409.927,0
ITC	29	3	25	9	1.740.444,9
CONSULTA EUROPA	2	1	15	5	1.244.243,7

Source: own work

Table 14. Research Framework participation – General data

INDICATORS		FP7 (2007-2013)	HORIZON 2020
Research institutions analysis	GLOBAL ANALYSIS		
	Average FP rank of the regional research organisations		1140,6
	Average success rate of the regional research organisations	32,42%	19%
	Average number of FP projects by research organisations	10	14
	RANKING		
	Name of the organisation with the most FP projects	ULPGC	ULPGC
	Share of the total FP Projects awarded to the first organisation	27,63%	23,48%
	Name of the second organisation with the most of FP projects	IAC	PLOCAN
	Share of the total FP Projects awarded to the second organisation	25,00%	17,39%
	Name of the third organisation with the most FP projects	ULL/PLOCA N	IAC
	Share of the total FP Projects awarded to the third organisation	11,84%	13,04%
	Name of the research organisation with the highest success rate	PLOCAN	ITC
	Name of the second research organisation with the highest success rate	CE	CE
	Name of the third research organisation with the highest success rate	IAC	PLOCAN
	ESIF / H2020 ratios		
	Name of the first research organisation with the highest ratio H2020 / ESIF amount		PLOCAN
	Name of the second research organisation with the highest ratio		CE

	H2020 / ESIF amount		
	Name of the third research organisation with the highest ratio H2020 / ESIF amount		ULPGC
	Name of the first research organisation with the highest ratio ESIF amount / H2020		IAC
	Name of the second research organisation with the highest ratio ESIF amount / H2020		ULL
	Name of the third research organisation with the highest ratio ESIF amount / H2020		ITC

Source: own work

In this case, the institution CONSULTA EUROPA has been included because of the importance of its participation in H2020.

As we can gather from this, in the case of FP7 projects submitted (279), the ULPGC stands out first, with a greater number of them, 107, followed by IAC with 74. However, the highest success rate (no. of projects awarded) belongs to PLOCAN, which achieved the approval of almost all of its projects (9 out of the 10 submitted).

The status of H2020 differs in that it significantly surpasses the number of submitted projects in this call by all institutions (529), except for ITC, but the success rate is lower.

Finally, if we analyse the **success rate** of FP7 (21%) and H2020 (16%) participation for Canarian institutions, it can be observed that the smaller research institutions have a higher success rate in projects awarded (33% PLOCAN and 22% ITC) followed by the ULPGC (17%), IAC (17%) and the ULL (10%).

In the table below the main information regarding the region's institutions and researchers with themes linked to RIS3 is shown.

Table 15. Number of researchers and researchers group related to RIS3 themes

Name of Research institutions	Number of research groups	Number of researchers
ULPGC	83	202
ULL	70	550
ITC	7	N/A
IAC	38	200
PLOCAN	1	N/A

Source: own work

As we can see, there is a high number of research groups (168 in total) that are mainly linked with two institutions (ULPGC and ULL), which comprise 153 groups. Considerably behind and with little relevance in comparison, ITC, IAC and PLOCAN are represented.

The University of La Laguna stands out, with 70 research groups and a total of 550 researchers; more than double those of the ULPGC, which, however, has 13 research groups more.

At the ULPGC, these groups range from 2 researchers to 39 (IUMA (Institute for Applied Microelectronics), giving an average of 2,4 researchers. At ULL, groups range from 2 researchers to 21 (INGEMAR), giving an average of 7,8 researchers.

Regarding the size of research groups, from the table below it can be inferred that those of medium or small size are prominent.

Table 16. Number of researchers per group

No. researchers per group	ULPGC	ULL
Between 2 and 5	30	26
Between 6 and 12	41	33
Between 13 and 18	08	10
+ 18	01	01

Source: own work

As for the **RIS3 priorities / innovation-market pair** themes within which research groups work, the 10 most important ones are highlighted in the table below according to research institution:

Table 17. RIS3 priorities / innovation-market pair per research institutions

RIS3 priorities / innovation-market pair	ULPGC	ULL	PLOCAN	IAC	ITC
Social and economic valorisation of specialised R&D		52			
Green Growth and Sustainability	12	14			
European Mid-Atlantic Reference		5			
Digital Agenda		05			02
Health	15				
Marine Science and Technology	14	1	1		
Astrophysics and Space	2			38	
Cultural and environmental reference	12				
ICT	13				
Business Centre	8				

Source: own work

Lastly, and concerning the **Number of OR research groups work with**, both ULPG (16 groups) and ULL (15 groups) show a similar number of research groups the work with OR.

Higher education training

Like the census of research capabilities, data collection was realised through the mobilisation of regional higher education institutions, focused on higher education training (Master's and PhD). In order to acquire information regarding higher education training, FORWARD partners were invited to report on their Master's and PhD degrees.

Based on the information facilitated, there are 47 Master's degrees related with some RIS3 priority at both public Universities in Canary Islands: ULPGC reported 36, while ULL reported 11.

All of these Master's degrees are oriented towards a research programme and the average total number of students in all of them is 818 students. 87% of them have a duration of one year, while 13% have a duration of two years. As FORWARD partners reported, Social and Legal sciences is the most common area within the available Master's degrees. Table 18 shows the areas and sectors of these Master's.

Table 18. Areas and sectors of RIS3 Master's degrees at Canary Islands public universities.

Area/Sectors of the courses	Number of Master's degrees
Social and Legal Sciences	11
Engineering and Architecture	10
Arts and Humanities	8
Sciences	4
Health Sciences	3
Science & Technology - Health	3
Applied Economy	2
Education	1
ICT	1
Science & Technology - Astrophysics	1
Science & Technology - Energy	1
Science & Technology - sustainability + Digital agenda	1
Sciences & Technologies - Marine Biology	1

Source: own work

The information of RIS3 priorities of these Master's degrees is available in Table 19. As FORWARD partners reported, the Cultural and environmental reference RIS3 priority is the priority with a greater number of Master's degrees related with it.

Table 19. RIS3 priorities of Master's degrees.

RIS3 priorities	Number of Master's degrees
Cultural and environmental reference	10
Business Centre	9
Social and economic valorisation of specialised R&D via thematic concentration	8
ICT	6
Marine Science and Technology	4
Green Growth	3
Smart and sustainable leadership in tourism	3
Digital agenda	3
Industry, Farming, and cattle raising	2
Logistic and Transport	1
Health	1
Energy, water and environment	1

Note: there could be Master's degrees with more than one thematic RIS3 area.

Source: own work

There is no information reported on the programmes by FORWARD partners.

Innovation capabilities

Research and technology organisations (RTO) are important in our region because they act as an interface between knowledge producers and users: clusters, technology transfer centres, incubators and support services for innovators, maker spaces, etc. The identification of these stakeholders relied on the participation of universities, chambers of commerce and public bodies or structural funds managing authorities. Each organisation bore the responsibility to fill in a questionnaire to gather this information.

Canary Islands FORWARD partners detected eight facilities or programme/support services in our region. These facilities were: General Foundation of the University of La Laguna; Technology Transfer Office of the University of La Laguna; Cátedra Fundación DISA de Jóvenes Emprendedores de la Universidad de La Laguna; Cátedra Fundación Mapfre Guanarteme de Tecnología y Educación de la Universidad de La Laguna; Cátedra Fundación Cepsa de Innovación y Eficiencia Energética de la Universidad de La Laguna;

Cátedra Institucional en Telemedicina, Robótica y Telecirugía Fundación Canaria Ágora-Universidad de La Laguna; IACTEC-Technological and business collaboration space; and PLOCAN-Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias. All of these facilities are **Innovative entrepreneurship support services or programmes**, except PLOCAN-Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias which is a **research and technology organisation**.

Innovative entrepreneurship

Innovative entrepreneurship support services or programmes are all support services or programmes dedicated to innovative entrepreneurship (Acceleration programmes, incubators...). Meanwhile Research and Technology Organisation, RTOs, are public or private non-profit organisations that provide a range of research, development and technology services, principally to businesses and governments.

The General Foundation of the University of La Laguna; Technology Transfer Office of the University of La Laguna; and Cátedra Fundación DISA de Jóvenes Emprendedores de la Universidad de La Laguna give their support in any of the Canary Islands RIS3 priorities, while Cátedra Telemedicina does in "RIS3-Canary Islands, Atlantic reference Knowledge Transfer: talent economy", IACTEC does in "RIS3-Strengthening in astrophysics and space" and PLOCAN does in "RIS3-Energy, water and environment/ RIS3-Marine sciences and technology / RIS3-Cooperation for development / Canarian R&D".

In order to illustrate the smart specialisation priorities of the region, in terms of entrepreneurial and social innovation projects, our partners and other regional intermediaries with an extensive knowledge of the business sectors identified a non-exhaustive list of regional initiatives. The amount of initiatives detected amounts to seventy-six. RIS3 priorities in innovation-market pair were detected, namely twelve of them, mostly related with Digital agenda (2), Social and economic valorisation of specialised R&D via thematic concentration (9), Green growth and sustainability (3) and Smart and sustainable leadership in tourism (1). Some of the specific topics associated with those priorities those initiatives are working on are Marine sciences and technology; Energy, Water and Environment; or Strengthening in astrophysics and space.

Targeted market segments are represented in Figure 13. Industry, value chain, wind park operators, wind park owners, utilities, etc. are the main target market in the Canary Islands' innovative entrepreneurship.

Figure 13. Targeted market segments in the Canary Islands' innovative entrepreneurship.

Note: Sectors without percentage in Figure 13 represent only a 1%.

Source: own work

The innovative aspects of these projects can be consulted at Table 20.

Table 20. Innovative aspects of the Canary Islands' innovative entrepreneurship.

PROJECT OR COMPANY NAME/ASSOCIATED FORWARD INSTITUTION	ACTIVITY	INNOVATION TYPE	STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT (TRL)	VALUE PROPOSITION / INNOVATION CORE	RIS3	TARGETED MARKET/CLIENTS
FABLAB SPIN-OFF ULL	Interdisciplinary designing and manufacturing of prototypes, mainly by 3D designing and printing. The prototypes are employed for scientific divulgation and teaching/learning needs of diverse scientific fields (e.g. Astrophysics and Biomedicine)	Product innovation	NA	Combination of artistic traditional art design techniques with new disruptive 3D designing and printing Use of advanced digital tools for designing and manufacturing	Digital agenda	Innovative educational & scientific diffusion educational materials Computer-assisted technology for designing and manufacturing
ZIKAssays PROJECT ULL	Development of diagnostic tools for ZIKA virus infection	Product innovation	TRL=3	First in situ test Affordable cost Requires less lab work	Biomedicine	Rapid diagnostics market
SMALL-SCALE PROJECT ULL	To facilitate and promote a tailored biogas industry in the Canary Islands	Process innovation	TRL=7	The adaptation to the Canarian context enables the diversification of the livestock and tourist sector while securing the environment protection	Green growth and sustainability	Livestock Canarian farms and hotels
KAIZTEN ANALYTICS - SPIN-OFF ULL	Disruptive software development by big data analysis for new planning processes and services in the transport sector (ports), and/or distribution companies	Process innovation	TRL>9	The dynamic optimization of the operating procedures allows the alignment with eco-efficient goals	Digital agenda	Transport companies (Tenerife Ports) Distribution companies
NEUROCLINIC SPIN-OFF ULL	Development of clinical protocols to apply Non-Invasive Brain Stimulation Techniques in the treatment of depression and other neurological diseases	Product innovation	TRL=7	Improved life quality for the patients, even when other treatments have shown ineffective Cost-saving option (up to 40% cost reduction per patient vs standard pharmacological treatment)	Social and economic valorisation of R+D	Public and private healthcare system Private insurance companies

PROJECT OR COMPANY NAME/ASSOCIATED FORWARD INSTITUTION	ACTIVITY	INNOVATION TYPE	STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT (TRL)	VALUE PROPOSITION / INNOVATION CORE	RIS3	TARGETED MARKET / CLIENTS
LAGUNA CHEMTECH PROJECT ULL	Development of disruptive chromatography techniques to widening and improving the study of new materials	Product innovation	TRL=4	Improvement of the efficiency and sensitivity of solid-phase microextraction chromatography to enable the analysis of compounds related to environment and health problems	Social and economic valorisation of R+D	Companies selling and/or distributing Chromatography technique and disposables
CANSWATER PROJECT ULL	SW and HW development to easy water purification management	Product innovation	TRL=4	Matching of demand fluctuation and production of purified water up to grade III adapted to the user	Social and economic valorisation of R+D	Users of purified water of different grades (e.g. hospitals, laboratories, research c.)
WOOPTIX ULL	SW and sensing solutions for 3D-capture imaging	Product innovation	2<TRL<8	Exploitation of powerful astrophysics sensing concepts to be applied for 3D-capture imaging	Social and economic valorisation of R+D	smartphone, automotive, manufacturing, digital cameras, ophthalmology
Astrophysics and Space Incubator	Development of High-Tech industry regarding Space and astrophysics	Product Innovation		Space and astrophysics	Strengthening in astrophysics and space	Start-ups/Tech companies
ENTROPI	Target investment to address critical challenges along the value chain supporting multi-use platforms.	Product Innovation		Cost reduction. Innovative mooring and anchoring solutions. Remote controlled security. Surveillance	Marine sciences and technology	Industry, value chain, wind park operators, wind park owners, utilities, etc.
ELICAN	Offshore Wind Turbines. Deep Offshore 5MW Prototype. The technology is exceptionally fitted to meet the technical and logistical challenges of the sector as it moves into deeper locations with larger turbines, while allowing for drastic cost reduction.	Product Innovation	TRL 8	This project will design, build, certify and fully demonstrate in operative environment a deep water substructure prototype supporting Adwen's 5MW offshore wind turbine, to be installed in the Southeast coast of Las Palmas (Canary Islands). It will become the first bottom-fixed offshore wind turbine in all of Southern Europe and the first one worldwide to be installed with no need of heavy-lift vessels.	Energy, Water and Environment	Industry, value chain, wind park operators, wind park owners, utilities, etc.
WIP10+	The project WIP 10+, "Wind integrated platform for 10+ MW power per foundation.	Product Innovation	TRL 5-6	The project WIP 10+ demonstrated at sea and at significant scale a fully integrated offshore wind floating platform Wind2Power that holds a couple twin wind turbines of up to 6 MW each, and that it is also able to host additional functions due to its size.	Energy, water and environment	Industry, value chain, wind park operators, wind park owners, utilities, etc.

Source: on work

Regional flagship initiatives

To complete this part, partners and other regional intermediaries selected twenty-two initiatives as flagship initiatives in the Canary Islands. Their decision was made based on their scientific excellence, their contribution to the regional development, etc.

FORWARD Partners also reported about the RIS3 priorities / innovation-market pair involved in the flagship initiatives selected. As Figure 14 shows, Marine science and technology is the topic with a more number of projects (8) followed by Astrophysics and space (7).

Figure 14. Number of RIS3 priorities/innovation-market pair initiatives flagship selected by partners in Canary Islands.

Source: own work

Their geographic scale can be found in Figure 15. It can be observed that the International scale is the most frequent.

Figure 15. Number of flagships initiatives filtered by their geographical scale.

Source: own work

As partners reported, Infrastructure is the type of flagship with a larger number of projects. The type and number of flagship initiatives can be found in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Number of flagship initiatives in Canary Islands filtered by category.

Source: own work

According to Figure 17, the main source of funding for projects is the European Commission, which funds three out of ten flagships initiatives detected by project partners. There are some projects funded by two or more funding sources.

Figure 17. Funding source of Flagship initiative detected by projects partners.

Source: own work

2) Regional research performance

Research institutions are a key component of the RDI ecosystem. In H2020, they represent 54% of the total participation and get 64% of the EU net contribution. To assess the performance of regional research systems and allow inter-regional comparison, a set of indicators were codified with the information reported by FORWARD partners.

Interested in finding out the thematic relation between the research groups and the number of approved projects, we connected each of the 193 research groups informed by FORWARD partners to a scientific domain. From this analysis, it is inferred that the thematic area with the higher number of research groups, whose research lines revolve around this theme, is Earth System Science, with a total of 20 groups in which there are 93 associated researchers. In order to conduct this analysis, the criterion of one research field per research unit has been considered.

It is important to note that Earths System and Science is the scientific domain with the greater number of approved projects in the Canary Islands, with 21 in total. However, it is

also noteworthy that the thematic area Systems and Communication Engineering has 100 researchers associated with 9 research groups, and that they have fewer approved H2020 projects, with a total of 11 (See Table 21).

Table 21. Number of research groups according to thematic area

Research domains	Code	Theme	No. of research groups	No. of researchers (owning a PhD)
Life Sciences	LS1	Molecular Biology, Biochemistry, Structural Biology and Molecular Biophysics	4	25
Life Sciences	LS2	Genetics, 'Omics', Bioinformatics and Systems Biology	2	10
Life Sciences	LS3	Cellular and Developmental Biology	3	23
Life Sciences	LS4	Physiology, Pathophysiology and Endocrinology	3	21
Life Sciences	LS5	Neuroscience and Neural Disorders	10	83
Life Sciences	LS6	Immunity and Infection	3	12
Life Sciences	LS7	Applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics, Therapies and Public Health	9	79
Life Sciences	LS8	Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Biology	12	76
Life Sciences	LS9	Applied Life Sciences, Biotechnology, and Molecular and Biosystems Engineering	15	70
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE1	Mathematics	6	43
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE10	Earth System Science	20	93
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE2	Fundamental Constituents of Matter	2	11
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE3	Condensed Matter Physics		
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE4	Physical and Analytical Chemical Sciences	11	69
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE5	Synthetic Chemistry and Materials	2	23
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE6	Computer Science and Informatics	9	70
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE7	Systems and Communication Engineering	9	100
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE8	Products and Processes Engineering	7	63
Physical Sciences and Engineering	PE9	Universe Sciences		
Social Sciences and Humanities	SH1	Individuals, Markets and Organisations	11	78
Social Sciences and Humanities	SH2	Institutions, Values, Environment and Space	6	49
Social Sciences and Humanities	SH3	The Social World, Diversity, Population	6	53
Social Sciences and Humanities	SH4	The Human Mind and Its Complexity	6	35
Social Sciences and Humanities	SH5	Cultures and Cultural Production	3	30
Social Sciences and Humanities	SH6	The Study of the Human Past	5	47
TOTAL			164	1163

Source: own work

Some information that helps to determine the level of economic research outcomes are the number of spin-off creations and international patents owned by research institutions. According to the information facilitated by FORWARD partners, the total number of spin-offs over the last 5 years was 2: one in the ULL and other in the ITC. The total number of international patents over the last 5 years from academics was 11 which came from ULPGC (8), ITC (2) and ULL (1).

Focusing on data facilitated by FORWARD partners, the total number of scientific publications between ULPGC, ULL, IAC and ITC, amounts to 23.680.

ULPGC reported 2.087, ULL, 18.959, IAC, 2.576 and ITC 58. Meanwhile, the total number of international co-publications between ULL and IAC amounts to 3292, with ULL reporting 2.915 and IAC 377. There's no data facilitated by ULPGC.

3) Private sector implication

Examining the evolution of private R&D expenditures can thus provide useful information on the dynamics of the regional system. Public and private R&D comparisons could help to underline the implication of private stakeholders.

In the Canary Islands, R&D activities are mostly supported by the public sector, with a lower level of entrepreneur participation, both in investment and in human resources. All of this is due, to certain extent, to the weakness of the Canary Islands production system characterised by a greater proportion of SMEs and micro-SMEs with little research capacity and specialised, mostly, in tertiary labour-intensive sectors and with little added value.

The effort in innovation, measured through the expense in technological innovation made by companies, falls in 2016 compared to 2015 around 17.23%, which places the Canary Islands at position 14 of all 17 Spanish Autonomous Communities in 2016.

Likewise, a low interaction between companies and research centres and universities is detected, leading to low levels of technology transfer (patents, licenses, spin-offs, etc.) and a reduced intensity of business innovation which in the Canary Islands is 0.18 compared to the notional total of 0.89 (2016 data).

According to the R&D&I Observatory of the Canary Islands (OBIDIC) <http://www3.gobiernodecanarias.org/aciisi/obidic/>, which compares the information given by the EUROSTAT and the ISTAC, entrepreneur investment in R&D in 2013 was highest in the period between 2012 and 2017. The total percentage in 2013 was 21.27%, lower than in the EU (63.76%) and Spain (53.07%). Although the investment in 2017 increased in the EU (65.98%) and Spain (54.93%), it did not in the Canary Islands (15.37%).

The ratio between R&D investment and GDP (2017) was 0.5 in the Canary Islands, while in Spain it was 1.20% and in the EU, 2.03%. The 0.5% is lower than the 0.62% reached in 2010 in the Canary Islands.

In terms of R&D human resources in 2013, the last year compared by the OBIDIC, the ratio of R&D staff compared with the total employed population was 0.47% in the Canary Islands, while in Spain it was 1.22% and in the EU, 1.25%. In 2016, the ratio of researchers compared with R&D total staff in the Canary Islands was 70.21%, a little higher than the 61.51% in Spain and 63.92% in the EU. In 2017, the ratio of R&D employees in the private sector compared with R&D total employees was 17.20% in the Canary Islands. This ratio was lower than the Spanish ratio (44.33%) and the EU ratio (56.62%).

4) RIS3 priorities

The Canary Islands has a RIS3 Strategy approved by the European Commission in which [5 priority thematic domains](#) were identified for the development of the Region.

Figure 18. Canary Islands RIS3 Priorities

One of those domains, “Socioeconomic valorisation of R&I, specialisation and strengthening in astrophysics and space, maritime-marine sciences, biotechnology and biomedicine related

to biodiversity and tropical diseases” includes actions directly related to R&I policies that are developed in the Canary Islands through the EJE 1 (AXIS 1) in [Programa Operativo FEDER \(2014-2020\), or Operational Programme ERDF \(2014-2020\)](#), designated as: *“Strengthening of research, technological development and innovation”*.

The *“Socioeconomic valorisation of R&I, specialisation and strengthening in astrophysics and space, maritime-marine sciences, biotechnology and biomedicine related to biodiversity and tropical diseases”* priority encompasses 4 specific objectives, as well as a series of defined actions for its execution:

1. Specialisation and strengthening of priority domains.
2. Generation of knowledge and promotion of excellence.
3. Transfer of knowledge and technology and an increase of private participation in R&I.
4. Development of human capital and attraction of talent of excellence.

This AXIS 1 of the FEDER programme has at its disposal 94,97 million Euros from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF, FEDER in Spanish) to develop the actions considered each year by the Government of the Canary Islands in this matter, and so it can be recognised as the base of R&I policies in the Canary Islands. To the European investment provided by FEDER, we have to add the one corresponding to the Autonomous Community and the General State Administration, resulting in a total sum of 111,09 million Euros that will be applied to the R&I System in the Canary Islands during the 2014-2020 period.

The expected actions in this axis are being performed by:

- Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Información, Canary Islands Agency for Research, Innovation and Information Society
- Dirección General de Promoción Económica (General Management for Economic Promotion)

The rest of the RIS3-Canary Islands priorities reflect domains approached from other AXES in the POC-FEDER Canary Islands and not necessarily from an R&I perspective. These priorities are:

Smart leadership in tourism:

- Improvement of the competitiveness and productivity of the Canarian tourist product
- Production diversification based on tourism

Canary Islands, Smart Atlantic referent:

- Canary Islands, knowledge, technology and operational centre for development cooperation
- Canary Islands, business platform and financial centre of the Mid-Atlantic
- Canary Islands, Atlantic cultural and environmental referent
- Canary Islands, nodal centre of the Mid-Atlantic

Digital Agenda:

- New-generation access infrastructures
- Digital development

Green growth and sustainability:

- Low-carbon economy, industrial development and energy efficiency
- Eco-innovation, agriculture, fishing and environmental protection
- Bioeconomy based on Canarian biodiversity, Canary Islands, natural laboratory

Table “RDI-8 RIS3 priorities” of the RDI mapping file collects all of this RIS3 Canary Islands priorities.

5) Public policies

Regarding R&I policies, table “RDI-9 Existing Policies” of the RDI mapping file reflects the structure that defines the Government of the Canary Islands’ R&I policies, which comprises two great objectives, from which several actions and instruments are derived:

- 1. Improvement of R&I infrastructures and capacities to promote excellence in R&I matters**, and promotion of centres of competence, in particular of those of European interest:

- Strengthening of R&I institutions and creation, consolidation and improvement of scientific and technological infrastructures.
 - Update of the scientific equipment for the Gran Telescopio de Canarias (GRANTECAN, Great Telescope of the Canary Islands).
 - Strengthening of the Instituto Astrofísico de Canarias (IAC) and its observatories as international astronomical locations and support for new telescopes installed by international consortiums in the Canary Islands.
 - Scientific equipment and infrastructures in universities and technology parks.
 - Scientific equipment and infrastructures in research institutes and technology centres.
 - Leveraging of international scientific-technological infrastructures (10% investment) that settle in the Canary Islands and entail an important socioeconomic impact in the Canary Islands, as well as technological and industrial benefits in RIS3- Canary Islands priority domains.

2. Promotion of business investments in R&I, development of connections and synergies between companies, R&I centres and the higher education sector, particularly through the promotion of investments in product and services development, the transfer of technology, social innovation, ecological innovation, public service applications, the encouragement of demand, network interconnection, associations and open innovation through Smart specialisation, and by means of supporting applied technological research, experimental lines, early product validation, advanced manufacturing capabilities and first production, in particular, for key enabling technologies and circulation of multipurpose technologies:

- Promotion of R&I activities led by businesses, support for the creation and consolidation of innovative businesses and support for innovation public purchasing.
 - Innovation bonuses.
 - Programmes for the promotion of innovation in businesses, technological transfer and circulation and cooperation

- Applied business projects in research activities and experimental development.
- Knowledge transfer and cooperation between businesses and research centres.
 - Networks of support for innovation and entrepreneurship based on innovation (CIDE, PIDi, EEN networks).
 - Spreading of science and technology (Ciencia Canaria).
 - Support to innovation clusters.
 - Transfer offices and networks and support for business-research centre-university cooperation.
 - Creativity, innovation in real environments and concept tests.
 - Social Innovation.
- Promotion and generation of boundary knowledge and knowledge oriented towards the challenges of society, development of emerging technologies.
 - R&I projects (public).
 - Applied business projects in research activities and experimental development.

C - Regional organisational characteristics

To evaluate the impact of the resources and strategies of institutions, we conducted a fourfold analysis:

1) Review of higher education and research organisations' participation determinants

According to the literature on FP participation, the inner characteristics of candidate organisations influence their chance of success, through 4 main determinants.

First, the size of the institution.

Once the data provided by FORWARD partners has been analysed, **the size of the institutions**, albeit an important indicator, does not seem to be a determining factor in the Canary Islands regarding participation in FP, as can be inferred from the table below.

Table 22. Relation between groups/researchers and FP projects

Name of Research institution	Number of research group	Number of researchers	Number of FP7 projects	Number of H2020 projects	Total FP projects submitted
-------------------------------------	---------------------------------	------------------------------	-------------------------------	---------------------------------	------------------------------------

			submitted	submitted	
ULPGC	115	1717	107	175	282
ULL	319	1914	57	130	187
IAC	38	200	74	109	183
ITC	7	84	29	25	54
PLOCAN	N/A	N/A	10	75	85
Total	479	3.915	277	514	791

Source: own work

We find that the ULL, the first regional institution in number of research groups and researchers, is not the first in FP participation. In fact, it holds the third position in the FP7 programme (behind ULPGC and IAC) and the second in H2020, although it is close to the IAC, a much smaller research institution in comparison.

The first position in FP projects submitted is held by the ULPGC, which, with a smaller number of research groups (almost a third of ULL's groups) and researchers than ULL, shows almost 100 projects more than the ULL.

It should also be noted that IAC, much smaller than ULL and ULPGC both, with just 38 research groups and 200 researchers, represents 23% of FP projects, compared with ULL's 23,6% and ULPGC's 35,6%.

Thus, it can be concluded that, in the Canary Islands, the size of the institution is not a determining factor in FP participation.

Secondly, the orientation: those which concentrate more resources to research show a higher rate of success than organisations which privilege teaching. This "research intensity" can be measured by the ratio between the number of PhD students and the number of undergraduates (Enger, 2017).

Orientation does not seem to be a determining factor either in the success rate in FP programmes for both Canarian universities. The table below showcases how ULPGC, with a lower PhD/ undergraduate ratio (2,4%) than ULL (5,4%), that is, with a lower "research intensity", has a much higher success rate (17% ULPGC and 7% ULL).

Table 23. Relation between PhD / undergraduate and FP projects

Name of Research institution	Average number of PhD students	Number of undergraduate	Ratio PhD/ undergraduate	Number of FP7 projects awarded	Number of H2020 projects awarded
ULPGC	397	16.459	2,4%	21	27
ULL	956	17.485	5,4%	9	9
IAC	66			19	15

Sources: ULL (2017/18 academic year) and ULPGC (2018/19academic year). Own work.

Thirdly, scientific excellence. Though many question the contribution of FP to the production of world-class scientific results, the scientific activity of an institution is of tremendous importance. Two indicators may be used to estimate this effort: the scientific productivity (measured by the number of publication per full time equivalent) and the impact (determined by the average number of publications' citations).

Regarding the estimation of the scientific excellence of the three main research institutions in the Canary Islands, the lack of data on the share of publications in the top 10% most cited, both for ULPGC and IAC, prevents the comparison of scientific production and its impact.

Table 24. Scientific publications and their relevance (top 10% most cited) per research institution

Name of Research institution	Number of scientific publications	% share of publications in the top 10% most cited
ULL	18.959	7,6%
ULPGC	2.087	N/A
IAC	2.576	N/A

Source: own work

Fourthly, the degree of international openness. More integrated units and institutions, which develop large-scale cooperation will also enjoy a greater participation rate. Openness can be estimated by the number of international co-publications, the share of foreign PhD or the number of foreign researchers.

In order to know the degree of international openness of the three main research institutions, a relation between the three indicators in the table below has been established: Number of co-publications with international partners (including partners from EU countries), Average number of foreign post docs per year and Share of foreign PhD students of total.

Table 25. Degree of international openness per research institution

Name of Research institution	Number of international co-publications	Average number of foreign post docs per year	Share of foreign PhD
ULL	2.915	115,4	11,95%
ULPGC	N/A	52	13,16%
IAC	377	19,80	30%

Source: own work

According to the data above, the institution with the highest degree of international openness is ULL, with a higher number of international co-publications and a share of foreign PhD similar to ULPGC.

2) Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions

Given that in the previous section it was concluded that in the Canary Islands the size of the research institution is a factor in the number of project submissions, although not as determining as it may seem, here the focus will be on the indicators related to the success rate, as well as their rank in terms of H2020 participation, which, once again confirm this affirmation.

Table 26. Ranking of research institutions according to H2020 participation

Name of Research institution	Number of H2020 projects	Ranking
ULPGC	21	645-680
PLOCAN	16	865-925
IAC	15	926-986
ITC	10	1386 -1529
ULL	9	1530-1709
FCPCT-ULPGC	3	4341-6318

Source: CORDIS. July 2019

As per the CORDIS table above, the Canarian research institutions have been classified according to the number of H2020 projects awarded and their relative position in a ranking of EU research institutions that participate in H2020. We find that, even though ULL is the region's first research institution in number of research groups and researchers, it holds the ranking's fifth position compared to other Canarian institutions, behind a medium research centre (IAC) and two small ones (PLOCAN, ITC).

If we analysed the **success rate** of H2020 participation for Canarian institutions, there are even more differences, as can be observed in Table 27, as the smaller research institutions have a higher success rate in projects awarded (36% ITC and 25% PLOCAN). ULL (7%) and ULPGC (14%), on the same level as IAC (14%), hold the last positions.

Table 27. Success rate of H2020 participation per research institution

Name of Research institution	Number of H2020 projects submitted	Number of H2020 projects awarded	Success rate
------------------------------	------------------------------------	----------------------------------	--------------

ULPGC	175	24	14%
ULL	130	9	7%
IAC	109	15	14%
PLOCAN	75	19	25%
ITC	25	9	36%

Source: own work

3) Analysis of institutional strategies

To conduct the analysis of research organisations, the Canary Islands FORWARD partners, ULL, ULPGC, ITC, IAC and PLOCAN, collected information from governance representatives of their organisations. The elements gathered from these interviews present the following results:

The five research organisations have experience in FP programmes, with different intensity in the number of projects, from 9 to 24.

Table 28. Number of H2020 projects by R&D organisation

R&D organisation	Number of H2020 projects
ULPGC	27
PLOCAN	20
IAC	15
ULL	9
ITC	9

Source: own work

The **ULPGC**, with the highest number of participations, recognises FP programmes are very important for the organisation and in line with some of the areas described in their Strategic Plan. The European Project Office (OPE) promotes EU funding opportunities through seminars and conferences, Infodays and training at Doctoral School. The OPE has participated in national programmes to consolidate their performance and productivity and to assist the ULPGC research groups to carry out the transition from FP7 to H2020 with full guarantees. The OPE follows up on the project proposals and projects achieved annually. The ULPGC participates in certain thematic networks with the involvement of the researchers themselves.

For **PLOCAN** the FP programmes are very important. It includes set out objectives concerning FP participation and implemented a monitoring system to follow the participation to FP programmes.

The **IAC** strongly agrees on the importance of the FP programmes for the organisation that are integrated as external funding to cover equipment, additional personnel and operational costs. The financial resources to implement the IAC Strategic Plan come primarily from three different sources: 1) The budget from the Spanish General State Administration (Administración General del Estado, AGE). 2) The budget from the Canary Islands' Regional Government. 3) External funding obtained under competitive calls, contracts, and other incomes, to carry out research and technology programmes, as well as to train new researchers and technicians. The IAC strategy regarding H2020 is to apply to those topics well aligned with IAC's strategic objectives. The IAC does not have specific FP objectives to achieve in terms of success rate, number of proposals, etc. There are not specific agents/offices representing their interest, but the regional and national funding agencies facilitate this role when required.

The **ULL** considers that increasing and widening the participation in FP programmes is the strategic goal of the Vice-Rectorate for Research. The ULL performs reviews periodically to quantify the number of projects presented and the budget requested. The ULL also sends a satisfaction survey about the current service of the support office. The ULL started to be more present in some forums at Brussels in 2019.

The **ITC** agrees that FP programmes represent a good instrument for generating a high level of knowledge and contacts for the R&D departments of their institution. A project office was created in 2017 with the purpose of facilitating access to different financial resources to the R&I departments of the ITC, including the FP programme. The ITC is working to increase the FP participation, with no concrete objectives yet. There is a grant unit to support the participation in funding programmes, not only FP, but a formal monitoring system should be implemented. The ITC has regular contact with the Canary Islands' Brussels office.

In addition, some **good practices regarding the governance of the organisation and FP programmes participation** were identified:

- To encourage the participation in FP programmes with internal control points:
 - First: to receive a preliminary summary by the proposer to evaluate the feasibility of the proposal and save the time of the PI in case the proposal is not well aligned with the call.
 - Second: to provide specific guidelines for each topic (tips, remarks, etc.) and to carry out a thoroughly review of each draft (at least twice).

- Third: to pass an internal threshold that must be achieved to go ahead with the submission.
- The promotion activities performed by the International Projects Office enabled to increase participation by 40%.
- To promote the COSTS action as a pre-frame for H2020 projects development and ERANET calls. ERANETs are found to be a Good alternative for researchers who feel overwhelmed by EU calls because the project management is performed by the AEI, as happens with national calls, to which researchers are more accustomed to.

4) Analysis of Support Services

The regional support services were provided by the FORWARD partners GOBCAN, ULL, ULPGC, ITC, IAC and PLOCAN¹ and collects difficulties and good practices from FP facilitators in their daily practice.

There are **four public support offices in the Canary Islands**:

- The International Projects Office (ULL-TTO) at ULL, created in 2018.
- The European Project Office (OPE) at ULPGC, created in 2014.
- The Institutional Projects & Technology Transfer Office (OTRI) at IAC, created in 1989.
- The branch of the Enterprise Europe Network in the Canary Islands (EEN-Canarias) at ITC, created in 2008.

These services are provided free of charge for the targeted public (ULL, ULPGC, IAC and Canary Islands SMEs and other organisations respectively)

Services description:

The ULL-TTO identifies potential H2020 successful participants and proposes adapted support to empower them with the correct skills, network, processes... It provides training on Horizon 2020 development process from the selection of the call to the submission of the proposal, sometimes with the support of private consultancy services. However, there is

¹ This data collection does not include research organisations outside the FORWARD partnership.

one member with professional experience in H2020 proposal writing. The ULL-TTO screens Horizon 2020 opportunities to share with potential H2020 candidates and is also planning the implementation of a plan for calls search by thematic areas. The office identifies the right partners and networks in order to join collaborate. It offers support in proposal conception, partners search, proposal writing, budget consortium coordination, drawing up budgets and proposal submission. The researchers are in charge of the technical project management, and the FGULL deals with administrative and financial project management.

The TTO provides support to ULL researchers on FP programmes (H2020), H2020, LIFE, COSTs, ERANETS and Interreg.

The OPE-ULPGC: The OPE is the link between researchers and NCPs to channel queries about topics; for proposals review (MSCA); resolution of legal and financial doubts. The OPE has organised infodays at the ULPGC with the participation of NCPs and regularly attends national infodays. The OPE belongs to the Spanish Network of European Offices (RedOE), participating in the Working Group of Promotion.

Annually, the OPE provides training sessions at the Doctoral School and teaching and research staff (PDI) of the ULPGC (How to find R&D opportunities in the EU -H2020 and DGs; Introduction to H2020 proposal writing). External consultants have also been hired to train researchers and the OPE staff in proposal writing and impact section.

The OPE provides support to ULPGC researchers on FP programmes (FP7, H2020, Horizon Europe) and other EU Funding programmes (DGs)

The OTRI-IAC: The OTRI is the local contact point for IAC researchers. It shares with the European institutions (Commission) and other national intermediaries (Ministries, NCP's) propositions to be included in Horizon 2020, promotes research capacities and important research fields for IAC projects.

The OTRI defines activities to increase the excellence of the researcher, sometimes with private consultants. The OTRI offers support in proposal conception, partners search, proposal writing, budget consortium coordination, drawing up budgets, proposal submission information point and support for the implementation of the project. It organises training on the Horizon 2020 development process from the selection of the call to the submission of the proposal.

The OTRI provides support to IAC researchers on FP programmes (FP7, H2020, Horizon Europe), National research programmes and other EU Funding programmes.

The EEN-Canarias service, at **ITC**, is the regional node of the Enterprise Europe Network that supports the participation in research EU projects, especially for SMEs. The ITC supports SMEs interested in H2020 SME Instrument with two workshops per year, in cooperation with the Spanish NCP. It also offers partner search in H2020 and other EU calls and reviews draft proposals for H2020 SME instrument. For SME instrument beneficiaries, the ITC works as KAM, in the implementation of the projects, helping the SME to identify their needs and the right coach to help them.

Regarding other H2020 programmes, the ITC promotes partner searches from other EEN nodes, helps local organisations to identify partners through their own partner search, disseminates call for proposals, info days, brokerage events... and provides advice to potential beneficiaries in administrative issues to participate in the calls, such as PIC registration.

The EEN-Canarias provides support to SME, companies and other organisations on FP programmes (H2020, Horizon Europe) and other EU Funding programmes.

Results:

- The average success rate of the support services ranges between 7% and 30%.

Support service needs identified:

- Human Resources: It is necessary to increase the number of long-term (permanent) OPE technicians.
- Training: the technicians need to be professionalised (continuous training)
- Division of tasks and staff: management vs promotion technicians.
- Protocols: need of protocols and manuals (internal for technicians) and external (H2020 participation guidelines for researchers).
- Real implementation of the EURAXESS services at the ULPGC is needed (implementation of HR4R logo, developing strategies for attracting foreign talent (MSCA-IF), mobility of ULPGC researchers abroad.
- It is necessary to involve more Canarian companies in FP and University-Companies collaborations.

- Close the circle to transfer knowledge and technology through the Transfer of Result Units (OTRIs) and the Intellectual Property Offices (patents derived from the projects).

Good practices identified:

- Promotional activities (Thematic Workshops H2020).
- Training in the context of the Doctoral School.
- Use of EEN as a good network for partner searches. Database of partner opportunities.

D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

The following subsections describe and analyse the Canary Islands' situation in terms of success, failure and self-selection in FP7 and H2020 programmes.

1) Patterns of success and failure

The FORWARD partners ULL, ULPGC, ITC, IAC and PLOCAN conducted a total of **45 interviews** to scientific and technical leaders of FP proposals in order to identify the keys to success and failure in FP7 and H2020 programmes. The interviews were organised into two groups, following the interview protocol provided by NEXA:

1. The **Participant Group**, composed by **32 regional participants** successful in 50 projects from FP7 and H2020 programmes.
2. The **Candidate Group**, composed of **13 regional candidates** unsuccessful in H2020 with 25 proposals.

The members of each group were interviewed to identify keys to success and failure factors, and find potential common traits among them related to their profiles in terms of scientific activity, international mobility, knowledge of the FP...

Keys to success

The most common traits of the 32 successful participants are:

- Research profile:
 - 93% of participants have a doctorate degree, from 1984 to 2014.

Figure 19. Research profile: doctorate degree

- International network:
 - 72% of successful participants have international mobility experiences, ranging from at least 1 year to more than 5 years.

Figure 20. International mobility

- 68% of participants have an international network with strong and regular collaborations with their partners. This group includes not only attendance

to annual conferences, but also collaboration in projects and co-publications.

Figure 21. International networking profiles

- FP Knowledge and experience:
 - Most of the participants have FP experience in 1 to 10 projects. There are two researchers with 20 participations and one with more than 50 participations.
 - Despite having almost half of the participants registered in the European Commission expert database, only 28% have participated as evaluators.

Figure 22. Registered as expert in the EC Expert Database

Figure 23. Participated in a proposal evaluation for the EC

The analysis of the FP projects reported revealed that the most common way of participation is building their own consortium (42%), followed by being invited by the core team, with (27%) or without (17%) previous cooperation. Mobilising a pre-existing network of collaboration represents the 12% and only 2% comes from partner's search processes.

The most used project development support services are private consultancy and the services provided by their own institutions, European projects office or similar.

Figure 24. How have you taken part in this project?

2) Analysis of self-selection determinants

The FORWARD partners ULL, ULPGC, ITC, IAC and PLOCAN conducted a total of **14 interviews**, following the interview protocol provided by NEXA, in order to identify the determinants of self-selection along four types of causes:

1. the lack of knowledge on the opportunities offered by FP
2. the perception of one's own abilities
3. the lack of interest in a programme
4. the lack of resources and support

The results of these interviews were included in FP-3 Self-Selection Determinants from the FP Participation file. The answers show that the most common determinants of self-selection were:

1. The lack of interest in a programme

- *“I found that the effort required to enter and FP programme (Master the programme, Build appropriate networks, time investments) is too great”*
- *“I believe the time needed to build a project is too important in comparison to the chance of success”*

2. The lack of resources and support:

- *“I do not have sufficient time or resources to dedicate time to such activity / I am overworked”*

III - Analysis of the representations

OR R&I community members often depict FP programmes as too complicated, competitive and unsuited to local situations and realities. These prejudices generate a lack of ambition and involvement. Though poorly studied and often underestimated, beliefs and fears constitute powerful obstacles to H2020 access; overcoming them can be energy and time consuming, particularly when building participative territorial action plans.

Therefore, the involvement of a large and diverse panel of members of the R&I community through interviews and a survey offers the opportunity to map and assess representations on FP participation and explanatory factors.

Based on the results of the interviews and survey, the following synthesis highlights the main determinants (obstacles & levers) that influence the participation of the Canary Islands according to local stakeholders. This synthesis emphasises the widespread beliefs and convictions, in terms of regional participation and determinants.

1) Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders (analysis of interviews; analysis of survey)

As a result of the analysis of the online survey and the interviews, the following obstacles and levers were identified:

1) Lack of technical and administrative support in proposal writing:

Obstacles	Levers
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Excessive bureaucracy and complex procedures.• Insufficient administrative support for researchers.• Lack of support to prepare proposals.• Lack of knowledge about the programme (clarity and orientation of the calls).• Lack of time to prepare the proposals (research staff overloaded).• Lack of incentives to participate.• Low level in foreign languages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Increase the capacity of European project support offices.• Information and support throughout the process.• Support for the development and direction of the project and preparation of proposals.• Have experts in different areas who advise on the preparation of proposals.• Administrative support plans.• Qualified administrative staff for these calls.• Use less money in intermediary structures and more in researchers.• Training on the call for proposals and the

	<p>processes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional support as a private consultancy. • Intermediary support organisations.
--	---

2) Difficulty to build partnerships and networking:

Obstacles	Levers
<p>Difficulty in partner search.</p> <p>Lack of international contacts to prepare proposals.</p> <p>To reach consensus among the consortium for common objectives and strategies.</p> <p>Insulation and costs.</p> <p>To create a reliable consortium, to find reliable partners.</p>	<p>To have a solid international network in advance.</p> <p>International network with high level researchers.</p> <p>Visibility at European level.</p> <p>Active networking.</p> <p>Strategies to recruit IPs in strategic areas.</p> <p>To generate large communication channels to enhance contacts.</p> <p>To connect Spain-Europe research.</p> <p>To participate in networking events.</p>

3) Small size of research groups and research centres:

Obstacles	Levers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small size of the R&D&i groups. • Excessive atomisation of the research groups. • Low experience / skills to lead proposals. • Competitiveness / excellence of research groups. • Lack of leading R&D centres. • Size of R&D organisations and the connection between them. • Lack of interest of the University in recruiting talented researchers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop good research and offer something different, an innovative approach. • Multidisciplinary teams. • Different contents of the programmes. • Previous experience. • Access to innovative information. • Knowledge transfer.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of incentives to participate. 	
--	--

4) Low participation of SMEs:

Obstacles	Levers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weak relationship between SMEs and the R&D ecosystem. • Companies do not usually develop R&D projects. • Lack of innovation in companies. • Low investment capacity of companies. • Absence of involvement of the private sector. • The size of our companies and R&D organisations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contacts in Europe with companies and researchers • Participation of SMEs in existing consortia • Collaboration with innovation agents to detect disruptive technologies • To encourage the participation of SMEs by providing advisory services • To increase the private investment

5) Lack of institutional support, public authorities support:

Obstacles	Levers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient support from government institutions. • Little support from universities. • Insufficient experience and specialisation of intermediate bodies. • Low capacities in management and administration by regional public institutions. • Low regional funding for R&D. • Lack of collaboration between government and companies. • Lack of human resources strategy for recruiting foreign researchers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional policies to reduce the administrative burden and teaching time of researchers. • To increase the efficiency and knowledge from the institution. • Instruments to develop international mobility. • Better knowledge of business reality to adapt support tools and programmes. • Institutional support to all parties involved in the value chain. • To attract talent to the region. • Funds for unapproved proposals. • Support for projects with the seal of excellence. • To increase salaries and stability of researchers. • Creation of special programmes. • To promote information seminars in each region. • To increase regional funds to be more competitive. • To improve Tenerife-Gran Canaria coordination. • Strengthen universities hiring young researchers. • To unify services to promote international

	<p>networks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To implement incentives for participation in H2020 calls. • To identify areas of regional research of interest (RIS3) • To redefine RIS3 strategies for better applicability. • More funds for infrastructure and research. • To improve the synergy of public-private investment. • Strengthen the Islands as "living labs". • Specific calls Macaronesia that combines RIS3 objectives and scientific excellence. • To hire candidates with languages, minimum C1 in English. • To create a Canarian research framework.
--	---

2) Analysis of the concordance or gaps between survey results and the data

Comparing the survey and interviews results with the data and facts analysed in part I (State of play of participation) and part II (Analysis of participation determinants) there is a concordance in the results. Nevertheless, some services seem to be unexploited and it will be necessary to improve the coordination among the different actors to get better results.

Survey and interview results:	Data and facts analysed:
1. Lack of technical and administrative support in proposal writing.	Existing support services: TTO-ULL, OPE-ULPGC, OTRI-IAC, EEN-Canarias.
2. Difficulty to build partnerships and networking.	The support services include infodays, training, partner search facilities.
3. Small size of research groups and research centres.	Higher education and research institutions with a high number of research groups, but not always aligned with FP programmes.
4. Low participation of SMEs.	Private sector implication with low participation in FP programmes. Some SMEs beneficiaries of H2020 SME instrument.
5. Lack of institutional support, public authorities support.	The Canary Islands' Brussels office available for research organisations. RIS3 policies different from FP programmes priorities.

IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation

Mobilising a broad panel of the regional stakeholders in a participative setting is essential to objectivise hypotheses, adopt new ambitions, develop strategies and prioritise actions to increase participation to H2020.

The regional partners conducted two workshops, one in Tenerife and one in Gran Canaria, using collective intelligence tools. In terms of methodology, the workshops followed a 3-step approach - share of the diagnosis - identification of major obstacles - definition of levers - by using the problem/solution tree logical framework. This tool helps find solutions by mapping out the anatomy of cause and effect of an issue.

Based on the results of the diagnosis and workshops, the following analysis highlights the major obstacles faced by the Canary Islands to participate in FP.

A - Major obstacles

Following the identification of major obstacles, detected through the online survey and the interviews, the following problems were the subject of analysis during the workshops, using the problem tree and solution tree methodology:

3. Lack of technical and administrative support in proposal writing.
4. Difficulty to build partnerships and networking.
5. Small size of research groups and research centres.
6. Low participation of SMEs.
7. Lack of institutional support, public authorities support.

These are the main conclusion following the two regional workshops:

Figure 25. Problem-tree 1: Need for technical/administrative support to develop proposals

The main causes discussed in relation to problem 1 revolve around the lack of prepared and stable in time human resources, the lack of institutional policies that promote and support participation, the lack of a participation culture in European projects, together with the complex bureaucracy that the application, processing and justification of these projects require.

Figure 26. Solution-tree 1. Objective: Provide qualified technical and administrative support to develop proposals.

One of the identified solutions to problem 1 was the necessity to have an office or a single regional helpdesk to horizontally support all R&I entities in the archipelago, provided with specialised staff and enough resources so that the results can be visible. The training of specialised staff, the expansion of communication channels and the promotion of an incentive plan with institutional support directed towards encouraging the participation of researchers in this programmes were also insisted upon.

Figure 27. Problem-tree 2: Difficulty to create consortiums and lack of support for networking.

When discussing the difficulties to create consortiums, the lack of knowledge on the work carried out by the research groups of the different centres in the Canary Islands, the reduced size of said groups, the deficiencies in terms of knowledge and languages command to search for partners and the lack of institutional support to promote important networking actions, among others, became patently clear.

Figure 28. Solution-tree 2: Objective: Supporting networking to increase participation in H2020 projects

The solutions to problem 2 involve improving the institutional communication and promotion of the excellence of the R&I produced in the Canary Islands, employing scientific outreach professionals, funding international mobility programmes and researchers exchanges, reinforcing connections with Brussels through the Canary Islands Office and promoting the role of consultant/adviser to communicate and defend the interests of the region, among others.

Figure 29. Problem-tree 3: Small size of research groups and research centres.

The causes of problem 3 revolve around the lack of leaders that can stimulate and guide research groups, the low capacity and few resources invested in R&I, work instability, little recognition, the division of existing groups when applying for funding, etc.

Figure 30. Solution-tree 3: Objective: Strengthening and support to research teams and centres.

The solutions to problem 3 involve promoting hiring and work conditions that facilitate the attraction of talent, generating incentives for all groups, big or small, generating policies that promote international consortiums, the creation of the role of exclusive researcher, improving the access to infrastructures and facilitating institutional support that promotes relationships between research groups and companies.

Figure 31. Problem-tree 4: Little participation of SMEs

The main causes of the lack of SMEs participation in framework programmes lies in the fact that the majority of Canarian SMEs are not innovating and have a low R&I capacity. This, together with the fact that the few knowledge-intensive Canarian SMEs face barriers in their development, results in very low participation levels.

Figure 32. Solution tree-4: Objective: Increase the participation of SMEs in R&D&I projects.

Some solutions involve habilitating a financial instrument that allows for the elaboration of viability studies for R&I projects by the university for companies or rewarding the investment of large enterprises in Canarian SMEs through fiscal incentives, bureaucracy reduction, visibility, etc.

Figure 33. Problem-tree 5: Little institutional/government support and involvement

The last identified problem was the lack of existing institutional support and involvement, which entails a lack of knowledge regarding the resources at their disposal, so they are not used, a lack of vision regarding what the impact of the participation in European projects implies for the Canary Island or the limited investment in R&I.

Figure 34. Solution-tree 5. Objective: Promote institutional support and involvement.

The solutions require the improvement of communication channels, the improvement of visibility, and the positioning of the Canary Islands in Budget distribution forums, and, ultimately, increasing the investment in R&I.

B - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP

Based on the preliminary diagnosis and on the workshops' report, the Canary Islands partners produced a final version of the regional diagnosis and drew a territorial strategic plan to increase regional participation to FP Programmes.

The strategic plan includes detailed actions with general and specific objectives, organisations in charge, targets, indicators of implementation and results.

General objective:

To redefine an appropriate public framework that allows the increase of the participation and return of the Canary Islands in European R&I programmes - Horizon Europe.

Specific objectives:

1. Promoting support and institutional engagement and networking.
2. Promoting a communication strategy raising awareness of the importance of the internationalisation of R&I.
3. Reinforcing and supporting research teams and centres to develop proposals.
4. Increasing SME participation in R&I projects.

1. Promoting support and institutional engagement and networking	
Main topics discussed to define this objective:	
It is necessary to increase the visibility in the Canary Islands of the impact of participation in European R&I projects at all levels, starting with the policy makers; we must make greater use of the information and existing channels at the European level in different government bodies and scientific institutions, which are not taken into account due to lack of awareness. It is necessary to align the European plans and policies with regional R&I strategies. It is necessary to have an active participation as a region in all the commissions, meetings and forums for the definition of programmes and the distribution of financing to R&I, supporting the political partners in generating the technical information required. It is necessary to measure and evaluate the research done in the Canary Islands. It is necessary to strengthen and boost the national and international network of contacts.	
Actions:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1. To create a regional network of support offices for the preparation of Horizon Europe proposals. 1.2. To refund 6.5% of IGIC¹ R&I to finance research activities 1.3. Call for proposals to prepare Horizon Europe project. 1.4. To prepare the drafting of a regional R&I strategy.
Descriptions of the Actions:	
Description of the activities to be carried out:	

¹ Canary Islands tax.

- 1.1. To create a regional network of support offices for the preparation of Horizon Europe proposals, the next EU research and innovation investment programme that supports scientific institutions and companies. This network will be created by the Government of the Canary Islands and must be formed by, at least, all the R&D centres of the Canary Islands, the public institutions involved in the management of R&I policies and budgets at the regional and European levels and the companies or entities that represent them. The main activities of this network are:
 - 1.1.1 Coordination: Governance and progress reports
 - 1.1.2 Regional characterisation: monitoring of the thematic topics of interest in the region
 - 1.1.3 Awareness: information days on Horizon Europe, Infodays on thematic calls of application in the Canary Islands, dissemination of relevant news about Horizon Europe.
 - 1.1.4 Internal training: development of skills for technicians offering support services on the European project offices. Increase awareness of the calls; increase the quality of the proposals prepared, share experiences nationally and internationally, international events to attract first level contacts, etc.
 - 1.1.5 Regional project office: call for proposals follow-up, workshops on proposal writing, project incubation, information on grants for the preparation of proposals, collaboration with the support offices of the R&D centres.
 - 1.1.6 Creation of expert groups: experts, evaluators for consultation and support in the preparation of proposals.
 - 1.1.7 Mapping the scientific and technical experts that will support policy makers to be prepared for national and international R&I forums, in order to reflect the Canary Islands' special conditions in the European R&I calls. In this way, there will be a direct and fast access to specialised sources of information that may be required.
 - 1.1.8 Reinforcing the communication channels to enhance contacts and create a solid international network with the contribution of all the members of the regional network.
 - 1.1.9 Identify and prepare a catalogue of existing resources at regional, national and European level to support the preparation of proposals, partner search, consortium generation, etc.
- 1.2. To refund 6.5% of IGIC⁽¹⁾ R&I to finance research activities, in the same way that it is applicable in other sectors. This refund will increase the resources to be allocated to R&I. The Network will facilitate the efforts to bring this proposal to the Government.
- 1.3. Call for proposals to prepare Horizon Europe project. To launch a regional call for the preparation of Horizon Europe project proposals, in a regular way over time and with flexible deadlines.
- 1.4. To prepare the drafting of a regional R&D&I strategy. There has been no reference framework for regional R&I since 2011. Nowadays the Smart Specialisation Strategy RIS3 is the only R&I framework available, and it depends on structural funds, which is insufficient. Regarding the next European period, 2021-2027, the work of revision of the current Canarian RIS3 Strategy should be used for the elaboration of the III Integrated Canary Islands R&D&I Plan of the Region and align it with the ERDF and ESF Operational Programmes for the coming years. A solid governance is needed, periodic monitoring and review reports.

¹ Canary Islands tax.

Organisations in charge:

1.1	Government of the Canary Islands , R&I institutions, companies
1.2	R&I institutions, Government of the Canary Islands
1.3	Government of the Canary Islands
1.4	Government of the Canary Islands

Target group:

Regional government, R&I regional institutions, researchers

ACTIONS	INDICATORS	U.	2020	2021	2022	TOTAL
1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4	Regional network of support offices for the preparation of EU proposals.	No.		1		1
	Participant organisations	No.		7	10	16
	Awareness actions	No.		4	8	12
	Persons reached	No. Persons		200	400	600
	Training actions	No.		3	3	6
	Persons reached	No. persons		60	60	120
	Increase of EU proposals submitted per year	%		5 %	7 %	12 %
	Economic return on EU projects per year	%		5 %	8%	13%

2. Promote a communication strategy raising awareness of the importance of the internationalisation of the R&I

Main topics discussed to define this objective:

Dissemination of the R&I excellence carried out in the Canary Islands; to have senior journalists to disseminate science, to join efforts and work in network; organise international events in the Canary Islands to attract first level contacts; greater awareness of the utility and

benefits of H2020 projects; increase the knowledge of existing services in the government and other institutions.

Actions:	<p>2.1. Development of a communication plan for the dissemination of the importance of R&I for the Canary Islands</p> <p>2.2. Collaboration agreement between the regional Government and all R&I centres to materialise the actions of the communication plan</p>
-----------------	--

Descriptions of the Actions:

Description of the activities to be carried out:

2.1 Development of a communication plan for the dissemination of the importance of R&I for the Canary Islands. It is needed to raise awareness among politicians, researchers and society in general, about the importance of knowledge and science to increase the competitiveness of our region. The strategic importance of participation in Horizon Europe projects to carry out excellence research. All these messages must be carried out in concrete actions and executed by means of a communication plan, led by the government, with the participation of all members of the Canary Islands research ecosystem. It is necessary to include measures targeted at the political leaders of the R&I, researchers, companies, students and society in general.

2.2 Collaboration agreement between the regional Government and all R&D centres to materialise the actions of the communication plan. Establishment of a joint framework, where all agents will participate, contributing with content and generating synergies to have the biggest impact on society as possible. Sharing social media messages, campaigns with interviews in radio and television, publication of articles in the organisations, etc.

Organisations in charge:

2.1	Government of the Canary Islands
2.2	Government of the Canary Islands , R&D institutions

Target group:	Politicians, researchers, companies, students, society
----------------------	--

ACTIONS	INDICATORS	U.	2020	2021	2022	TOTAL
2.1, 2.2	Joint communication impact	No.		40	60	100
	Persons reached	No. persons		10.000	20.000	30.000

3. Reinforcing and supporting research teams and centres to develop proposals

Main topics discussed to define this objective:

Establishment of institutional policies to motivate participation in Horizon Europe (generation of R&I incentives for all groups, large and small), increase the stability and specialisation of the project offices staff of R&D regional institutions, improve access to information, the availability of infrastructures, technical and human resources, and strengthen relations between research groups of different centres and between research groups and companies.

Actions:	<p>3.1 To generate a work stability plan for EU support offices staff of R&D centres. The instability of the EU support offices staff is recurrent in many of the R&D centres in the region. This problem should be raised to the competent authorities to find a continuity solution. The provision of additional resources and collaboration with the Network described in section 1.1 of this section will contribute to increasing their capacities and reducing the administrative burden generated by these projects.</p> <p>3.2 To provide a consensus document to the Regional Government on the need to update the research career focus, facilitating the participation in Horizon Europe It is necessary to reflect on measures to be taken to create multi-disciplinary research groups, encourage the hiring of young researchers and type II professors, reduce administrative work, facilitate research activity, etc.</p>
-----------------	---

Description of the Actions:

Description of the activities to be carried out:

- 3.1 To generate a work stability plan for EU support offices staff of R&D centres. The instability of the EU support offices staff is recurrent in many of the R&D centres in the region. This problem should be raised to the competent authorities to find a continuity solution. The provision of additional resources and collaboration with the Network described in section 1.1 of this section will contribute to increasing their capacities and reducing the administrative burden generated by these projects.
- 3.2 To provide a consensus document to the Regional Government on the need to update the research career focus, facilitating the participation in Horizon Europe It is necessary to reflect on measures to be taken to create multi-disciplinary research groups, encourage the hiring of young researchers and type II professors, reduce administrative work, facilitate research activity, etc.

Organisations in charge:

3.1	R&D institutions
3.2	R&D institutions

Target group:	Regional government, R&D regional institutions, researchers
----------------------	---

ACTIONS	INDICATORS	U.	2020	2021	2022	TOTAL
3.1	Increase of EU proposals submitted per year	%		2 %	2 %	4 %
3.2	Consensus document	No.		1		1
	Increase of researchers participating in EU project proposals per year.	%		2 %	3 %	5 %

4. Increasing SME participation in R&I projects.

Main topics discussed to define this objective:

The few knowledge-intensive SMEs in the Canary Islands face barriers to their development. A more diversified and knowledge-based economy is needed. It is necessary to create synergies between businesses and university research and to increase the investment in private R&I.

Actions:	<p>4.1 Enhancing the activity of CIDE¹ type 1 centres to create time-stable meeting points between public and private R&I agents.</p> <p>4.2 Training executives and business people in R&I.</p> <p>4.3 Enabling financial instruments for conducting feasibility studies of R&I projects for companies with the university and research centres.</p> <p>4.4 Strengthen the collaboration with the national contact points, NCPs-CDTI in Spain, which has the financing programmes for SMEs.</p>
-----------------	---

Descriptions of the Actions:

Description of the activities to be carried out:

4.1 Enhancing the activity of CIDE “type 1 centres” to create time-stable meeting points between public and private R&I agents. The Canary R&I system has a stable structure over time, the CIDE Network, which has two “type 1 centres”, which are CIDEs for technological support and transfer, with a close relationship with knowledge agents and the university . These technicians, as well as the rest of CIDE technicians, will be trained in

¹ Red CIDE is the regional network of innovation agents in the Canary Islands www.redcide.es

acquiring knowledge in the preparation of project proposals, supporting SMEs to increase their participation. The training activities will be coordinated with the proposals in section 1.1 of this section.

4.2 Training executives and business people in R&I: organisation of working and training sessions that include the identification of research lines with future market development, how to collaborate with R&D centres, financing company's R&D activities, etc.

4.3 Enabling financial instruments for conducting feasibility studies of R&I projects for companies with the university and research centres. The characteristics of a financial instrument that includes this type of project will be submitted to the body responsible for the Canary Islands' R&I policy. It will also apply to companies that want to apply for the 2021 Enhanced EIC Pilot financing lines and future programme. An initial draft of the instrument can be prepared by the CIDE Network.

4.4 Strengthen the collaboration with the national contact points, NCPs-CDTI in Spain, which has the financing programmes for SMEs; Eurostars and Eranets. Organisation of infodays, etc.

Organisations in charge:	
4.1	Government of the Canary Islands , CIDE network coordinator
4.2	Government of the Canary Islands , CIDE network coordinator
4.3	Government of the Canary Islands , CIDE network coordinator

Target group:	Companies
----------------------	-----------

ACTIONS	INDICATORS	U.	2020	2021	2022	TOTAL
4.1, 4.2	Training for companies	No.		2	2	4
	Persons reached	No. persons		30	30	60
4.3, 4.4	Increase of companies participating in EU projects per year.	% No companies		3 %	5%	8 %
4.3, 4.4	Economic return on EU projects per year	%		5 %	8%	13%

EXCEL TOOLS

1. RDI Mapping Canary Islands
2. FP Participation Canary Islands
3. Regional Figures Canary Islands

TABLE OF ANNEXES

Annex 1: Reports on surveys and workshops.

Annex 1: Reports on surveys and workshops.

OR R&I community members often depict FP programmes as too complicated, competitive and unsuited to local situations and realities. These prejudices generate a lack of ambition and involvement. Though poorly studied and often underestimated, beliefs and fears constitute powerful obstacles to H2020 access; overcoming them can be energy and time consuming, particularly when building participative territorial actions plan.

Therefore, the involvement of a large and diverse panel of members of the R&I community through survey offers represents the opportunity to map and assess representations on FP participation and explanatory factors. Such survey tests a potential gap between the collective representations and the facts characterised in the analysis.

To that end, partners first determine the type and number of actors to be questioned, according to their community characteristics (diversity and size). Partners choose to implement a generic survey or several specific surveys adapted to the intended audiences, and/or the various fields of analysis. To ensure significant participation and generate significant results, partners have to elaborate an efficient dissemination and stakeholder's involvement strategy. The diffusion of the surveys also represents an opportunity to promote the Forward project within the regional community and therefore should be developed in accordance with the WP8 communication strategy.

The questions of the survey were common to all the OR. It consisted of 9 questions on “*How do you perceive the participation of the Canary Islands in Horizon 2020 (European framework programme for research and innovation)?*” and is available online for the Canary Islands community at <http://cort.as/-J-HG>.

How do you perceive the participation of the Canary Islands in Horizon 2020 (European framework programme for research and innovation)?

The questionnaire consists of 9 questions for a response time of about 10 minutes. This anonymous questionnaire is part of a study conducted within the framework of the European project FORWARD "fostering research innovation in outermost regions" (Description: <https://nil.ly/2H0vrmN>). Thank you for your cooperation.

NEXT

Never submit passwords through Google Forms.

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google. [Report Abuse](#) - [Terms of Service](#)

Google Forms

SURVEY RESULTS AND INTERVIEWS RESULTS

The survey was conducted online from June 7 to June 27, 2019, with 135 answers submitted, mainly by researchers.

On the other hand, a total of 66 interviews were conducted by FORWARD partners to researchers and other profiles with experience in FP proposals, in order to determine keys to success, failure factors and self-selection determinants.

As a result of the analysis of both the survey and the interviews, the following barriers were identified:

1. Lack of technical and administrative support in proposal writing.
2. Difficulty to build partnerships and networking.

3. Small size of research groups and research centres.
4. Low participation of SMEs.
5. Lack of institutional support, public authorities support.

Those problems were the subject of analysis during the workshops, using the problem tree and solution tree methodology.

REGIONAL WORKSHOPS (TENERIFE AND GRAN CANARIA)

The FORWARD workshops were held in Tenerife on July 17, 2019 and Gran Canaria on July 18, 2019 with the following agenda:

Workshop: Análisis y mejora de la participación de Canarias en H2020

forward

Dirigido a: entidades y empresas I+D+i

Lugar: Sala de formación, Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias (ITC), Plaza Sixto Machado, 3, Santa Cruz de Tenerife

Fecha: 17 de julio de 2019

Inscripciones: <http://cort.as/-LOH9>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

9:00 – 9:15	Presentación de los participantes
9:15 – 9:25	Presentación de resultados: Diagnóstico Regional y Encuesta percepción de participación en H2020
9:25 – 9:35	Presentación de herramientas (Árbol de problemas y de soluciones)
9:35 – 10:40	Trabajo en grupos: Análisis árbol de problemas
10:40 – 11:45	Trabajo en grupos: Identificación árbol de soluciones
11:45 – 12:00	Conclusiones

Logos of participating organizations: ITC, FRCT, PLOCAN, and others.

The participants were regional stakeholders from businesses, academia and public authorities, already involved in the survey and interviews works. The workshop was also open to other profiles active in the R&I ecosystem of the Canary Islands.

The workshop was organised following the collective intelligence tools. In the first part, the FORWARD project was presented as well as the preliminary diagnosis, state of the participation of Canary Islands in FP projects and the identification of major obstacles after the interviews and surveys. The second part of the workshop focused on starting problem/solution trees from the barriers already identified.

The participation in the workshop was very active, with 28 participants in Tenerife and 36 in Gran Canaria, distributed as follows:

Tenerife Workshop – Share of participants' profiles

- FORWARD partners participating: ITC (organiser). ACIISI, ULL, IAC
- Other research organisations: IEO, OAG, INEUSTAR, FGULL.
- Business organisations: Chamber of Commerce of Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Sustainable Construction Cluster, TITSA, Toledo y Heras Arquitectos.

Gran Canaria Workshop – Share of participants' profiles

- FORWARD partners participating: ITC (organiser). FPULPGC (co-organiser) ACIISI, ULPGC, PLOCAN y CE.
- Other organisations: SODECAN.

- Business organisations: AdQuiver, Edataconsulting, Evolution Europe, Farapi FEMEPA, Lightbee, Nuria Ferrera, Rethink Medical, Acosta Ingeniería.

Tenerife and Gran Canaria workshops.

French Guiana

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems

FRENCH GUIANA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 824550

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction.....	3
Methodology	4
I - State of play of participation.....	6
II - Analysis of participation determinants	13
A - Network analysis	13
B - Regional innovation system	14
C - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level	20
III - Analysis of the representations.....	51
IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation	55
<i>A - Major obstacles</i>	55
<i>B - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP</i>	56

Introduction

Research and Innovation (R/I) are one of the areas in which there is consensus in Europe on the value of a global approach among member states in order to allow the EU to maintain an advanced position in world research. Hence, the successive framework programs tend to promote European research in practically all strategic sectors. In addition, Research and Innovation are seen as essential levers for the competitiveness of our economy.

However, the European Commission has noted a great heterogeneity in the responses coming from the ORs and has decided to launch calls in order to improve the number and quality of projects in the least mobilized territories, especially for the next European framework program (2021-2027).

The interest of the approach for French Guiana (FG) is multiple:

- Apply a shared methodology for analyzing the R / I ecosystem in order to better understand its weaknesses;
- Being able to compare with other ORs and other comparable European territories with present more or less similar handicaps;
- Identify the common problems and specificities of French Guiana compared to the other ORs;
- Set up networks between R / I organizations in each ultra-marine territory;
- Establish exchanges on good practices;
- Set up an action plan in order to improve the positioning of French Guiana in European calls in the field of R / I.

Locally, there is some issue defining a strategy for financing R / I between the OPs (ERDF and EAFRD), regional cooperation programs (INTERREG, PCIA Amazonia, Guyamazon) and European calls on R / I. More broadly, it will be necessary to put in place and promote the partnership and the R / I network structured by FORWARD.

Methodology

The diagnosis of the R / I ecosystem was carried out by essentially applying the WP2 methodology proposed by NEXIA.

This is how we identified 10 research organizations present in French Guiana. But this figure hides a larger reality. In fact, many French, European and third-country researchers carry out ad hoc missions in French Guiana mainly in the field of knowledge of Amazonian biodiversity (plant, animal, terrestrial and aquatic).

To conduct the surveys and inform the documents of WP2, the CTG mobilized the Director of the Research Innovation Digital Development Department (Marc SAGNE), the Head of the Innovation Research Service (Ms. Aïra TRIBORD REZAIRE) and a GDI project manager seconded to full time (Subriena BAKSH). A combination of one-on-one interviews, telephone exchanges and work meetings was used.

In addition, the CORDIS and EUROSTAT databases and exchanges with research organizations were used; data collection has been supplemented by the content of the schemes concerned by R / I:

- ✓ STDEII (Territorial scheme for economic development, innovation and internationalization);
- ✓ SRESRI (Regional Scheme for Higher Education and Research)
- ✓ SRI (Regional Innovation Scheme)

It should be noticed the great difficulty encountered in mobilizing research organizations. Likely causes are the lack of information about the program, the lack of short-term financial stakes and low availability. In addition, quite often, the information requested was either dispersed locally; or to be collected directly in France from the structure's national headquarters. The workload required for this collection and analysis was initially undervalued. To face this situation, we decided to hire a project manager in November 2019. This largely explains the significant delay in the reporting of WP2 data.

The research organizations were brought together for the first time for information. Then, at the beginning of 2020, a workshop was organized based of the work methodology proposed by

NEXIA. The participants highly appreciated the methodology and the content of the discussions. They asked to regularly renew this type of meeting. As a reminder, there is in French Guiana a consultative body for research organizations (IRISTA) in which all the Research organisms are presented. But this one works mainly on the projects in progress little on the strategic approaches of R / I on the territory.

I - State of play of participation

1) Evolution of regional participation

1. Evolution of regional participation based on data collection (FP1 FP2) (CORDIS; H2020 ECORDA)

The participation in FP7 and in the current year of H2020 framework program is very low regarding of the presence and implication of the research organization present in French Guiana. Indeed, we observe that very few projects were submitted and funded in these framework programs. That is to say, that the submission of projects is very qualitative and present very good quality.

In addition, the participation rate has increased from FP7 to H2020 has shown in the table below.

Programmes	Submitted	Funded	Projects
FP	5	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- STRONGER (IPG)- Doris_net (GDI)- AGROCOS
H2020	6	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- TROPICSAFE (Cirad)- ODYSSEA (Cirad, UG)- EO2HEAVEN (Privat)- BiodivERsA3

French Guiana has actively 5 participations in H2020 and 4 signed grant agreements and in FP7 2 signed grants (source *H2020 dashboard*)

Both Doris_Net (GDI) and EO2HEAVEN (NEVANTROPIC) were dropped by French Guiana's local partners.

The other bodies' structures do not participate in these types of programs.

2. Evolution of regional participation

For the global performance framework programs FP7 projects have a success of 80% and H2020 projects 83%. We can notice that our participation in these programs has stagnated.

Moreover, the ratios of number of projects / number of researchers are very low and so is the ratio number of projects / number of researchers per 1000 inhabitants 27% (FP7); 33% (H2020).

These ratios show that researchers are not active in Framework Programs.

- *EU Contribution per program*

Programmes	FP programme	Total Requested EC Contribution
EO2HEAVEN	H2020	140 203,20
DORIS_NET	FP7	16 000
STRONGER	FP7	3 726 156
AGROCOS	FP7	706 753
ODYSSEA	H2020	13 500
BiodivERsA3	H2020	
TROPICSAFE	H2020	

- *EU contribution*

The EU's contribution is 10,717,283 € for FP7 and € 13,693,518 € for H2020 despite a smaller number of projects (4 for FP7 and 2 for H2020).

Indicators	Total of EU funding
Ratio between H2020 and other EU competitive funding	0,9
H2020 funding as percentage of GDP	1432,8 (INSEE 2015)

3. Participation to the different programs and funding schemes

French Guianese research organizations obtained participation in H2020 MSCA and in H2020 Grants ERC frontier research, 3 participations in H2020 coord & support actions projects and in 2 H2020 R&I.

Programs participation

Indicator	Number
FP7 Collaborative projects	2
FP7 Coordination and support actions	2

4. Thematic distribution RIS 3 and H2020 : common priorities (FP 1 RF 1 participation data)

- *Scientific domains analysis*

Most represented scientific domain (projects)	FP	H2020
Agriculture and biological sciences		2
Medicine	1	
Environmental sciences		1

The evolution of scientific fields between the FP and H2020 could be explained by the launch of regional ERDF and EAFRD programming. Thus, the large endowment of tropical health research projects in the FEDER 2007-2020 calls explains the absence of health projects in H2020. Conversely, in the field of agriculture funds have been significantly constrained for current programming. This explains why only 2 were accepted in H2020.

- RIS3 domains analysis

S3 was developed in coherence with the strategic axes of economic interest of the territory.

Therefore, we see that they are well represented in the calls for projects:

- Biodiversity (knowledge, preservation and valorization);
- Tropical diseases;
- Tele-technology and tele-detection;
- Social innovation;
- Support to economic field (fishing, gold mines, agriculture, wood, ..).

Indicators	FP	H2020
Total number of RIS3 priorities in the region		3
Total number of RIS3 priorities with a minimum of 1 FP project	1	4

5. Stakeholders mapping

Indicators	FP7	H2020
Number of Higher education establishments participating in FP		1
Number research organizations participating	2	2
Number of public bodies participating in	2	2
Number of companies (PRC _ Private for Profit)	0	0
Number of SME participant to FP Projects participating in FP	1	0

Participation in calls is essentially the result of research organizations. Only one SME is piloting a project for FP7.

6. Participation profile

- *OR role in project*

Indicators	FP	H2020
Number of organizations participating in a minimum of 1 FP project	2	4
Number of FP beneficiaries as coordinator	1	0
Number of FP beneficiaries as WP leader	1	1
Share of FP beneficiaries as WP leader	50%	25%

Despite the very small number of projects, the positioning of French Guianese research organizations as coordinator or leader (50% for FP and 25% for H2020) is appreciable. By

comparing this to the high rate of projects selected, we can deduce that the projects submitted by French Guiana are of quality and that this excellence is recognized by the partners.

7. Regional collaboration

- *With OR H2020*

Indicator	Number
Number of projects involving a least a second partner from OR	2
Number of projects including a neighbouring third country	1

The top 5 OR responding to H2020 are:

- *With third countries*

The top third countries are :

A - Network analysis

1) Global connectivity

We must distinguish 2 cases. On one hand the University of French Guiana (UG) and on the other hand research organizations.

As a reminder, the UG was created in 2014 following the split between the University of the French West Indies Guyana. Several laboratories have left for Martinique and Guadeloupe. The internal reorganization (educational, scientific and financial) took almost 5 years. This is how the new premises for the research building and those of the administration should be delivered in 2020. In all objectivity, it is possible to predict that the UG will be in working order for the next programming. In addition, the report (HCERES in French) about the UG's publications for the 2013-2018 period shows that they are constantly increasing.

The aim of the CTG is to make the UG the hub of research in French Guiana, which is accompanied by the strengthening of joint research units in partnership with research organizations.

As for (national) research organizations, they all benefit from an international relations department which allows them to develop their R / I relations in Europe and with third countries. The overseas departments are generally little involved, although concerned, in the international strategies of these research organizations.

2) Thematic connectivity

The main themes of the projects are agriculture and biological sciences, tropical medicine and environmental sciences.

The IRS includes other very promising themes which are of interest to all ORs such as tele-technologies (remote sensing, telemedicine, tele-training), support for economic activity (fishing, tourism), the digital economy, green economy (renewable energies, sustainable construction, etc.) and social innovation (digital inclusion, social and solidarity economy). French Guiana must take advantage of the FORWARD program to reinforce the themes already underway and bring out the others of common interest for the ORs.

Some themes are more specific to French Guiana such as support for the timber industry and the mining sector. These are the subject of promising exchanges within the framework of regional cooperation (PCIA programs in Amazonia, Guyamazon).

3) Relative position

French Guiana's R / I organizations were coordinator of a project for 1 FP project and leader of 1 FP project and 1 H2020 project. This reflects an honorable positioning given the small number of projects concerned (2 FP projects and 4 H2020 projects). In summary, French Guyanese research organizations submit few projects, but they are well positioned in terms of coordination and leadership.

4) Third countries participation

French Guiana has 2 European regional cooperation programs INTERREG Caribbean and the PCIA Amazonia. For INTERREG, French Guiana is indirectly concerned by a cooperation program on agroecology led by INRAe (whose headquarters are in Guadeloupe). No research organization has positioned itself on the Amazon PCIA. This is very unfortunate because Europe is developing active cooperation with Brazil in the area of research. Thus, for the FP7 and H2020 combined, the EU finances 174 projects for an amount of € 45 million. No exchange with French Guiana takes place when the financing agreements for these research and innovation programs are concluded. However, R/I is eligible for the PCIA Amazonia (for cross-border states) and INTERREG Caribbean for the other states of Brazil.

Through the Guyamazon program, based on Brazil and France partnership, the Territorial Collectivity is involved in France's R / I cooperation strategy. The same approach remains to be driven for Europe / Brazil cooperation in the field of R / I.

B - Regional innovation system

1) Mapping the regional research system

- *Research organizations*

Research structures in French Guiana by research domain are presented in the table below:

	Name	Acronyme	Domaines de recherche
1.	National Museum of Natural History	MNHN	Human social sciences
2.	French National Research Institute for Development	IRD	Pedology, teledetection
3.	The French Research Institute for the Use of Marine Resources	IFREMER	Marine biodiversity
4.	The French geological survey	BRGM	Geosciences Renewable energies
5.	The French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development	CIRAD	Tropical agriculture
6.	The French National Centre for Scientific Research	CNRS	man-nature relationships in the amazon region
7.	Institute Pasteur of French Guiana	IPG	Tropical vector diseases
8.	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment	INRAe	Agroecology
9.	Institute of technology for Life, food and environmental sciences	AgroParisTech	Tropical agriculture
10.	HYDRECO Guyane		Biologie, chemistry

There are 10 research organizations present in French Guiana, added with the University of French Guiana and 6 scientific partners established on the territory.

- *Research Laboratories*

Laboratory Biodivhal (Ifremer)	Ecology
LEEISA (CNRS – UG – Ifremer)	Amazonian biodiversity
Parasitology unit (IPG)	Tropical Health
Virology unit (IPG)	Tropical Health
Epidemlogy unit (IPG)	Tropical Health
Interactions virus and others unit (IPG)	Tropical Health
Medical entomology unit (IPG)	Tropical Health
Microbiota of mosquitoes unit (IPG)	Tropical Health
UMR ECOFOG (AgroParisTech, Cirad, CNRS, INRA, Université des AG)	Ecology
UMR ESPACE-DEV (UG)	Energy and sensors
UMR QUALISUD (Université de Montpellier Université d’Avignon ; Université de la Réunion ; CIRAD ; Montpellier SUP Agro ; Université de Guyane ; Université des Antilles)	Biodiversity
MINEA (UG)	Social and Human Science
EPAT-TBIP (UG)	Health
UMR PaLOC (MNHN, IRD)	Human Science
UMR AGAP	Biodiversity
UMR AMAP	Biodiversity
UMR Innovation (CIRAD)	Agriculture
UMR SYSTEM (CIRAD)	Agriculture
UPR Bioagresseurs (CIRAD)	Bio pests
UPR HORTSYS (CIRAD)	Horticulture

Guyana has two forest research stations, one piloted by CIRAD and the other by CNRS. The research themes concerned are extensive. They include the study of forest ecosystems and their dynamics, in particular related to logging, as well as research on the carbon fluxes of the forest. These two sites are showcases of Amazonian European research. As an example, the Paracou station hosted, in 2019, 23 research projects (119 researchers including 39 international), 5 student visits (92 people including 21 international). Research conducted on the site resulted in 41 publications (2019).

Indicator	Number
Higher education and research establishment	1
Research organizations	10
UG research groups	6
UG <i>Researchers</i>	75

2) Regional innovation system performance

French Guiana has only one structure devoted to innovation; French Guiana Development Innovation (GDI) which works for economic development and innovation. It therefore supports companies in their creation and development.

The structure animates and manages a nursery of innovative companies. For the innovation component, GDI's mission is to make the link between businesses and research. Its headquarter is located on the university campus. It is therefore an essential link in the territory's R&I ecosystem. It is in particular this structure which supports research organizations and companies for the filing of patents.

As for the UG, new tools are programmed for the development of bioresources: a technological hall (shared and decentralized processing tools: herbal tea, essential oils, oils, manufacture of plant extracts, freeze-drying) and an experimental farm for the development of production routes for fish farming, the breeding of wild animals and medicinal plants.

3) Regional research performance

French Guiana's research ecosystem includes one higher education institution, which is the UG that houses a doctoral school, a prerequisite for obtaining a doctoral scholarship.

Each academic year, an average of 17.2 students obtains their doctorate, including 3.2 foreign students. This is how foreign doctoral students represent 18% of total doctoral students.

It should be noticed that this high rate of foreign researchers does not reflect only the scientific attractiveness of French Guiana. In fact, many of these researchers are present in French Guiana for economic reasons depending on migratory waves (Haiti and the African continent mainly). In 2019, nearly 250 publications produced by researchers were listed; 4.3 publications per researcher and per year (2019).

The inventory of research structures and researchers

For the period 2015-2019, 993 publications were published by researchers of French Guiana. (SCOPUS)

By affiliation

We can note that CNRS, the mixt unit ECOFOG, INRA, and IPG published the most during this period.

By author

The most active authors for a period of 5 years are doctors (5 from EPAT and Hospital), researchers from the health field (3 from IPG), Ecologistes (4 from EcoFoG and 1 IRD-Amap).

D. Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

The main areas of research are:

- ✓ Applied biology / biochemistry and ecology;
- ✓ Social Sciences;
- ✓ Tropical diseases;
- ✓ Earth Science;
- ✓ Biology and biochemistry.

1) Private sector implication

Unfortunately, we note that the private sector does not participate in R / I programs, whether for FP7 or H2020. It should be noted that 98% of French Guiana's economic fabric is made up of very small businesses and that 70% of them have only one employee. Some of them forge establish partnerships with research organizations, but rather in the case of AAP PO FEDER.

2) RIS3 priorities

The current S3 for French Guiana is scheduled for the period 2014-2020.

At the beginning of the European programming, this program was divided into 3 main axes:

- Development of primary resources and the Amazon ecosystem
- Support of the development of emerging sector
- Emergence of the social innovation

Strategic action areas and corresponding sectors

3) Development of primary natural resources and the Amazon ecosystem

This part is called "historic" or "traditional" areas of the territory for which a certain critical mass (in terms of the number of players in research, higher education or companies) exists but in an incomplete manner. These sectors concern knowledge, enhancement and sustainable exploitation of Amazonian ecosystems.

The logic of improving the competitiveness of "traditional" areas aimed at taking advantage of the exceptional double positioning of Guyana, a territory that is both European and Amazonian (orientation 1): very application projects, search for partners, technology transfer, structuring of actors...;

The development of primary natural resources and the Amazon ecosystem is of economic and strategic interest for the territory. It concerns in particular the following sectors:

1. Sustainable development of forest and mineral resources;
2. The development of agroecology and agro-transformation;
3. Development of marine resources and primary resources;
4. Identification and enhancement of active Amazonian molecules;
5. The development of Amazonian ecotourism.

1. Development of forest resources

The "development of forest resources" sector is a traditional economic sector in French Guiana which relies on the natural resources present in the territory.

The forest covers 96% of Guyana's territory, or more than 8 million hectares. Composed of three distinct groups, it mainly comprises the large primary forest, established on the Precambrian basement of the interior which brings together nearly 1,600 species of trees. There is also a narrow coastal fringe as well as the lowland forests. France is the only European country to manage a tropical rainforest which it has undertaken to manage and exploit in accordance with the Rio Earth summit (1992) conference (IEDOM 2012 Report, 2013 Edition).

The market is in high demand for wood of tropical origin, produced in an eco-responsible fashion. At the local level, the market is also demanding the adaptation of mastered techniques for European woods in an Amazonian context (glulam, composite frames, etc.).

The orientation scheme of the West Indies and French Guiana Center 2013-2020 provides for the creation of Research / Training / Innovation Devices in Partnerships "(DP) in front of" allow, within the framework of finalized research projects, to analyze in situ the functioning natural and production systems and the necessary innovations in the agro-ecological and socio-economic environment of the tropical zone ". The DP5 "Ecology of tropical forests" is supported by the French Guiana Forest Ecology UMR which brings together Cnrs, CIRAD, AgroParisTech and UAG.

The wood industry has 210 companies generating around 900 direct jobs and an income of nearly 60 million euros, ranking this sector in 4th place for economic activities in Guyana.

The demands of this sector in terms of R&D work are globally structured and meet needs in terms of conquering new markets and / or gaining competitiveness (the use of tele-technologies and ICTs to reduce the costs of logging as well as environmental impacts, development of innovative frameworks based on tropical wood).

2. Agriculture and agro-processing

The "agriculture and agro-transformation" sector has been and remains one of the fundamental bases of local economic development in French Guiana.

There were nearly 6,000 farms in agriculture in 2010 (AGRESTE, 2010 data, Number 2, 2011). The agricultural and food industries brought together 152 establishments in 2010 and 333 employees (DAAF, 2012).

As part of its orientation scheme for the French Guiana and West Indies Center 2013-2020, it is planned to create a transversal DP "Agroecological strategies for quality products which the objective will be to promote a convergence of programs around the issue finalized the design of production and transformation systems with high environmental and food quality.

As the other French regions, it should also be noticed that French Guiana is engaged in the implementation of the 2018 Écophyto plan, which, following the Grenelle de l'Environnement, aims to reduce the use of pesticides by 2018, taking into account the specificities of specific crops and conditions favorable to the proliferation of pests.

The development of the "agriculture and agro-transformation" sector responds to a triple demand which concerns:

- reduction in imports (according to INSEE the overall coverage rate for all sectors combined fluctuates structurally around the range of 10% to 15%; in the Agriculture, forestry, fishing and Agri-food industries, the coverage rate for all branches combined hovers around 10%) in connection with the development of high value-added sectors, making it possible to offset the high labor costs;
- Territory planning;
- Access and dissemination throughout the territory of scientific, technical and financial resources concentrated in large urban centers.

French Guiana is therefore facing a major challenge: supporting the agricultural "mutation" in a context of population growth.

Within the framework of territorial development plans, it is a question of settling the slaughtered animals, answering the needs of adapted technical routes, and the challenges linked to the management of fertility, to the acceptance of innovation by the populations, to support the actors.

- Regarding to other European territories, French Guiana has several comparative advantages in this area;
- easily accessible production and processing capacities for tropical and Amazonian products;
- capacity to enhance European know-how with neighboring countries due to the geographic proximity of French Guiana, a European territory, with its neighboring countries;
- a capacity for transferring research in agronomy under development, with the establishment of two innovation and technology transfer networks, from the Overseas General States: the Technical Innovation Network Agricultural (RITA) which has two components: plant and animal. The animal component is the responsibility of IKARE, the plant component is the responsibility of CIRAD in Guyana, in collaboration with all the usual partners (public actors, communities and in particular DAAF).

On the other hand, the “Agriculture and agro-transformation” sector has to face direct competition from neighboring countries for export, because these countries benefit from more advantageous production conditions: greater availability and easier, weaker access to land, labor costs, opportunities to achieve economies of scale to make investments profitable, etc.

In addition, apart from certain sectors such as animal husbandry and market gardening, many farms are organized on a family and traditional basis, with low yields and limited valuation of products.

3. Development of marine and primary resources

The “Development of marine and primary resources” sector is another “historic” sector in the territory. This sector concerns both fishing (shrimp and fish) and mining (in particular gold mining).

French Guiana’s continental shelf, receiving the waters of the Amazon River, is one of the most fish-rich areas in the world.

The marine ecosystem remains poorly described, in terms of marine resources, and little known in terms of functioning.

Thirty species are exploited, but 5 to 6 species (shrimps, snappers, red acoupa) alone represent 90% of the production carried out by a fleet of about 200 vessels including twenty trawlers, to which is added about forty Venezuelan ships. The other vessels are mostly wooden, of modest size with outboard motors exploiting fish from the very coastal area. Production in 2012 was around 3000 tons for inshore fishing, 1000 tons for shrimp and 1500 tons for snapper.

The local market narrowness (around 250,000 inhabitants) and remoteness in which Guyanese operators can be competitive (Europe) are two factors which contribute to explain moderate fishery exploitation (5,500 tons). In terms of the state of resources, regardless of the effects of climate change, there are therefore significant development margins.

The ecosystem is productive and in relatively good condition, so doors are open for the exploitation of new species, but also new products from secondary processing.

In addition, the new Community provisions (rejection directive 0) will lead to some restructuring or the establishment of new sectors, in particular for the shrimp fishery which generates significant discards of fishing (trawling is not very selective and a large quantity of this catch other than shrimp is discarded at sea). Discards will be prohibited.

Therefore, this requires actions at two levels :

- i) improving the selectivity of trawls by setting up by-catch reduction devices and, in order to tend to reach 100% selectivity;
- ii) setting up a recovery network bycatch and its recovery for human consumption or fish farming, for example, which is set to develop in parallel.

Thus, for increased production, an increase in co-products will be observed making it profitable to set up value chains for co-products.

With regard to the other European territories, French Guiana finally presents several proven or potential comparative advantages in this area:

- the richness of the fishery resource in French Guiana: this resource is generally poorly exploited (unlike what is observed in many European areas), even if certain species are subject to entropic pressures (such as the Red Acoupa);
- the mining sector represents the largest export sector in terms of value (€ 65.3 million in 2012). French Guiana has a real advantage for its development from this point of view, even if margins of competitiveness must be developed, in particular in the field of compliance with regulations and reduction of environmental impacts. In this area, several work tracks are already being studied, such as the re-vegetation of sites;
- potential oil resources: the maritime sector has experienced strong momentum in recent months with the launch of the first prospective oil drilling off the coast of French Guiana. If future drilling confirms the presence of oil, the territory would have a real advantage for the development of primary resources.

However, the general level of knowledge on these environments remains low.

The recent development of a research strategy on the marine environment should allow a clear improvement in the years to come.

In addition, local products are hardly processed because they are used for direct consumption. Co-products (in particular by catch) are also poorly valued.

For this sector, the areas of work and tools that can be implemented as part of intelligent specialization are as follows:

- improving knowledge and monitoring of the marine ecosystem in French Guiana;
- evaluation, exploitation, transformation and marketing of new species or the local production of species in the field of continental aquaculture with a view to an internal and external market;
- development of high added value enhancement of products and co-products from the exploitation of the marine environment (new forms of transformation for already exploited

species; enhancement of co-products (species usually rejected, processing waste) for the production of enzymatic hydrolisates for example or flours / oils for fish farming...);

- development of a local food for fish feeding, even export;
- development of professional structures: structured dedicated to the production and marketing of suitable fishing materials; structures dedicated to the construction, repair and maintenance of traditional fishing boats;
- development of a greener operation with a lower impact on primary resources (for example the development of more energy-efficient boats, etc.).

4. Active molecules

The extreme richness of Amazonian ecosystems is also reflected on a molecular level by a very high diversity.

“Chemo-diversity” offers significant potential for the region and enhancement opportunities in several fields: cosmetics, perfumery, agrochemicals and pharmacology. This branch could also offer additional diversification elements for several sectors: wood, agriculture or fishing (development of co-products and / or species not yet exploited).

Several elements, however, constitute obstacles to the development of this branch of activity:

- very long delays in the marketing of identified active substances (in particular in pharmacology);
- issues related to intellectual property and patents: the procedures are cumbersome and complex, in particular where traditional know-how comes into play;
- strong international competition.
- With a view to developing “chemo-diversity”, the territory has started developing various tools in recent years:
 - the establishment of the first naturothèque or sample banks for the 2007-2013 program;
 - the current implementation of ABS (access to benefit-sharing) regulations finalized at the end of 2013;
 - the creation of an environmental and the collection of biodiversity (botanical, animal and entomological) as part of the 2014-2020 programming.

In addition, research themes are emerging on the territory. They concern less competitive sectors than cosmetics or pharmacology. These include, for example, the use of naturally

occurring molecules to fight metal corrosion or the use of bacterial biofilms for the production of electricity.

The related fields which can contribute to an added value of the “Active molecules” sector are the following:

- forest management and agriculture;
- the chemistry of natural substances;
- biodiversity knowledge and inventory;
- ethnology and ethology.

Figure 19: Correlated variety for the “active molecules” sector

5. Development of Amazonian ecotourism

The tourist potential of French Guyana is quite important, in particular regarding of the development of its natural heritage and its cultural diversity. Tourism generates significant direct and indirect effects on other branches of the local economy (trade, transport, services, etc.) in terms of added value and job creation.

Of course, the value chain of the tourism sector is made up of a wide variety of actors around different functions: accommodation, catering, transport, travel and receptive agencies, tour operators, car rentals, leisure companies and businesses more broadly, managers of natural sites (parks for example) ... Almost all of the players are present on site with the exception of tour operators (mainly based in France).

Tourism in French Guiana only really started in the 1980s and the sector is not yet structured. It is located in a very competitive regional environment (North of Brazil, Suriname, Guyana).

Today, it is a sector which receives around 110,000 visitors annually (2009 figure), represents the second source of wealth in the territory (9% of GDP) and contributes 26% to the export effort of regional economy. The estimation of the effect on employment into this sector establishes a participation of 6,000 positions distributed in various sectors and structures of very variable sizes, including a majority of micro-enterprises and VSEs.

Some benefit should allow the department to stand out from its regional and even international competitors. The first one which offers it a tactical positioning on a global level is to be the only European territory in the Amazon. This ideal situation gives the territory significant advantages, especially for a Western audience. We can particularly cite membership of the euro zone, a certain feeling of security (political stability, security of goods and people, equipment and health services to European standards. The second advantage refers to the place of space tourism linked to the activities carried out in the space sector in French Guiana is without equivalent in the world. This is one of the main reasons for coming to French Guiana which captures the majority of the tourist business flow, as well as a good part of the tourist flow.

This position sometimes leads to consider Kourou as a captive market. Space also plays a significant role in the tourism development of other parts of Guyana around the space center.

The sector is nevertheless struggling to develop in particular because of the high costs (air transport from Europe to Guyana) and the competition from other countries operating on this market: Costa Rica in particular, Guatemala, Peru are developing the same offer. Outside the classic Rio-Salvador-Fortaleza - Pantanal circuits, Brazil is also developing an increasingly large and quality offer in the legal Amazon (especially around Manaus).

Therefore, one of the challenges is in any case to develop advantages in terms of non-price and non-cost competitiveness, which suggests the achievement of significant efforts aimed at improving the professionalization of reception and renovation of certain reception structures, to the identification of hiking trails...). In this sense ecotourism (or agritourist, green tourism, nature tourism, sport tourism ...), which is a form of expanding tourism, and which aims to reduce or cancel the ecological damage during the trip constitutes a niche of opportunity not aiming to develop mass tourism, especially in the face of price differentials in neighboring territories, but rather to move towards a high-end welcome with more readable services and higher added value.

Ecotourism is now defined as responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment, sustains the well-being of the local people, and involves interpretation and education” (TIES, 2015). Education is meant to be inclusive of both staff and guests.

Ecotourism is based on four principles:

- promoting the preservation and protection of the environment and biodiversity while minimizing impacts;
- the equitable contribution to local economic development by improving local employment opportunities;
- taking into account the needs of host communities by seeking a better understanding of nature, society and local culture;
- the promotion of an authentic and responsible tourist expression.
- Adaptation of constructions (bringing solutions from sustainable tropical buildings to traditional housing)
- Services to national and European standards

The contribution of R / I to the sector can be summarized in a better understanding of biodiversity and traditional knowledge:

- Adaptation of infrastructure and activities to a preserved natural ecosystem;
- Improvement of the quality, interest and attractiveness of actions to discover the natural environment (R/I associated with scientific training sessions for guides)
- Integration of new forms of tourism: solidarity tourism, fair tourism, integrated and diffused tourism, scientific tourism.

Specifically for science tourism, teams from around the world are coming to French Guiana to study the ecosystem, flora and fauna of the Amazon rainforest.

The research organizations concerned are looking for quality turnkey services (transfers, accommodation, catering, basic scientific equipment, qualified nature guides).

Inventory of emerging and high potential sectors

The “high potential emerging sectors” identified at this stage are:

1. "management and exploitation of biomass and carbon";
2. "environmental management and monitoring";
3. “tele-application”;
4. "Eco-construction - tropical buildings";
5. “tropical health and emerging diseases”.

It will be recalled that most of these areas are at the crossroads of different themes which represent niches with very high added value and very high technicality. On the other hand, the actors in these fields are often few and the critical mass incomplete.

1. Management and exploitation of biomass and carbon

Several observations suggest that the “Biomass and carbon management and exploitation” sector is a promising sector for French Guiana:

- French Guiana is faced with significant development needs in terms of agricultural clearing, urban extension, road development, etc., but most of the biomass obtained by agricultural, urban clearing or logging is currently little or no valued;
- with a very large territory (around 16% of the area of France) and almost entirely covered by tropical forest, French Guiana takes advantage from the presence of a significant carbon stock at the national level;
- the territory is a major importer of fuels with a double impact in terms of carbon economy;
- knowledge on the carbon stock in French Guiana is poorly developed, whereas this knowledge is a necessary prerequisite for the development of more detailed follow-up actions and / or the search for solutions with a lower impact on the environment.

In this respect, initiatives could in particular concern:

- knowledge, monitoring and development of French Guiana's carbon stock;
- defining innovative processes with low carbon costs, in particular in the logging and agriculture sector;
- development of biomass, particularly for energy, which has significant positive spinoffs (coupled spinoffs).

Correlated variety for the “carbon-biomass” domain

Correlated benefits of the “biomass” sector in Guyana

2. Environmental management and monitoring: remote sensing

French Guiana, a space land, had to develop activities related to space. Due to the isolation of the territory and the difficulties of access to certain areas of this territory, satellite-assisted surveillance remains at this stage the only economically viable solution. Recent news items (problematic of illegal fishing or illegal gold mining) show that there is a real need for remote sensing.

The revival of the dynamics around the SEAS satellite image reception station as well as the development of new satellite observation tools (in particular very high optical or radar resolution) offer interesting opportunities for business development. However, there is a risk that the problems of the past will continue (problems of governance and the station's business model).

In addition, a critical mass is being formed with the announcement of the local establishment of several companies of national scope around the operation of the station (SIRS, CLS, Telespazio ...).

Once again, neighboring and even European countries, facing the same problems, represent important potential markets. This is particularly true for Amazonian countries because FG has the only spot5 image reception station for the entire north of South America and part of the Antilles.

Thus, the processing of images captured by the satellite as soon as it passes over the areas concerned represents an important advantage in terms of efficiency, particularly for applications requiring high reactivity (monitoring of illegal exploitation of resources, natural disasters, etc.) . Integration into major European networks or approaches is also possible, more particularly through initiatives such as the network of European regions using space technologies (NEREUS) or the European Earth observation program Copernicus (eg GMES).

Correlated variety for the "environmental management and monitoring: remote sensing" sector

3. Tele-applications

As mentioned above, the development of the “tele-applications” sector is mainly driven by internal demand, but also by external demand from neighboring countries:

- internal demand is linked to the constraints of French Guiana, which are the (internal) isolation and the distance to the European Union. Initial attempts at developing applications have been successful, in particular with regard to telemedicine (with the support of the Space Center):

telemedicine suitcases are in use in various isolated sites with recent developments such as the implementation in place of an ultrasound robot (Maripasoula-Cayenne);

- the demand for this type of tool also comes from neighboring countries which face identical problems.

Demand also comes from certain economic sectors (such as oil exploitation).

However, there are several obstacles to the development of the Tele-applications sector:

- the costs of implementing the technologies concerned remain relatively high;
- the economic development of the products developed is difficult to implement;
- the current development of this sector is generally subject to the proper development of digital spatial planning policies.

A margin of maneuver must therefore be found on these various aspects to ensure the development of this sector, in particular by calling on cooperation.

Correlated variety for the tele-applications sector

4. Eco-construction – tropical building

The construction industry in the broad sense employed almost 3,400 people in 2011. According to the Need for Labor (BMO) survey, the construction industry would represent 25% of the hires envisaged in 2013 (i.e. 1,445 potential hires), more than the half of these recruitments are considered "difficult".

More specifically, the “Eco-construction - tropical buildings” sector can be defined as including the creation, restoration, renovation or rehabilitation of buildings, taking into account tropical

specificities (with the associated risks) and current issues of sustainable development and energy management (in an environment where energy resources are scarce and expensive). Concretely, the “Eco-construction or tropical buildings” sector in a tropical context covers two main fields of activity:

- materials and construction: ie bio-sourced materials from renewable plant resources, recyclable and generated from local resources; and the building stakeholders who use these materials;
- energy systems which group together the equipment contributing to energy management (for example: regulation equipment, energy consumption optimization services, etc.), the use of renewable energies (RE) in buildings (photovoltaic integrated into the frame, solar water heater) through equipment allowing their integration into the frame. This also includes energy diagnostic services.

The value chain of the sector can be broken down around the following trades:

- manufacturers and / or distributors of building materials;
- manufacturers, distributors and / or installers of equipment contributing to energy management;
- building and public works companies;
- engineering and design services (design offices, architects);
- public and private developers and promoters;
- owners of built heritage, in particular public authorities (for example the Region for the school park).

The tropical building sector maintains close links with the ENR sector in its photovoltaic component, solar water heater and smart grids. The tropical built sector is undoubtedly one of the essential support points for the diversification of solar players. The challenges in terms of employment are obviously high, due to the weight of construction in the regional economy. We will therefore focus here essentially on the challenges in terms of markets.

The major challenge of the construction industry as a whole, and of the tropical construction sector in particular, is above all the response to domestic demand, under the combination of three factors:

- the housing needs of the territory linked to demographic growth (the Guyana region aims to achieve more than 1,500 new social housing units per year and a plan for overseas housing is currently being prepared by the DEGéOM);
- changes in regulations setting new requirements;
- the state of the built heritage which is significantly behind in terms of energy consumption.

The "tropical buildings" sector therefore has strong potential for internal development with players active throughout the value chain. In the field of materials, traditional materials are mainly imported (concrete, plasterboard, etc.), even if some local companies offer opportunities to diversify sources of supply (cf., for example, the emergence of the production of cold-made bricks with local laterite). Local biomass is still little exploited for construction, while the biomaterials sector does not exist.

Room for maneuver must therefore be found on different aspects to ensure the development of this sector and reduce the development brakes currently existing:

- the players in the "tropical building" remain few in number and isolated without sufficient interaction between them, which means that they still have little impact on the construction industry as a whole;
- most of the projects in progress relating to innovations mainly concern new constructions, while the renovation needs are also significant;
- the subject is still insufficiently supported by public procurement to initiate this dynamic and consolidate the skills and know-how developed locally; the area of thermal renovation of the social housing stock could provide a relevant point of support to initiate large-scale grouping of players and consolidate the growth of the sector.
- there is also great inertia on the use of new materials on the part of concrete manufacturers and importers of construction materials

Correlated variety for the “Eco-construction - tropical buildings” sector

5. Tropical health and emerging diseases

Health issues in the tropics are not strictly speaking part of the economic sector in the sense that they are not or only slightly creating jobs and businesses. However, this sector is potentially a source of economy for the territory (reduction in the impact of certain infections or epidemics), of excellence, and from time to time the development of economically valuable tools.

Vector-borne tropical diseases affect millions of people and cause thousands of deaths worldwide each year (endémies). In addition, due to global warming and ever-increasing population flows, this type of disease also affects temperate countries. Thus, the first case of dengue with indigenous transmission was observed in hexagonal France (2011), its vector (*aedes aegypti*, moreover also vector of yellow fever) is now established permanently in the south of France .

In the field of health, the identification of factors and the understanding of epidemic and / or emergence phenomena are key elements for the development and conduct of public policies in terms of prevention and control including economic benefits direct or indirect can be major (death, hospitalizations, work stoppages, absenteeism etc ...).

With the support of FP7 funding and due PO FEDER, the Pasteur Institute of Guyana and the Cayenne Hospital Center are developing research capacity on emerging diseases, in particular on the means of control and / or the problems of vector resistance.

This sector offers significant opportunities for partnerships with other actors on an international scale and potential fertilizations with other sectors can be envisaged:

- the chemistry of natural substances: search for active molecules to fight against emerging diseases or the spread of their vectors;
- ecology: impacts of environmental changes on vector populations and therefore epidemiology.

There are also possibilities for coupling with satellite-assisted environmental observation.

Correlated variety for the “Health in tropical environment” sector

Social innovation

Development of social and solidarity economy

Social innovation was first introduced into the European regional programs during the 2014-2020 programming. As this area is new, action strategies have struggled to emerge. Initially, the CTG’s public policies focused on supporting the social and solidarity economy. In fact, this sector of activity often responds to strong social demand and constitutes an important source of jobs.

This is how CTG supports the structuration of the sector through the actions of CRESS (Regional Chamber of Social and Solidarity Economy) whose action plan is as follows:

- Professionalization of the offer;

- Identification and solvency of the request;
- Use of the digital system (digital platform) for the territorial reconciliation of supply and demand, often being local services.

The main sectors concerned are:

- Personal services
 - o Children's free time
 - o Support for the elderly
 - o Household services
- Agriculture and agro-processing (integration farms)
- The building sector

The current scheme is being renewed. Reflections are underway to strengthen actions in the humanities on the subjects of immigration and indigenous peoples. The department of human sciences of the UG is thus called upon. It is a question of clarifying the public policies to be conducted in these 2 fields.

The implementation of pilot self-construction actions

Self-healing is part of the traditions of the Guyanese populations.

With the partnership of developers and social landlords, a pilot project will soon be launched.

The potentials of the different sectors identified, with regard to the factors specific to intelligent specialization are referenced in the following table:

Strategic action areas	Critical mass			Potential markets			Competition
	Research	Education	Business	Local	France/ Europe	Amazon Guyana Plateau	
Forest resources	++	0	+	+++	+++	+++	+++
Agriculture and agro-processing	+	+	+	+++	+++	-	+++
Ecotourism	+	+	+	+++	+++	+	+++
Marine and primary resources	+	0	++	++	++	---	+++
Biomass and carbon	++	0	+	+++	+	+++	+
Active molecule	++	0	0	+	++	+	+++
Eco-construction – tropical building	+	+	+	+++	+	+	++
Télé-applications	+	0	+	+++	+	+++	+
Télé-détection	++	+	+	+++	+	+++	+
Hearth in the tropics	++	+	0	SO	SO	SO	SO

Note : SO : not applicable

Spatial activity

French Guiana is the European launching ground for rockets and satellites. The territory is not affected by upstream activities such as the assembly of satellites and rocket stages. This is how all space research is concentrated in continental Europe (design of launchers and satellites).

In order to change the situation, within the framework of the call "Industrial Territories, the CTG in partnership with the EPCIs, is taking action to strengthen the spinoffs of space in French Guiana, both in terms of industrial production and research. It is a question of strengthening the territorial governance on the space activity and of making the territory more attractive for this activity.

In the context of this call for projects, two other action sheets were selected: the training of technicians and then space engineers with the creation of a department dedicated to space within the UG. Ultimately, the University's rise in competence suggests the conduct of doctoral students. The other action sheet concerns the hosting of start-ups related to space activity. As you can see, the beginnings of a new space ecosystem are taking shape. This new proactive approach is favored by a reshaping of the European launch chain, essentially under pressure from American competition (Space X).

The priorities of the S3 that could be of interest to the other ORs are as follows:

- Tropical vector diseases;
- Support for historic sectors (agriculture, fishing);
- Emerging sectors such as the green economy (enhancement of biodiversity, renewable energy, green building, eco-tourism), the blue economy (sport fishing, aquaculture), the digital economy (remote sensing, digital transition of companies), the SSE (including digital inclusion).

For the next program, the social innovation component will be enriched in order to well take into account the problems and challenges of French Guianese society. Therefore, two new areas will be introduced: immigration and indigenous peoples. The aim is to provide decision-makers with reliable and up-to-date data on the situations encountered, to provide analysis and recommendations for decision support. In this context, the university's humanities department will be in high demand.

6) Public policies

Mobilization on the H2020

The intervention of PO FEDER of PO FEADER in R / I is supervised by S3.

Innovation and research benefit from € 30 million in ESI funds; i.e. respectively 7.6% of the ESI for the 2014-2020 programming and 17 € / year / inhabitant.

Strategic development frameworks

The new SRDEII (Regional Plan for Economic Development, Innovation and Internationalization) adopted in December 2019 is the start from the previous plans. Indeed, it tries to take

objectively into account a particular situation in French Guiana with a high unemployment rate (Unemployment 9% (INSSE 2018), against 9% in France), a significant proportion of young people in the population (50 % under 25) due to strong demographic growth (+ 2.6% per year, against + 0.3% in France, - 0.1% in Guadeloupe and - 0.7% in Martinique. One of the primary objectives of this scheme is the creation of 3000 jobs / year.). For this, it is a question of no longer being content with satisfy increasing domestic demand but putting priority on endogenous development through the development of local resources. Public policies in the field of research and innovation can play an important role in achieving these objectives.

The promotion of Amazonian bioresources and know-how

The strategy aims to develop high value-added products from agriculture, agro-processing and biodiversity from Amazonian bioresources and associated traditional knowledge. It is a question of setting up tools allowing the development of the richness in biodiversity of FG.

It is also necessary to take into account the distinctive feature of the particular economic fabric of FG: 98% of TPE of which 70% with only one employee.

This typology partly explains the low involvement of companies in contracting for research or innovation. In many cases, the support action begins with the upgrading of traditional production standards to allow these family structures to access the conventional market.

The innovation must make it possible to make standards not of a competitive handicap but a qualitative asset on the national, European and international markets.

Given the low volume of the productions concerned, intervention by the public authorities is essential to enable VSEs to pass this milestone.

Public action in favor of bioresources is divided into the following axes:

- Technical, scientific, legal and financial support for local VSEs in the creation or growth phase and creating shared development tools.
- Capture the attractiveness of external industrial companies for Amazonian bioresources by offering services with high added value (bioprospecting, biocollect, agricultural production and primary processing). It is in this logic that the CTG signed a partnership agreement with the

"Cosmetic Valley" (national cluster around cosmetic products). Note also that this cluster provides support and expertise to small local producers.

- Create new cooperative tools for promotion

o The experimental farm

Following the registration of 15 local plants in the French pharmacopoeia, it is a question of going from picking to agricultural production in order to meet market demand (locally or export depending on the plants). The missions of the farm are to develop cultural routes in order to indicate to the farmers how to produce and to define technical and economic benchmarks in order to generate a potential income.

o The technological hall

The aim is to provide small processors with shared bioresource transformation chains (herbal tea, liquid extracts, oils, essential oils, freeze-drying).

- Protect and enhance traditional knowledge

In the Amazon, there are many examples of biopiracy of traditional knowledge from the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industry. Beyond the resources of biodiversity, the associated traditional knowledge constitutes a wealth and a potential often underestimated locally. They allow either to identify new avenues of valorization (new discoveries of uses); or to accelerate research and innovation processes (scientific confirmation of use). A specific action in favor of traditional knowledge is underway with 5 components: inventory, conservation, transmission, legal protection and promotion. This action is due to economic issues. It is also urgent because the holders of knowledge are often elderly people.

The development of Amazonian aquaculture

The high rainfall and the large number of rivers and the large continental shelf (13,298 km²) make FG a land of choice for freshwater and marine aquaculture.

The development plan for roe-goat rearing, which was set up occasionally during the Green Plan for Guyana (1975), ended in failure. The conditions of the breeding were not adapted to the Amazonian conditions (pumping necessary) and relatively hot renewal water (28 to 31 ° c) which increases the oxygenation needs. The new development plan for the sector gives pride of place to Amazonian species already adapted to the ecosystem.

Development of new agro-ecological practices

Agricultural development strategies and the application of agricultural practices have been slammed into patterns of production in France. As European agriculture approaches a transition to agroecology, we are rediscovering the virtues of traditional farming practices. With the INRAE partnership, the inventory of traditional practices is becoming a source of innovation towards this transition. This is particularly the case for agroforestry.

Renewable energies development

French Guiana is the region of France with the highest rate of green energy (60%). Due to their isolation, all the ORs are constrained by the lack of interconnection. Optimizing the energy mix adapted to each situation therefore becomes the rule.

The priority research areas are:

- Biomass energy from sawmill waste and agricultural deforestation. The sustainability of the sector requires the mixed replanting of timber species and biomass. With the assistance of CIRAD, varieties of biomass canes are currently being tested. This will diversify the sources of supply.
- Fuel cells constitute the new component of the energy mix taken into account in Guyana. Their reliability increases over time and their cost decreases rapidly.
- Turbines at sea and in rivers represent an interesting potential because of the large size of the continental shelf and the large number of rivers present in Guyana.

Adaptation of economic sectors to climate change

The first significant signs of climate change in the Amazon are the succession of severe droughts and the appearance of major floods and strong winds.

The sectors most affected are agriculture, fishing in the short term and, in the longer term, the wood sector with the drop in forest production yield.

For agriculture, the resilience action of the sector is oriented towards research on the adaptation of agricultural practices and financial support for the acquisition of equipment. A second part concerns the culture shelters. Farmers must be supported both technically and financially for the acquisition of equipment. Again, new innovative practices are to be developed for dissemination to professionals.

Such as support for the rise of the UG (As a reminder, the UG was created in 2014.)

The mobilization of H2020

The mobilization of H2020 is very modest in FG. This program is thus relegated to third position after the national OPs and Calls. In fact, the 2014-2020 programming saw the CTG become a managing authority. The political and administrative challenge was high to see CTG succeed in this new responsibility. There was therefore no leverage from H2020 on project funding.

- Public policies

Synergy of funds	
Total H2020 per capita per year	14,6
Total ESIF dedicated to R&I from 2014 to 2018	10 267 900
Total ESIF dedicated to R&I per year per capita	10,2
Ratio between (Total H2020 per capita per year) and (Total ESIF dedicated to R&I per capita per year)	1,4

Synergy of funds

A more in-depth analysis of the H2020 / ESIF synergy will make it possible to make a comparison with other ORs and other territories in continental Europe.

C - Regional organizational characteristics

1) Review of higher education and research organizations' participation determinants

In French Guiana, only 3 research organizations participated in FP7 and H2020: CIRAD, IPG and UG.

In general, the size of the research team seems to play a decisive role in applying for the PS.

For the UG, the determining factor seems to be the international personal relationships of the researcher carrying out the project.

With regard to IPG and CIRAD, the international unit at the headquarters of the structure (Paris and Montpellier) seems to have played a decisive role.

2) Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions

In all overseas territories leaders in research and innovation (Canaries, Acores, Madeira, Reunion), the university plays a major role in excellence and plays a locomotive role for all R&D institutions local.

The University of FG created in 2014 first had to settle the financial and administrative questions due to the separation from the West Indies.

Within the former UAG (University of the West Indies Guyana), there was a breakdown of the priority areas of teaching and research: Guadeloupe for the hard sciences, Martinique for the human sciences and Guyana for the technologies (due to the presence of space on the territory.)

During the split (which was done in pain following a hard strike in French Guiana and against the current of the national strategy of regrouping of universities), several laboratories in human sciences migrated towards Martinique and in particular that of materials sciences in Guadeloupe. During the 2014-2020 programming, a significant effort by teacher-researchers was made to validate their HDR (habilitation to supervise research: supervision of PhD students), for the eligibility of research projects presented to ESIF. In summary, it can be argued that the UG will not be fully operational for actions only for the next 2021-2017 programming.

However, it is important to take into account the management of the strong growth in the number of students. They were 250 in 2017, 4200 in 2018 and 4500 in 2019. The chronic understaffing of teacher-researchers must not unbalance the distribution of time between research and teaching.

The CTG (management authority of the ESIF) intends to do everything possible to make the UG the engine of research in FG in synergy with the national research organizations. To this end, particular attention will be given to strengthening UMRs (Joint Research Units).

3) Analysis of institutional strategies

Exchanges, surveys (8 returns from questionnaires / 10 organizations: INSERM, UG, IFREMER, LEEISA, IRD, IPG, MNHN, APT) and interviews with research organizations and the UG revealed the following points regarding their strategy toward FP programs:

- Supports

- Lobbying

- Priority to ESIF projects

Most of the projects submitted to the ESIF are subject to prior negotiations with the managing authority. This proximity to dialogue greatly contributes to the submission of projects that fit well into the territorial R&I strategy. The main interest for research organizations is that the time spent setting up projects is very well valued financially compared to national and European calls. Indeed, the lower complexity and selectivity of projects associated with higher rates of public funding makes ESIF very attractive.

- Centralized governance of research organizations

For national and European calls, the hexagonal headquarters of research organizations have greater control over local decisions to respond to them. National team projects are often favored in the allocated envelopes, which can explain the very low participation of research organizations in AAP in FP programs.

4) Analysis of Support Services

There is no local support structure for poultry, setting up or running projects.

D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

1) Patterns of success and failure

The exchanges, surveys or interviews carried out highlighted the following elements of analysis on the chances of success or the risks of failure of projects:

- The network must pre-exist the project

One of the most important key to success is the good knowledge and trust between the partners prior to the CALL. CALLs should improve an existing network and not just be the opportunity to create one. In addition, for the outermost regions, setting up this network takes time and quickly becomes expensive. In summary, the quality of the network is an essential factor in the success of an application and the successful completion of the project.

- Experience in setting up and managing FP projects

The establishment and management FP projects require expertise that is often acquired during the first project. It is therefore advisable to capitalize and disseminate (training sessions and internal support) this expertise within local teams in order to improve overall quality.

The scientific excellence of the researcher and the research team are also a crucial factor.

A good researcher gives himself the best chance of succeeding in an AAP FP. This excellence must also be appreciated by the entire research team.

-The existence of an efficient information system

Information about the publication of CALLs often arrives late. In addition, the time required to set up projects is greatly increased in OR due to distance communication and the limitation of local resources (human and material).

2) Analysis of self-selection determinants

We were only able to collect 4 surveys on the 10 structures present in FG. The researchers mainly retained the following points:

- Small size of the research structure (C8);
- The absence of networking networks in their area of competence (C13);
- The energy expended for FP programs is very high (C14);
- Prefer to collaborate with non-European high level structures ((C17);
- Lack of interest in collaborative research on a European scale (C16);
- Projects are currently funded by less selective programs (C18);
- Not enough time to respond to FP AAP (C19);

- Lack of support structures for setting up and managing projects;
- Time spent setting up the project too important with regard to selectivity (C15);
- Difficulties accessing European resources for setting up projects (C20);
- Dependence on the national headquarters of the research structure (C22).

III - Analysis of the representation

1) Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders (analysis of survey; analysis of interviews)

a) Analyse of Interview FP organizations strategies

Of the 10 structures present in FG, a focus was made on 9 of them: IPG, IRD, IFREMER, CNRS, MNHN, CIRAD, UG, INSERM.

The table below summarizes the percentage of positive responses to the questionnaire.

Table of positive responses to the questionnaire "FP organizations strategies"

The following comments may be made:

- Of the 10 structures, 54% of have already answered a FP AAP;
- Most of the structures indicating the existence of an internal strategy (54%) also mention that it is effective at national level;
- Similarly for lobbying (54% positive response), it is organized at national level with often a representation in Brussels;
- The existence of supports for setting up projects (33%) is mainly due to structures that have already responded to the FP AAP;
- The rate of good practices is low (22%) is mainly the result of structures that have already responded to the FP CALL;
- Paradoxically, one holder of FP projects does not have a PhD;
- International mobility is superior to national mobility. This can be explained by the fact that a large proportion of the organizations present in Guyana also operate throughout the tropical zone. This positively affects the mobility of researchers;
- It should be noted that there is a very low rate (11%) of researchers involved in international networks. Most of those who responded positively also applied for the FP.
- Finally, 22% of researchers participated as an expert in FP AAPs.
- The survey is adapted to the Anglo-Saxon research system in which research is carried out by a department of a university. In France, the research units are the operational structure. Ultimately, the questions have different targets:
- For the survey FP Participation / Internal Strategy: research unit are the target;
- Lobby, Promotion Activities, Incentives, Support activities: the answer must come from the national level.

In French Guiana, only the university is relevant to respond: the other structures (AgroParisTech and national research organizations) do this at the national level. To conclude, the local representatives of an organization (like me for AgroParisTech) are not relevant on any point. It will be difficult to compile these responses to draw conclusions.

In conclusion, it emerges from this survey that the organizations that respond to FP FPs have the following characteristics:

- Existence of an internal strategy;
- The presence of a lobbying cell in Brussels;
- Incentives for researchers are implemented within the structures;
- International mobility seems to be a positive factor.

The main obstacles mentioned are:

- Remoteness for communication with partners;
- The small size of the research teams;
- The complexity of setting up and managing projects;
- The volume of administrative burdens for researchers who encounter difficulties in freeing up time for calls;
- Lack of training in setting up projects.

The analysis of the responses to surveys and interviews reveals two subgroups among the researchers, those who have had the experience of applying and led projects and others. Indeed, the experience of FP AAPs has some common points and shares a particular vision of participation. In contrast, researchers never had taken the step of applying to express positions that could be classified.

Commonalities :

- o They are motivated and believe that collaborative science and internationalization is a real asset towards excellence;
- o They have even basic experience of exchange in an international network (active participation in networking);

A common vision:

- o The small size of the structures is not an unavoidable handicap;
- o The production of international publications is the laboratory's calling card

As suggested later in the action plans, awareness-raising and training are first steps in the process of improving the score for responding to CALLs. It is necessary to change the representations and seek a first experience ("the appetite comes by eating").

2) Analysis of the concordance or gaps between survey results and the data

The first elements of analysis of the results of the surveys in relation to the collected database are as follows:

- The size of the structure to search does not seem to be a major blocking factor;
- A solid network of partners is undoubtedly an important factor in responding to vocational training programs;
- The presence of a support structure even located in France is a decisive asset.

IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation

The FORWARD workshop was held on January 27 with 17 participants. The problem tree methodology proposed by NEXA was applied.

A - Major obstacles

The main obstacles identified are:

- The low critical mass both in human resources and in infrastructure;
- Significant team tuning (especially at the level of research organizations and not at all for the university);
- Lack of motivation of researchers;
- Complexity of setting up projects in relation to the benefits that can be drawn from them;
- Very high selectivity and high risk of loss of time if the project is not selected;
- The success rate is correlated with the national performance of the structure;
- The choice of themes poorly suited to the Amazon context (eg carbon balance in urban areas and for transport, not for natural environments);
- Insufficient monitoring of FP programs;
- Low attractiveness of local research structures to interest consortia.

Actions suggested

- Create an ERA chair RUP to attract experienced researchers and thus contribute to the rise of excellence of local teams;
- Increase the number of doctoral and post-doctoral grants;
- Lobbying upstream of the CALL in order to better take into account the problems of RUP;
- Create a mission to support projects including monitoring, support for setting up and managing projects as well as training;
- Consistency of FP programs with local policies.

B - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP

Axis 1: STRENGTHENING UG

THE PROBLEM: Particularity of FG: A university under construction. The UG is currently the main weak link in the R&I ecosystem. After a recovery phase since 2014, the UG must initiate a phase of rebirth and fulfillment; which requires strong support from the State and the CTG.

OBJECTIVE: To make the UG the pivot of the French Guiana R&I ecosystem.

THE ACTIONS:

- Priority funding for the establishment of quality research infrastructures;
- Consolidation of the doctoral school through the increase in the number and amount of doctoral scholarships;
- Improving the response to the needs of the economic sector and the tools for transfer to the private sector;
- Strengthening of the partnership between research organizations and the creation of new UMRs;
- Strengthening of partnerships with ROs, neighboring countries (including Brazil) and EU member countries.

AXIS 2: INCENTIVE TO THE EXCELLENCE OF THE LOCAL R&I ECOSYSTEM

THE PROBLEM: FESI funds compete with those of national CALLs and the FP

OBJECTIVES: Take a first step of excellence through FESI

THE ACTIONS:

- Generalization of the framework agreement between the CTG and the research organizations which sets objectives of excellence specific to each structure;
- Establish indicators of excellence in the specifications of FESI AAPs with modulations of intervention rates according to the level of excellence of the structures:
 - o Introduction of internationalization criteria (encouragement for the creation of international consortia);

- o Improve expertise in project appraisal and project evaluation with the creation of a group outside the territory covering the fields of competence of the priority areas;
- o The number of international publications over the last 5 years and citations;

AREA 3: CONSOLIDATE THE INNOVATION LINK OF THE FRENCH GUIANIA R&I ECOSYSTEM

THE PROBLEM: The structure in charge of innovation has neither the means nor the tools allowing it to fully play its role of interface between research and the economic world

OBJECTIVE: To strengthen the role of GDI as an ecosystem leader and a major player in recovery

THE ACTIONS:

- Improve the innovation network at different levels: regional, national, European and international;
- Create tools necessary for support (particularly VSEs) and technology transfer (experimental farm, technology hall, fablab, numlab, etc.);
- Define indicators of innovation excellence and a partnership roadmap;
- Establish a permanent physical and virtual exchange space between companies and research.

AREA 4: SUPPORT FOR NATIONAL CALLS AND FP PROGRAM APPLICATIONS

THE PROBLEM: Local research structures do not have project engineering allowing them to tender and manage projects.

OBJECTIVE: Provide research and innovation structures with shared and efficient training, monitoring and support for setting up and managing national and European call projects

THE ACTIONS:

- Intelligent and targeted monitoring of calls: collection, sorting, analysis, dissemination of information;
- Creation of a pooled cell between all the support organizations for setting up national and FP projects;
- Information for these researchers on the FP program and training on setting up and managing projects;

- Creation of a toolbox of the candidate for national and FP programs;
- Support in setting up and managing projects;
- Creation of a file of potential partners for the priority research themes decided;
- Animation for the exchange of good practices with a capitalization of experiences of application;
- The CTG could reserve a financial envelope for the co-financing of national and international projects in order to make them more attractive.

AXIS 5: NETWORKING OF PARTNERS

THE PROBLEM: due to the distance networking is a significant additional cost for ROs. However, it is obvious that for the implementation of solid partnerships physical meetings are essential.

OBJECTIVES: Creation of a network of partners upstream from national and European calls

THE ACTIONS:

- Support in networking (identification of networks of excellence and making contact, joining networks, etc.);
- Funding for networking on the ESIFs;
- Creation of an R&I network for the ORs.

AXIS 6: LOBBING AND COMMUNICATION

THE PROBLEM: Many national calls and especially European calls do not take into account the particularities of ORs. This constitutes an additional handicap in the performance of ORs in responding to the calls.

OBJECTIVE: Act upstream of the calls for more efficiency

THE ACTIONS:

- Creation at the OR level and with the European Commission (in Brussels) of a lobbying unit for FP calls:
- Act upstream in the drafting of priorities for programs FP and calls.
- Set up targeted communication actions on overseas R&I with the Commission and the European Parliament for a better understanding of the particularities and challenges of overseas on the subject.

Guadeloupe

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems [Guadeloupe]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 824550

Summary

This diagnosis is a first step to better understand the drivers to increase research and innovation local community participation in FP tools.

It demonstrates the willingness of the research community to improve their participation and to play a key role in the next program. They also acknowledge their weakness and praise for some support.

Regarding the figures, the scarcity of some data made the analysis difficult.

This exercise will have to be renewed on a regular basis to evaluate the impact of the actions and tools put in place.

Introduction

As underlined in the 2017 Memorandum of Understanding of the outer-most regions (OR), ORs acknowledge the upmost need for their research and innovation community (R&I Community) to efficiently mobilize UE framework programs. All the more, jointly, they offer an unexpected network of open test bed field, relying on good research capacities and agile and innovative SMEs.

Indeed Guadeloupe R&I community develops a different topic of research to address local economic issues as well environmental and social ones, as prioritized in its smart specialization strategy (RIS3). Further, its geographic location puts the territory at the front line of global challenges, like climate change, aging of the population, natural disasters, biodiversity loss, vector borne and emerging diseases. Taking into account the size of the archipelago, Guadeloupe can be considered as a real open laboratory where a holistic, trans-disciplinary approach is a pre-requisite to tackle efficiently these cross-sectorial challenges.

Thanks to structural funds, research infrastructures and Innovation support, facilities have been funded. Meanwhile, research collaborations with neighboring territories have been supported and fostered due to the quality of the facilities. It makes the R&I community well connected with Caribbean research networks. But, its participation to EU framework program appears to be low compared to that of structural funds.

Nevertheless, structural funds are the easiest and the smallest part of the EU budget dedicated to support Research excellence, Innovation and SME competitiveness. We assume the amount of structural funds will decrease due to financial constraints. Further, Research excellence relies on the quality of facilities and the connection with successful and recognized laboratories. As well, Innovation and SME competitiveness are linked to a continuous dialogue between researchers and SME, well-shaped supporting services and transfer facilities and to complete value chains. The RIS3 of Guadeloupe mentions actions to be developed in order to increase research excellence and stimulate innovation. Among those, mobilizing framework program is the major one. Indeed Framework programs allow such connections. It may also highlight activities implemented in Guadeloupe and their added value to EU.

So, in order to develop a resilient economy regarding the fast changes the territory has to face with, it as to be based on a pragmatic and good knowledge which fuels companies and citizen's involvement and where the uptake of research results goes easily. Then to avoid re-inventing the wheel and to go faster, collaboration and exchange with European Research Area, in a teaming and twining perspective, are crucial to foster Guadeloupe R&I community capacities to sustain the local economy. Therefore, increasing its participation to framework program is a need. To do so, an objective and deep diagnosis is a pre-requisite to design an adequate and operational strategy and draw an action plan.

Methodology

Regional council of Guadeloupe thanks the local partners from research centers, innovation poles and others who contributed to the survey and dedicated time to fill in the different templates. Their insight and recommendations helped us draft this first diagnosis.

The regional council of Guadeloupe acknowledges their involvement is the design of this very first deliverable of FORWARD. It shows a real interest in framework programs, these highly competitive tools compared to structural funds. In a way, we now know where we are, where we start. We can and have to do better from now.

3 partners from Guadeloupe, University of Antilles, innovation pole Synergîle and the regional council of Guadeloupe, are involved in the FORWARD project. Regional council of Guadeloupe leads the activities in close relation with the two other partners.

The diagnosis has been conducted based on the methodology and materials provided by WP2 leader and its support and advice throughout the duration of the diagnosis.

First, on March 22nd, a presentation of FORWARD project, its objectives, expected results and output has been made to the local R&I Community. The idea was to give them a whole picture of the project and its potential links with some future work like the update of the RIS3 and the next EU operational program 2021-2027. It was also to introduce them to the survey.

Second, the questionnaire was sent to the members of the R&I community. Synergîle made a deep review of its members to collect information and evaluate their knowledge of EU framework program (FP) as well as their interest in these tools. After reaching out to research centers, several phone interviews were conducted as well as physical meetings to get more precise information. The diagnosis has been conducted at different levels. At first we met directors of research centers. To deepen the results and fine-tune them, we met some researchers.

- 7 researchers who never applied or been part to a FP project even if they are well connected to different networks and publish in high impact factor review,
- 5 researchers who were not successful at H2020, but only tried once,
- 6 researchers who were successful and led one or more FP Projects.

We completed the survey with internal data. Indeed, the regional council has been involved in some FP projects itself.

Third, we crossed the information collected with a research analysis made on CORDIS project database. We also used the EU dashboard (webgate.ec.europa.eu). Indeed, the diagnosis is based on 14 years of R&I activities and research teams changed sometimes.

Fourth, we used the RIS3 strategic domains to organize the data in a more accurate way.

Finally, crossing the figures and analyzing the feedback and comments from the R&I community gave us some main tendencies regarding FP mobilization and some expectations from the R&I community to better mobilize FP tools.

To conduct the analysis, we did not consider projects selected or applications made through COFUND project joint call (ie. ERA-Net COFUND project launching a joint call) either with EU fund or without) as data to be taken into account.

Nevertheless, the scarcity of some data may jeopardize the quality of the analysis. Indeed, some researcher organizations based in Guadeloupe are not registered as from Guadeloupe, but from France, in the database. Therefore some figures do not really reflect the involvement of local teams and the amount the EU money they benefit from.

We also missed some key feedback from the R&I community view on its level of excellence and its capacities to apply to FP tools and on which actions to implement to increase its success rate or attract more R&I community members to use them.

We hope to gather more information during the whole project in order to fine tune the exercise. We plan to use the template in a long term perspective to evaluate the impact of the joint strategy that will come out from the overall diagnosis. Coming back to R&I community on a regular basis to collect the information along the way.

I - State of play of participation

1) Evolution of regional participation

Participation

Considering the R&I community in Guadeloupe, we may consider different levels of involvement in FP project. The more common are as coordinator or as WP Leader. We also have to take into account the case when local researchers take part to the research activities even if the name of the facilities doesn't appear.

From FP7 to H2020, there is an increase in R&I community participation in FP, +50%. Meanwhile, for H2020 it has been less successful, with +22% increase.

About FP7, looking at the figures collected, we identified 10 proposals. Nevertheless, the success rate of proposals, 90%, appears to be very high. Indeed, the average success rate of applications is around 20.5%¹. But, we ignore the number of applications made before being successful. Indeed, among the 10 proposals identified, only one has been coordinated by a local research center. Considering this proposal, it has been successful at the third attempt. Further, the tool "REGPOT" was specifically dedicated to low performing regions.

About H2020, the number of proposals raised up to 13 and the funded ones is up to 9. Further, the total number of participations is around 12 which is relatively low. The success rate of proposals is around 69,2%. As for FP7 the average success rate is 16%².

There are some newcomers, like Synergile innovation pole or the chamber of commerce. But the Hospital Center did not make a new attempt or has not been contacted to get in a new project.

¹ Seventh FP7 Monitoring Report 2013 (EC, DG research&innovation – Evaluation unit, 2015)

² Horizon 2020, first results (EC, DG RDT – evaluation unit, 2015)

Graph 1 : Success rate & Number of proposals

EU contribution

Some research centers from mainland France are present in Guadeloupe and carry out research programs with local researchers. Nevertheless, these local researcher centers do not appear in the EU database. The database only mentions the funds allocated to the national research centers without detailing the allocation between the different regions. This bias has also an impact on EU money the local R&I community receives. As the grant agreement only mentions the mainland research center, we don't even have access to the EU money shared among the different teams, including the ones located in Guadeloupe. Therefore we only have the real figures for 4 projects, amongst the 9 funded ones (5 projects are led by national research centers).

Nevertheless, amongst the 5 projects carried out by national research centers in Guadeloupe and funded by EU money it is impossible to know the percentage of EU funds actually dedicated to the programs carried out in Guadeloupe. Therefore graphs 2 and 3 do not reflect precisely the existence of EU funds in research programs in Guadeloupe.

First, despite the increased number of proposals funded, Guadeloupe R&I community received less EU money in H2020 than in FP7, from now. Indeed, among the 9 applications funded under FP7, one (EPIGENESIS) was coordinated by a local research team and it was the only beneficiary. Even, if there are more projects with a WP leader under H2020, being a coordinator has a strong impact on the funding awarded.

Further, the average number of participants involved in H2020 projects granted is around 22, compare to an average number of 17 participants, regarding projects granted under FP7.

Graph 2 : Funding awarded

Graph 3 : EU awarded & Average EU per regional partner

2) Participation to the different programs and funding schemes

From FP7 to H2020, some new funding schemes disappear while new ones appear. For instance, Research Potential has not been pursued under H2020. H2020 implementation relies on a complementary and synergy with the use of structural funds as well as on leverage effects with national and regional funds. Era-Net COFUND tool is in this spirit.

Graph 4 : FP7, participation per specific program

The programs dedicated to cooperation and capacities were the most mobilized. These two specific programs address some main issues as fostering excellence of research teams and increasing collaboration to tackle great challenges. Nevertheless, people specific program which include MSCA grant, which is also a key tool to reinforce research excellence and attract high profile, was not mobilized.

Graph 5 : FP7, participation per funding schemes and action types

Graph 6 : H2020, participation per specific program

Societal challenges specific program reached the highest score. Projects funded under this specific program are mainly cooperation ones with big consortiums.

In FP7, we had one infrastructure project. Still under H2020, though Science excellence project, we have 2 projects. But no project has been funded under “spreading excellence and widening participation”. Regarding the profile and background of the R&I community, this specific program should have been mobilized to increase its performance on FP.

Graph 7 : H2020, participation per funding schemes and action types

We may notice one project under the SME instrument, P2EI project. It aims at fostering FP tool dedicated to SME. It went from 2017 to 2018. It will be interesting to check the results and impacts regarding the number of proposals under SME instrument.

The kind of funding schemes mobilized from FP7 to H2020 are quite similar: collaborative projects, research infrastructure and coordination actions.

Apart from H2020, only one project has been funded under another competitive EU program, LIFE “Vida for citrus”. This project is linked to pre-HLB, funded under H2020, as well as CAVALBIO funded with structural funds. It demonstrates the complementarity and synergies research teams try to develop between the different tools to tackle some issues.

The study of the thematic distribution of the projects funded under FP7 and those granted under H2020 could also show if there is a continuity in the research implemented and the consortium, or if each project was a “one shot” experience for local members of R&I community.

3) Thematic distribution

Each region had to design its own smart specialization strategy (RIS3). It relied on research and innovation assets and comparative advantages. One of the aims of RIS3 was to concentrate funds on fields of expertise with a real leverage effect on territory competitiveness. Framework program, like FP7 and H2020, are the main tools to support Europe competitiveness and its sustainability.

RIS3 of Guadeloupe has three strategic domains (SD):

- Valorization of the diversity of island resources : agro-ecology, circular economy, biomaterial, valorization of molecules of interest, renewable energies, smart grid,
- Risk Management and Prevention in Caribbean area : natural disasters, restoration of ecosystem, emerging and vector-borne diseases, aging people and linked diseases, sickle cell disease,
- Promotion of creative industries : creative industries, culture, tourism

ICT¹ is a transversal topic.

The thematic distribution gives us some insight on the main field of expertise where Guadeloupe R&I community is involved in EU FP tools and the one totally missing.

There were 23 thematic priorities under FP7. The 9 granted projects identified are linked to 6 thematic priorities, an average share of 26%. Taking into account the strategic domains of Guadeloupe RIS3, the thematic priority “Energy” is missing.

The distribution among the 6 priorities, is as follow:

¹ ICT : Information and Communication Technologies

Graph 8 : Distribution of FP7 projects per thematic priorities

Environment (including climate change), Food, Agriculture and Fisheries and Biotechnologies and Research potential have been equally mobilized. These thematics are aligned with the strategic domains of Guadeloupe RIS3.

Graph 9 : Distribution of projects under FP7 per strategic domains of the RIS3

Either on FP7 or H2020, some projects funded sometimes refer to more than one strategic domains of RSI-S3.

There are 38 thematic priorities under H2020. We cannot really compare the scope of the thematic priorities of FP7 to those of H2020. The 9 granted projects identified are linked to 5 thematic priorities, so an average share of 13%.

The distribution among the 5 priorities, is as follows:

Graph 10 : Distribution of H2020 projects per thematic priorities

Projects seem to be more distributed. But it relies on the scope of the thematic. Indeed, the thematic “food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research and the bioeconomy”, which deals with natural resources, reaches the highest score, followed by the one dealing with climate “climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials” and research infrastructures.

The first two thematics are almost similar to those mobilized under FP7. Meanwhile, we may notice that the topic “natural disasters” does not appear clearly. Natural risks and “natural disasters” are supported by INTEREG-type territorial cooperation funds or ERDF funds from 2011-2019, for an envelope of 14 projects. This topic covers the fields of marine submersion, coastal risks, major climate and environmental risk assessment. In FP 7 this thematic has been addressed through the thematic “Research infrastructure”.

Then, there is some continuity between FP7 and H2020. Nevertheless, the thematic “Energy” is still underrepresented. But, we identify one project on this thematic among the failed ones less represented. But, this thematic is strongly supported locally by ERDF-type structural funds 2007-2020, 64 M € FEDER.

Graph 11 : Distribution of projects funded under H2020 per RIS3 strategic domains

So, either on FP7 or H2020, the thematic distribution is quite similar and is aligned with RIS3 strategic domains. But, some key scientific domains and field of expertise listed in the RIS are still underrepresented, like renewable energies/smart grids, or valorization of molecule of high interest for biodiversity, or even on marine biodiversity and finally aging people issues.

Regarding the un-successful proposals, the thematic distribution is almost the same, apart from one attempt in the field of energy

We may notice that thematic from FP7 and from H2020 are slightly different. To overcome this situation and deepen the analysis, we look at ERC domains.

Having a look at them, based on the low number of successful applications, it is quite difficult to identify some tendencies. Nevertheless, 3 main pillars are represented, either on FP7 or H2020:

- Life Sciences, with LS6 “Immunity and infection” and LS9 “Applied life science, biotechnology, and molecular and biosystem engineering”;
- Earth Sciences, with EP9 “Universe sciences” and EP10 “Earth system science”
- Humanities, with SH1 “Individuals, Market and Organisations” and SH2 “Institution, values, Environment and Space.

On FP7, Life sciences issues were mostly represented. On H2020, it is more balance between the 3 pillars.

Knowing the different hazards the island is exposed to, either natural disaster or vector bone diseases, the results are quite coherent. Further, increased concerns about pesticides use reduction; pest control and mitigation of climate changes on agriculture also explain the number of projects on life science.

Graph 12 : ERC domains representations in applications on FP7 and H2020

4) Stakeholders mapping

FP are dedicated to a wide range of actors, from research centers, including universities and research infrastructures to SMEs and clusters, and public bodies like chamber of commerce or local authorities. Figures illustrate this diversity of stakeholders. Coordinators and participants are included in the figures.

Guadeloupe Research landscape is composed of a university; a university hospital center and several research centers. These research centers are mainland ones with research teams and facilities located in Guadeloupe. Some of them are among the oldest research organizations based in Guadeloupe (i.e. INRA is 70 years old and it is the INRA center in the overseas). The university is quite young appearing in the eighties. INRA and CIRAD also concentrate most of the research capacity in agronomy, composed mainly of 2 to 3 teams. Further, they benefit from the dynamism of their main office to integrate FP project. The university is composed of around 10 research teams, meaning several small teams.

Graph 13 : Guadeloupe research landscape -Research human resources

This landscape has a strong impact on FP participations and results. The figures reflect this landscape. As we'll see on graphs below, INRA, CIRAD and OMSG-IPGP are the top 3 either on FP7 or H2020.

On Graph 14, FP are mostly mobilized by research centers. University and university hospital center are less successful in FP projects. But, they've been active. Indeed, they failed in 2 attempts on H2020; as did BRGM and INRA. We may also notice that they applied several times on calls launched within ERA-Net COFUND. University has been successful then, as a partner. As a coordinator, it was not.

Then, specific actions should be implemented to increase HES success rate and to take benefit from RES experience.

Graph 14 : Type of stakeholders mobilizing FP7 and H2020

Having a more precise look on research centers, Graph 15 gives a view of the distribution among the research centers located in Guadeloupe. CIRAD seems to be a very good performer, closely followed by INRA and OVSG-IPGP. So, in somehow, the distribution is quite balanced among them, but it might be fragile.

Graph 15 : Research centers mobilizing FP7 and H2020

CIRAD, INRA and OVSG-IPGP concentrate most of the funding from FP. The number of applications and the lack of datas does not allow a deeper analysis at individual level. Further, some tools like Reg-Pot does not exist on H2020. Nevertheless, regarding these 3 organizations, it is each time, almost the same team who is involved in.

Still as individual level, it is more distributed in projects involving university teams. Indeed, the failed attempts were initiated by different laboratories on different topics.

5) Participation profile

Reg Pot tool eased participation of convergence regions as coordinator. As well, INCO Net tool promoted convergence regions participations in FP projects either as coordinator or WPL (workpackage Leader). Graph 16 illustrates this situation.

Graph 16 : Participation profile in FP7 and H2020 projects

Reg Pot toll has disappeared in H2020. Nevertheless, participation in FP projects as partner increased around 66% between both FP.

6) Regional collaboration

Based on Graph 17, Guadeloupe mainly cooperates with Reunion. Cooperation with Canaries islands and Azores closely follows. And after, come collaborations with French Guyana.

Regarding the topic of emerging diseases or vector borne diseases, Guadeloupe and Reunion are often involved in the same projects.

Graph 17 : Collaborations with ORs

Regarding collaborations with Canary Islands and Azores, they rely on some Era-Net and CSA projects, as well as climate change and natural disasters.

The figures reflect the above paragraph. We notice a high participation of 3 main research centers, CIRAD, INRA and IPGP (OVSG). INRA has only one office in the french overseas territories which is located in Guadeloupe and covers also Martinique and French Guyana, with some research teams in French Guyana (Ecofog). CIRAD based in Guadeloupe, also covers Martinique and French Guyana. For each of these overseas, CIRAD has some research teams' based there. CIRAD also has an office in Reunion with some research facilities. Finally, IPGP¹ has a department in Guadeloupe, Martinique and Reunion. But these department do not have a legal status (mean not VAT number). Then, even if the volcanic and seismologic observatory from Guadeloupe take part to a project with the one from Martinique, they are consider as the same and unique research organization. This is not the case for CIRAD Antilles –Guyane and CIRAD Reunion. Each of them has a different VAT number.

To conclude figures show a low number of cooperation between French OR and the Spanish and Portuguese ones. French OR, due to the research organization landscape, tend first to cooperate among the same group of research centers (CIRAD, IPGP). Nevertheless, when it comes to university, it seems slightly different. Unfortunately, the low number of projects cannot confirm this tendency.

¹ IPGP : Physical Globe Institute of Paris

Analysis of participation determinants

B - Network analysis

1) Global connectivity

Guadeloupe stakeholders tend to cooperate with around 23 EU mainland countries. It gives us more than 130 different organizations they get connected with thanks to FP projects.

Graph 18 : Number of participants per EU country

Among the Top 20% countries, Guadeloupe stakeholders are connected with, there are: first comes Italy, then Netherlands, Spain and just below United Kingdom. Partners from these countries are mostly mobilized in projects involving Guadeloupe Stakeholders.

If we look at the number of projects shared with EU mainland countries, these 4 countries also appear at the top 20%. The order is different: Spain and just below the threshold comes United Kingdom. Netherlands and Italy come after.

Last, if we look at the number of different participants, the diversity of partners connected with. These 4 countries are still in the Top 20%: Italy, Netherlands, Spain and United Kingdom.

Comparing the number of projects and the number of different partners, Spain is at the top.

Apart from this group of 4 countries, we may identify another group, with a lower number of common projects, but with a good diversity of partners. It is the case with Germany, Belgium, and Switzerland.

Graph 19 : EU countries Guadeloupe stakeholders are mostly connected with

Germany Spain and United Kingdom are among the most successful EU countries on mobilizing FP tools.

2) Relative position

Guadeloupe RIS3 has 3 Strategic domains of activities (SDA), with one transversal dealing with ICT. The survey underlined the focus on emerging and vector bone diseases as well as natural disasters.

Back to graph 16, involvement as a key player in a project is low. Nevertheless, RIS3 domain “Risk Management and Prevention in Caribbean area” reaches the highest score with 1 coordinator position and all the WPL ones.

3) Third countries participation

Participation with neighboring countries is mainly due to the INCO Net project EUCARINET. The lack of collaboration with partners from these neighboring countries underlined that EUCARINET did not really reach its goals in fostering consortium to mobilized FP tools. Nevertheless, collaboration is high with neighboring as Interreg Caribbean program is successful.

About third countries, they are wide spread on the globe, from Australia to Canada, from Algeria to South Africa, and in South America. Nevertheless, most of them are located or dealing with tropical and subtropical issues, either on agronomy or health.

C - Regional innovation system

1) Regional research performance

Graph 13: Guadeloupe research landscape – Research human resources per organization

Compare to EU mainland research center where the average size of a team is around 100 researchers per laboratory, Guadeloupe landscape show a lack of critical mass. Looking at the number of team per organization it is even more visible (Graph 20).

Graph 20 : Number of team per research organization

Nevertheless, research organizations do mobilize EU funds to cooperate with foreign countries, mostly neighbor ones, thanks to Interreg Caraïbes programme. Further, University

host around 600 hundred foreign research per year. Indeed, University highly mobilized the regional funding tool available to host foreign post-doctoral on 2 years research projects.

For instance, University got 6 postdoctoral grants on the 8 granted. One was to INRA, another one to INSERM. Meanwhile, CIRAD highly mobilizes Interreg Caraïbes program. Indeed, CIRAD got 5 projects granted compare to the 11 funded, knowing researchers are eligible to this funding scheme.

2) Private sector implication

Guadeloupe is mainly composed of very small companies with low funding capacities. Then standard indicators like R&D expenditure are not really meaningful. Indeed, some national funding tools like “Crédit impôt recherché” are not highly mobilized. But most of these funding mechanisms are focus on technical innovation. Then they do not plenty reflect innovation dynamism.

Actually, different tools foster R&D activities and innovation:

- Call for R&D proposal launched by Innovation cluster Synergile, in the field of alternative energies, energy consumption management and raw materials. It is funded under ERDF OP. These projects involved a company and a research team or several companies and several research teams. At least, there should be either one company and research center or 2 companies;
- I-NOVA, Call for innovative project launched by Regional council to detect early stage innovative project and ongoing innovative projects looking for leverage funding.

Regarding the first tool it is about 8 joint projects funded. Thank to I-NOVA, 20 innovative projects which have been selected for around 100 000 € value.

3) RIS3 priorities

Projects granted under FP7 and H2020 all belong to one or more RIS3 Strategic Domains. Graph 9 and Graph 11 show are SD2 is over represented.

If we look at ERDF, regarding the 1st call for joint proposals, the balance between SD1 and SD2 is quite similar (Graph 21). The 2nd call for joint proposals has the same tendency, all the more this is a higher number of medicine research project.

But, SD covers agriculture and environmental issues. These topics are also supported by EADRF and ERDF dealing with environment. Then the total amount of structural funds dedicated to SD1 is higher and we cannot only have a look on research supporting tools.

Graph 21 : ERDF distribution per RIS3 strategic Domain

Regarding the value chain with the different SD of RIS3:

- Agronomy&agriculture

Figure 1 : value chain in agriculture&agronomy

Looking at emerging diseases and vector bone ones, Pasteur Institute is also mobilized. But then, the topic belongs to SD2.

- Alternative energies and raw materials

Figure 2 : Value chain in alternative energies and raw material

Back to the figure regarding FP mobilization, INRA, CIRAD are well represented. RITA and Assofwi a farmer community are also involved in 1 FP project as Synergile. But, from now, it is too early to well evaluate the impact of their participation. Further, Synergile, as an innovation cluster, has to be active in future FP as it is highly requested by the national government and the local authority.

In the field of health, Guadeloupe host several research centers and facilities like gene banks. Nevertheless, links with companies are poor and need some improvement.

Regarding, natural disasters, researcher centers are well organized. Nevertheless, the uptake of the results is weak. Dissemination of the results to citizen could benefit from serious game to be more efficient and reach its goals. Meanwhile, collaboration with architect and national body regarding regulation is efficient. But still training to update practices need some time. The value chain may be improved in the field of raw material based on bio resources and taking into account updated regulation. Nevertheless, combining natural disasters (earthquake and hurricane, flooding and erosion) regulation and law energy consumption regulation is challenging and some companies thank to Synergile call for proposal try to innovate.

D - Regional organizational characteristics

1) Analysis of institutional strategies

Since 2005 regional council of Guadeloupe supports research teams' willing to mobilize FP. Regional council of Guadeloupe invites research teams to consider ERDF as a springboard or a leverage effect to jump to FP tolls. To do so, several actions have been implemented.

First, Regional council jumped into some FP projects (Net-Biome ERA-Net, NETbiome CSA, Biodiversa ERA-NET COFUND, BioDivClim ERA-Net COFUND) to know how it works, how to manage. The idea was to identify internal barriers which could restrain local teams and administration to participate to FP projects and experiment difficulties or administrative burden and then look for pragmatic solutions.

Second, to design a support services to address research teams needs to be able to apply to FP call or to join consortium setting-up. This has been implemented during 3 years, funded by ERDF.

Third, local stakeholders suffer from a lack of credibility. Further, ERDF is seen as a quite easy source of funding. Last, FP projects are mainly collaborative ones. It means to develop some internal expertise on managing different partners and so on. To foster this approach and also put local teams in similar conditions (in somehow) to FP call, Regional council put in place call for joint proposals with scientific independent evaluation to get ERDF.

Fourth, Regional council believes FP has an important leverage effect on research excellence capacities and may foster innovation on key challenges. So working on the draft documents, attending information meeting to promote local capacities, to leave room for local stakeholders so they could benefit from this research and innovation ecosystem and contribute to its recognition at the international level is the fourth axe of its supporting strategy.

After, at the level of research centers, from the survey conducted, apparently, this is no specific strategy. There is no clear incentive to researcher to go to FP call.

But, at the national level, for instance INRA is among the most successful research center in mobilizing FP tools. Further, each national research center (INRA, CIRAD, CNRS, IRD, ...) has a specific referee to follow EU announcements on FP call program and to lobby its field of interest.

So, there is some room for improvement to capitalize on these capacities and promote OR interest too and make them more visible.

Synergîle, innovation cluster is linked to Capernegies, pole de competitivité. "Pôle de competitivité" are highly invited by the French government to mobilize FP tools. Synergîle is a newcomer and are discovering the FP landscape.

2) Analysis of support Services

Local stakeholders are asking for a local support services. All participants of the survey agree on this.

The support services set up for 3 years allowed a local team to be successful on Reg Pot call for proposals (it was their third attempt).

The support service was in 3 parts:

- Setting up a regional page on CORDIS regional portal (no longer in place)
- Newsletter on calls for proposals, with technical advice on some specific issues (IP, partnership agreement, ...), a testimony from a local researcher on its experience in a FP project or attempt to mobilize FP tool and a calendar of local activities implemented by the research community. The newsletter was available only and sent to some contact point at national (ministry of research, ministry of overseas, research funding agency) and EU level (DG region OR Unit, DG RDT INCO unit, thematic unit);
- Some days of consultancy to :
 - 1st option: support a team to draft its application, mainly the management and the budget section.
 - 2nd option: help a researcher/team to join a consortium in order to really benefit from the project and valorize the researcher/team capacities.

The newsletter was a good way to make the community and its activities known. The technical advices also were appreciated. The support to the team on the management part, the design of the budget and the drafting regarding some fulfillment to achieve (open access, ethics rules, deontology issues) is missing now.

E - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

1) Patterns of success and failure

Unfortunately few researchers have been interviewed. Then, it might be difficult to assume that the results of the survey reflect the whole community position. Nevertheless, most of the researchers shared a common profile:

- Connection to international network;
- Average 5 years mobility
- A minimum of 60 rank A publication
- A H-index between 25 and 30
- It was not their first attempt.

Whenever they asked for a support service, it was a private one, meaning they did not mobilize an in house support service. None of them is registered as an EU expert in the database.

2) Analysis of self-selection determinants

Some researchers have been interviewed to identify potential existing barriers and angle on mobilizing FP tools. Among 4 proposed types of causes, all of them have been selected. It means researchers acknowledged the following points:

- The lack of knowledge n the opportunities offered by FP;
- The perception of their own abilities;
- The lack of interest for FP.
- The lack of support and resources.

The pool underlined the lack of topics and research fields meeting their interest. Topics of FP calls are mainly oriented on mainland research issues. Researchers mostly tend to cooperate with Caribbean countries and USA. Interreg program is less competitive. Caribbean research community shares same topics of interest either on agronomy, natural disasters, energy issues and so on. It is the same with USA.

But, looking at some collaboration developed by Caribbean countries, one may notice that they often work with EU mainland research centers on topics addressed in Guadeloupe researcher centers. Therefore, we should investigate why.

II - Analysis of the representations

Taking into account the number of answers, the results should be looked wisely. It cannot really be considered as representative of the community view.

1) Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders (analysis of interviews; analysis of survey)

- **Analysis of survey:**

Among the 14 respondents, public researcher community is highly represented (Figure

Figure 3 : Distribution of online survey respondent

Half of them has already tried to build a FP project and has been involved in a FP-funded project (Figure 4).

Survey's : views

Heard of these programs & been part of a FP-funded project

Figure 4 : Involvement in FP projects

According to the results of the online survey, the RIS3 is well known by respondents (Figure 5).

Survey's : views

Have taken part to the elaboration of the regional innovation strategy S3

Figure 5 : Involvement in RIS3 design

The results of the online survey are quite coherent with those of the interviews. Indeed, support services and the use of ERDF as a leverage tool are recognized as the most influential factors (Figure 6).

Survey's : views

Evaluate the factors that determine the participation of the Guadeloupe in the framework programs of Research & Innovation

Figure 6 : determinant factors to mobilize FP tools

Respondents believe the research and innovation community is performing well and support services are good. But they underline the lack of tools to support their participation as well and the lack of information on FP call. Last the low interest of SME to these very competitive tools.

Knowing these results might not be really representative; one may notice the request for information and training.

Nevertheless, it is quite surprising that they underlined the attractiveness of FP scheme. (Figure 7)

Survey's : views

In terms of **performance**, how do you evaluate the **ecosystem of research and innovation in the Guadeloupe – per subject?**

Figure 7 : Guadeloupe research and innovation ecosystem performance

- **Analysis of interviews:**

Based on the results of the online survey, it appears that the main obstacles are the following ones:

- The local scientific domain is not represented in FP programs,
- The critical mass of researchers must be reached to develop excellent research,
- The lack of resources and support to access at the FP program,
- The perception of one's own abilities with a feeling of practice a non-competitive research,
- The geographic position because network is more important with the Caribbean and US countries than European countries.

In order to overcome them, respondents praised for:

- The increase of lobby activities in national and local research institutions,
- The development of a support service to help researchers to show a FP project
- The increase the One Health research to increase our international visibility
- The creation of sustainable network of researchers (with ERDF or other projects) to use as a lever for encouraging and building capacities for Horizon 2020 participation

2) Analysis of the concordance or gaps between survey results and the data

Support services to help research team, develop capacities to manage FP projects and mobilising ERDF as a leverage effect to increase FP participation appear both in the interviews and the online survey.

As well critical mass is identified as an obstacle in the both exercise.

The perception on the research and innovation community excellence capacity on the overall seems more balanced.

We may notice that respondents underlined the attractiveness of FP tools. Attractiveness is different from competitiveness. During the interview, researchers have been asked on the accessibility of FP tools.

Table of figures

Figure 1 : value chain in agriculture&agronomy	25
Figure 2 : Value chain in alternative energies and raw material.....	26
Figure 3 : Distribution of online survey respondent	30
Figure 4 : Involvement in FP projects.....	30
Figure 5 : Involvement in RIS3 design	31
Figure 6 : determinant factors to mobilize FP tools.....	31
Figure 7 : Guadeloupe research and innovation ecosystem performance.....	32

Table of graphs

Graph 1 : Success rate&Number of proposals	7
Graph 2 : Funding awarded.....	8
Graph 3 : EU awarded&Average EU per regional partner	8
Graph 4 : FP7, participation per specific program.....	9
Graph 5 : FP7, participation per funding schemes and action types.....	10
Graph 6 : H2020, participation per specific program	10
Graph 7 : H2020, participation per funding schemes and action types	11
Graph 8 : Distribution of FP7 projects per thematic priorities	13
Graph 9 : Distribution of projects under FP7 per strategic domains of the RIS3	13
Graph 10 : Distribution of H2020 projects per thematic priorities	14
Graph 11 : Distribution of projects funded under H2020 per RIS3 strategic domains...	15
Graph 12 : ERC domains representations in applications on FP7 and H2020	16
Graph 13 : Guadeloupe research landscape -Research human resources	17
Graph 14 : Type of stakeholders mobilizing FP7 and H2020	18
Graph 15 : Research centers mobilizing FP7 and H2020	18
Graph 16 : Participation profile in FP7 and H2020 projects	19
Graph 17 : Collaborations with ORs.....	20
Graph 18 : Number of participants per EU country.....	21
Graph 19 : EU countries Guadeloupe stakeholders are mostly connected with	22
Graph 20 : Number of team per research organization.....	23
Graph 21 : ERDF distribution per RIS3 strategic Domain	25

La Reunion

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems

La Reunion

Project Acronym	FORWARD
Project name	Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions
Grant agreement n°	824550
Project type	Coordination and Support action
Start date - End Date	01/01/2019 - 31/12/2021
Workpackage	WP2
Responsible partner	Nexa
Contributors	Gaston Bigey, Nexa Philippe Holstein, Nexa Fanny Mazella, Nexa Evelyne Tarnus, Nexa
Delivery date	2019/11/22

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550

We thank our colleagues from Nexa who provided support and expertise that greatly assisted the diagnosis. We thank the researchers, entrepreneurs, public officers, elected representatives for their support and cooperation during the interviews, the workshops and informal discussions. We would also like to show our gratitude to Nicholas Harrap, from the Joint Research Center of the European Union, for sharing his insights with us.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction.....	5
State of play of participation.....	7
A - A limited participation	7
B - Few stakeholders explore limitedly H2020 opportunities	11
C - A minor participation spread across a large number of fields	16
Promising under-used networks.....	24
A - Connections with European stakeholders	24
B - Regional connections	34
Regional system.....	38
A - A fast-growing, yet vulnerable region	38
B - An embryonic research and innovation system	49
C - Regional policies, the unfindable synergies ?.....	65
Regional organizations	81
A - The University of La Réunion	82
B - Other organizations.....	102
Individual's factors and representations	113
A - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level	113
B - Questioning regional representations, lessons learnt from the survey.....	119
C - Perceived barriers and levers to H2020 participation	129
Ambition & Preliminary action plan	138
A. Obstacles synthesis	138
B. Priority 1 : Increase the performance of the regional R&I system	145
C. Priority 2 : Develop a European ambition and culture within organisations.....	146
D. Priority 3 : Make FP participation desirable and achievable	147
Annexes	150

Introduction

Through its smart specialization strategy, La Réunion carries out an ambitious transformation program toward an ecological and social resilient island. This strategy relies on the adoption of a new paradigm, which embraces and valorizes regional singularities, rather than treating them as “handicaps” that ought to be corrected and dissolved. Indeed, being a remote island with exceptional yet highly vulnerable ecosystems and few resources to support a dense population, La Réunion is facing a challenge that will concern tomorrow every territory of the earth: invent an ecological economy which respects the capacities, boundaries and rhythms of the ecosystems which condition all human existence and constitute its main assets. This urge offers a unique opportunity to develop knowledge, know-how and solutions that not only reduce the current dependency and vulnerability of the island but also address the needs of other regions in Europe and elsewhere.

This strategy is also based on our ability to strengthen our research and innovation capacities and to connect to other European and international research and innovation ecosystems. In an era of globalization, marked by the concentration of means and talents in a few global hubs, peripheral territories risk to be trapped in a vicious circle, where the lack of resources hinders the emergence of a performant and attractive RDI ecosystem, which in turn inhibits the development of critical masses. To counteract this dynamic, La Réunion thus combines smart specialization with smart connections with European and worldwide partners.

In this perspective, European funds for research and innovation, both structural and competitive, represent essential levers to lead the region's ambition. And, while the challenges of the European Union may seem remote from the island realities, La Réunion is actually already dealing with topics at the heart of European policies: decarbonisation of large-scale electricity generation, conservation and ecological restoration, climate change mitigation and inclusive society in a multicultural environment... That is why, in 2014, the regional innovation agency, Nexa and the University created a European office whose goal is to connect Réunionnais research groups and innovation stakeholders to European centers of excellence in strategic areas. Funded by the Structural Funds, the State and the Regional Council, the European office gives support to the setting up of projects responding to calls of proposals launched by the European Union, using when relevant synergy between funds schemes. However, despite a positive dynamic during the last five years, our participation in Horizon 2020 remains weak : 14 participations for 1.88 millions euros.

If some consider the “structural characteristics” of La Réunion - insularity, geographic remoteness, small ecosystem, etc. – a natural explanation, the factors that inhibit the participation have so far not been reviewed by a proper, evidence-based analysis. Prior to the Forward project, the question of the participation of La Réunion and more globally Outermost Regions in the Framework Programmes for Research remained a blind spot.

The diagnosis conducted through the Forward project, was therefore a unique opportunity to characterize the participation, complete a thorough investigation on the determinants and factors and to question collective perceptions and determinist rhetoric.

According to the methodology guidelines developed by Nexa as WP2 leader¹, a holistic analysis of the situation of La Reunion was performed between April and November 2019. This study relies on an extensive literature review on FP participation, the mapping and analysis of all FP projects involving stakeholders from La Réunion as well as the regional innovation system, the collection and analysis of data provided by European database (Cordis / H2020 dashboard, Eurostat, ETER, Scimago Ranking), the organization of 27 face to face interviews with regional stakeholders, an online survey (59 respondents) and 2 collective workshops.

The main results are presented in this report through

- *the state of play of the participation* : this section describes the evolution of the participation of La Reunion between FP7 and H2020, draws a comparison with EU NUTS 2 and French regions, analyzes the types of stakeholders applying to FP calls, the mobilized instruments, the scientific thematics and the roles played in FP projects by local partners ;

- *an analysis of networks* : this part analyses the existing relationships between La Réunion and the European stakeholders, the intensity and the quality of such connections and also questions the well-established rhetoric which depicts La Réunion as a “European Innovation Hub/Platform” in the Indian Ocean, through the evaluation of collaboration with third-countries from an H2020 perspective.

- *a "dissection" of the regional system* : in this chapter, the impact of demographic, socio-economic and higher education-research-innovation factors on the participation is examined, independently as well as in a cumulative way, through a benchmark analysis with regions sharing similar characteristics ; the effect of R&I public policies, in terms of thematic concentration, organization of the entrepreneurial discovery process, and ERDF/FP synergy is also analyzed;

- *an analysis of the regional organizations* : this section evaluates the impact of the resources and strategies of institutions on FP participation with a strong emphasis on the higher education and research institutions which constitute a large share of FP participation.

- *an investigation at individual's scale*, taking advantages of the small size of our regional system : first, individual's determinants are evaluated through interviews questioning the patterns of success and failure as well as self-selection behavior ; second, perception, beliefs and fears are scrutinized through an online survey ; finally, main obstacles and levers according to stakeholders are mapped and organized to draft orientations responding to user's needs;

In a final section, a territorial strategic plan to increase regional participation to FP programs is presented. This plan has been drafted on the basis of the factual and symbolic diagnosis displayed as "problem trees" and embraces three priorities, nine strategic objectives and 31 priority actions.

¹ Under WP2, Nexa was in charge of developing a specific methodology for all ORs to map and analyze their performance and compare themselves to other OR and EU regions. The guidelines are detailed in the deliverable 2.2 of the project, available on the forward website.

State of play of participation

One word sums up the involvement of La Réunion in the European framework programmes for research and innovation: limited. A limited and highly concentrated number of stakeholders involved; a limited list of projects submitted and accepted; a limited spectrum of instruments mobilized; a limited participation in the funded projects. All of which result in a very limited EU contribution, which makes the island one of the least active FP region of the Union.

A - A limited participation

Between 2007 and 2018, La Réunion has been implicated in 9 FP7 and 13 H2020 projects. In terms of EU contribution, such participation represented respectively 3,63 and 1,88 M€. The marked drop between the two periods reflects a major shift in the way the island is implicated in FP which will be analyzed in infra.

1) Compared to other NUTS2 regions:

With 1,879 million euros, La Réunion occupies the 253th place on 274 NUTS 2 regions, in terms of H2020 contribution¹. Such record represents 75% less than the average regional participation which amounts to 139,6 M€. Even among the 10% least beneficiary regions, the island performs far below the decile limit (3,5 M€).

¹ The comparison is based on the data on NUTS3 regions uploaded on the H2020 “country profile” dashboard on July 16th 2019, aggregated by Nexa at a Nuts 2 level.

Table 1. Distribution of H2020 contribution to NUTS2 regions

Decile	Net EU Contribution (€)
D1	3 580 605
D2	10 331 325
D3	16 866 679
D4	26 679 549
D5	43 690 458
D6	68 577 169
D7	107 084 694
D8	185 062 479
D9	364 477 049
La Réunion	1 879 192

To neutralize the demographic heterogeneity of NUTS 2 regions (from 800 000 to 3 million inhabitants) which may induce a size-effect, the comparison can be improved by estimating the level of EU contribution per inhabitant, per year.¹ With 0,44 euro per year, La Réunion would then rank 258 on 274 European regions, still on the first decile :

Table 2. Distribution of H2020 contribution to NUTS 2 region per inhabitant, per year

Decile	Net EU Contribution per inhabitant per year (€)
D1	0,75
D2	1,51
D3	2,85
D4	4,49
D5	6,17
D6	8,80
D7	13,33
D8	19,63
D9	34,61
La Réunion	0,44

The 16 regions that participate less comprise 3 French outermost regions (Guyane Martinique and Mayotte), the autonomous cities of Ceuta and Melilla, the Finish island province of Åland and 10 lagging behind regions from Bulgary, Poland and Romania, located on the map below :

¹ Pontikakis et al. *Mobilising European Structural Funds and Investment Funds and Horizon 2020 in support of innovation in less developed regions*

2) Compared to NUT3 regions

Considering its mono-departmental status, La Réunion is both categorized as a NUT2 and NUT3 region. Even compared to the latter which generally present a much smaller size and population (average 380 000), its participation remains limited. On average these regions have been part of 83 H2020 projects between 2014 and 2018, for a total EU amount of 32,9 M€, representing 10 € per inhabitant, per year. Though La Réunion is close to the median in terms of FP participation, the minor role played in projects combined to its relatively large population negatively impact the EU contribution per inhabitant :

Decile	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2	Net EU Contribution	Participations	Population NUTS3
D1	0,00	171 125	2	92 257
D2	0,21	567 797	3	127 053
D3	0,67	1 157 492	5	163 642
D4	1,24	1 948 777	8	211 649
D5	2,02	3 212 048	13	264 738
D6	3,18	5 569 827	20	324 500
D7	5,25	10 328 000	34	410 072
D8	9,64	22 395 944	70	544 482
D9	23,65	63 118 542	177	722 716
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192	14	852 924
La Réunion ranking	988	731	561	98

The analysis of the distribution confirms the strong concentration of Horizon 2020 beneficiaries in a limited number of highly competitive regional poles: 100 regions capturing 75% of the 39 billion euros awarded by the EU Commission since 2014. At the opposite end of the spectrum, 151 regions have played no role in Horizon 2020, and 349 obtained less than La Réunion.

Net EU/hab.

3) Compared to France

The analysis of the 101 French departments corroborates the critical concentration of Horizon 2020 participation : 10 departments accounts for more than 80% of the 4,9 billion euros awarded to French partners. La Réunion is thus way beyond the average French participation (115 projects representing a total of 50,6 M€). Yet, such situation is not exceptional : 40 departments are less involved, be it in number of participations or EU contribution. The singularity of the island stems once again from its large population which shrinks the contribution received by inhabitant.

Decile	Net EU Contribution per inhabitant per year (€)	Net EU Contribution	Participations	Population
D1	0,16	311 108	3	177 855
D2	0,42	925 478	4	256 700
D3	0,69	1 412 939	6	332 583
D4	1,04	1 858 960	9	386 489
D5	1,43	3 689 995	15	532 874
D6	2,09	5 635 931	22	606 076
D7	3,57	10 748 380	38	746 643
D8	5,73	27 247 666	83	1 055 071
D9	12,33	74 218 987	212	1 379 971
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192	14	852 924
La Réunion ranking	80	60	49	25

B - Few stakeholders explore limitedly H2020 opportunities

This participation appears as a consequence of the reduced interest paid to FP by regional stakeholders, who do not exploit the variety of instruments proposed.

1) A highly concentrated participation

Formally, La Réunion presents a high success rate: 37,5% on FP7 and 28% on H2020, much higher than the European average of 11%. Such performance can be explained by the restricted number of proposals submitted : 24 between 2007 and 2013, and 50 since 2014. Despite a notable growth, few organizations dedicate time and resources to this activity : 7 on FP7; 13 on H2020.

Such concentration contrasts with the relatively large number of organizations that compose the regional innovation system, described in infra, and may be linked to the minor importance attached to FP in their respective strategies. Only 2 institutions – the University of La Réunion (UR) and the Regional Council – have been continuously submitting proposals on the two periods. UR itself accounts for 62% of the FP7 and 52% of H2020 proposals. This relative contraction has been compensated by the involvement of 2 stakeholders with 5 proposals each (Nexa & Reuniwatt). Together, these 4 organizations submit 75% of proposals.

The number of organizations which actually access FP is particularly restricted: 5 during FP7 and 5 during H2020; the Regional Council and UR being the only continuous beneficiaries. The latter stands out as the number 1 beneficiary with 55% of the participations during FP7 and 57% during H2020.

From a financial point of view, the concentration appears even more clearly. UR absorbs more than 64% of the EU contribution flowing to the island. Combined to the “Institut de Recherche pour le Développement” (IRD) and to the regional agency for development and innovation (Nexa), this proportion reaches 90% of the funds awarded between 2007 and 2020. In the case of Nexa, the contribution is largely inflated by its important role in the present Forward project.

As a consequence, La Réunion presents a peculiar profile in terms of stakeholders involved compared to European standards; notably a 1,5 time larger share occupied by higher education establishments. Interestingly, research centers which used to account for a fourth of the contribution under FP7 (through IRD), no longer participate; illustrating the high dependency on a limited number of stakeholders. Though the share of private companies seems close to the rest of the Union (29% vs. 25%), the figures do not really reflect the mobilization of local businesses. Indeed 90% of the funds were granted to Nexa, a semi-public company, directly controlled and funded by the Regional Council. Tagging Nexa as Other (like the urbanism agency, Agorah) would thus bring the share of private company to 2,7%, 10 times less than in Europe.

2) A limited use of available instruments

The few organizations that access the framework programmes mobilize only a portion of the funding schemes proposed. Since 2007, no individual grant dedicated to excellence science, through the European Research Council or the Marie Skłodowska-Curie programme has been obtained. The instruments dedicated to SME's also remain largely under-used: no “research for the benefits of SMEs” on FP7 and only one SME instrument on H2020.

During FP7, participation has been restricted to capacities and cooperation pillars, without any project on Ideas or People. A strong emphasis was laid on structuring regional research efforts through capacity-building and networking instruments :

3 projects mobilized coordination and support actions (including 2 Regpots : RUNEMERGE and RUNSEASCIENCE°

2 CP-CSA designed to optimize research infrastructures usages.

The 4 remaining were classic collaborative projects (CP), focused on research activities. La Réunion did not contribute to any “network of excellence” or “joint technology initiative”. Compared to the rest of the Union, La Réunion logically shows an over-concentration on the 3 mobilized instruments.

During H2020, La Réunion developed projects on 4 of the 5 pillars, at the notable exception of “Spreading Excellence and Widening Participation”, French outermost regions being excluded from this critical program to build critical masses. On the 13 projects which included local partners, 7 contributed to “societal challenge”, 4 to “excellence science”, one on “science with and for society” and one “industrial leadership”. The analysis of funding schemes confirms the importance of research and innovation actions and coordination and support actions. The projects developed under the societal challenge pillar are for the most part dedicated to low TRL initiatives.

C - A minor participation spread across a large number of fields

The lack of involvement of regional stakeholders contrasts with the extensive number of scientific domains explored: the 22 projects are scattered across 9 scientific domains. Such fragmentation contributes to, and is influenced by, the difficulty to be identified as valuable partners in a specific field of excellence, leading to minor participations in the projects developed.

1) A highly fragmented participation

Since 2007, La Réunion has been involved in varied scientific fields, each represented by a limited number of projects. With 4 projects, the more active domains are earth system science and social sciences (“institutions, values, environment and space”, according to the 2019 ERC evaluation panel). They are followed by 3 themes with 3 projects each : ecology, evolution and environmental biology; applied life sciences; and immunity and infection. Energy transition represented by “Systems and communication engineering” accounts for 2 projects. Three other themes participated once : computer sciences, scientific education (“the social world, diversity, population”) and applied medical technologies.

The detailed review of the projects (excl. Forward) and the analysis by fields of interest rather than scientific domains temper this fragmentation impression. One major pole concentrates 7 projects : the observation and conservation of the unique island ecosystems, through adapted policies and the ecological transformation of economic activities :

Acronym	Title	Objectives	Regional partner	Programme
BIODIVERSA 3	Consolidating the European Research area on biodiversity and ecosystem services	Network of 32 funding agencies to coordinate research support effort on biodiversity and implement co-funded calls for project.	Région Réunion	H2020
ENVRI PLUS	Environmental research infrastructures providing shared solutions for science	Cluster of research infrastructure for environment observation	OSU-R – University of La Réunion	H2020
NETBIOME	Strengthening European research cooperation for	Cooperation between regional stakeholders and mobilization of research effort to address	Région Réunion	FP7

	smart and sustainable management of tropical and subtropical biodiversity in outermost regions and overseas countries and territories	biodiversity policy needs.		
RUN SEA SCIENCE	Improvement of the Tropical Sea Sciences Research Potential in Western Indian Ocean, and of the Technology Capacities in La Reunion Island	Regpot project dedicated to the construction of a regional critical mass in the observation and protection of marine environment.	IRD	FP7
SCREEN	Synergic Circular Economy across European Regions)	Reinforcing the synergies between RIS3, Structural funds and Horizon 2020 to accelerate the regional transition toward circular economy models.	Nexa – Regional agency for development and innovation	H2020
URBAN-WASTE	Urban strategies for waste management of tourist cities	Reduce the production and improve the valorization of waste induced by tourism activities.	Agorah (urbanism agency)	H2020
VIBRANT	Virtual biodiversity research and access network for taxonomy	Digital solution to support the development and network of biodiversity research communities	University of La Réunion	FP7

The sustainable economic use of regional biodiversity, notably through biotechnologies, completes the “ecological economy” value-chain that constitutes the core of La Réunion smart specialization strategy.

Acronym	Title	Objectives	Regional partner	Programme
ECSAFESEAFOOD	Priority environmental contaminants in seafood	Identification and monitoring of the risks induced by the presence of biotoxins in sea food.	Arvam	FP7
DEMA	Direct Ethanol	Biofuel production	Ercane	FP7

	from Microalgae	project based on the engineering of cyanobacteria.		
MADE	Mitigating Adverse Ecological impacts of open ocean fisheries	Reduction of by-catch of sea-birds, turtles and sharks induced by tuna fishing	University of La Réunion	FP7
TASCMAR	Tools and strategies to access to original bioactive compounds from cultivation of marine invertebrates and associated symbionts	Production and extraction of bioactive ingredients for pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals and cosmeceuticals industries.	University of La Réunion	H2020

The third pole, in terms of participation and EU contribution focuses on health issues, with a net predominance of infectious diseases and transmission mechanisms, through a “One Health” approach, which reflects the island exposition to such emerging pathologies :

Acronym	Title	Objectives	Regional partner	Programme
ICRES	Integration of Chikungunya research)	Coordinating European research efforts on the mechanisms, impacts, diagnosis and potential treatments of the disease.	University of La Réunion	FP7
RUN EMERGE	Supporting the research potential on emerging infectious diseases in La Réunion Island, an EU outermost region in the South-Western Indian Ocean	Regpot project designed to develop a regional inter-disciplinary research capacity on emerging diseases.	University of La Réunion	FP7
ZIKALLIANCE	A global alliance for Zika virus control and prevention	Global network of clinical and basic research institutions working on the comprehension and management of epidemic threats.	University of La Réunion	H2020
EUROLINKCAT	Establishing a linked European	European network to optimize diagnosis, prevention and treatment of	Centre hospitalier universitaire	H2020

	Cohort of Children with Congenital Anomalies	these pathologies.	de La Réunion	
--	--	--------------------	---------------	--

Contrary to the three previous fields, the fourth pole relies on a single structure : the “OSU-R”, a joint Earth system observatory operated by the CNRS and UR. It encompasses the observation of atmospheric processes and their potential impact on air quality and climate change through:

Acronym	Title	Objectives	Regional partner	Programme
ACTRIS	Aerosols, Clouds, and trace gases research infrastructure network	Coordinating European effort through a network of ground-based stations that use the same observation protocols and share data.	OSU-R – University of La Réunion	FP7
ACTRIS 2	Aerosols, Clouds, and trace gases research infrastructure network	Coordinating European effort through a network of ground-based stations that use the same observation protocols and share data.	OSU-R – University of La Réunion	H2020
ARISE 2	Atmospheric dynamics research infrastructure in Europe	Observation and modelling of the middle atmosphere to improve weather forecasting through a European network.	OSU-R – University of La Réunion	H2020

In line with regional challenges and strong research-innovation capacities, a fifth pole has emerged under H2020 : energy transition in island context. Such field is characterized by a strong innovation orientation, with the only SME instrument and one innovation-action project :

Acronym	Title	Objectives	Regional partner	Programme
E-space monitoring	e-solar performance analysis and data collection for energy monitoring	Assessment of photovoltaic installation performance through the measurement of solar irradiance.	REUNIWATT	H2020
REACT	Renewable Energy for self-sustainable island communities	Increasing island energy system resilience through production and	LE2P – University of La Réunion	H2020

		consumption modelling, supply optimization and synergies between micro-grids.		
--	--	---	--	--

The emergence of new research and innovation fields is accompanied by a significant difficulty to capitalize on previous initiatives to develop more FP projects. Such phenomenon appears clearly at the scientific domain scale : 4 themes present under FP7 have disappeared from H2020, including marine biology and ecology, funded by the “Research potential programme” (REGPOT) – RUNSEASCIENCE whose precise objective was to “unlock and develop existing or emerging excellence in the EU’s convergence regions and outermost regions” to “become more active players in the European Research Area”¹. The other REGPOT beneficiary – Immunity and infection – has seen its participation shrunk from 2,1 M€ to 110 000 €.

Excluding the two REGPOT and Forward, no theme has been mobilizing more than 600 000 euros between 2007 and 2019.

¹ European Commission. *Final evaluation of FP7 research potential programme*. 2014

2) La Réunion plays a minor roles in the projects

The limited amount of EU contribution obtained reflects the role played by La Réunion in the funded projects. Excluding the 2 Regpot and the SME instrument, no stakeholders did assume the role of coordinator and only 3 acted as a work package leader (on MADE, ICRES and Forward). On average, the stakeholders from the island obtained 3,2% and 1,8% of the budget awarded to the projects they were involved respectively in FP7 and H2020 (excl. Forward & the 2 Regpot). This global situation masks a large heterogeneity among the themes:

According to the funding intensity, 3 types of participation scenario can be elaborated.

- 1) Less than 2% of the budget clearly indicates that La Réunion is considered an “add-on” to a preexisting proposition, which it will enrich through some minor contribution (one more observation site; outermost regions status, etc.). Local partners are generally invited followers, who joined the consortium at a late stage and who concentrate on producing data or providing an observation site for the project activities, designed by other. Such is particularly the case for 3 earth system projects (ACTRIS, ACTRIS2 and ENVRI PLUS) for which the OSUR was only integrated as third party of the CNRS; as well ECSAFE, EUROLINKCAT, SEA FOOD, SCREEN, URBAN-WASTE, VIBRANT.
- 2) The projects that dedicate 2 to 5% of their budget to partners from La Réunion perceive a strong added-value of the island, provided by its specific natural conditions and the quality of the research activities, for the very objectives of the project. For instance, in ARISE 2, DEMA or REACT.
- 3) More than 5% attests from the significative role played by regional partners in the development of the proposal at an early stage, capitalizing on pre-existing networks: TASCMAR, ICRES, MADE.

Combined to the EU contribution expressed in absolute number, this intensity criteria illustrate a global shift from FP7 and H2020, toward the multiplication of minor collaborations and projects.

Promising under-used networks

To better understand such low level of participation, investigating the international connections constitute one major clue. Indeed, being part of powerful, existing networks remains a precondition to participate in the Framework Programmes. Because of their collaborative and competitive nature, the latter are indeed characterized by a strong concentration, materialized by the extensive domination of a few stakeholders, who benefits from the cumulative advantages induced by prior participation¹. Some authors underline the existence of “persistent oligarchic networks that would appear to constitute clubs, closed to those less fortunate”. Meanwhile, newcomers to European research, seeking funding without well-developed networks and with no prior experience, are likely to fail” (Enger 2017). Besides this direct relation, global connections, especially through the integration in the European Research Area, play a key role in the transition toward knowledge economy. For a remote island, such relations offer the opportunity to reinforce the regional capacities to produce, absorb and transform knowledge into innovative solutions, as well as to reach the lacking critical masses, which in turn will influence its participation in Framework Programmes.

Analysing the existing relationships between La Réunion and the European stakeholders, the intensity and the quality of such connections, thus constitutes a major opportunity to understand the obstacles and the potential levers to increase the participation (A). Network analysis also offer the opportunity to question the well-established rhetoric which depicts La Réunion as a “European Innovation Hub/Platform” in the Indian Ocean (B)

A - Connections with European stakeholders

Thanks to CORDIS and the grant agreements scrutinized, a list of all partners involved in the 9 FP7 and 13 H2020 projects that include La Réunion, was established; constituting a total sample of 113 organizations in FP7 and 274 in H2020.

1) Partners' profile

Compared to the global structure of Horizon 2020, these partners present a peculiar profile, which corresponds to the singularities of the projects that implicate La Réunion, described in supra. If the share of research organizations is close to the European standard (28,5% vs. 32%), two categories appear under-represented : higher education establishments (30 vs. 39%) and more critically, private for profit (12 vs. 25,5%). On the other and, public institutions are over-represented with 21% vs. 3,3%, a consequence of the lion share detained by coordination and support actions or Era-Net cofund. The progression is particularly notable between FP7 and H2020 (from 8 to 21%).

¹ Lepori et al. 2015

Strong differences can be deciphered between scientific domains. Two are highly dominated by public organizations:

- “institutions, values, environment and space”, which brings together stakeholders involved in the design, implementation and coordination of public policies, in fields like circular economy
- “ecology, evolution, and environmental biology”, due to the very nature of the only project represented - the Era-Net, Biodiversa 3, composed of public authorities / funding agencies.

At the opposite end of the spectrum, two themes presenting an advanced TRL and proximity to the market, mostly mobilize private institutions: “applied life-sciences and biotechnology” (represented by TASCMAR, a research and innovation action project) and “systems and communication engineering”, focusing on energy transition (REACT project).

The two most FP active themes – Earth System Science and Immunity and infection – are research oriented and thus mobilize higher education and research organizations.

2) La Réunion mostly collaborates with minor FP players

The analysis of the “quality” of these partners, measured by the number of FP participations, lays emphasis on the lack of exploitation of the existing relations, especially connections to “locomotives”, which could integrate La Réunion in many new projects. Indeed, under FP7 and H2020, respectively 25 and 38 partners were involved in at least 100 projects, representing 22 22% and 14% of the total number of partners.

Such stakeholders includes French institutions like the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, (CNRS) or the Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale (INSERM) that are directly connected to La Réunion through joint research units or platforms (like the OSU-R dedicated to earth system science; or the CYROI for medical sciences), and indirect partners like the Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique et aux Energies alternatives or the “Institut National de Recherche Agronomique” (INRA).

Yet national connections are not predominant; for they only represent 4 of these 38 partners, based in 14 countries.

Countries	Nb of +100 projects partners
Austria	1
Belgium	2
Denmark	3

Finland	3
France	4
Germany	4
Ireland	1
Israel	1
Italy	1
Netherlands	3
Norway	2
Spain	2
Sweden	4
United Kingdom	7

Though the proportion of top organizations appear substantial, 78% of the projects mobilize partners with less than 50 participation; 35% with less than 10.

Based on these data, institutions have been positioned on a “H2020 ranking” determined by the number of participations of the 30 472 active organizations. They occupy a modest, average 3 303 rank. Once again, these results vary greatly from one field to another. The two most FP active domains are also the ones which enjoy the highest connections to top players, which confirms the analysis developed by Enger & al. Indeed, Earth System Science and Immunity and infection have implicated respectively 19 and 10 organizations part of the top 100 H2020 participants. On the contrary, the themes represented by projects developed through political networks mobilize very few top 10 or top 50 institutions; especially in social sciences:

Domains	TOP 10	Top 15	TOP 20	TOP 50	TOP 100
Earth system sciences	5	7	8	15	19
Immunity and infection	4	4	5	6	10
Applied medical technologies	1	1	1	2	4
Systems and communication engineering	1	1	1	1	4
Institutions, values, environment and space	1	2	2	3	3
Ecology, evolution and environmental biology	0	1	1	1	1
Applied life sciences	1	1	1	1	1
The social world, diversity, population	0	0	0	0	0

Such phenomenon is logically reflected by the number of projects or the ranking.

3) Connections remain largely unexploited

During FP7 and H2020, one time collaborations concerned respectively 105 of the 113 and 245 of the 274 partners involved. In other words, 93,5% and 89,4% of the organizations developed only one project with stakeholders from La Réunion. This confirms the difficulty to capitalize on preexisting relations or projects highlighted in the analysis of the participation. However, though they represent only a minor share, recurrent partnerships have slightly progressed between the 2 periods from 2 common projects to 5.

Number of common projects	Number		Proportion	
	FP7	H2020	%FP7	%H2020
5	0	1	0,00	0,36
4	0	1	0,00	0,36
3	0	4	0,00	1,46
2	7	23	6,48	8,39
1	101	245	93,52	89,42
Total	108	274	100	100

Such recurrent partners represented 14 of the 115 interactions under FP7 (i.e. the total number of collaborations) and 67 of the 312 interactions under H2020. This indicates that the

participation remains scattered across a large number of stakeholders and not concentrated on a few stakeholders.

4) Determining entry points

Regular interactions offer powerful clues to identify the existing networks leading to FP participation. Such networks constitute major entry points in the programmes; confirmed during the 9 face to face interviews conducted with successful candidates, who were notably asked how they entered the consortium. On the 22 projects (minus 1 mono-beneficiary SME instrument), 3 types of networks play a critical role.

The first network, mentioned earlier, stems from the historic, strong connections with mainland France research institutions, which played an active role in at least 8 projects. 4 of these 8 projects were developed through the integration of OSUR in the national earth system observatories network, coordinated by the “National Institute for Universe Sciences” (INSU) managed by the CNRS. 3 other projects were initiated or facilitated by the regional representation of the “Institut de Recherche pour le Développement” (IRD), active in La Réunion directly and through joint research units with the University of La Réunion. Such projects include the two Regpot (Run Emerge & Run Sea Science), and Made, dedicated to the ecological impact of fisheries, which also benefited from the regional presence of the IFREMER. The last project (Stories) has been designed by the French conference of universities to adapt the European Researchers’ Night concept. The University of La Réunion was invited to replace a defaulting partner, after the submission of the project.

The second largest network in terms of projects (7) is composed of the agglomeration of several individual networks. These people capitalized on prior collaboration, through common research projects or professional networks, and their reputation to join successful consortia. Most of them were invited to join this team because of their expertise and the singular aspects that La Réunion may bring to the projects, as experiment sites or primary resources provider. This is notably the case of three biotechnology projects (DEMA; ECSAFESEAFOD; TASCAR), three medical projects (EUROLINKCAT, ICRES, Zikalliance), and one computer science project focusing on the creation of a digital network for biodiversity research (VIBRANT).

The third network is composed of the outermost regions, which accounts for 4 of the 21 projects. 3 of the 4 are direct result from preexisting relations between regions : NetBiome CSA and its follow-up Biodiversa3 dedicated to the coordination of public support and research effort to preserve biodiversity; and Forward. The last project, Urban Waste relies on a broader network than the single OR, but is coordinated by the government of the Canary Islands, who invited to the projects representatives of La Réunion, i.e. the regional urbanism agency. Including two other projects, which implicated other partners from the OR but not centered on their challenges (ARISE2 and SCREEN) and excluding Forward, La Réunion has been collaborating 15 times with other partners from the OR. This figure appears relatively limited compared to the total 382 interactions with European institutions registered between FP7 and H2020. The absence of cooperation in common research fields such as blue economy, emerging diseases, energy transition in island context, marine biotechnologies,

highlights the potential for increased connections. On these 15 interactions, the Canary and the Azores constitute the two major partners, with respectively 6 and 5 participations, way beyond Guadeloupe (2) and Guyane (1). Expressed by partners, FRCT constitute the number 1 institution (2 common projects excluding Forward),

A fourth kind of network has emerged between FP7 and H2020 as a consequence of the European office created by Nexa and the University to support access to H2020. One of the main activities of this office, described in the next section, is to increase the connection to European stakeholders, notably through the promotion of the island’s expertise to consortium leaders. Thanks to the office own networks, La Réunion has been part of 2 projects: SCREEN, dedicated to the transition toward circular economy and REACT on energy transition.

5) A strong national orientation

Under FP7 and H2020, La Réunion has been collaborating with stakeholders based in 51 countries.

This participation is highly concentrated : 5 countries accounted for 52,7% of the FP7 and 50,7% of the H2020 participation.

Countries	% FP7 partnerships	Countries	% H2020 partnerships
France	15,18	France	17,50
Germany	9,82	Spain	10,36
Netherlands	9,82	Germany	7,86
Spain	8,93	United Kingdom	7,86
United Kingdom	8,93	Italy	7,14
Portugal	7,14	Netherland	4,29
Italy	5,36	Portugal	3,93

At one exception (Finland), these countries also host the top H2020 institutions with whom La Réunion has been collaborating more than once.

In this podium, mainland France still constitutes the number one source of partners. At one exception (REACT), La Réunion has never been part of a project that does not include a French partner. Such proximity can be as the consequence of three intertwined factors : a historic integration/dependence to national research centers (the University of La Réunion used to be an extension of Aix-Marseille Academy), the preexisting professional networks of researchers who, for the most part, originate from or were trained in mainland France, as well as the comfort offered by a same language.

B - Regional connections

In its 2008 Communication¹, the European Commission called for a paradigm shift that would “make the most of the characteristics of the OR” and turn them in “outposts of the European Union in the world”. At that time, Outermost Regions were described as the “vanguard of the EU’s position vis à vis other major economic blocs”, that would fully “participate in the development of a true wider neighbourhood policy through their geographical, cultural and historical links with other countries and peoples, particularly in Africa and the Americas” and become “platforms for the dissemination of technologies and veritable scientific portals in their respective environments”. Such ambition was recalled 10 years later, in the 2017 Communication, which insisted on the necessity to “strengthen cooperation initiatives” and “facilitate exchanges and joint projects, between the outermost regions, their neighbouring countries and territories, and regional organisations”².

Analyzing the participation of La Réunion neighbouring countries in the Framework Programmes offers an unique opportunity to question the factuality of such ambition, which constitutes the core of European declarations but also of a well-established local rhetoric that depicts the island as a “knowledge hub” or “expertise center” exporting training, research and innovation to the Indian Ocean.

1) Neighbouring countries are familiar with Horizon 2020...

According to the data provided by CORDIS and the Horizon 2020 dashboard, neighbouring countries present a mixed profile in terms of FP participation. The first cooperation circle, composed of Mauritius, Madagascar, the Seychelles and Comoros present a very limited implication. The second circle composed of Eastern African countries appear more dynamic and led by two major players : Kenya (50) projects, and South Africa (139).

Countries	Signed grants	Participations	EU contribution
Comoros	0	0	0
Kenya	50	70	€ 13 580 258
Madagascar	5	8	€ 952 420
Malawi	9	11	€ 2 301 431
Mauritius	2	2	€ 24 750
Mozambique	9	1	€ 1 010 658
Seychelles	1	1	€ 79 500
South Africa	139	201	€ 31 568 969
Tanzania	20	25	€ 7 320 821
Zambia	5	5	€ 1 442 452
Zimbabwe	0	0	€ 0
Total	240	324	58 281 260

¹ European Commission. *The outermost regions: an asset for Europe*. 2008

² European Commission. *A stronger and renewed strategic partnership with the EU's outermost regions*. 2017

They represent a total of 240 projects and a net EU contribution of 58,2 M€. Such participation highlights once again the abnormal situation of La Réunion, which despite its natural connections with Europe and strong R&I effort, presents scores close to countries like Mozambique (9 projects for 1,1 M€), Madagascar (5 projects, 952 420 €), Malawi (9 projects; 2,3 M€) and Zambia (5 project, 1,4 M€).

The fields of interest of the projects developed present strong connections with the domains of excellence of La Réunion : climate action, environment and resources; food security and sustainable agriculture; health and demographic change.

2) ... but seldom cooperate with La Réunion...

Despite their active participation, very few projects include both La Réunion and one neighbouring country : 1 under FP7 with Seychelles (Made) and 1 under H2020 with Madagascar (ARISE 2). These joint projects account for 0,28 and 0,19% of the budget obtained by these countries during the two periods.

	FP7	H2020
Total EU Contribution	67 870 862 €	58 281 260 €
Joint projects	187 050 €	110 000 €
%	0,28	0,19

Such limited collaboration appear all the more surprising, that many projects involving these partners are in direct line with the island fields of expertise. For instance, the Seychelles

are part of Farfish, a research and innovation action, dedicated to the “management of EU Fisheries outside Europe”; South Africa of TROPICSAFE, which focuses on the prevention of “insert-borne prokaryote associated diseases in tropical and subtropical perennial crops” (such as citrus) and implicates stakeholders based in La Réunion, like the CIRAD. Kenya for its part is implicated in many food safety and one-health projects like LEAP-AGRI (“A long term EU Africa research and innovation partnership on food and nutrition security and sustainable agriculture”), PALE-Blu (“Understanding pathogen, livestock, environment interactions involving bluetongue virus”), or B3Africa (“Bridging Biobanking and biomedical research across Europe and Africa”). It is also a full partner of a project dedicated to ecosystems monitoring through Earth Observations (EcoPotential), which was joined by La Réunion with the help of ERDF, after the project submission...

All the more, these common fields of interest are often the subject of joint research programmes supported by INTERREG. Between the 2007 and 2013, and 2014-2018, respectively 22,8 M€ and 15 M€ were mobilized to support research and innovation programmes with countries like Mauritius, Madagascar, Seychelles, South Africa (not under the last period). Yet, such investments were not transformed in FP projects, which represent less than 1% of the amount mobilized.

	2007-2013	2014-2020
INTERREG	22 756 833 €	15 045 510 €
FP	187 050 €	110 000 €
%	0,82	0,73

The very limited synergy between INTERREG and Horizon 2020 as well as low level of cooperation in competitive projects clearly indicates that for now La Réunion is not identified or considered by its neighbors as an expertise center or a valuable partner which could contribute to their research effort or increase their chance to access H2020. This diagnosis questions the whole scientific cooperation strategy implemented on the island since the last 20 years, which considers regional cooperation as a first step to develop the island innovation system and increase its international position.

3) ... contrary to national organizations

Indeed, such partners prefer to orient themselves directly toward national organizations, who despite their proclaimed commitments to make La Réunion their regional hub, develop strong connections and projects, which do not include the island. According to the H2020 dashboard, France is number one partner for Madagascar with 11 common participations (and only 1 with La Réunion), and the number 3 partner for South Africa (185 common participations, none with La Réunion).

More, national organizations do not have the reflex to include partners from La Réunion in the consortia they coordinate. In Mauritius, the Institute for Research on Development (IRD) coordinated a Marie Slodowska-Curie staff-exchange project on “Slavery in Africa : a dialogue between Europe and Africa”, whose objective is to “establish a top level

scientific network of institution from Europe and Africa on the field of slavery studies”, that include several organizations from mainland France, Kenya, and South Africa. The National Agency for Research (ANR), leads with the help of 3 institutions based in La Réunion (IRD; the French Agency for Development - AFD, and the CIRAD, whose 2nd largest implantation is La Réunion), a 33M€ ERA-NET dedicated to a “Europe-Africa flagship initiative for Food and Nutrition Security and Sustainable Agriculture” : LEAP Agri. In Madagascar, the National Institute for Agronomic Research (INRA) and its counterpart for tropical regions (CIRAD) are leading a project on soil carbon sequestration in agriculture.

Such examples reveal the long way ahead to integrate La Réunion in the regional and european networks and to turn them into effective FP projects, through the common mobilization and effort of all stakeholders – national and regional authorities and funding agencies, national research organizations and their regional representations, regional research and innovation organizations – to turn La Réunion into a real European Hub in the indian Ocean. To that end, one priority to consolidate and develop a research and innovation system, which despite the great efforts engaged in the last years remains at this stage, one of the bottleneck of an increased participation in the future Horizon Europe.

Regional system

La Réunion's limited participation in the European Framework Programmes and fruitful connections to major players are both a symptom and a cause of the weak performance of its regional innovation system, itself embedded in a dynamic, yet vulnerable development model, which makes the island of the poorest and most transfers-dependent region of the Union. To address the major economic, social and ecological challenges and organize the transition toward a more resilient model, La Réunion is engaged in an ambitious smart specialization strategy, based on a conviction : the very sources of vulnerability offer opportunities to design innovative solutions that may be exported to other islands or tropical regions, and provide new niches of values and jobs. To build these new competitive advantages and reach the required critical masses, a strong focus has been set on integrating La Réunion in the major European and global networks, notably through an increased participation to Horizon 2020. Though important means were mobilized since 2015 to support the production and transformation of new knowledge into solutions, the participation in FP has paradoxically been divided by more than 2. Such paradox may find its source in the marked disconnection between the ambition proclaimed by public policies and the modes of allocation of ERDF funds, which have comforted and extended to the realm of research and innovation the rent-seeking behavior inherent to its economic model.

A - A fast-growing, yet vulnerable region

Like the other French outermost regions, La Réunion presents a very peculiar economic model, shaped by the “departementalization” process, engaged in 1946. After three centuries of colonization, several decades of structural crisis and 4 years of British blockade, the institutionalized plantation system which fashioned the island's population, economy, social practices and landscapes, faced a dead-end. The ruined colony held the world record of infant mortality (14,5%) and life expectancy barely reached 48 years. In reaction, local representatives initiated a law, which abolished the colonial status and organized the complete integration to the French rule of law. During the 60s, this new status met the ambition of Michel Debré, former Prime Minister and local deputy, which deployed a thorough modernization policy to “decree” development, to organize the economic and social “catch-up” toward a naturalized European standard. Such policy relied on three main pillars, that still constitute the core of public intervention today:

- construction of world-class infrastructures to address the population needs (physical and digital communication; education; health, etc.)
- development of human capital through education and training policies, support to social integration, etc.
- consolidation of the established agro-industries (dominated by sugar production) and the promotion of alternative economic activities, through protection (Octroi de mer) and public support.

1) A formal convergence

The transformation engaged in the 60s relied on the large mobilization of public resources : between 1970 and 2015, government expenditures have risen from 100 M€ to 6,2 Bn €, excluding the tax reductions and subsidies injected in the economy :

Such engagement rapidly altered transformed living conditions, erasing the chronic mal-nutrition and exposition to malaria, and led to a demographic revolution. Since 1945, life expectancy has almost doubled (80,4 years in 2015), the mortality rate has been divided by almost four and the natality rate by almost three.

This shift provoked an accelerated demographic transition and a critical increase of the population, from 227 000 people to 866 000 in 2019. With an average 17,7% natural change per year, La Réunion has the fastest growing population of all European regions.

This demographic shift has been supported by an impressive economic growth : the GDP per capita progressed from 683 to 20 608 € between 1970 and 2015. With a 3% annual growth rate, La Réunion now belongs to the 40 most dynamic European regions (NUTS 2). Such performance contributed to an accelerated economic convergence, though the GDP per capita is still 69% of the EU average.

The remarkable demographic and economic growth, combined to new desires and schemes of consumption, created a dynamic and solvable local market, supported by public expenses. Such market has led to a profound transformation of the economic structure of the island, centered around this captive, domestic demand. Local services account for more than 66% of the GDP (36% public/30% private), transport and retail trade 16%, construction 7% and industries 8%. The latter are composed of three main activities : sugar production, food-industry and construction materials, supported by an import-substitution strategy which relies on duty protections and subsidies. The primary sector, former cornerstone of the plantation systems, now represents less than 1,5% of the GDP.

The shift is even more pronounced through the employment lens, the mechanization of sugar-cane production having led to a decline of agricultural jobs.

2) Strong dependencies and vulnerabilities

Though the regional economy appears dynamic and engaged in a strong convergence toward European standards, a closer analysis exposes strong singularities that restrict its innovation potential.

First, the island suffers from a financial dependency on public transfers from the mainland. Between 1983 and 2010, they grew from 800 million to 6.5 billion euros, representing respectively 38 and 42% of the GDP.

Public expenses alone represent 35,6% of the GDP compared to 20,4% in the European Union. They also play a major role in private consumption, largely supported by social transfers, as well as in the development of private investment mainly focused on construction. The emergence of a protected, predictable and profitable interior market constitutes a strong incentive to concentrate investments and resources on inward-looking activities, fueled by a demand that represented in 2015 more than 105% of the GDP.

The rapid demographic and economic growth since the 1970s and the introduction of mass-consumption has generated a tremendous need for resources which contrasts with the limited carrying capacity of the 2 500 km² of the island. Between 1946 and 2017, imports thus grew from 230kg to 3,8 tons per year, for a total cost of 5,8 billion euros. Besides the

financial dependency, La Réunion is thus facing a major material dependency, more than 17 million tons of imported resources are necessary to maintain its metabolism.

While imports were fast growing, export remain limited. Besides the traditional exports of sugar and rum, protected by European quotas, the high-production costs and the perceived risks and lack of profitability of exposed activities in limit their development. Exports thus rely primarily on raw products (fresh fruits and fisheries) and on the resell of imported goods, be it waste or productive equipment. As a consequence, La Réunion presents a marked trade deficit (26% of the GDP)

Despite its dynamic, the local market proves to be insufficient to support the activities and the job creations needed to integrate a fast-growing active population which has more than tripled between 1967 and 2010.

The direct consequence of this gap is a particularly low employment rate. With 39,5% of the 15-64 year old occupying a job, La Réunion lies among the bottom 5 European regions, almost 30 points below the E.U. average :

Due to the global disequilibrium between work demand and supply, La Réunion presents of the highest long-term unemployment rate (267 on 274 regions) : 16,9% of the population has been looking for a job for more than 12 month, versus 4,2% in mainland Europe.

As a consequence of such large unemployment, the island face a great social dependency issue : more than 164 000 people (19% of the population) entirely rely on social benefits and half of the population lives beyond the national poverty line. Facing such mass unemployment, entrepreneurship often remains the sole option left. La Réunion thus present a strong entrepreneurial spirit, with 44 267 companies, representing a 16% net creation rate between 2000 and 2016. Yet, 68% have no employee, 95% less than 10. As a consequence, only 53% of the firms are still active five year after their creation (60% in mainland France).

3) An abnormal participation

If these characteristics constitute a major obstacle to participate actively in H2020, they alone cannot explain the difficulties encountered, for other island, outermost, sparsely populated or poor regions perform better.

a) Compared to small size regions...

A small population is often pointed out as an obstacle to innovation due to the lack of critical mass of stakeholders and resources, essential to reach a competitive advantage in a specified field of interest. Yet, compared to 31 regions whose population is comprised between 600 000 and 1 million inhabitants, La Réunion shows a peculiar profile. Despite a much higher population density which could favor frequent social interactions leading to innovation, the net EU contribution obtained since 2015 appears 20 times higher in other NUTS2 regions

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2 (Euro)	Net EU Contribution (Euro)
La Réunion	0,4	1 879 192
Average	10,7	40 910 239
Average Nuts 2	12,9	135 880 529
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	1	1

b) ... other islands

The second frequently invoked obstacle is geographical. Due to their small size and remote position, island are often treated as “handicapped” regions, lacking the naturalized continental assets: critical mass, diversified economy, strong connections. If these traits may impact the participation, La Réunion presents once again a high singularity among the other 18 other EU islands considered:

- 2 independent States : Cyprus and Malta
- 6 outermost Regions : Açores, Canary, Guadeloupe, Madeira, Mayotte, Martinique
- 3 Baltic regions : Aland, Hovedstaden, Sjaelland

- 7 Mediterranean regions : Balears; Corsica, Crete, Notio Aigaio; Voreio Aigaio; Sardegna, Sicily

With a total contribution of 1,9 M€, La Réunion performs 30 time less than the average EU island.

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2 (Euro)	Net EU Contribution (Euro)
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192
Average	10,5	59 583 139
Average Nuts 2	12,9	135 880 529
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	2	3

The only islands obtaining less than La Réunion are the French overseas department and the Finish archipelago of Aland.

Divided by the number of inhabitants, La Réunion is the 5th least participating island region of the Union.

c) ... or poor regions

The economic characteristics of the island cannot either explain alone its limited involvement in FP. Compared to the 44 regions with a GDP per capita comprised between 18 and 22 000 €, La Réunion is situated among the 10% less active regions in terms of contribution per capita and the 20% less performant in terms of EU contribution.

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2 (Euro)	Net EU Contribution (Euro)
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192
Average	5,13	34 972 504
Average Nuts 2	12,89	135 880 529
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	1	2

A very low employment rate (below 60%) is no more a convincing reason, for the 27 regions that share the same characteristic (including many islands Regions, like the Canary, Guadeloupe, Martinique, Sicily, etc.) have obtained on average 65,8 M€ since 2014.

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2 (Euro)	Net EU Contribution (Euro)
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192
Average	9,27	65 813 091
Average Nuts 2	12,89	135 880 529
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	2	3

B - An embryonic research and innovation system

Since demographic and economic conditions reveal themselves insufficient to explain such a weak participation, the analysis of the regional research and innovation system may bring some complementary evidences.

1) A small and scattered network

Innovation is above all a social process, which depends on regional stakeholders' ability to produce, combine and turn existing knowledge into "novel solutions, successfully embedded into society". Schematically, innovation is considered an outcome of a regional system composed of intertwined organizations, which influence and are influenced by the global dynamics through their interactions. Such organizations can be divided into 6 blocks: higher education; research; transfer & innovation intermediaries;

Source: Kuhlmann and Arnold (2001: 2)

a) Higher education system

The structuration of the higher education system began in 1963 with the creation of the Institute for law, economic and political studies, an antenna of the Institute of business administration from Aix-Marseille. In 1970, this institute, then composed of three faculties – Law-Economics, Humanities and Sciences – became the university center of La Reunion. In 1982, it acquired the status of university¹. Since its creation, the institution has experienced a critical growth, from 400 students in 1963, to 2 000 in the early 80's and almost 20 000 today. The University of La Réunion (UR), which is analyzed in details on infra, remains the cornerstone of this subsystem, concentrating 66,5% of the island's students:

¹ free translation of the SOURCE (strategic plan of the University of La Reunion)

Tertiary education¹

Higher education institutions	Share of students (%)
University of La Reunion	66,5
Higher technicians sections	20,4
Medical and social schools	6,6
Higher School Preparatory Classes	3,3
Schools of Arts and Cultures	1,4
Business schools	0,8
Other	1,0

Among the 20 000 students, approximately 302 are engaged in a PhD each year

PhD students

Doctoral schools		Average number of PhD students per year (calculated over 2014-2017)	Number of research groups linked to the doctoral schools	Number of scientific domains (according to HCERES definition)
Health, Sciences and Technology	phD students	146	16	12
	phD graduation	25		
Humanities and Social Sciences	phD students	156	8	6
	phD graduation	16		
Total	phD students per year	302		
	phD graduation per year	42		

b) Public research system

The University of La Réunion also constitutes the core of the public research system, which brings together the University Hospital (CHU) and the regional representations of 5 national organizations :

- « Bureau de recherches géologiques et minières » (BRGM)
- « Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement » (CIRAD) :
- « Institut français de recherches pour l'exploitation de la mer » (IFREMER)

¹ data from the SEFORRE (Regional strategy for higher education and research)

- « Institut de recherche pour le développement » (IRD)
- « Météo France »

Other national research organizations are represented on the island through individual researchers involved in local research groups, such as the French Scientific Research Council (CNRS), the French medical research institute (INSERM), The Paris Institute of Earth Physics (IPGP), the French Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA).

Overall, 477 permanent researchers (361 full-time equivalents) are currently working in 40 research groups. Researchers from the University of La Reunion represent 60% of the research effort (with 326 FTE and excluding PhD students), making the University the first R&D public employer before the CIRAD and the IRD (with, respectively, 55 and 44 FTE).

The 40 groups are composed of 9 joint units ("UMR" - *unité mixte de recherche*) that gather the University of La Reunion with one or more national research organizations; 17 joint units between national organizations and 14 research labs, composed of a single institution. The relative large share of joint units is the consequence of a strategy developed in the late 2000s to reinforce the integration of La Réunion in the national research landscape and to contribute to the emergence of critical masses in such fields where La Réunion singularities constitute an asset for research effort.

Despite the limited number of researchers, these groups embrace a broad panel of scientific domains: 24 operate in life sciences, 10 in physical and engineering sciences and 8 in social sciences and humanities; with a net preeminence of applied life sciences, which alone form a third of the groups.

Scientific domain	Panel ¹	Number of groups
Life sciences (24 groups)	Physiology, Pathophysiology and Endocrinology	1
	Applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics, Therapies and Public Health	2
	Genetics, 'Omics', Bioinformatics and Systems Biology	1
	Immunity and Infection	2
	Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Biology	4
	Applied Life Sciences, Biotechnology, and Molecular and Biosystems Engineering	13
Physical sciences and engineering (10 groups)	Earth System Science	5
	Products and Processes Engineering	1
	Synthetic Chemistry and Materials	1
	Systems and Communication Engineering	1
	Computer Science and Informatics	1
Social Sciences and humanities (8 groups)	Cultures and Cultural Production	1
	Individuals, Markets and Organisations	1
	Institutions, Values, Environment and Space	1
	The Social World, Diversity, Population	4
	The Study of the Human Past	1

The research effort is supported by 6 cutting-edge platforms, covering the main fields of investigation, excluding energy transition:

- the Cyclotron Reunion Indian Ocean Biotechnology Platform (CYROI)
- the infectiology technical platform (PLATIN-OI)
- the Centre for Clinical Investigation and Epidemiology (CIC-EC)
- the Observatory for earth systems (OSU-R)
- the Center for Satellite-assisted Environmental monitoring of the Indian Ocean (SEAS-OI)
- the Plant protection plateforme (3P)

Name of the facility	Description	Owner	Human resources (FTE)	Facilities	Research activities	Research Support	Innovation support	European infrastructures network
CYROI	Biotechnology platform	University of La Reunion / Centre hospitalier Universitaire	20-25 (approx.)	Cyclotron, small animal PET-scan, P2-P3 labs, NMR facility, microbiology	Emerging infectious diseases, metabolic diseases,	Access to lab, research & technical equipment and offices	Access to lab, Physical, chemical and biological	NO

¹ According to ERC Panel structure 2019 : <https://erc.europa.eu/content/erc-panel-structure-2019>

				gy and molecular biology equipments, ...	biodiversity extraction		analyses, business incubator	
PLATIN-OI	Infectiology technical platform	University of La Reunion	1	Level-three-security laboratory, animal facility and insectary	Emerging infectious diseases			NO
OSU-R	Observatory for earth systems	CNRS / University of La Reunion	15	Atmospheric observatory and instruments, hydrological station, Marine reef station, Forestry station	Systems monitoring and climate change effects	Integration of specific equipments, data provision, data analysis, researchers hosting		ACTRIS, ARISE, ENVRI+
SEASOI	Satellite-assisted Environmental monitoring of the Indian Ocean	French government / Regional council of La Reunion / IRD/University of La Reunion	15	Data reception and remote sensing center of expertise	Urban planning, Coastal area management, flood risk	Data provision		NO
CIC-EC	Centre for Clinical Investigation and Epidemiology	Centre hospitalier Universitaire / INSERM	4	Clinical research capacities, medical data system, patient survey platforme, biological samples conservation and analyses		Epidemiology studies support (methodology, statistique and logistical) for metabolic infectious and perinatal diseases	Clinical research for private sectors	NO
3P	Plant protection platforme	CIRAD / University of La Reunion / Anses / FDGDON	N/A	Plant health laboratory, Plant clinic, NS2-NS3 quarantine	Plant Health, Pathology and Molecular genetics,	Access to lab, research & techniquequipment and offices	Technology transfers, Biotech SMEs hosting,	NO

				levels labs, trial plots with insResearch hect-proof shade houses, NS1-2 green houses, microbiolo gy unit, mycology unit, chemical ecology center, insect breeding unit, biological resources conservati on center, offices	Ecology, Biologic al resources conservat ion & dissemin ation		Analyse s for private compani es	
--	--	--	--	---	--	--	--	--

c) Transfer and innovation intermediaries

Driven by numerous national initiatives and regional support, multiple structures emerged during the 2000 to support the development of innovation projects :

- three centers specialized in technology transfer toward the private sector : CRITT for food-industries (run by the Reunion Chamber of Commerce), CIRBAT for construction and materials (Run by the chamber of trade and craft industry) and CITEB for aquaculture and marine bioresources (run by Nexa) ;
- the regional agency for development, innovation and investment, Nexa which assists the Regional Council in the design and implementation of research and innovation policies (such as the S3) and provides support to entrepreneurs and researchers in projects' funding, notably through H2020.
- the “Technopole” association, created in 2001 to manage business and technology parks
- a research incubator, operated by the Technopole
- a biotech incubator (CB-Tech) run by the CYROI platform
- a joint unit dedicated to support the dissemination, transfer and use of academic research results coordinated by the University of La Reunion and the Consortium de Valorisation Thématique Sud (The French consortium dedicated to the transfer of technology to Southern countries)
- a competitiveness cluster, Qualitropic, created in 2005 to develop synergies and cooperation between companies, research and training centers in the agro-industry and bioeconomy field.

- a cluster dedicated to Energy transition, Témergie.

According to a study conducted by Nexa in 2016 on the collaboration between academic and economic stakeholders, based on return on experiences on 60 projects, the most used types of collaboration were :

- collaborative projects (18)
- the mobilization of a PhD student for a private project (CIFRE) (9)
- the mobilization of a post doctoral student (9)
- the creation of a start-up, with the support of a regional research group (7).

On the contrary, very few projects (2) were developed as spin-off from a public research activity. The main motives for collaboration were the need of scientific expertise, preexisting relations and the access to high-quality equipment. Most of these collaborations (56%) gave rise to product innovation, process and service innovation.

d) Private sector

Aside from Qualitropic and Temergie which present a marked innovation-orientation, several business sectors operate on the island, like :

- Green, a cluster dedicated to waste management run by the union of trade and import businesses (SICR)
- Club Export, gathering international companies
- Digital Réunion, dedicated to ICT.

According to the last only and last edition of the Community Innovation Survey, conducted between 2008 and 2010, 53% of the local firms employing between 10 to 250 people had been innovating. The most cited types of innovation were organizational and marketing; product innovation appeared less represented than in mainland France.

% of innovation by category		
Type of innovation	La Réunion	France
Product innovation	17	24
Process	19	23
Organizational	43	36
Marketing	27	25
Total	53	53

Though regional and national scores appear very similar, this study does not reflect the reality of the innovation effort, for the sample considered excludes 95% of the productive system. 3 kind of entreprises dominate the innovation scene :

- established family firms, focused on the local market, that will develop organizational, processes, marketing and to a lower extent product innovations to preserve the relative market share
- ICT firms, which mobilize the digital transformation to propose new services to businesses and, to a lesser extent, to households
- Small high technology businesses, usually ran by an individual possessing a scientific background. Most of these firms are easily identified since they constitute the core user groups of the innovation-support system. They also frequently take part in local and national challenges, such as “I-lab”, organized by the Ministry for Research and Innovation. Since 1999, 33 firms have been primed, 28 in the “emergence” category, 5 in “Development” phase. Most of them concentrate on computer sciences and engineering.

2) Limited and fragmented innovation efforts

Despite the efforts engaged to structure the regional innovation system, its performance remains limited, whatever the criteria considered. Such situation stems from the conjunction of three phenomenon: reduced human and financial resources dedicated to R&I, a high thematic fragmentation which inhibits the emergence of critical masses, and a marked lack of cooperation and coordination among stakeholders.

a) Limited capacities and efforts

The transition toward knowledge economy is first conditioned by the general education level of the population. Yet, the recent introduction of a modern and universal education system and its lack of adaptation to the postcolonial, multicultural and diglossia context, has

generated a persistent illiteracy issue. More than 116 000 people (23% of the 16-65 year old) do not read or write easily. Such phenomenon is not a temporary, generational matter, but a structural characteristic : more than 11% of the 18 years old are concerned, compared to 3,6% of the overall French population¹.

Despite the presence of the University and several graduate schools, welcoming each year more than 20 000 students, only 20,8% of the 25-64 year old have successfully completed tertiary studies, 10 points lower than the average NUTS2 score. La Réunion thus belongs to the 20% least performant regions in terms of tertiary education. Like illiteracy, this gap is not generational, but stronger for the 30-34 year old.

	Tert. Educ. 25-64 (%)	Tertiary educ. 30-34 (%)
La Réunion	20,8	28,7
Average EU 27	31,0	39,1
Decile	2	2
Ranking (274)	228	233

The lack of training impacts the research and innovation capacities. With 115 000 people with tertiary education and/or employed in science and technology, La Réunion belongs to the 10% least endowed European regions. This represents 29% of the active population, 10 points less than the European average score.

	Persons with tertiary education (ISCED) and/or employed in science and technology	% of active population
La Réunion	115	29,08
Average EU 27	377,16	39,77
Decile	1	2
Ranking (274)	233	236

Moreover, the tertiary educated workforce is for the most part not engaged in research or innovation activities, which mobilize only 755 people on the island (447 working for public or semi-public research institutions). In 2015, high-technology and researchers represented respectively 4 and 0,3% of the total jobs, which makes La Réunion one of the 20% least active regions.

¹ INSEE Réunion. *116 000 personnes en situation d'illétrisme en 2011 à La Réunion*. Octobre 2013

	Researchers (%)	High tech jobs (%)
La Réunion	0,30	4
Average EU 27	0,66	1,7
Decile	2	2
Ranking (274)	185	243

The limited implication of the workforce reflects and contributes to the reduced financial resources dedicated to R&I, which represented 0,58% of the GDP in 2013, compared to an average 1,48% in NUTS2 regions. The private sector represents only 20% of the effort, a consequence of the limited size of businesses and their orientation toward a protected local market, which requires a low level of innovation.

	R&D expenditures (%GDP)	Share of private R&D
La Réunion	0,58	0,2
Average EU 27	1,48	0,5
Decile	3	2
Ranking (274)	182	256

b) Fragmentation

Despite the limited resources mobilized on research and innovation, the effort is fragmented on a broad number of “priorities”, which for the most part, lack the required critical mass to produce distinctive knowledge, know-hows and innovations. Such dispersion may be considered a consequence of the non-cooperative strategies engaged by stakeholders and institutions, nurtured by the lack of coordination and prioritization by public authorities, whose intervention focus on the distribution of the ERDF envelop across the most pressing lobbies.

This phenomenon can also be witnessed in the innovation-support system, composed of at least 30 structures, which propose close services to the same kind of stakeholders and share a common objective : extend rapidly their perimeter of intervention to increase their negotiating position toward funding authorities. Such superposition is not only detrimental to the final users, who regularly complain on the complexity of the system, but also to the structures themselves, which more the most part struggle to comply to the European regulation on state-aid that limits the public support to 50% of the budget.

3) Impact on H2020 participation

Though the regional capacities and involvement in R&I remain weak, they alone cannot explain the very limited participation in Horizon 2020. Like for socio-economic indicators, La Réunion was compared to a series of region which present a similar profile in terms of tertiary education, R&D expenditures, or researcher number. Whatever the criteria considered, this analysis confirms the existence of an abnormal situation.

a) Tertiary education

On the 95 NUTS2 regions, with 20 to 35% of their 30-34 year old population engaged in tertiary education, La Réunion (28,7%) occupies the 90th rank in terms of H2020 per capita, per year. It is also part of the bottom 20% of the sample in terms of net EU contribution, with 1,8 M€ compared to an average 65 M€.

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2 (Euro)	Net EU Contribution (Euro)
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192
Average	5,49	65 190 659
Average Nuts 2	12,89	135 880 529
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	1	2

Such gap cannot be explained by economic conditions, since these regions share a close GDP per capita. Yet, La Réunion presents a peculiar profile, marked by a very low

population (almost half of the sample average) and the limited number of students involved in tertiary education. Combined to this size effect, the number of people holding a tertiary degree and/or employed in science and technology (HRCT) is almost three times higher in the other regions (314 000 vs 115 000). With the same level of tertiary education, La Réunion seems less engaged in the knowledge economy: research and innovation accounts for 0,58% of its GDP, and 1,1% in the sample. This could lead to a lesser participation in Horizon 2020.

b) Active population in R&I activities (%)

The island was then compared to 71 regions with a close level of HRST (15 to 25% of their active population). This group includes many island or outermost regions such as Balears, Corsica, Guadeloupe, Guyane, Notio Aigaio, Voreio Aigaio, Sardegna, Sicily, Madeira. All of these regions have in common a globally weak participation to Horizon 2020 (with 3,8 euros per capita per year), that confirms the determinant impact of human resources. Yet, among them, La Réunion distinguishes itself with a much higher GDP (top 20%) and a relatively large investment effort (top 40%). Once again, its small population (bottom 30%) and limited tertiary education affects the human capacity, measured by HRST expressed in thousand people (20 041 vs. 49 999). Though the gap is less critical than the previous sample, La Réunion belongs to the 3rd decile in terms of EU contribution and to the 2nd per capita.

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2 (Euro)	Net EU Contribution (Euro)
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192
Average	3,81	35 277 350
Average Nuts 2	12,89	135 880 529
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	2	3

c) Active population in R&I activities (nb)

To neutralize the size effect of the two previous samples and better reflect the human capacities (potentially) engaged in research and innovation, the analysis of HRST expressed in number of people is instructive. The 33 regions with 80 to 150 000 people holding a tertiary degree and/or engaged in scientific and technological activities, are for 90% of them less populated and dense than La Réunion. Yet, their tertiary training effort appears significantly higher (in 80% of the considered regions) with 40% of the 30-34 year old versus 29% in La Réunion. They also dedicate a much larger share of their GDP (1,25 vs. 0,58%) to research and innovation. Despite their limited size, these regions thus show a strong R&I orientation which leads to a higher performance than the average Nuts2 regions in terms of EU contribution per inhabitant. Once again, La Réunion belongs to the bottom 10% regions using this criteria and the bottom 20% in net EU contribution.

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2 (Euro)	Net EU Contribution (Euro)
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192
Average	13,48	37 219 659
Average Nuts 2	12,89	135 880 529
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	1	2

d) Researchers in the active population

Once again, the 68 regions with a close share of researcher in their active population (0,2 to 0,4%) comprise many islands such as the Azores, Balears, Canary, Cyprus, Malta, Sicily. This group presents very similar performances to La Réunion in terms of tertiary education (24 vs. 20,8%) HRST (33 vs. 29%); R&D intensity (0,68 vs. 0,58%) and GDP (21 158 vs. 20 400€ per capita)

Yet, despite these similitudes, the regions obtain on average 13 more H2020 funds and 8,5 per capita.

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2 (Euro)	Net EU Contribution (Euro)
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192
Average	3,76	24 523 351
Average Nuts 2	12,89	135 880 529
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	1	2

e) Research and innovation expenditures

The 81 regions that dedicate 0,3 to 1% of their GDP to R&I share many common points with La Réunion : a close GDP (21 488 vs 20 400), a close proportion of researchers (0,36 vs. 0,29% of the active population). However, they tend to invest more in higher education (36 vs. 29% of the 30-34 year old). In this sample, La Réunion constitutes the 2nd least H2020 beneficiary per capita, and the 4st least globally, far away from the average scores of 5,71€ per capita and 40 M€ per region since 2014.

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2 (Euro)	Net EU Contribution (Euro)
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192
Average	5,71	40 122 710
Average Nuts 2	12,89	135 880 529
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	1	1

f) Profile of other EU regions presenting the same H2020 participation

To better understand the singularities and blocking points faced by La Réunion, the reverse comparison with regions that present a close level of H2020 participation is particularly instructive. Compared to the 33 regions which obtain less than 1 euro per inhabitant, per year, the island presents a much higher GDP per capita (20 400 vs. 15 625 €) which makes it one of the 20% richest. It also lies in top 10% in terms of researchers employed and R&D expenditures. Yet, even compared to this sample, La Réunion presents a low performance in terms of tertiary education, and a slightly above average percentage of the active population holding a tertiary degree and/or employed in scientific or technological activities.

g) Synthesis

The comparative analysis of demographic, socio-economic and innovation-related indicators highlights the cumulative effect of a set of factors. Physical, deterministic approaches which consider small size and insularity as key obstacles to participate in Horizon 2020 are not confirmed by the analysis: these regions present a performance slightly inferior to the average Nuts 2. As mentioned earlier, regions with very limited tertiary educated active population (in absolute numbers) even participate more than average.

	Criteria	EU contribution per capita per year	La Réunion position
Physical	Islands	10,51	2
	Population 600 to 1 M	10,67	1
Socio-economic	PIB 18 to 22 k€	5,13	1
	Employment rate < 60%	9,27	2
	Unemployment rate 18 to 27%	5,53	3
Education	Tert 30-34yr; 20 to 35 %	5,49	1
Research and innovation	HRST 25 to 35% pop active	3,81	2
	HRST 80 to 150 000	13,48	1
	GERD	5,71	1
	Researchers 0,2 To 0,4	3,76	1
Average NUTS 2		0,44	1
La Réunion		12,89	

Conversely, La Réunion participation appears to be first undermined by its relatively low GDP, a phenomenon common to most convergent regions and confirmed by the analysis

conducted by the Joint Research Council on the Widening Program¹. This economic obstacle is reinforced by the small proportion of the people benefitting from tertiary education and above all by the very limited importance of knowledge economy on the island. The global lack of involvement of the private sector in the research and innovation effort (80% of which remains public), the strong focus on local and protected economic activities lead to an underuse and misuse of this human potential. As a consequence, the economy remains trapped in low added-value specializations, and does not reach the required critical masses of financial and human effectively mobilized resources.

Yet, the characteristics of the regional innovation system do not, by themselves, explain the limited participation in Horizon 2020, which remains abnormal. The compilation of 4 major indicators – a GDP between 18 and 22 k€ per capita, a HRST between 20 and 35% of the active population, a R&D effort inferior to 0,6%, a population between 200 and 1 M€ inhabitants – constitute a group of 9 regions :

- 3 Greek (Dytiki Makedonia; Ionia Nisia; Sterea Ellada)
- 2 Italian (Molise and Basilicata)
- 4 Portuguese (Algarve, Alentejo, Açores, Madeira)

¹ PONTIKAKIS et alii. *Mobilising European structural and investment funds and Horizon 2020 in support of innovation in less developed regions*. 2018

3 of these regions are islands and/or Outermost regions the rest occupy a peripheral position, with frequently mountainous landscapes. With similar characteristics, they have obtained on average 3,84 euros per capita, representing 7,9 million euros.

	GDP	HRST	HRST %PA	Intramural R&D expenditure (GERD)	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts ²	Net EU Contribution
	PPS per HAB	Thousand	%pop active	% of GDP	Euro	Euro
Dytiki Makedonia	18 792	32,9	27,3	0,33	1,99	2 794 219
Ionia Nisia	19 925	21,1	21,7	0,27	1,10	1 137 631
Stereia Ellada	18 875	56,0	23,1	0,39	4,70	13 110 235
Molise	20 342	43,4	31,8	0,51	0,99	1 556 207
Basilicata	19 725	70,0	29,8	0,60	2,14	6 178 712
Algarve	21 783	52,2	25,2	0,36	6,19	13 672 326
Alentejo	19 400	81,2	24,7	0,54	4,54	16 936 151
Azores	19 008	24,1	22,7	0,42	4,41	5 435 166
Madeira	20 433	27,3	23,9	0,35	8,49	11 102 508
Average	19 809	45,3	25,6	0,42	3,84	7 991 462
La Réunion	20 400	115	29,08	0,58	0,44	1 879 192

C - Regional policies, the unfindable synergies ?

One of the explanations to this abnormal participation, almost 9 times inferior to reference regions, may be found in the way regional policies for research and innovation have so far been implemented. In 2013 and 2014, to counteract the major dependencies and sources of vulnerabilities exposed on (A) more than 200 people took part in the design of the smart specialization strategy. This exercise was then considered an opportunity to collectively question the development model inherited from the departmentalization and to turn the high ecologic, energetic, economic and social challenges into new opportunities of prosperity and resilience. Such strategy relied on a strong outward looking orientation, notably through the proclaimed will to reintegrate La Réunion in the European research and innovation ERA to reach critical masses and position the island as a European knowledge hub in the Indian Ocean, exporting innovative solutions to third countries. Despite the efforts and resources mobilized, the experiences developed, the participation in FP has registered a sharp decline between FP7 (3,6 M€) and Horizon 2020 (1,8 M€). Largely because the established habits and behavior detrimental to H2020 remain and have been encouraged by the management of ERDF funds dedicated to research and innovation.

1) S3, a transformation challenge

The elaboration of the smart specialization strategy occurred few years after a crisis that revealed the very vulnerability of the economy, whose growth and sustainability mostly relies on massive and regular financial, material and energy flux that supports the population growth and a solvable, internal market, protected from imports. If the 2007 crisis constituted a first alert, major phenomenon threatens the pillars of this model in the medium term. The global ecological crisis, biodiversity collapse, soils exhaustion and material depletion will lead in the coming years to a critical reduction of the imported flux necessary to maintain the island metabolism. Meanwhile, the critical demographic and economic growth on a small territory, dominated by vulnerable endemic ecosystems, has led to major ecological challenges, which need to be urgently addressed. The import-substitution economic model is itself threatened by the progressive saturation of the local market, the European liberalization dynamic and free-trade agreements, as well as the downturn of public transfers due to budgetary constraints.

Facing such threats, the first reaction stands in the traditional “insularity fatality” syndrome : due to its limited size and resources, its negligible bargaining position and the lack of economy of scale, La Réunion would be condemned to suffer passively such evolutions and to ask for more protection and help. The alternative approach, promoted by the S3, calls for a paradigm shift on the way island characteristics are considered: the so-called “handicaps” are naturalized disadvantages induced by the import of a mass-production/consumption economic system that relies on fossil fuels and economies of scale. Such model is currently collapsing, challenged by revolutions like the ecological economy, digitalization and 3-D printing, the return of territories and proximity economy, the shift of the global economy toward Asia and Africa. All these revolutions offer the opportunity to reconsider island singularities as valuable assets rather than handicaps to be suppressed. Indeed, because of its characteristics – a densely populated, resource-consuming remote island with vulnerable ecosystems – La Réunion faces a challenge that will concern tomorrow most the territories : invent an economy respectful of the capacities and rythms of natural ecosystems, which constitute its main asset. This represents a unique opportunity to turn the island into a European living lab for ecological transition and develop knowledge, know-how and exportable solutions for other territories in Europe and elsewhere in the world.

The actualization of such ambition is dependent on the ability to strengthen research and innovation capacities to connect to other European and international research and innovation ecosystems. In an era of globalization, marked by the concentration means and talents in a few global hubs, peripheral territories risk to be trapped in a vicious circle, where the lack of resources hinders the emergence of a performant and attractive RDI ecosystem, which in turn inhibits the development of critical masses. To counteract this dynamic, La Reunion thus combines smart specialization with smart connections with European and worldwide partners.

2) Priorities

The S3 priorities were defined according to their capacity to contribute to a more resilient region through the development of innovation solutions exportable to other regions

and the creation of critical mass of singular knowledge and know-hows. Globally, 5 priorities emerged : tropical bio-economy, energy transition, healthcare solutions hub, experiential eco-tourism, and social innovation.

a) Solutions for a tropical bioeconomy

To secure the productive basis in a coming era of scarcity, the first imperative remains the conservation of the islands' ecosystems, which condition all social and economic activities and play a key role in the development through the production of ecological services such as climate regulation, rainfall, fertile soil, raw materials and energy. This challenge is especially relevant in a small region of 2 500 km² where 30% of the surface is covered by slopes with an incline greater than 30% and facing a growing conflict of land use. The effects of anthropization, climate change and the proliferation of invasive species put these habitats at risk. This constraint can be treated as an incentive to develop an ecological economy, that addresses the need of a fast growing population while preserving thriving ecosystems. Such opportunity incorporates not only products but also expertise, built along a coherent value chain made of 5 segments :

- Ecological monitoring, conservation and restoration solutions for tropical insular environments
- Marine biodiversity conservation and management
- Agro-ecological practices and production
- Active ingredients and agroproducts from local biodiversity

Sectorial mapping in tropical bio-economy

Innovation-market pairs	Research centers	Transfer & innovation support	Other public bodies	Business clusters
Ecological conservation and restoration solutions for tropical insular environments	CIRAD Botanical Conservatory of the Mascarene Islands University of La Reunion Research groups : PVBMT, OSU-R,	ARMEFLHOR (agricultural technical institute) 3P	National forestry commission County council National Park of Reunion Island	Qualitropic horticulturists association
Agroecological practices and production	CIRAD University of La Reunion eRcane (sugar cane private center)	Chamber of Agriculture ARMEFLHOR (agricultural technical institute) 3P (plant protection plateforme) RITA (Networks for agricultural innovation and technology transfer)	National Park of Reunion Island	Qualitropic Farmers's associations (AROPFL, AVAB, GAB), Sugar producers' union, Medicinal plant producers associations (ADPAPAM, APLAMEDOM, CAHEB)
Marine biodiversity conservation and management	IRD IFREMER University of La Reunion Research groups : ENTROPIE ESPACE DEV	CITEB	Regional blue institute Reunion natural marine reserve	Qualitropic Maritime cluster
Active ingredients and agroproducts from biodiversity and tropical resources	Academic labs (LCSNSA, DETROI, PIMIT, PVBMT) eRcane	CYROI CRITT SAS Eco-ex CITEB		APLAMEDOM ADIR (Association for Reunion 's industrial Development) AROPFL (Federation of fruits and vegetables producers' associations) Qualitropic

b) Energy transition in islands

The departmentalization marked the entry of La Réunion into the "thermo-industrial" era, where techniques, knowledge and practices relied heavily on fossil fuel exploitation. If this change has triggered a clear improvement in life conditions and a substantial growth in population, it also led to an exponential increase of the carbon dependency. In a time of global declining resources, this shift has tremendously increased the vulnerability of a small and isolated island that lacks fossil fuel resources, and thus imports up to 800 M€ yearly. The

decarbonization challenge is thus an ecological and economic opportunity, which considering the absence of connection to a continental grid, necessitates to adapt the energy demand to local production capacities. . This ambition raises technological, economic and social issues : in a centralised but non-interconnected power system, dealing with intermittent energy sources makes the management of supply and demand a real difficulty and constitutes an obstacle to the integration of RES on the grids. Moreover, in a tropical humid and warm climate, thermal comfort solutions and industrial heat/cold needs rely on carbon-intensive electricity sources. In addition, large-scale renewable energy plants generate use-conflicts with agricultural land, essential to food security, or natural habitats providing ecological services... These constraints are actually opportunities to strengthen knowledge and know how in energy transition in tropical islands that will be exported in territories facing tomorrow our today's challenges. Three innovation-market pairs constitute our research&innovation priority in energy transition:

- Tropical bioclimatic eco-building
- Renewable energies production
- Smart and small grids in non-interconnected system

Sectorial mapping in Energy transition

Innovation-market pairs	Research centers	Transfer & innovation support	Other public bodies	Business clusters
Tropical eco-building	University laboratories (LE2P, PIMENT)	CIRBAT	Ademe EDF CAUE	Consular chambers ADIR FRBTP CerBTP
Renewable energies production	University laboratories (LE2P, PIMENT)		Ademe EDF SPL Energie Reunion Nexa	Temergie
Smart and small grids	University laboratories (LE2P, PIMENT)		Ademe EDF SPL Energie Reunion Nexa	Temergie

c) Regional healthcare solutions hub

During the last 50 years, La Réunion has undergone a health revolution, accompanied by an epidemiological change : infectious diseases which were responsible for almost 50% of the deaths in 1950s, now accounts for less than 2%. 2005. As a result of rapid and massive changes in lifestyles and environment, Reunion is now exposed to metabolic, diabetic and cancer risks. The most frequent diseases encountered in Reunion are related to the circulatory system and tumours (30.3% and 20.6% of deaths, respectively) as in mainland. In addition, the subtropical climate and geographical proximity with Africa's estearn coast puts Reunion & Mayotte at risk for new infectious diseases, espacially vector-borne epidemics (Dengue, Zika). Therefore, the health system has to become “glocal”, in order to respond to local and

global issues. La Reunion needs to manage health hazards caused by the local specifics, which were catalysed by departmentalisation : metabolic diseases, diabetes, obesity, kidney disease, hypertension, birth but also monitor and eliminate tropical hazards which affect the Indian Ocean area. In this context, two innovation-market pairs have been identified :

- Prevention of metabolic and infectious diseases in insular tropical context
- Innovative integrated & customised diagnostics and therapies

Sectorial mapping in Health

Innovation-market pairs	Research centers	Transfer & innovation support	Other public bodies	Business clusters
Metabolic and infectious diseases prevention in insular tropical context	University of La Reunion CHU INSERM IRD CIRAD Research units : DETROI, ICARE, IRISSE, MIVEGEC,	CYROI CIC-EC	ARS	CB tech Qualitropic
Innovative diagnostics and therapies	University of La Reunion CHU INSERM IRD CIRAD Research units : DETROI, IRISSE, PIMIT, DSIMB, MIVEGEC	CYROI CIC-EC Eco-Ex	ARS	CB tech Qualitropic Aplamedom GIS TESIS

d) Experiential eco-tourism

La Réunion holds remarkable comparative advantages for tourism : exceptional natural heritage (protected by a National Park, part of the Unesco World Heritage, thanks to its Cirques, Pitons and Remparts, its Volcano, biodiversity hotspot, Marine Park), tropical climate, diverse recreational activities, cultural, religious and gastronomic culture, modern equipment in a safe health and political environment, and, finally, its status as a French island at the heart of the Indian Ocean. In total, tourism already makes up almost 8% of the island’s GDP and creates 6,750 direct jobs. Thus, tourism is a regional priority, as it has an immense growth potential to create diverse jobs and support the development of other sectors through an integrated approach (development of farming, traditional and industrial productions; services; commerce; digital solutions; environment; developing the island’s highlands, etc.). The goal of S3 is to focus on innovating the island’s tourism offering, by emphasizing differentiation, capturing high-value market niches (which are characterized by a relatively inelastic demand due to transportation and accommodation costs), proposing appealing solutions, and maximizing economic spin-offs. Innovation also seems to be the key to

reducing the tourism industry’s exposure to current risks (international competition, natural hazards, such as sharks) and future risks (increase in transportation costs, emergence of new destinations, etc.).The tourism innovation strategy relies on emphasizing differentiation and capturing high-value market niches in tropical multicultural environment.

Sectorial mapping in Eco-tourism

Research centers	Transfer & innovation support	Other public bodies	Business clusters
University of La Reunion IRD CBNM Research group : OIES, CEMOI		Park national of La Reunion National forestry commission Regional council Departemental council SPL Musées régionaux DAC OI	Tourism Club FRT Sports federations

e) Social innovation for a responsive and smart territory

Through its history, La Réunion has been stricken by numerous shocks and crises, overcome thanks to the resilience of its inhabitants. Today, new challenges are emerging and the society needs to adapt at accelerated rythms, despite the dissappereance of several social “shock absorbers” through the “modernization processes”. The island’s resilience, agility and, capacity to bounce back can no longer be considered a lifetime warranty. They must be renewed, strengthened, and adapted to new challenges through the mobilization of regional stakeholders to better address non-covered social needs, notably adapted education and effective illiteracy programs, stronger community relationships, promotion of self-organization, etc.

Sectorial mapping in Social innovation

Research centers	Transfer & innovation support	Other public bodies	Business clusters
University of La Reunion IRD Research groups : ICARE, LCF, OIES	CRESS Couveuse reusit Boutique de Gestion	AGORAH Regional council	

3) Innovation system action plan

In addition to these thematic priorities, the S3 proposes on a structural, cross-cutting action plan designed to facilitate the entrepreneurial discovery process, i.e. reveal through a trial and error process the precise activities that will forge the new knowledge economy and hold a competitive advantage. To do so, the S3 pursues one objective: to increase the quantity and quality of innovative projects developed on the island. This objective itself depends on the ability to produce and absorb knowledge and skills and mobilize effectively such

resources to generate new activities and prosperity. To support his endeavor, five axes have been determined:

a) Strengthening and mobilizing talents

To address the relatively limited regional capacity and will to innovate, the first priority focuses on capacity-building through :

- the development of excellence research and innovation infrastructures and programs, as well as investments in tertiary education (notably through higher education infrastructures, doctoral and post doctoral scholarships)
- the stimulation of a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship, through a regional promotion strategy and training programmes adapted to all key audiences (students, PhD students, entrepreneurs, employees, established firms, public stakeholders) supported by a common programme of conferences, prizes and competitions
- the mobilization of businesses and business support entities through advanced training on innovation methods and new business models; the detection of potential innovations and the support for innovation management.

b) Developing fruitful proximity and efficient collaborative support services

Proximity plays a major role in the innovation process : it facilitates the production and exchange of knowledge and their combination into innovation, as well as the constitution of critical masses. To encourage such fruitful interactions, several type of initiatives are supported : the development of research and innovation networks and clusters, the promotion of collaborative projects, the mobilization of regional stakeholders in prospective and territorial intelligence activities. Collaboration is also key lever to increase the quality of the support services provided to entrepreneurs and innovators, which suffers from the high fragmentation depicted supra. To counteract these tendencies and propose clearly identified, accessible and effective services, a strong focus is paid to the structuration of a regional, mutualized and coordinated support service, that relies on two principles : the specialization of each support structure on a specific field of activity or service, the mutualization of generic services (like financial engineering, access to competitive funds, expertises, etc.).

c) Encouraging international connections

The lack critical mass, attributed to the island's small size and remoteness, is no fatality. In a world of large communication networks, its isolation appears less physical than relational : La Réunion narrowly focuses on itself and mainland France and limitedly exploit the opportunities offered by both the Indian Ocean basin and the European Union. In order to take advantage of these opportunities, a strong attention is paid to the integration in promising networks, through a double orientation.

On the one hand, the reinforcement of the region's attractiveness, to attract and preserve resources and talents that will condition its innovation capacities and competitiveness.

Such attractiveness strategy is based on a clear positioning: make La Réunion known as a European hub for ecological transition in tropical island context. A selected promotion strategy is thus implemented to identify and attract strategic partners in the S3 sectors, exploiting the strategic position, the quality of the ecosystem and the privileged funding conditions proposed.

On the other hand, a large emphasis is put on the international development of local businesses through the export of high quality, singular, products, services and concept. This is achieved through the development of knowledge – on target markets, on the island's competitive positioning, on potential stakeholders and regions with which synergies can be established – as well as a support of business clusters, the participation to business meetings and the organization of export missions.

d) Promoting the integration within European research and innovation area

To accompany the economic transformation of the island, and accelerate the construction of competitive advantages, the connection to global networks of excellence is a prerequisite. Besides the creation of new knowledge and the increased scientific productions through cooperation, such integration constitutes an opportunity reach critical masses through networking and to play a role in the global knowledge economy. Since the latter is conditioned by agglomeration effects, it encourages – coupled to globalization – the concentration of resources and talents in a few dynamic hubs, which becomes more attractive and competitive... At the opposite end of the spectrum, small and remote region face a risk of marginalization, for they don't present the required critical masses. To break this vicious circle, the S3 thus dedicates means to reinforce the integration in the European research and innovation area, through the development of H2020 projects.

To that end, in 2014, the regional innovation agency – Nexa, and the University of La Réunion created a mutualized European office whose goal is to connect Reunionese research groups and innovation stakeholders to European centres of excellence in strategic areas. It thus presents an original organization compared to other European support services, traditionally integrated in one organization and accessible for its members only. Having a common EU support services at a regional level presents many benefits: all organisations can refer to the same support service and offer a global vision of the various project opportunities; resources can be pulled and engineers fully dedicated to the development of projects; it also encourages cooperation.

Funded by the Structural Funds, the State and the Regional Council, the European office provides support to the setting up of projects responding to calls of proposals launched by the European Commission. It offers free services to researchers and innovators from the University, research centers, regional institutions and SMEs to help them develop projects in Horizon 2020, Interreg Europe and other EU funding opportunities such as the Life and best programmes. Two projects engineers originally the European Office which mobilizes an average 55 000 euros per year to finance the activities carried out. Since 2016, the office is

restricted to Nexa, as the University redirected its personnel to the development and management of ERDF projects.

The services proposed have been adapted to the large proportion of “new comers” in Horizon 2020. For these users, having a successful first experience in project submission is decisive to avoid a perceived waste of time and resources which may result in increasing self-selection behaviour. Yet, their probability to succeed remains limited. To combine these two objectives, a specific process of project development has been developed with the help of “Key Innovation”. Composed of 9 steps, this process aims at qualifying the maturity and success potential of the project, allowing the candidate to stop the development if the chances or resources are too low.

Type of services	Description
Interface with European commission, NCPs...	The European Office, shares with the European institutions (Commission, Parliament) and other national intermediaries (ministries, NCP's) propositions to better include OR in Horizon 2020, promote research capacities and important research fields for Reunion Island in the EC work programmes. It also informed local researchers of important EU decisions in their fields.
Horizon 2020 Awareness raising	The European Office is the local contact point to the Reunionese research and Innovation community; it maintains a certain level of understanding of the framework programmes in the community and promotes opportunities and in participating in H2020.
Detection of potential regional project leaders	The European office identifies potential H2020 successful participants and proposes adapted support to empower them with the correct skills, network, processes...
Horizon 2020 training	Training on Horizon 2020 development process from the selection of the call to the submission of the proposal.
Detection of funding opportunities	The European Office screens Horizon 2020 opportunities to share with potential H2020 candidates.
Consortium building and networking support activities	The European office identifies the right partners and networks in order to enter collaborative projects. When detecting a strongly relevant call the European office produces a promotion document presenting the added value of local partners. This is sent out to European networks and actors potentially developing a proposal. This has led to the participation of Reunion in the REACT project.
Proposal development cycle	Support in proposal conception, partners search, proposal writing, budget consortium coordination, drawing up budget, proposal submission
Supporting implementation of successful projects	information point and support for the implementation of the project

Since 2014, a total of 27 projects have been financed by EU funds (all competitive programs considered). 25 of them benefited from a support from the European Office. 92% of

the Horizon 2020 successful projects were supported by the office and only 64% for other types of competitive programmes (LIFE, COSME, Interreg Europe, BEST etc...). The prevalence of Horizon 2020 in the support provided to successful project may be the result of an internal policy to concentrate the European office effort on research and innovation programmes which resulted in hiring project engineering more specialised on FP programmes. In 2019, Nexa hired another project engineer to further develop projects in conservation oriented European programmes such as LIFE and BEST.

On the 13 successful H2020 projects developed on the island, 12 have been supported by the European Office. This indicates a strong visibility induced by the organization of many awareness sessions and regular encounters with regional stakeholders. On this 12 projects, 2 have benefited from support during the proposal development phase only; 2 at the implementation phase only and 8 during both steps. Thanks to the awareness sessions organized and the regular encounters with regional stakeholders, the office benefits from a strong visibility : only 2 projects were submitted during Horizon 2020 without any support

3 of the successful projects (SCREEN, REACT, FORWARD) as well as 1 Interreg Europe (REPLACE) included regional partners thanks to the connections of the European office, which highlights the importance of consolidating and developing relations with European networks such as ERRIN or Eurada, to increase the participation of Outermost regions.

4) The ERDF complex

Though the regional smart specialization strategy conditioned the access to and was supported by structural funds, their impact on H2020 participation remains ambiguous.

a) A large ERDF endowment for research and innovation, with limited H2020 impact

The Thematic Objective n°1 of the 2014-2020 ERDG programme mobilizes 136,9 €. If one enlarges the budget to the categories of intervention contributing to the development of research and innovation, the efforts sums up to 175 M€, distributed as follow :

To ease the comparison, the relevant categories of intervention were aligned on those selected by Pontikakis & al in their 2018 report on less developed regions¹. Half of this budget is dedicated to public research infrastructures and projects, 15M€ for cluster and business networks and 61 million for SME business and innovation development.

Thanks to the “ESIF viewer” tool developed by the JRC on the S3 platform, data on regional innovation expenditures per capita, per year, were extracted on 124 NUTS2 regions (the initial list of 194 included 70 NUTS1 regions). Such effort represents an average 23€ per inhabitant. With 32€, La Réunion lies among the 20% regions that dedicates the highest amount to research and innovation. This performance is largely due to the large ESIF obtained by the island (1,66 billion euros).

The comparison between the amounts of ESIF and H2020 obtained confirms the singularity of La Réunion, and its abnormal participation. Among the 40 regions that dedicate between 20 and 50 € ESIF to research and innovation, the island belongs to first decile either in terms of net EU contribution (4,2M€) or per capita, per year (0,7€). Measured by capita, its performance appears to be 10 times lesser than the average NUTS2, though these regions present a close GDP per capita (19 561 vs 20 400 €), level of R&I effort (0,8 vs 0,58% of the GDP), tertiary education (34 vs 29% of the 30-34 year old) and percentage of active population

¹ Pontikakis et al. *Mobilising European Structural and Investment Funds and Horizon 2020 in support of innovation in less developed regions*. JRC Technical Report. 2018

	Net EU Contrib. /Y.hab.Nuts2	Net EU Contribution
	Euro	Euro
La Réunion	0,44	1 879 192
Average Nuts 2	4,41	30 730 922
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF
Decile	1	1

This gap highlights the critical difficulty faced by La Réunion to turn ERDF investment in research and innovation into Horizon 2020 participation. Indeed, the island presents the 15 lowest H2020/ESIF ratio of the 193 regions analyzed¹ : 0,014, demonstrating a substitution effect between the two sources of funds. Even among EU islands Region, the intensity of this phenomenon appears particularly striking:

¹ The method used is based on PONTIKAKIS & al (2018); data on ESIF R&I expenditures were extracted from the «R&I regional viewer» tool provided by the Smart Specialization Platform; data on Horizon 2020 were extracted from the H2020 dashboard in July 2019 and divided by the population of these regions in 2015.

b) A large substitution effect

Such difficulty to establish a synergy between the two funds can be explained by three main phenomena.

First, despite a proclaimed ambition to concentrate resources on the island competitive advantages the S3 adopted a very broad perspective which embraced almost all research and innovation activities developed on the island. This perspective is itself the consequence of the exacerbated influence of interest groups induced by insularity and strong social bonds. Paradoxically, the introduction of conditionality criteria, thought to increase the effectiveness of the S3, annihilated its very foundation, in the sense that all themes were to be made priorities, whatever their potential, to ensure their eligibility to structural funds.

Secondly, the island suffered from a clear disconnection between the strategy (handled by the Regional Innovation Committee) and the management of the funds allocated to the Thematic Objective n°1 (piloted by the Regional Council as ERDF managing authority). Not only did the institution in charge of S3 not orient the funds, but worse, the latter were distributed in ways that contradicted the very objectives of the strategy. For instance, research projects were funded through two series of calls for projects (2015 and 2019) based on the same format: research centers were offered the opportunity to submit projects, financed up to 1 M€, based on the analysis of a single expert.

Contrary to the proclaimed objective of critical masses, such method led to the fragmentation of the research effort across regional organizations (different and rival organizations working on close thematic) and inside laboratories (which sometimes obtained 2 or 3 grants). Contrary to the proclaimed objective of long term planning and effort, such method led to the multiplication of short-term, opportunistic projects, not inscribed in a strategic plan. In 2019, the urgency to spend the credits even led the managing authority to limit the projects to a 2 year length... Contrary to the proclaimed objective of internationalization, such method encouraged parochialism for it offered easily accessible and less competitive funds that limited the will as well as the capacity to submit H2020 projects, research teams being focused on managing and implementing their ERDF-funded projects. The latter thus led to a typical “dutch-disease syndrome”, where the financial flux induced by a rent conduct stakeholders to concentrate their effort on capturing to this profitable source, at the expense of long term strategic investments in future competitive advantages.

This phenomenon is easily illustrated by the relative weight of ERDF and H2020 in the development of research projects. At the exception of social sciences, which were not granted access to ERDF, no field of expertise presents a positive lever effect.

Far from reorienting stakeholders' behaviors and lack of interest for H2020, the broad, unstrategic use of ERDF confirmed a tendency exacerbated by the very strategies of the regional organizations.

Regional organizations

Organizational characteristics and orientations play a significant role in the regional participation in framework programmes. In La Réunion, such participation is highly concentrated on a limited number of stakeholders: 6 active in FP7, 7 in H2020, representing a total of 9 institutions.

Though the 5 five categories of stakeholders mapped by CORDIS are represented, higher education establishments account for more than half of the H2020 projects developed on the island. With 3 projects, the second main category, labelled “Other”, regroups the regional agencies for urbanism (Agorah) and for development and innovation (Nexa). Private companies, public sector and research organizations complete the description with 1 project each.

A - The University of La Réunion

In respect to this marked concentration and to its weight in the regional research & innovation system, this report proposes a strong emphasis on the University of La Réunion (UR).

1) Description of the University of La Reunion

a) FP participation

Between 2007 and August 2018, the University of La Réunion has been part of 5 FP7 and 8 H2020 projects. 6 out of these 13 projects were financed under “research infrastructures” work programmes. Such proportion stems from the critical role played by “OSU-R”, the joint Earth System observatory operated by the CNRS and the UR, which conducted these 4 infrastructure-related projects.

The importance of OSUR is also reflected in the topics explored, dominated in terms of project numbers by Climatology and Climate change. The second field of interest – immunity and infections – is composed of 3 projects (incl. one Regpot); while the five other themes have been only active once in FP.

To evaluate the success rate of the institution, 4 projects where UR entered as a third party of the CNRS (Actris, Actris 2, EnvriPlus, Zikalliance) were excluded.

	Number or proposals	Number of grant signed	Success rate %
FP7	15	4	26,7
H2020	23	5	21,7

With 37,8% of active laboratories, submission to FP appear to be more concentrated in the UR than in most French universities, where 70% of research groups directors (141 on 200) declare having submitted a proposal¹.

	FP7	H2020
Number of applying research groups	6	9
Total number of research groups ²	18	22
% of research groups applying to FP funding	33,3	40,9

Not only do research groups submit less projects, but their mobilization is unequal through time. Only a third of them have submitted proposals in both FP7 and H2020; 5 newcomers joining in the last period.

In terms of topics, a marked growth of social humanities, physics and engineering (related to energy transition) and earth system sciences may be noticed. The research groups involved in the latter were already active in FP, as third-parties. In the same time, immunity and infection which constituted an important field of FP7 projects for the University (thanks to the Regpot “RunEmerge”) is no more represented. The proposals in applied life sciences have also decreased, since the “Taskmar” project, submitted 3 times on FP7, has been accepted.

¹ Secrétariat Général pour la modernisation de l’action publique – *Enquête auprès des entreprises et des unités de recherche publiques sur leur perception du Programme Cadre de Recherche et de Développement Technologique de l’UE*. Octobre 2015

² Between 2010 and 2018, some research groups have merged and new ones created. The allocation of a proposal to a specific research group is based on the researcher’s affiliation.

The observation of proposals and signed grants by H2020 pillars reveals a strong concentration on societal challenges and excellent science.

	Number or proposals	Number of grant signed	Success rate %
Excellent science	8	2	25
Industrial leadership	1	0	0
Societal challenges	13	2	15
Other – Science with and for society	1	1	100
Total	23	5	22

In terms of funding schemes, candidatures to individual fellowships (ERC & MSCA) have remained so far unsuccessful; most projects mobilizing coordination and support actions, research and innovation actions and innovation actions' schemes.

	Number or proposals	Number of grant signed	Success rate %
ERC	3	0	0
MSCA-IF	3	0	0
RIA	9	2	22,2
IA	5	1	20,0
CSA	3	2	66,7

Compared to rejected proposals, signed projects turn out to be much larger either in the grant amount or the number of partners, with a more limited role of the University of La Réunion, which confirms the necessity to cooperate with successful H2020 players to integrate the program.

	Number	Mean duration (in months)	Total Requested Grant	Participant Requested Grant	% participant funding request (compared to total requested budget, excluding mono-beneficiary proposals)	Number of Partners (excluding mono-beneficiary proposals)
All proposals	23	40	3 742 023 €	393 333 €	9,7	15,0
Rejected proposals	18	41	3 404 265 €	485 547 €	12,8	12
Signed projects	5	37	4 687 748 €	208 904 €	6,0	19,0

b) UR's vision and actions for H2020

To better understand the vision of the University, an interview was conducted with the President of the Academic Council and the Officer for Innovation. According to them, increasing the participation in FP constitutes one of the key objectives of the University's strategic plan (the "Source"), as a means of increasing research capacities and excellence through new collaborations, and the internationalization of the institution.

Yet, such ambition is not supported by a defined strategy or objectives. More, since 2016 and the election of a new governance a marked reorientation toward ERDF can be witnessed : H2020 accounts for 7,8% of the European funds (ESIF + FP) supporting research projects vs. 17,7% on the 2007-2013 period.

Since 2016, excepting Forward only two projects have been financed by the European Commission:

- One dedicated to research : REACT (Renewable Energy for self-sustainable island communities) which begun on January 2019 which involves the LE2P laboratory
- One dedicated to science promotion : STORIES (European Researchers' Night in France) involving the administration

This shift is also illustrated by the evolution of support services proposed to researchers. In 2013, UR and Nexa, the regional agency for development and innovation, set up a mutualized “European office”, whose mission was to promote, train and support all kind of stakeholders in the development of FP proposals. Such office was composed of two fully dedicated agents, mobilized by the two partners, and an action plan financed by ERDF and the Regional Council. From 2016, UR reallocated the working time of its agent to the development and management of ERDF projects, at the expense of the Horizon 2020 support. Such reorientation and the lack of adequate support services by the University is now pointed out by many researchers interviewed as one of the most pressing blocking points for H2020 access.

2) Characteristics

To better understand the participation of the University and the obstacles encountered, the characteristics of the institution have been analyzed according to the 5 main determinants that, according to the literature, influence higher education establishments:

- size, measured by the number of academic staff; i.e. personnel dedicated to education and research (such as professors, associate professors, instructors, lecturer
- orientation, defined by the relative importance of research activities vis à vis training in the institution

- scientific excellence, characterized by scientific productivity and impact
- international openness and integration in the major research networks
- prior participation in FP.

In the absence of contribution of the University of La Réunion to the Work Package 2 of Forward, the data were gathered from three sources: the “bilan social 2015-2016”, the reports produced by the “Observatoire des Sciences et Techniques”¹ and the “Haut Conseil de l’évaluation de la recherche et de l’enseignement supérieur”

a) Size

The University presents a modest size in terms of personnel: 496,5 academics (in full time equivalent – FTE) and 615,3 administrative staff².

Staff composition		
	Number	Full time equivalent
Academic staff (permanent and non permanent)	514	496,5
Administrative staff (permanent and non permanent)	638	615,3
Total staff	1152	1111,8

Evolution of staff composition at University of La Reunion					
		2013	2014	2015	2016
Academic	Number	509	495	498	515
	FTE	492,7	476,8	481,5	497,5
Administrative	Number	555	555	535	638
	FTE	549,2	544,2	526,9	615,3
Total	Number	1064	1050	1033	1153
	FTE	1041,9	1021	1008,4	1112,8

Academic staff accounts for 45% of the total staff, a notably low share at the European level.

¹ Observatoire des Sciences et Techniques – Rapport sur les publications scientifiques 2012 à 2017

² Université de La Réunion – Bilan social 2015 & 2016

b) Research intensity

The University of La Réunion is composed of 412 permanent and non-permanent researchers, including 216 “maîtres de conference” and 94 full professors. Since the latter dedicate part of their time to teaching activities (50%), the theoretical research capacity of UR reaches 217,9 full time equivalents. To determine how much research-oriented the University is, we restrict the analysis to the permanent academic staff (to reduce yearly variations induced by PhD candidates).

Permanent academic staff			
	Number	FTE	Research dedicated FTE
Researchers (with teaching activities)	326	324,4	162,2
Teaching only personnel	113	11,6	
% dedicated to research	74,26	4,40	37,20

In theory, researchers represent 326 FTE and account for 74,3% of permanent academic staff. Yet, after deducting the time dedicated to teaching, the overall staff focusing on research activities equals 162,2 FTE. That is to say, 37,2% of the academics, expressed in full time equivalent; which highlights a strong training-orientation of the UR. 26% of the academic staff is composed of teachers with no research activities.

This limited research capacity is aggravated by a strong fragmentation. The 397 researchers are divided into 21 research groups and 37 sub-groups which embrace very diverse fields.

As a consequence, the average group aggregate 19 researchers and no group exceeds 43. A ratio 10 times lower than in mainland France, where the average size reaches 131 FTE. The limited number of researchers cannot be compensated by non-academic staff (engineers, technicians, etc.) since only 11 % of them are working in research teams¹. Such orientation can be confirmed by evaluating the PhD intensity of the institution, i.e. the ratio between the number of PhD students and the total number of students involved in License and Master degrees².

¹ Bilan social 2016 : Répartition des personnels BIATSS titulaires par composante en ETP

² ETER Handbook, p.68

PhD intensity according to ETER handbook (page 68)	
Number of PhD students	245
Number of students in Licence & Master degrees	13227
PhD intensity	0,019

As explained in supra, this PhD intensity appears to be very limited, compared to other European institutions. The strong focus on license and master can also be illustrated by a comparison with other French Universities: 81% of the student population is pursuing a first degree, 20 points higher than in mainland France¹

c) Scientific excellence

The scientific level of research organizations can be evaluated by their productivity (measured by the global number of publication per full time equivalent) and their impact (determined by the average number of publications' citations). In terms of productivity, an independent report from the Observatoire des Sciences et Techniques, based on the Web of Science database provides the following data

¹ Repères et références statistiques – enseignements, formation, recherche 2017

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Number of publications (all sciences)	173	189	263	300	309	370
Ratio number of publications (all sciences) / FTE academic staff*	0,35	0,38	0,53	0,60	0,62	0,75

	2012-2014	2013-2015	2014-2016	2015-2017
Number of publications per year on a 3 year period (all sciences)	208,3	25,7	290,7	326,3
Ratio number of publications over 3 years (all sciences) / FTE academic staff	0,42	0,05	0,59	0,66

These data were compared to the largest bibliometric database on universities' publications – the CTWS Leiden Ranking. On the 308 European universities listed, UR occupies the 266th rank in terms of number of publications, and belongs to the bottom 20% European universities. Such performance may be overrated since the Leiden Ranking is based on English publications, registered in Web of Science, while the data for UR encompass French-speaking publications.

	Number of publications (2014-2017)
D1	1164
D2	1361
D3	1600
D4	1915
D5	2322
D6	2855
D7	3629
D8	4933
D9	7758
University of La Réunion	1242

The limited importance of UR in the overall publications is partly explained by the fact that 25% of the permanent researchers do not publish research articles¹.

The evaluation of the impact of such publication proved to be impossible by the time of the analysis, since the publications of UR are neither analyzed by the Leiden Ranking, or by the OST.

¹ AERES 2014

d) International openness

In the absence of data on foreign staff members, students, PhD candidates and post-docs, the evaluation of the internationalization of the UR is compromised. One clue lies in the evaluation of international collaborations leading to scientific publications. With 52,9% of its 2014-2017 publications written with an international partner, UR belongs to the top 30% European universities mapped by the Leiden Ranking. However, such co-publications are essentially developed with non-European partners: EU28 represents only 10,7% of the total publications of the university and 20% of its international publications, 10 points less than French universities. Such score reflects the inscription of UR in its geographical basin and the priority awarded to regional collaborations.

	University of La Réunion	French universities
% of the publications with international partners	52,95	52,95
% of EU28 copublications	10,75	16,85
% of EU28 on international copublications	0,20	0,29

3) Comparative analysis

Based on this description, a comparative European analysis has been conducted with the help of 4 sources of data:

- The ETER database, 2019 edition which compiles information on European Higher Education institutions
- The Leiden Ranking, mentioned above
- The H2020 dashboard, “H2020 funded project” extracted on July 2019
- The Observatoire des Sciences et Technologies report on the University of La Réunion

The list of all “higher or secondary education” (HES) establishments active in H2020 was extracted from the H2020 dashboard. It specifies for each institution the net EU contribution as well as the number of participation.

From this list, 968 H2020 active institutions were identified on ETER. 12 indicators were then selected based on the main determinants of HES FP participation, mentioned in the literature:

- The size of institutions measured by personnel expenditure, current expenditure (€), the total number of academic staff (expressed in full time equivalent), number of full professors, the total staff, the total number of students enrolled (ISCED 5-7), students enrolled in ISCED 8 (PhD & postdoc),

- The research orientation measured by the PhD intensity, and full professors /academic staff, academic staff/total staff ratios.
- International openness, measured the share of foreign students (ISCED 5-7), the share of foreigners academic staff, the share of mobile PhD students
- The participation to FP, expressed by the number of participation, the EU contribution, FP researchers mobility, FP staff mobility and FP research training cooperation.

HES for which ETER offered no data or which presented extraordinary characteristics (such as a very limited number of students or full staff) were suppressed, constituting a sample of 789 institutions.

a) Relative position of the University of La Réunion

The University of La Réunion was first compared to the 789 institutions, according to the 12 criteria listed above. For each of them, we determined the distribution by decile, the ranking of UR and the average performance of European institutions. If terms of size, UR is in line with the median of European HES:

	Total Current expenditure (M€)	Total students enrolled ISCED 5-7	Total staff (FTE)
Average	173,1	14797	2097
University of La Reunion	106,6	13227	1111,8
Decile	6	6	5
Ranking	465	348	514

Yet, the analysis of staff-related indicators reveals some striking facts :

- With only 496,5 academic staff for 13 227 ISCED 5-7 students and 245 PhD candidates, UR mobilizes less than 3,7 academic staff for 100 students. Such ratio makes it one of the 40% less endowed institutions of the panel.
- On the contrary, UR is situated among the 40% highest non-academic staff effectives. It thus presents a severe disequilibrium between academic and non-academic staff, which makes it one of the most “administration-oriented” institution of the panel
- Though academically understaffed, UR hosts a relatively large number of full professors, which places the institution in the 20% HES with the highest share of professors in the academic staff.

	Total academic staff (FTE)	Number of non-academic staff (FTE)	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)	Total number of full professors	Full professors / academic staff (HC)
Average	1097	1002	0,57	176	0,148
University of La Reunion	496,5	615,3	0,45	94	0,1800
Decile	4	6	2	5	8
Ranking	565	455	683	480	306

The comparative analysis also confirms a marked teaching orientation of the institution: UR welcomes only 245 PhD candidates for 13 227 license and master students, which represent a PhD intensity of 0,019; a score that places UR in the 30% less research-oriented institutions of the panel.

	Total students enrolled at ISCED 8	PhD intensity
Average	808	0,061
University of La Reunion	245	0,019
Decile	4	3
Ranking	583	645

In terms of H2020, the University of La Reunion has been active in 7 H2020 projects for a total EU contribution of 1,042 M€; far away from the average score of 34 participations for 16,3 M€. This gap confirms the fact that La Réunion usually plays a minor roles in the projects to which it participates. Finally, like 80% of the sample considered, the University of La Réunion enjoys no FP-financed researcher or staff mobility of research training cooperation.

b) Comparison to organizations which present similar characteristics

To deepen the analysis, the University of La Réunion was compared to 9 groups of institutions, sharing a common characteristic, like an approaching number of H2020 participation or staff. For each of these groups, the average score and the distribution (measured through deciles) of the members were determined for the 12 indicators mentioned above. We then calculated the relative position of UR to underline its singularities and common traits.

- **Close participation in H2020 (5 to 8 projects)**

UR was first compared to 111 HES which have been active in 5 to 8 projects. Such institutions are generally smaller than their homologue, which is part of the top 30% in terms of current expenditure and students ISCED 5-7. They also appear to be more implicated in the H2020 projects they develop, with an average EU contribution of 1,6 M€ compared to 1,02 M€ for the UR (which is part of the 40% least beneficiaries). The sub-performance of UR can be explained by the allocation of human resources, characterized by a marked academic understaff and non-academic overstaff. It also stems from a neat teaching orientation, induced by the large number of students and a limited number of PhD students.

	H2020 Net EU Contribution (M€)	Current expenditure (M€)	Academic staff (FTE)	Full professors	Non-academic staff (FTE)	Total staff (FTE)	Students enrolled ISCED 5-7	Students enrolled at ISCED 6	PhD intensity	Full professors / academic staff	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)
Average score	1,6	76,2	656	105	573	1229	9528	345	0,038	0,139	0,558
University of La Réunion	1,04	106,6	496	94	615	1112	13227	245	0,019	0,180	0,450
All HES	16,35 €	173,0	1 097	176	1 002	2 097	14 797	808	0,061	0,148	0,565
Average +/- 20%	INF	SUP	INF	-	-	-	SSUP	IINF	IINF	SUP	-
Decile	4	8	5	6	7	5	8	5	4	8	1

(Red indicates that UR presents a score 20% below the average and/or belongs to deciles beneath the median (5); Green a score 20% above the average and higher than 5 deciles; Yellow a score equal to the median.

- **Close H2020 contribution**

The comparison with 138 HES that obtained between 700 k€ and 1,5M€ in H2020 confirms the previous analysis. Despite a much larger size which should normally lead to an increased H2020 participation, UR shows close results and occupies a minor role in such projects. The over-representation of full professors and non-academic staff is confirmed.

	H2020 Participations	Current expenditure (M€)	Academic staff (FTE)	Full professors	Non-academic staff (FTE)	Total staff (FTE)	Students enrolled ISCED 5-7	Students enrolled at ISCED 8	PhD intensity	Full professors / academic staff	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)
Average score	4	71,0	578	96	456	1 024	10 138	267	0,029	0,136	0,581
University of La Reunion	7	106,6	497	94,0	615	1 112	13 227	245	0,019	0,180	0,450
All HES	34	173,08	1 097	176	1 002	2 097	14 797	808	0,061	0,148	0,565
Average +/- 20%	SUP	SUP	-	-	SUP	-	SUP	-	INF	SUP	INF
Decile	9	9	5	6	8	7	8	6	5	7	1

- **Close number of full professors**

The 96 institutions which host an approximate number of full professors (80 to 120) are globally more engaged than UR in H2020, be it in terms of number of projects (18,6 vs. 7) or funds obtained (7,7 vs. 1,04 M€). Such gap indicates that the number of full professors working in UR does not equal its potential for H2020 project development. They are indeed over-represented in an academic staff, which is one-third smaller in La Réunion. Research efforts cannot either be sustained by PhD candidates; UR being among the 20% institutions in terms of ISCED 8 students.

	H2020 Net EU Contribution (M€)	H2020 Participations	Current expenditure (M€)	Academic staff (FTE)	Non-academic staff (FTE)	Total staff (FTE)	Students enrolled ISCED 5-7	Students enrolled at ISCED 8	PhD intensity	Full professors / academic staff	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)
Average score	7,7	19	113,0	742	649	1391	12138	493	0,035	0,140	0,543
University of La Reunion	1,04	7	106,6	497	615	1112	13227	245	0,019	0,180	0,450
All HES	16,35 €	34	173,08 €	1 097	1 002	2 097	14 797	808	0,061	0,148	0,565
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF	-	INF	-	IINF	-	IINF	IINF	SUP	-
Decile	4	5	6	3	6	3	7	2	4	8	2

- **Close number of academic staff**

Though they share an approximate number of academic staff (400 to 600 FTE), the 83 HES and UR diverge a lot in terms of size. The latter belongs to the 10% biggest institutions in terms of current expenditure, total staff and students enrolled at ISCED 5 to 7. Yet, despite their limited size, such establishments benefit twice more of H2020 (2,5 M€ vs. 1,04). The difference may stem from a more research-oriented strategy and flexible approach, while UR dedicates many resources to the administrative and pedagogic responsibilities engendered by its greater number of students.

	H2020 Net EU Contribution (M€)	H2020 Participations	Current expenditure (M€)	Full professors	Non-academic staff (FTE)	Total staff (FTE)	Students enrolled ISCED 5-7	Students enrolled at ISCED 8	PhD intensity	Full professors / academic staff	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)
Average score	2,52	7	69,49	122	378	878	9824	308	0,033	0,144	0,589
University of La Reunion	1,04	7	106,6	94	615	1112	13227	245	0,019	0,180	0,450
All HES	16,35 €	34	173,08 €	176	1 002	2 097	14 797	808	0,061	0,148	0,565
Average +/- 20%	INF	-	SUP	INF	SUP	SUP	SUP	INF	INF	SUP	INF
Decile	6	8	9	7	9	9	9	4	4	8	1

- **Close number of total staff**

Compared to the 63 institutions of the panel that employ between 900 and 1 200 full time equivalent, UR enjoys a larger budget, which is related to the higher number of license and master students trained. The analysis highlights once again the imbalance between academic and non-academic staff : UR is situated among the 10% institutions that present the lowest numbers of academic staff and the 10% institutions with the largest non-academic staff personnel. Due to this allocation of resource, UR trains a fewer number of PhD students. In terms of H2020 participation, UR shows an average performance, yet the EU Contribution obtained remains very limited (1,04 M€ vs. 4, 08), which reveals the little role played in the projects.

	H2020 Net EU Contribution (M€)	H2020 Participations	Current expenditure (M€)	Full professors	Non-academic staff (FTE)	Academic staff (FTE)	Students enrolled ISCED 5-7	Students enrolled at ISCED 8	PhD intensity	Full professors / academic staff	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)
Average score	4,08	8	80,67	150	454	607	10 903	337	0,038	0,138	0,573
University of La Reunion	1,04	7	106,6	94	615	497	13 227	245	0,019	0,180	0,450
All HES	16,35 €	34	173,08 €	176	1 002	1 097	14 797	808	0,061	0,148	0,565
Average +/- 20%	INF	-	SUP	INF	SUP		SUP	INF	INF	SUP	INF
Decile	6	7	8	7	9	7	8	4	4	9	1

- **Close number of students**

Excluding their close number of students (11 to 15 0000 ISCED 5-7), UR and the 98 institutions which compose this group have little in common. The latter are way bigger, in terms of financial and human resources. UR is academically under-staffed with 496,5 academics compared to an average score of 1011 people; which places it among the lowest 10% establishments. UR presents a strong teaching orientation with only 245 PhD candidates, versus an average 807. It thus belongs to the bottom 30% in terms of PhD intensity. Due to

the concentration of limited resources on teaching activities, UR involvement in H2020 is almost 20 times lower than its counterparts (1,04 M€ vs. 19,26 M€)

	H2020 Net EU Contribution (M€)	H2020 Participations	Current expenditure (M€)	Academic staff (FTE)	Full professors	Non-academic staff (FTE)	Total staff (FTE)	Students enrolled at ISCED 8	PhD intensity	Full professors / academic staff	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)
Average score	19,26	38	202	1011	171	903	1914	807	0,052	0,131	0,556
University of La Reunion	1,04	7	106,6	497	94	615	1112	245	0,019	0,180	0,450
All HES	16,35 €	34	173,08 €	1 097	176	1 002	2 097	808	0,061	0,148	0,565
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF	INF	INF	INF	INF	INF	INF	INF	SUP	-
Decile	3	4	5	2	4	6	3	3	3	9	2

- **Close number of PhD students**

The 55 institutions of this panel share similar characteristics to UR. Their reduced number of PhD students (200 to 300) contrasts with a high number of license and master students (12 273 on average), which mobilize the same level of financial and human resources. Yet the latter are concentrated in UR on non-academic staff, at the expenses of academic staff. This lack of research potential is thus reflected in H2020 participations : in a group limitedly implicated (3,5 M€ vs. 14,4 for all HES), UR belongs to the bottom 30% institutions with 1,04 M€.

	H2020 Net EU Contribution (M€)	H2020 Participations	Current expenditure (M€)	Academic staff (FTE)	Full professors	Non-academic staff (FTE)	Total staff (FTE)	Students enrolled ISCED 5-7	PhD intensity	Full professors / academic staff	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)
Average score	3,56	11	120,68	751	110	563	1273	14402	0,036	0,106	0,589
University of La Reunion	1,04	7	106,6	497	94	615	1112	13227	0,019	0,180	0,450
All HES	16,35 €	34	173,08 €	1 097	176	1 002	2 097	14 797	0,061	0,148	0,565
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF	-	INF	-	-	-	-	INF	SUP	INF
Decile	3	4	6	4	7	7	5	7	4	9	2

- **Close number of publications**

Through the Leiden Ranking, a list of 61 universities with 1000 to 1 500 publications from 2014 to 2017 was constituted. Their characteristics were specified with the help of ETER and the H2020 dashboard. Through this comparison, UR appears to be a very scientific productive institution, which rivals with much larger institutions in terms of academic staff, full professors, students and PhDs Yet this analysis overestimates the performance of UR, its publications number integrating French journals. Despite this bias, UR belongs to the bottom 10% institutions in terms of H2020 contribution (1,04 vs. 4,7 M€).

	H2020 Net EU Contribution (M€)	H2020 Participations	Current expenditure (M€)	Academic staff (FTE)	Full professors	Non-academic staff (FTE)	Total staff (FTE)	Students enrolled ISCED 5-7	Students enrolled at ISCED 8	PhD intensity	Full professors / academic staff	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)
Average score	4,72	20	155,9	844	83	782	1626	10855	544	0,071	0,083	0,516
University of La Reunion	1,04	7	106,6	497	94	615	1112	13227	245	0,019	0,180	0,450
Average +/- 20%	INF	INF	INF	INF	-	INF	INF	SUP	INF	INF	SUP	-
Decile	1	1	4	1	2	2	1	4	2	1	9	2

c) Conclusions

Whatever the criteria considered, UR presents an abnormally low participation in H2020, especially in terms of EU contribution.

	H2020 Net EU Contribution
EU contribution 700 to 1,5 M€	-
H2020 participation 5<8	INF
400 to 600 academic staff	INF
80 to 120 full professors	INF
Total staff : 900 to 1200	INF
Students ISCED 5-7, 11 to 15 k	INF
Students ISCED 8 200 to 300	INF
Publications (1000 to 1500)	INF

Such performance cannot be explained by a limited size, expressed by the number of people employed, the budget or the number of students. The latter are indeed largely superior to institutions with similar characteristics:

	Total Current expenditure (EURO)	Total staff (FTE)	Total students enrolled ISCED 5-7
EU contribution 700 to 1,5 M€	SUP	-	SUP
H2020 participation 5<8	SUP	-	SUP
400 to 600 academic staff	SUP	SUP	SUP
80 to 120 full professors	-	INF	-
Total staff : 900 to 1200	SUP		SUP
Students ISCED 5-7, 11 to 15 k	INF	INF	
Students ISCED 8 200 to 300	-	-	-

On the contrary, the human resources may be considered a critical factor. Globally understaffed, the University privileges the recruitment of non-academic staff. It is part of the 10% institutions with the lowest academic/non-academic staff ratio, whatever the criteria of comparison considered. It also belongs to the low 10% in terms of academic staff when compared to same size institutions (in terms of total staff and student numbers).

Such disproportion may also be noticed at the national level. According to the French ministries for “National Education” and for “Higher education, research and innovation”¹, the share of academic staff in La Réunion was 10 points lower in La Réunion compared to other universities.

	Higher education institutions	Universities (excl. Medical faculties)	Universities (incl. Medical faculties)	University of La Réunion
Academic staff (FTE)	97 381,7	72 514	31 270	496,5
Non academic staff (FTE)	83 776,5	59 145	22 548	615,3
Academic staff / Total staff	0,54	0,55	0,58	0,45

The lack of academic staff is aggravated by the over-representation of full professors, systematically above the average score, which mobilizes important financial resources.

¹ Bilan social du ministère de l'Éducation nationale et du ministère de l'Enseignement supérieur, de la Recherche et de l'Innovation - 2016-2017

	Total academic staff (FTE)	Number of non-academic staff (FTE)	Academic staff / total staff (FTE)	Total number of full professors	Full professors / academic staff (HC)
EU contribution 700 to 1,5 M€	-	SUP	INF	-	SUP
H2020 participation 5<8	INF	-	-	-	SUP
	-	-	-	-	
400 to 600 academic staff		SUP	INF	INF	SUP
	-		-	-	
80 to 120 full professors	INF	-	-		SUP
Total staff : 900 to 1200	-	SUP	INF	INF	SUP
Students ISCED 5-7, 11 to 15 k	INF	INF	-	INF	SUP
	-	-	-	-	
Students ISCED 8 200 to 300	INF	-	INF	-	SUP

Internal resources being dedicated to training and handling the challenges posed by more 13 000 license and master students, research remains a secondary priority; despite the high ratio of titular professors. Such orientation is revealed by a very low level of PhD students and intensity.

	Total students enrolled at ISCED 8	PhD intensity
EU contribution 700 to 1,5 M€	-	INF
H2020 participation 5<8	INF	INF
	-	-
400 to 600 academic staff	INF	INF
	-	-
80 to 120 full professors	INF	INF
Total staff : 900 to 1200	INF	INF
Students ISCED 5-7, 11 to 15 k	INF	INF
	-	-
Students ISCED 8 200 to 300		INF

B - Other organizations

Excluding University, 18 regional organizations have been submitting proposals and 9 successfully participating in FP:

Such restricted mobilization contrasts with the dense network of organizations that constitute the innovation ecosystem. To explore this paradox, we propose an overview of the experiences, motives and obstacles of the different categories of stakeholders.

1) Regional representations of national research centers

Besides the University and the University hospital, the public research effort of the island is concentrated in local representations of national research centers:

- The *Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement* (CIRAD)
- The *Bureau de recherches géologiques et minières* (BRGM)
- The *Institut français de recherches pour l'exploitation de la mer* (IFREMER)
- The *Institut de recherche pour le développement* (IRD)

a) FP participation

On a national level, these institutions show a marked interest for FP.

According to a Cordis extraction, dating from July 2019, they occupy high ranks, BRGM and IFREMER belonging to the top 300 on 9 864 organizations.

Organizations	Participation	Rank
IFREMER	45	268
BRGM	41	290
CIRAD	21	567
IRD	31	388
UNIVERSITE DE LA REUNION	7	1956

Yet, local teams are seldom integrated in such projects. Between 2007 and 2019, BRGM and IFREMER have submitted no proposals, CIRAD and IRD one. The latter remains to this day, the only participant through the Run Sea Science project, financed through a Regpot scheme under FP7, which represented 4,3% of the EU contribution obtained by the IRD.

Such limited participation cannot be explained by the inadequacy of the thematic call for projects. At least 7 H2020 projects involving the CIRAD and IRD present close connections with research activities conducted on the island:

- TROPICSAFE (“Insect-borne prokaryote-associated diseases in tropical and subtropical perennial crops”) coordinated by CIRAD
- LEAP Agri (dedicated to the “sustainable intensification of African food systems), including CIRAD and IRD
- PROIntensAfrica (“Towards a long-term Africa-EU partnership to raise sustainable food and nutrition security in Africa”) including CIRAD
- BlueBRIDGE (“Building Research environments for fostering Innovation, Decision making, Governance and Education to support Blue growth”) with IRD
- RINEA (“Research and Innovation Network for Europe and Africa) with IRD
- INFRAVEC2 (“Research Infrastructures for the control of vector-borne diseases”) with IRD

Three times, researchers based in La Réunion were not involved in projects in which the island was represented by another local partner:

ACRONYM	Project	Local partner	National institution
MADE	Mitigating ADverse Ecological impacts of open ocean fisheries	University of La Réunion	IFREMER
MADE	Mitigating ADverse Ecological impacts of open ocean fisheries	University of La Réunion	IRD
Envri Plus	Environmental Research Infrastructures Providing Shared Solutions for Science and Society	University of La Réunion	IRD
Zikaliance	A global alliance for Zika virus control and prevention	PIMIT	IRD

b) Analysis

To understand why local capacities are seldom turned into FP participations, the strategies of such institutions should be questioned. To that end, three semi-structured interviews were conducted with the representatives from the CIRAD, IFREMER and IRD. Despite several attempts, the BRGM did not respond positively to our invitation.

2 out of 3 delegates mentioned H2020 as a major priority of their local representation, with very different motives. As a consequence of its status (a public body engaged in commercial activities) and its large implantation in La Réunion (170 employees, representing a tenth of the national staff), the CIRAD is looking for financial resources to support the operational costs and secure its economic model. Up to day, those are covered by a 2014-2020 agreement with public authorities, supported by structural funds. In times of uncertainty, H2020 is seen as considered an instrument for economic diversification and consolidation. Such viewpoint reflects the national position expressed in the “Contrat d’objectifs Etat-CIRAD” 2014-2018, which describes H2020 as a lever to “develop, consolidate, optimize financial resources to stabilize the economic model of the institution on the long-term”¹. For the IRD, FP participation is seen as a lever to develop international collaborations, essential to avoid a local tendency to isolationism which can be prejudicial to research activities. H2020 is thus approached from a scientific point of view. Promoting such collaborations is also considered a way to position the institution as an European leader in the field of development studies.

Unanimously, the three institutions point out the availability of large structural funds dotation as the number one obstacle to the development of H2020 projects. In the case of CIRAD, human resources and research activities are entirely centered on the objectives defined by the 2014-2020 agreement which leaves no time for researchers to engage in other type of projects, despite their interest. Though more flexible and project-oriented, IFREMER and IRD concentrate their efforts on the mobilization of more accessible and less competitive

¹ CIRAD, *Contrat d’objectifs Etat-CIRAD, 2014-2018*, p.21

regional (European Maritime and Fisheries Fund; ERDF and INTERREG) or national funds that can support their orientation, respectively the development of blue economy and the Millennium Sustainable Development Objectives.

Such orientation is confirmed by the analysis of the European funds (ERDF + FP) mobilized by these institutions between 2007 and 2019. IRD remains so far the only institution engaged in a FP project, which accounts for 13,8% of the total EU budget obtained.

Though most interviewees expressed the will to increase the local participation to H2020 and to design and implement an internal and regional strategy, they enjoy a very limited autonomy in decision making processes. Local heads of office mostly focus on the day to day management the structure, the identification of financial resources to support the activity, the relation to policy makers, the collaboration with local institutions and project follow-up. H2020 is managed directly by national services / directions, which design the institution’s strategy, conduct lobbying activities at the national and European level, and determine the relevant calls for projects and the team involved in the proposal drafting. Local researchers / units may thus be excluded from projects which are in line with their research thematics, as seen earlier. The dependence on the mainland is reflected in the project development process. Local representations fully rely on a national “European office” to promote and support H2020 participation. These offices centralize the organizations of information sessions and trainings, identify the calls in line with the strategy and fields of interest, and relay information to research teams. Interested researchers are then taken in charge, by a support program which varies from one organization to another: administrative & financial support (CIRAD & IRD) by staff trained to FP specificities; proposal review, budget development, expert analysis (IFREMER)

2) Indirect participation through Joint research units

In contrast to the BRGM, CIRAD, IFREMER and IRD, other national research organisms are indirectly represented through their contribution to joint research units with UR such as:

Acronym	Name	National partners
DéTROI	Reunion, Indian Ocean Diabetic atherothrombosis therapies	INSERM
Entropie	Pacific an Indian Ocean tropical marine ecology research centre	CNRS, IFREMER, IRD
Lacy	Atmosphere and cyclones research lab	CNRS, Météo France
LGSR	Réunion geosciences laboratory	Institut de physique du globe de Paris
PIMIT	Infectious Processes in tropical island environments	CNRS, INSERM, IRD

The major played by the CNRS and INSERM in European R&I networks and H2020 (through respectively 1036 and 239 projects) could be a powerful driving force to increase the participation of La Réunion. Yet, so far, the integration has remained modest and indirect. As mentioned earlier, through the example of OSUR, local organizations are positioned as third-party of the CNRS, with minor contribution to the project.

Acronym	Project title	Organization involved	Requested EC contribution (€)	% of the total requested EC Contribution
ACTRIS	Aerosols, Clouds, and Trace gases Research Infrastructure Network	OSUR	45486	0,58%
ACTRIS-2	Aerosols, Clouds, and Trace gases Research InfraStructure	OSUR	38657	0,41%
ENVRI PLUS	Environmental Research Infrastructures Providing Shared Solutions for Science and Society	OSUR	9584	0,07%
ZIKAlliance	A global alliance for Zika virus control and prevention	PIMIT	110000	0,92%

3) Research and innovation platforms

Research and innovation platforms propose mutualized technical equipment and well trained staff to support scientific and economic stakeholders in their activities. As described earlier, La Réunion benefits from a dense network of high quality infrastructures which, combined to its exceptional location and singular conditions, can be seen as strong assets to integrate H2020 projects. Once again, the actualization of such potential remains difficult. Between 2007 and 2019, only two platforms have been participating in FP :

- Ercane, a sugarcane resource development center owned by TEREOS, which conducts research on plant breeding, cultivation techniques, green chemistry and industrial processes.
- OSUR, the environment and climate change monitoring observatory.

Three other platforms remain out of the scene:

- 3P (Plant Protection Platform), described as the Indian Ocean resources center for agronomy
- CYROI, a medical and biotechnology platforms organized around a Cyclotron
- SEAS-OI, a satellite and remote-sensing monitoring platform

Their lack of involvement may be explained by a conjunction of factors. First, these platforms have been designed to address the needs of local stakeholders and contribute to regional cooperation in the Indian Ocean basin. Such self-centered orientation reflects in an assumed dependency to direct or indirect public support, through the delivery of services to local stakeholders, such as research groups or innovative companies, themselves subsidized.

Finally, excepting the 3P run by the CIRAD, these structures are operated by a weak governance, with various and sometimes antagonistic interests, who have high difficulties to define a strategic roadmap. As a consequence, no international strategy of promotion and integration to the major European infrastructures network has been elaborated and these structures remain largely unknown to potential partners.

4) Other kind of stakeholders

Organizations other than higher education establishments and research institutions represent 42% of the Horizon 2020 proposals of the island. According to the frequency of their participation, two kinds of stakeholders can be identified: one-time candidates who are trying to seize an opportunity or invited to join an already well established consortium; and enduring organizations that consider H2020 in integral part of their strategy and dedicate time and resources to increase their participation. Such behavior appears to be independent from the status of the organizations : 5 out of 7 companies are regular participants, 1 out of 2 public body and 1 out of 5 “other” institutions. To better understand the profiles and motives of these organizations, face to face interviews were conducted with the person in charge of their project.

a) Private companies

As seen in the analysis of the regional innovation system, private efforts remain so far very reduced due to the very nature of an economy, centered on a protected regional market which hinders the incentive to invest in perceived risky activities. As a consequence, the larger companies, ran through a financial logic, show no interest in H2020. SME’s participation remains equally limited: only one company has been submitting a proposal, the Groupe Dijoux. This 120 people company realizes a global turnover of 22 M€ through the installation of solar water systems, solar panels and self-consumption solutions.

The 4 other companies that submitted proposals on FP7 (1) and H2020 (3) presents a very homogenous profile : technology-oriented, they have been recently founded by former researchers or technology expert, maintain close ties with local research teams and the innovation support system and are aiming external markets. Considering their high capital-intensity and the vivid global competition that characterize their activities, such firms are currently engaged in fundraising, public and private. For the two companies that have been regularly submitting proposals to SME instruments (STEMCIS and REUNIWATT), the benefits are twofold: financial and reputational, a successful application being seen as a “seal of excellence”, which will reinforce their visibility & credibility vis à vis potential investors and public authorities managing ERDF.

All of the 4 present an extensive track record of participation in regional and national “innovation challenges” and dedicate a large share of their limited resources (excluding REUNIWATT, none of them employ more than 5 people) to such promotion activities.

Name	Domain	Activity	Nb of proposals	Nb of projects
PEACCEL	Bioinformatics	Protein engineering for chemical and medical applications	2	0
REUNIWATT	Renewable energy	Forecasting solutions for solar energy production	5	1
STEMCIS	Biotechnology	Valorization of stem cells from adipose tissue for regenerative medicine	2	0
TORSKAL	Biotechnology	Green chemistry production of nanotheranostics for oncology application	1	0

b) Innovation support services & clusters

On the 3 technical centers of the island (CRITT, CIRBAT and Hydro-Réunion), only the latter has been implicated in H2020. This structure, closed in 2018, was created by the merging of two formerly independent structures: ARDA (marine and terrestrial aquaculture) and ARVAM (valorization of marine biodiversity and biotechnologies) which were part of a common FP7 project : ECSAFESEAFOOD - *Priority environmental contaminants in seafood: safety assessment, impact and public perception*. They were invited to the project by one of the partner, which constituted an opportunity to consolidate and expend their European network. Such participation remained exceptional, and considered a bonus, vis à vis the core activities of the structure, which necessitates time and resources.

Only one business cluster, Témergie, did unsuccessfully take part in the same proposal as Groupe Dijoux, which at the time occupied the presidency. Such lack of implication may look surprising for structures, specializing in innovation projects development and fundraising such as the “pole de compétitivité” Qualitropic, dedicated to tropical bioeconomy. Once again, they reflect the limited appetite for innovation and internationalization of the well-established firms that make of their adherents. Moreover, in a context of easily accessible ERDF funds, H2020 is neither seen as an attractive funding source for the projects developed, nor for the clusters themselves, whose costs of operation rely heavily and structurally on public subsidies.

c) Regional agencies

In contrast to private entities, three regional agencies have been active so far. One unsuccessfully : the local public company “Energies Réunion”; and two successfully : the regional agency for urbanism (Agorah) and the regional agency for development, innovation and investment, Nexa.

Agorah contributed to a CSA project dedicated to urban strategies for waste management in tourist cities, which brought together several local authorities and agencies involved in urban planning. Its implication was made possible through the outermost regions

network, the project being coordinated by the Canary islands, which invited other partners. Currently, Horizon 2020 does not constitute a priority for the agency, which focuses on “its regional objectives”

The implication of Nexa in H2020 has been progressive. As mentioned earlier, since 2013 the agency promotes and supports the participation to framework programme, as a mean to integrate La Réunion in major European research and innovation networks and reach the critical masses necessary to build competitive advantages. Though Nexa had been developing an expertise in project development & management and strong connections with potential EU partners, it did not candidate until 2016. The shift was motivated by the will to reinforce collaborations with other policy makers to accelerate the island’s transition toward a more resilient and ecological development model. To that end, Nexa’s been part of a CSA dedicated to the development of regional synergies for circular economy (SCREEN) and candidate to two other proposals. Its implication in Forward is a mean to expand and deepen collaborations with outermost regions and to design public policies and support services which can lead to a significant increase of La Réunion participation in Horizon Europe.

d) Public bodies

The participation of the Regional Council of La Réunion is focused on political cooperation with Outermost Regions and Territories to preserve and manage biodiversity. Since the beginning of the century, numerous initiatives were developed to that end :

- the BIORUP consortium Initiated by the French C3I group (gathering the CIRAD, INRA, IFREMER and IRD) and involving the regional governments of the Açores, Canary islands, and Madeira, this network was setup in 2002 to increase cooperation between France, Spain and Portugal and promote singular scientific assets from Outermost regions, mainly Biodiversity and Natural ecosystems conservation. The consortium produced an expression of interest in response to the call launched by the european commission in june 2002 to identify projects that could match the new instruments developed for the 6th FP (such as the ERA-NET) ;
- the ERUP study “Mieux connaître la place de la recherche et développement technologique dans les régions ultrapériphériques (RUP) de l’Europe et mieux les intégrer dans l’espace européen de la recherche” (Rapport Lengrand, Juillet 2002, <http://www.erup.org/>) ;
- the plan d’action pour la recherche commun aux 7 Régions ultrapériphériques européennes (Juin 2003)
- several international conferences in the Indian Ocean (2003), Amazonia (2003), Pacific (2004), ...
- the 2004 Communication from the Commission on “a stronger partnership strengthened for the outermost regions: assessment and prospects” which encouraged *“Projects to promote cooperation and the coordination of research activities and innovation (ERA-NET), a new feature of the sixth framework programme, are open to participation by at least three countries, which should*

encourage participation by the outermost regions and their integration into the European Research Area"

In response to this opportunity, the Regional Council submitted a proposal in 2005, which was not selected. Yet in 2006, the EC invited the consortium for a negotiation. During this negotiation phase, the Regional council received the help of the BIODIVERSA consortium (ERANET project aiming at "Consolidating the European Research Area on biodiversity and ecosystem services" funded in 2005). The NETBIOME project (2006-2012) which emerged from these discussions, brought together regional bodies from 5 member States, with the objective of structuring a network of regional research policies on biodiversity in the European tropical and subtropical regions and territories (Guadeloupe, Martinique, Guyane, La Réunion, Nouvelle-Calédonie, Polynésie Française, Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores, UK Overseas Territories, Netherlands Antilles), through improved knowledge and funding of both basic and applied research.

The core team of the consortium then developed a follow-up, the FP7-NETBIOME-CSA (2013-2016), a coordination and support action project led by FRCT from the Azores. In this second project, the Regional Council of La Reunion was the leader of the WP6 related to the sustainability of the network.

In 2015, the NETBIOME group joined the BIODIVERSA consortium for the 3rd phase of the project. Funded under the ERANET COFUND scheme of the Horizon 2020 programme, Biodiversa3 gathers 39 of the main biodiversity research funders in 24 different countries, both from the European mainland and overseas and aims at developing a sustainable mechanism to promote strategic cooperation in biodiversity research and related disciplines at a European scale. In this project, the regional council of La Reunion is co-leading a task in the workpackage 2 dedicated to OR and OCTs (WP led by REG GUA).

Individual's factors and representations

Most studies on FP participation focus on network, systemic or organizational determinants and privilege quantitative analysis based on large databases like CORDIS and ECORDA. Yet, the sum of individuals' profiles, strategies and (mis)perceptions can have a major influence on the regional performance taken as a whole. Taking advantage of the small size of OR innovation systems, Forward thus offered the opportunity to investigate three elements at the individual scale:

- the determinants of researchers' implication in FP, through semi-structured interviews questioning the patterns of success and failure as well as self-selection behavior;
- the perceptions of the regional participation through an online survey to better understand the beliefs and fears expressed by stakeholders as well as potential gaps with the facts highlighted through this analysis;
- the barriers and levers identified by the individuals questioned during both interviews and survey to design an action plan adapted to users' needs.

A - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

To increase the regional participation in Horizon 2020, a critical attention must be paid to the factors that influence individuals' decisions and capacities to apply. Based on the common methodology developed to conduct regional analyses, Nexa deployed 2 qualitative, interview-based, analyses.

The first investigated the existence of regularities and common traits among successful individuals and the characteristics of unsuccessful candidates to highlight the potential existence of a pattern of success or failure and prerequisites which could lead to a more effective supported service, concentrated on the candidates that present the highest chances of success.

The second questioned the "self-selection phenomenon" through which individuals decide not to submit proposals, either because of their perceived weaknesses and limited chances to be funded, or because they concentrate their efforts on other funding sources, despite their capacities to develop successful projects.

To that end, three groups of individuals from local research institutions and companies were constituted:

- Group A composed of researchers that participate or have participated to FP projects (FP7 and H2020)
- Group B composed of unsuccessful candidates to Horizon 2020
- Group C composed of not participating actors (self-selection) with high scientific production and/or with faculty responsibility (such as research group management)

21 face-to-face and semi-structured interviews were conducted, 9 with FP successful participants, 5 with FP unsuccessful candidates and 7 with FP non-applying candidates. The groups' characteristics are detailed below:

Interviewees' characteristics :

Group	Number	FP7/ H2020	Organisation	Average number of years since phD graduation
Group A	9 2 Females, 7 Males	3 FP7 6 H2020	University : 4 Research centers : 2 Private companies : 1 Other : 1	22,4
Group B	5 1 Female, 4 Males	0 FP7 5 H2020	University : 5	16,2
Group C	7 : 3 Females, 4 Males	0 H2020 / 0 FP7	5 from university 1 from IRD 1 from CIRAD	NA

1) Patterns of success and failure

The first sets of interviews aimed at better understanding the patterns of success and failure (group A and B) by questioning two families of potential discriminative traits. On the one hand, individual capacities, measured by :

- scientific excellence, quantified by the total number of publications and the H index
- mobility profile, described by the fact that the candidate has or not obtained her/his PhD in the institution (s)he currently works for, and (s)he has or not a national and/or international experience (for a short (1-2 years), medium (2-5 years) or a long period (>5years))
- FP knowledge, determined by the number of FP projects the candidate was involved in during her/his career, the fact that (s)he is registered as an expert in the EC database and has participated to proposal evaluations for the EC

On the other hand, the way the project development was conducted:

- built or not on an existing network
- central/secondary role taken by the candidate in the proposal building,
- implementation of lobbying activities
- support from a public service or private consultant

The results of such interviews appeared insufficient to determine whether the determinants identified by the literature apply or not; since the two groups shared many similarities. Successful and failing candidates indeed show a close level of scientific productivity measured by the rates of publications and H-index. Little difference can also be found in terms of mobility experiences: 1 of the 5 unsuccessful candidates obtained its PhD in its current organization, compared to 2 out of 7 successful candidates. In both groups, such experience rarely led to the development of FP projects: only 2 candidates were involved in projects developed abroad, 1 from each reference group. The knowledge of FP procedures could not be tested, since none of the interviewees registered as an evaluation expert for the European Commission or contributed to the evaluation of a FP project in their career.

The comparison of the two groups is instructive on the impact of networks. Indeed, 80% of the unsuccessful researchers built projects with their preexisting networks, compared to 55% of the successful group. This shows that relying on existing networks is not a sufficient condition to ensure participation, if such network does not include highly successful organizations which are likely to develop more projects. The gap may also illustrate the capacity of regional stakeholders to integrate existing consortia, and thus to be recognized as valuable, competitive partners.

Two main differences were identified between the two groups. First, a larger number of successful candidates played a more prominent role in the development of the projects (87%) than failing participants (40%). Secondly, successful candidates mobilize more frequently support services (56% vs 20%) and lobbying activities (78% vs. 20%), that unsuccessful candidates; confirming the hypothesis according to which many unsuccessful proposals are the consequence of late-stage project development, lacking the required preparation time.

2) Analysis of self-selection behaviors

The second set of interviews, conducted with group C, aimed at testing frequently invoked causes that prevent researchers from applying to FP. Based on a previous survey conducted by the Nexa in 2018 with 60 respondents and also on regular feedbacks from researchers, a questionnaire with 16 direct questions was built investigating the:

- interest for EU level cooperation
- perception of one's own capacities (and English level)
- level of FP knowledge
- interest in FP
- access to resources and support

For each question, interviewees were to indicate if they agree or not with the statement. The selected group for self-selection presented an average citable citations of 47,7 +/- 30 and an average H index of 20,8 +/-11,9¹, it included 3 Research group directors and 1 Master

¹ * The number of citable publications and the H index of the non-applying candidates are not statically different from the successful or failing individuals (T-Test).

degree teaching manager. Interestingly, the 7 individuals have a number of citable citations and an H-index similar to the groups of successful and failing candidates. Further characteristics are detailed in the table below:

Self-selection group characteristics :

M/F	Scientific Domain	Panel	Organisation	Number of citable publications*	H index*	Connected to international network
F	Life Sciences	Health	IRD	32	18	Yes
M	Life Sciences	Ecology	University	85	27	Yes
M	Life Sciences	Ecology	CIRAD	95	38	Yes
M	Physical sciences and Engineering	Physics	University	16	8	No
F	Social Sciences and Humanities	Literature	University	40	NA	Yes
F	Social Sciences and Humanities	Education	University	26	13	Yes
M	Social Sciences and Humanities	Sociology	University	40	No	Yes

The 16 questions were precious to better understand the motives and the obstacles encountered by local researchers. They first deconstruct established representations, according to which researchers are not willing or capable to engage in FP projects.

First, all interviewees share the importance of developing collaborative research at European level. Such position contrasts with the high dominance of mainland France in existing partnerships as well as with well-established discourses and policies which consider that the priority should be put on regional integration, to make La Réunion the “European knowledge hub of the South-West Indian Ocean”. Only 1 of the 6 interviewees mentioned that “*La Réunion shared more common interests with organizations from the Indian Ocean zone than with European mainland partners*”; and only 2 “*preferred working with high level organization outside Europe*”.

They also question a common stance, often reaffirmed to explain the limited participation of La Réunion in FP: the lack of appropriate calls in line with the singular fields of interest/expertise of the island. Only one researcher agreed with the statement “*my research fields do not represent any interest for Europeans or my scientific domain is not represented*”

in FP programmes". Such surprising result may stem from our sample or from the interview conditions (face to face interview with a European project manager).

According to the interviews, the limited involvement in FP projects does not come either from a lack of capacities. Only 2 out of 6 respondents considered her/his level of scientific excellence insufficient regarding the global competition to integrate a consortium. Interestingly the 2 positive answers came from researchers involved in humanities and social sciences. The ability to connect to promising consortia was not supported either : only 2 of the 6 respondents (once again in HSS) agreed with the proposition "I do not have the right networks for this type of projects".

Conversely, the analysis highlights some key obstacles.

First, the level of English may still contribute to explain individual reluctance to apply to FP. On the 6 respondents (one did not answer the question), 3 considers that English is problematic and 3 not.

Second, a global lack of knowledge of FP, which was already pointed in an internal survey conducted in 2018 which showed the pervasiveness of preconceived ideas. On the seven respondents, 3 consider not to have sufficient knowledge on FP. These three individuals also think that H2020 is only built for big organizations, and two of them agreed with the statement that "*Horizon 2020 does not fund basic research but only applied research*". Interestingly, out of the four people considering having knowledge on FP, three also think that H2020 does not fund basic research. Third, FP may not be the adequate tool for some scientific fields. One sociologist explained that his field of research is divided into geographical schools, leading francophone sociologists to publish mainly in French with their homologues from France, Canada Switzerland. Moreover, he indicated that, at the national level, the career development is based on publications in francophone reviews and on the ability to get competitive national funds. This researcher even acknowledged that he wasn't aware if an active European network existed in his field.

Fourth, FP are facing the competition of large, easily accessible, less competitive regional funds, supported by ERDF. Though only half of the interviewees consider that the time dedicated to build a project is too important in comparison with the chances of success, 5 out 7 people indicated that the efforts required to enter FP (mastering the programme, building a winning consortium) are too demanding. One researcher mentioned that entering FP must be seen as a real research-behavioral change with an important conversion cost, particularly for "elder" researchers. Five interviewees totally agreed on the idea that the access to other less competitive funds such as ERDF, ANR (national funds) or CIR prevent them from applying to FP.

Fifth, researchers consider that the organization they work for do not ease the participation with adequate resources and supports. Five respondents reported not having sufficient time or being overworked. The lack of time is indeed a very common barrier evocated to explain the weak participation to H2020 (85% of the survey respondents on Norwegian participation in Horizon 2020). Besides the lack of resources or institutional choices which reduce the available time for research activity, the very attention paid to FP

should be questioned. Four respondents affirmed that FP projects do not constitute a priority for the organization at the institutional level (governance); among them, 3 considered that they don't have access to the appropriate resources, needed to apply. Interestingly, on the 3 respondents estimating that FP participation is a priority for their organization, 2 mentioned to be too overwhelmed to participate, disconnecting their relative overwork from their organization's strategy. As specified by one of the interviewee, *"FP participation is actually encouraged by my institution, [but] it is in addition of what I already do on ERDF funding and the latter takes a majority of my time"*. One researcher explained that *"There are not a lot of incentives to support researchers effort to develop European collaborative programmes"* while another stated *"The support I receive for the running of my ANR research programme is absent and the requested internal administrative effort is extremely time consuming"*. Finally, the 3 interviewees that are connected to national research centers (one of them belongs to a joint research unit with a national organization and the other two are agents of a national organization) agreed that their participation depend on the national strategy and to a national centre that centralizes all proposal initiatives.

One last hypothesis to be tested concerned the potential lack of resources and support.

To summarize, we can note that the 3 categories of stakeholders express the same will to collaborate and present similar characteristics (or non-significant differences) in terms of: scientific capacity, international connections / mobility, English level, knowledge of H2020.

These individual characteristics can influence the participation to FP, however and according to the above analyses, the patterns of success & failure and self-selection behaviors seem to be mainly and largely determined by extra individual settings or causes influencing the decisions of the individuals. Indeed, our analyses seem to show that inadequate work organizations, a lack of institutional strategy in favor of Horizon 2020 and adequate support services may deter individual from applying, since do not feel like they enjoy the means and support to succeed and manage their projects. The lack of ambition, means and incentives to conduct competitive research projects and integrate competitive networks, at research organization's level as well as at territorial level, also prevent individuals from acquiring the necessary will and ways for a competitive participation. These extra individual causes hence appear to take a more important role, nurturing self-selection mechanisms and driving the components of the individual's patterns of success & failure more than individual stories or characteristics themselves.

B - Questioning regional representations, lessons learnt from the survey

In addition to the interviews, a consultation was conducted to map and assess perceptions on FP participation and regional performance through an online survey. Such survey questioned both the representations of stakeholders on the factors that influence the participation in the Framework programmes (taken globally) as well as the specific factors that affect the performance of La Réunion. The survey was a self-administrated questionnaire submitted to actors through internet and was composed of 15 closed questions on the perceived performance of La Reunion in FP participation and on knowledge about the determinants that affect FP participation. Respondents were also asked to freely express themselves on the main obstacles and levers to FP.

59 people provided their inputs: 38 public researchers, 11 private companies (CEO or employee), 7 employees of facilitators/innovation intermediaries, 3 members of public administration.

1) Level of FP knowledge in the respondents

The first question of the survey reveals the level of FP knowledge in our sample. Most of the respondents know about FP programmes: 69% of them have received emails, assisted to conference or participated to training sessions on FP (41 people) and 17% had tried to build or been part of a FP project (10 people). Only 8 people (14% of the respondents) had never heard of FP (4 out of 11 the private and 2 public researchers out of the 38 participating to the survey).

This reflects a similar situation pointed out at national level (France). Indeed, as shown in the "*Rapport sur la participation de la France au PCRI*": French public researchers are mostly aware of the opportunities offered in FP (>90% of research groups considered to have sufficient information about FP) but not the private sector (>50% of the private companies have never heard of FP programmes).

FP knowledge of the respondents to the survey

a: All respondents

b: According to category

2) Knowledge on the factors influencing FP participation

As described in the determinants section, FP participation is conditioned by different factors: access to competitive networks, R&I system performance, synergy/complementarity in public funds, organization's strategy and size... The survey was a great opportunity to question whether the actors were acculturated to this knowledge. 12 potential factors corresponding to 4 types of determinants (Regional system, networks, Organization, individual's capacities) were submitted to the respondents who were asked to assess whether each factor was influencing or not FP participation.

List of potential factors tested in the survey

Family	Factors
<i>Regional system</i>	Regional research performance (Scientific excellence)
	Attractiveness towards foreign researchers of the regional research system
	Implication of business sector in R&D expenditures
	Use of ERDF or regional policies as a lever for encouraging and building capacities for Horizon 2020 participation
<i>Networks</i>	Connection to the most Horizon 2020 successful institutions/networks
<i>Organization</i>	Size of research/innovation organizations
	Local organizations strategy and tools to encourage and ease the participation of candidates
	Quality of support services to develop and manage H2020 projects
<i>Individual capacities</i>	Scientific productivity of individual researchers
	International connections of individuals
	Knowledge of candidates about framework programs
	Relative attractiveness of Horizon 2020 compared to other available funding

Overall, the set of factors presented in the survey are considered having a strong or very strong influence by more than 50% of the respondents. However, three categories of factors can be distinguished among the respondents:

1) Determinants considered as strongly influential by more than 80% of the respondents:

- Quality of support services to develop and manage H2020 projects (83%)
- Regional research performance - Scientific excellence (81%)
- Connection to the most successful Horizon 2020 institutions/networks (80%)

2) Determinants seen as strongly influential by between 60 and 80% of the respondents:

- Attractiveness towards foreign researchers of the regional research system

- International connections of individuals
 - Knowledge of candidates about framework programs
 - Local organizations strategy and tools to encourage and ease the participation of candidates
 - Use of ERDF or regional policies as a lever for encouraging and building capacities for Horizon 2020 participation
- 3) Determinants considered as less influential :
- Size of research/innovation organizations
 - Implication of business sector in R&D expenditures
 - Scientific productivity of individual researchers
 - Relative attractiveness of Horizon 2020 compared to other available funding

Such results show that while some determinants underlined by the literature are clearly identified as important by the respondents (regional research system performance, connection to successful networks, etc.) others critical challenges remain out of the scope (size of the organizations, private sector implication in R&I, funds synergy, etc.).

The survey also reveals a marked tendency to preferentially point out systemic factors (regional system, networks, organizations) rather than individual factors. For instance, only 58% of the respondents considered “scientific productivity at individual level” as a determinant.

According to respondents, the most important factor (83%) is the quality of the support services. Considering the very low submission activity of La Réunion in Horizon 2020, such position may reveal the existence of strong self-selection behaviors, confirmed by the interviews : in response to the competitiveness of FP, stakeholders feel a strong need for efficient support, which according to the interviews is lacking in organizations that do not place Horizon 2020 at the core of their strategy.

If the quality of support services is underlined by both researchers and private companies, the latter also insist on the use of ERDF, while researchers predominately point out “the performance of the regional system and its attractiveness” (79%) and “the institutional strategies of organizations (75%)”

TOP 3 of factors for public researchers and private companies

We also analyzed if knowledge or experience in FP could modify how the actors perceive the level of influence of each factor. Interestingly, out of the 12 factors tested, 4 are particularly influenced by the level of FP knowledge:

1) Use of ERDF or regional policies as a lever for encouraging and building capacities for Horizon 2020 participation

If in principle, people believe that ERDF can be a lever (100% of respondents that never heard of FP agrees with this stand), having an experience with H2020 modifies such opinion: less than 40% of the FP experienced believe ERDF can be an important determinant in accessing Horizon 2020. This may either indicate that respondents did not perceive a positive synergy between the two funds, or that they perceive a potential substitution effect induced by the time and resources needed to manage an ERDF funded project.

2) Relative attractiveness of Horizon 2020 compared to other available funding

Most of individuals that do not know FP (90%) believe that the relative attractiveness of Horizon 2020 compare to other funding is an influential factor, unlike the respondents experienced in H2020 (only 20%). The latter thus appear to perceive the intrinsic value of the programmes. This shows that it is important to pursue the promotion of FP advantages and added-value in comparison to other funding to encourage participation.

3) Knowledge of candidates about FP

Near 90% of the respondents with no FP experiences and almost 80% of the one having followed trainings or heard about the programmes in some ways believe that knowing the programmes is crucial to increase participation. This is not the case for more than half of the experienced respondents. This illustrates self-selection behaviours preventing potential candidates from participating because they do not fully understand the programmes or feel like they have few chances to succeed.

4) Size of research/innovation organizations

60% of actors that do not know Horizon 2020 believe that the size does not matter, when they are 75% to believe so for experienced respondents.

3) Perception of the participation of La Reunion in FP

Besides testing the FP culture of regional stakeholders and its influence on participation, the survey offered the opportunity to evaluate their perceptions of the performance of La Réunion. To that end, two questions were introduced : "*According to you, how many Horizon 2020 funded projects include from La Reunion?*" "*Compared to average European regions, do you think this number of FP funded projects in La Reunion is low/in the average/high?*"

Overall, the respondents have a quite clear understanding of the participation and performance of La Réunion in H2020 program when compared to the global European participation. Indeed, less than 10% think that the island does not participate at all to Horizon 2020 and none thinks that the number of projects is above 50. Nonetheless, 66% of the respondents believe that La Réunion has been part in less than 10 projects and 27% estimate this number between 10 and 50. Interestingly, the 4 individuals believing that La Réunion does not participate at all in Horizon 2020 are public researchers.

Furthermore, the vast majority of the respondents (68%) believe that the number of projects involving La Réunion represents a « low » or a « very low » participation, 22 % think it corresponds to the average European participation and 10 %, more optimistic, thinks it is above the European average.

4) Perception of the determinants that influence La Reunion's participation in FP

In addition to the global performance, individuals were asked to evaluate the relative position of the island for the different factors that are reputed to condition a regional performance.

For all the factors (except « the use of ERDF ») more than half of the respondents believe that La Réunion is low performing or not performing at all on the main determinants. For the 4 following factors the performance of La Réunion is considered weak or very weak by 70% of the respondents:

- Implication of business sector in R&D expenditures (88% of the respondents)
- Size of research/innovation organisations (75%)
- Connection to the most Horizon 2020 successful institutions/networks (71%)
- Knowledge of candidates about framework programs (71%)

Marked differences can be noticed between the different categories of stakeholders : while respondents from the public administration appear more optimistic (9 of the 12 factors are considered satisfying or very satisfying), private companies stand out as particularly pessimistic. They consider that La Réunion is under performing in all factors (except for « the

use of ERDF »). Companies particularly agree (91%) on the weakness of the performance for the “implication of business sector in R&D expenditures” and the “Connection to the most Horizon 2020 successful institutions/networks”. Researchers present more heterogeneous positions; yet they tend to agree on 4 factors (with at least 70% of approval) regarding the low performance of La Réunion in the “implication of business sector in R&D expenditures” (87%), the “Size of research/innovation organisations” (76%), the “Knowledge of candidates about framework programs” (71%), and “connection to the most Horizon 2020 successful institutions/networks” (71%).

The level of knowledge and experience of FP also strongly modifies the perception.

- The great majority (80%) of respondents with a previous experience in FP indicate that La Réunion is well performing in terms of “regional research performance” (only an average of 40% of the other profiles shares this view). 67% of those H2020 experienced respondents think that when it comes to “scientific productivity of individuals researcher” La Réunion is also well performing, while only 35 % of the other profiles agree with such position.
- These same individuals also state that La Réunion is underperforming in terms of organizations’ strategies (100% respondents within this category agree); on the contrary 67% of the actors with none or little knowledge on Horizon 2020 consider that La Réunion is well performing in this matter.
- Finally, in regards to the «Use of ERDF», 75% of the actors having already developed a proposal and 100% of the ones that participated in a project believe that La Réunion is not performing when it comes to use ERDF as a lever. This is contradictory with the position of actors with no experience in FP, 60% of them estimating that La Réunion knows how to use the ERDF as lever to Horizon 2020.

In essence, the analysis of the perceptions shows that out of 12 factors, 3 are clearly identified as important determinants to FP participation by a great majority of the respondents : regional research performance, connection to the most Horizon 2020 successful institutions/networks and the attractiveness of the regional system. For all of these determinants La Réunion is perceived as low performing: less than one respondent out of two thinks that the research regional system is performing, 7 out of 10 believe that the connection to the important networks is insufficient, and 6 out of 10 that the regional system is not attractive.

Other factors essential for the participation in FP, are less clearly acknowledged, in particular the size of the organizations or the dynamics of the private sector (only 59% and 51 % of the respondents qualify them as influential). Nonetheless, 75% of the respondents deem the size of the organizations as insufficient in La Réunion and 91% of them believe that the implication of business sector in R&D expenditures is not satisfying. This demonstrates a good understanding by the respondents of the gap between the situation in La Reunion and the European standards.

Finally, this study also shows that the synergy between H2020 and ERDF is a relatively badly understood concept. Indeed only 64% of the respondents think synergy can be an influential determinant in the participation to FP and nearly 60% of the actors believe that ERDF is rightfully used as a lever, this falls to 10% when questioning actors with FP experience. The lever effect of ERDF is not thus perceived as an important determinant when developing proposals.

C - Perceived barriers and levers to H2020 participation

Perceived barriers and levers OR R&I community members often depict FP as too complicated and unsuited to local situations and realities, generating a lack of ambition and involvement. Though poorly studied and often underestimated, beliefs and fears constitute powerful obstacles to H2020 access and overcoming them can be energy and time consuming. They are also critical to adjust design and implement an action plan that addresses the common obstacles identified by stakeholders, which have an immediate impact on their willingness to engage in, and experience of, Horizon 2020. To analyse such obstacles and levers, specific questions were thus introduced in the 21 semi-structured interviews and self-administrated survey.

1) Analysis of the perception of the perception of the respondents to the survey

Through two open-ended questions, survey's respondents were questioned about the main obstacles and levers that should be activated in order to increase Horizon 2020 participation. 258 verbatim were collected and analyzed, leading to the identification of 8 types of obstacles (based on 144 ideas extracted) and 7 types of levers (based on 114 ideas). Four types of obstacles are particularly cited by the respondents:

- 1) The absence of strategies within the organisations towards Horizon 2020 participation (20% of the citations); accurately “lack of institutional supports”, “lack of H2020 culture at institutional level”;
- 2) The lack and quality of support (20% of citations) of two different types (1) support for the building of FP projects, (2) administrative and technical support within research groups. This later is a crucial obstacle that was also indicated during the interviews and that should be addressed. Indeed, the lack of support forces researchers to take on those activities (technical and administrative) themselves which leaves them with little time to engage themselves in research.
- 3) The lack of knowledge and know-how of individuals in terms of H2020 projects (18%) generally expressed along a need for FP support;
- 4) Underperforming Research and Innovation system (18%) and in particular the quality of research. Indeed, two third of the citations mentioning the low performance of the R&I system concerns the research component).

Interestingly, geographical isolation and the lack of lobbying are often mentioned by governance of institutions and other decision makers however in this survey, those two obstacles are not largely indicated and they only recall for 6 and 3 %.

In an almost symmetrical manner, the main levers mentioned by the respondents are: 1) strong institutional strategies with a clear ambition toward H2020 (23%), 2) improving research support services (23%) especially those allowing researchers to dedicate time for research work and develop research projects; and 3) raising H2020 awareness and proposal development trainings including opportunities watch (19%)

In essence, the survey reveals several important lessons and inter-dependence on the perception of the respondents that needs to be appropriately addressed in order to increase the participation to FP:

- 1) A strong need for institutional incentives, translated in the respondents answers by more “communication on the interest and objectives” and “practical levers” ;
- 2) A need for a steady targeted watch and opportunities identification and the necessity to clarify the confusion between FP projects and ERDF projects. This confusion is mainly due to the terminology «European projects» that does not allow to differentiate FP competitive projects financed by the European commission from projects locally funded on European funds such as ESIF. The survey actually collected citations such as «ERDF financing is not adapted to research activities», «it seems as difficult to carry out a H2020 projects as it is to carry an ERDF project», «it should not be required to provide 3 quotations for each foreseen expenditures». Among the individuals mixing up the two programmes, a fair number report issues with administrative tasks for project development or their implementation. Thus, difficulties experienced with ERDF projects are transferred on H2020 programme even when actors do not have knowledge of FP procedures; this lack of knowledge increase self-selection.
- 3) A need for empowerment of the researchers: in one hand projects development support and a better knowledge of FP opportunities are perceived as pillars of the participation; on the other hand according to a large number of respondents being aware of FP opportunities, building proposals and identifying networks are not part of their job, as researchers.

2) Analysis of obstacles and levers defined during the interviews

During the interviews, the individuals were asked to freely express themselves about the main obstacles to address and levers to activate in order to increase FP participation of La Reunion. We therefore collected 113 statements corresponding to obstacles and 86 corresponding to levers, which we divided into four types of barriers: “regional policies”; “networks”; “organization”; “individual capacities”.

a) Obstacles mentioned

On the 113 statements, almost half of them (48) concern obstacles dealing with their own institutions’ organizations or support.

Out of those 48, 30 occurrences point out the “*lack of individual’s time due to establishment bad work organization*”. Indeed, two third of the interviewees evoke this problem as a main barrier, speaking about “*administrative burden*”, “*having too many responsibilities*”, “*too much teaching activity*”, “*no time for research*”... and this barrier represents a common and clear concern whatever the interviewee profile (successful, unsuccessful and non-applying candidates). At the organization's level, in this context of “*lack of time*”, interviewees also evoke that the “*lack of FP institutional ambition and strategy*” prevents them from participating, as well the “*in-adaptation of the support services*” and the “*lack of human resources in the lab*”.

Most of the successful candidates clearly share that their successful participation was not due to the support of their institutions, which moreover imposed unnecessary burden to such candidates. For them, the major barriers lie within “*in-adapted support services*” and “*lack of FP institutional strategy*”. Non applying candidates are fully aware of those barriers : they insist on upstream aspects of the participation with “*lack of adapted human resources*” and “*lack of individuals time due to establishment bad work organization*” preventing them from participating. For them, the feedbacks from colleagues and their own experiences on other competitive calls and projects generate an anxiety on the difficulties they may be facing while carrying out an FP project. Interestingly, unsuccessful candidates do not mention at all “*in-adapted support services*” or “*lack of human resources in the lab*” but more upstream barriers such as “*lack of institutional ambition & strategy*” and “*individual time and institution bad work organisation*”. This shows that they think their non-participation is due to systemic problems rather than project's quality.

Three other categories of barriers are depicted by the researchers: Individual capacities (23 statements), Network (22 statements) and Regional policies (20 statements),

In terms of individual capacities, interviewees mention (i) the lack of engagement/interest in fundraising of some researchers - and for some, in research itself (“*Only one third of my lab colleagues are interested in doing research, some are focused on teaching activities*”), (ii) the lack of FP knowledge (“*we need to be trained in proposal writing*”) and a tendency to self-inhibition (“*we are too small to coordinate*”, “*English level is too low*”). They recall they interest to engage in FP, though it is not their number 1 priority at the moment. These barriers are quite well mentioned by the three profiles.

Regarding the barriers related to Network (22 statements), successful candidates depict the successive obstacles to connection: first, the lack of visibility/reputation of the institution, second, the difficulties to identify the right networks/partners, then the difficulties to connect / engage in networking activities and finally the difficulties to transform networks in projects. The other interviewees focus their analysis on the difficulties to connect / engage in networking activities (*physical distance is an obstacle to maintain interpersonnal collaborations*), showing that less experienced individuals are as aware of the steps to develop distant and foreign collaborations. This is to be linked to the fact that local funds attribution do not depends on the capacity to develop networks, but rather, *local ERDF managing authority does not allow the funding of foreign partners*.

Regional policies are actually fairly mentioned by the interviewees (20 statements). One main political determinant is the “ERDF antagonism effect” (12 occurrences), which is the second main evoked from all barriers with 12 occurrences. Indeed, the lack of synergy between ESIF and H2020 is well perceived by the actors : “*ERDF funded projects induces “un repli sur soi”, “it inhibits visibility and collaborations development*”. Many interviewees actually invoked to be too busy working on ESIF projects to start collaborations at EU level (*EDRF funded projects that I'm running now give little time to develop H2020 projects*) and that the abundance of ERDF funds without scientific policy and vision at regional level tends to lead to research fragmentation (“*There is a lack of coordination of research effort in a*

common strategy, we lack critical mass"). Although these "political" barriers are mentioned by all candidates, successful ones particularly insist on such factors.

The profile of the interviewee reveals the influence of a previous participation in FP on the perceived obstacles. Firstly successful candidates identify a larger number of obstacles (on all the families of obstacles) and point out mainly the lack of complementarity between ERDF and H2020 and the competitive approach between the two. Unsuccessful candidates are less aware of the obstacles and only mention 7 barriers out of the 14 extracted and mainly comment on lack of individual time and poor institutional organization. Self-selected or non-applying candidates are fully aware of the wide range of obstacles and like the successful candidates mention most of the barriers (12 out of 14); they are also particularly preoccupied by the lack of individuals' time and bad work's organizations.

b) Analysis of levers

As shown in the following figure, the most important family of levers to activate (most cited by the interviewees) deals with organizations strategy and support (31 verbatims out of 86) followed by networks issues (22), regional policies (15), and individuals capacities (15).

As expected, issues regarding the organizations gather the greatest concerns when it comes to barriers and the highest number of propositions when it comes to levers. Firstly, interviewees ask for adapted supported services (*"an H2020 experienced support team"*), which is the most cited of all levers. This is a call from all kind of profiles. Four other promising levers to activate within institutions are also praised by the interviewees : to have a clear and credible institutional ambition and strategy, to develop incentives to increase FP applications and implementation (*"FP participation could be facilitated through tools such adjusted teaching hours"*), to increase academic, technical and European staff in research lab (*"we should have dedicated project manager in the lab"*), to redirect internal mobility tools towards research/FP.

Successful candidates equally support the need for adapted support services and for a clear and credible institutional ambition and strategy favouring research and FP participation, highlighting the fact that participating in FP should not be the effort of a few lucky researchers but a global ambition carry out by all phases of the institutions and providing the appropriate means. This is also largely supported by both non-applying actors and unsuccessful candidates. Unsuccessful candidates in priority mention the need for "academic, technical and European staff in research lab" and "incentives and to increase FP participation and facilitates FP implementation", this is another reminder of the need to develop a vision

and strategy not only for FP but for research in general at institutional level. Interestingly, only non-applying candidates supported the idea to redirect internal tools towards research/FP impact mobilities, showing that incentives and coherent means can have a strong impact on self-eviction.

The second category of levers most brought up by the interviewee deals with networks issues. Most of them mention the organization of FP oriented event in Reunion ("*summer schools represent a great lever*") and the development of a marketing strategy as interesting levers ("*We need to develop a network of international key opinion leaders promoting reunion's capacities*"). Unsuccessful candidates also propose to develop international master training offers ("*We should develop Europe masters*") acknowledging the fact that networking should be approached globally and include in teaching activities for researchers and futures researchers. Building bridges with other community should be a priority for all academic and research components of the institutions allowing the development of a European networking culture.

Regional policies are the third category of levers identified during interviews. Interviewees request a clear synergy of funds between ERDF and FP, to build regional governance and to improve the ERDF implementation to support effectively research activities ("*EDRF should support long-term strategic programme of research groups*"). As one said, *it is crucial to raise awareness on international collaboration and FP of policy-makers and institutions' leaders*. Interestingly, the use of ERDF to build a limited number of excellence domains is identified as the main political lever for successful candidates, showing the impact of FP experiences and European collaborations on the perception of the global dynamics of research.

Within the "Individual capacities" category, developing researcher's skills through training appears to be decisive, for fundraising as well as for networking (train research and PhD students to build international networks). The promotion of role models is also mentioned but quite modestly.

Perceived levers according to the interviewee's profile

3) Conclusions

Whether from the interviews or the survey, personal interest for FP is often reaffirmed by individuals but the reasons advanced to explain the lack of FP participation, are often disconnected from individuals will or power. This could be a reflexion of self-criticism difficulties or indeed a consequences of a global system that tent to have become an obstacle to Horizon 2020 and that let very little place for individuals will to change the story.

For all types of questioned individuals whether from the survey or the 3 interview profiles, it emerges a deep craving for more means, and strategy with better organisation and stronger governance. This feeling reflects literature reviews and the findings of our analysis in a sense that good FP participation arises from a web of factors that can only be implemented with strong political will at all level of decisions followed by dedicated measures.

Ambition & Preliminary action plan

The multidimensional analysis conducted during more than six months thanks to Forward has offered a unique opportunity to better characterize and understand the participation of La Réunion in the Framework Programmes. Such participation appears particularly limited : 9 projects under FP7 and 13 under H2020 for a respective EU contribution of 3,6 and 1,8 M€. These scores position La Réunion on the 250th rank out of 274 Nuts 2 European regions. Expressed per capita, this contribution reaches 0,44 € per year under H2020, compared to an average score of 13,7 €, placing La Réunion in the 258th position. The limited participation is also illustrated by the reduced number of stakeholders involved: 3 organizations account for 75% of the proposals submitted by only 18 active organizations; and only 9 of them have effectively taken part in a successful proposal. Excepting 2 Regpot projects and one SME instrument, the role played by these organizations in the projects remain marginal, with no coordination role and 3,2% of the budget awarded to the project.

Such limited participation cannot be considered a natural consequence of an “island syndrome” or of unfavorable socio-economic or research & innovation capacities and results. The comparison with other European and Outermost regions which present close performance in these matters highlight the existence on a critical and so far unexplained under-participation of La Réunion. Considering the resources and capacities available on the island for the development of knowledge economy, the “normal” participation should indeed be 10 times larger : 3,8 € per capita, per year, rather than 0,44€ today.

To explain such paradox, the four main determinants identified by the literature on FP participation have been scrutinized and tested extensively: the integration in the European Research Area and connection to the most successful organizations that dominate the FP scene; the maturity, dynamic and effectiveness of the regional innovation system; the characteristics, strategy and policies of regional research and innovation organizations toward H2020; as well the individual factors which determines the will to apply or not to calls for projects (self-selection mechanism) and the chances of success.

A. Obstacles synthesis

The striking facts identified through data collection and analysis, face to face interviews, benchmarks and qualitative analysis can be summarized in three explanatory factors, inhibiting the participation :

- Public policies do not enough encourage and support the participation in FP
- La Réunion suffers from a lack of connection to major European networks
- Organizations and individual do not have the required resources to build competitive projects.

The causes and sub-causes of these factors as well as their consequences have been summarized in problem trees to facilitate their comprehension and propose a synthetic vision.

uch problem trees, defined through the diagnosis, were discussed with 17 regional stakeholders in a collective intelligence workshop organized on the 25th June 2019.

1) European, national and regional public policies do not enough support the participation of La Reunion in the European Research Area & Innovation Union

Public policies play a significant role in an economy which mostly relies on public expenditures and support. Yet, such policies so far fail to encourage the participation in Horizon 2020 because of three main factors.

First, knowledge economy remains a secondary priority on the regional agenda, in the absence of strong political leadership supporting the vision of a “smart & resilient island” and as a consequence of the influence of an established discourse which opposes economic convergence and innovation, the latter being seen as a far horizon which will come a reality and a priority, once the convergence with the EU will be achieved. The lack of importance attached to knowledge economy is itself reflected in the limited public resources dedicated to organize and accelerate the transition.

Second, these public resources dedicated to knowledge economy have yet not been transformed by the smart specialization approach. Though the island is engaged in an ambitious RIS3, to turn into an ecological and social resilience living lab, the strategy is not aligned with the allocation of public funds, which do not consider the integration in the ERA a strategic priority and remain allocated through instruments which are sometimes contradictory with the very objectives of RIS3, since they encourage the fragmentation of research and innovation efforts and the focalization on regional funds and activities.

Finally, easily accessible ERDF dotation leads to a powerful substitution effect, deterring organizations and stakeholders to engage in H2020 (self-selection) and are not used strategically to increase the participation, notably through the implementation of synergy of funds strategy.

The lack of adapted policies may result in three critical consequences : the lack of incentives to integrate the ERA; the incapacity to develop strong competitive advantages in a limited number of highly singular fields of expertise and as a consequence the risk of being marginalized and excluded from the “innovation market” in a world marked by an extreme polarization, where few highly attractive and competitive knowledge hubs concentrate most of the resources and capacities and peripheries are trapped in a vicious circle where the absence of critical masses hinders their competitiveness, which in turns reduces their attractiveness and their capacity to build critical masses...

La Reunion faces the risk of an increased marginalization in a world characterised by the extreme polarization of resources

The fragmentation of the R&I effort inhibits the emergence of critical masses and comparative advantages in key activities

Regional stakeholders feel no incentives to widen their horizon and collaborate with their European counterparts

Problem 1

European, national and regional public policies do not enough support the participation La Reunion in the European Research Area & Innovation Union

Knowledge economy remains a secondary priority

The RIS3 fails to transform the uses of public funds

There is a substitution effect between ESIF & FP

Weak/no political leadership on research & innovation and knowledge economy	Priority is given to economic convergence	No shared ambition for the integration of the ERA and the Innovation Union	RIS3 spirit is not shared	Easily accessible ESIF generate a self-selection mechanism	Lack of strategic use of ERDF to support FP Participation
Established « handicap discourse » vehicles a negative and inhibiting vision of the region's potential	Strong lobbies	Research policy is divided between national, Regional, managing authorities and research centers	Lack of preparation of ESIF programming	ESIF are less competitive, collaborative and more generous than H2020	Lack of knowledge on synergy of funds
Lack of alternative « desirable future » based on knowledge economy	Knowledge economy (RIS3) is seen as a threat to the established economy	Lack of comprehension of the importance of international connections to reach critical masses	ESIF « distribution culture » encourages the fragmentation of R&I activities	Access to ESIF is not conditioned to FP Participation	Investments in R&I infrastructures do not take into account H2020 or international uses/networks
Social & Economic emergencies tend to oppose convergence & innovation	Reduced % of ESIF dedicated to R&I compared to EU average	Integrating the ERA is not considered a prerequisite for scientific excellence	ESIF « consumption culture » supports the distribution of credits without an R&I oriented strategy	Funds are distributed to regional stakeholders to support their common expenses and investments	Funds are dedicated to events not to the development of networks
Lack of dialogue between science & Policy and between Science & Civil society - Quadruple Helix	Difficulty to identify the return on investment of R&I projects encourages the development of infrastructures	S3 mobilizes a minor share of the ESIF	Research infrastructures are not designed, as strategic, attractive assets	Lack of skills of managing authorities on R&I challenges	Strong lobbying from research institutions to fund « localized research » with little EU added value
					Lack of incentives and mini-schemes to support FP active stakeholders

2) A lack of connection of La Reunion to major European networks

Because of its competitive nature, the participation in the Framework Programme is dependent on cumulative effects : the most successful organizations/candidates present a higher probability to develop new successful projects or to integrate promising consortia, than external stakeholders, which lack the proper reputation. Horizon 2020 is thus sometimes labelled an “oligarchic club”, dominated by a reduced number of organizations. Being connected to such organizations is on the other hand a great lever to increase rapidly the regional participation. Yet at this stage, the connection remains inhibited by three main factors.

First, organizations present a limited interest for European collaborations, because of the historic ties and continuous collaboration with mainland France and the strong emphasis laid on regional collaboration (which itself do not lead to H2020 projects with third countries). Even if European collaborations may appear desirable, they are not supported by a powerful strategy, relying on adequate means and resources.

Second, the fields of excellence of the OR in general and La Réunion in specific suffer from a lack of visibility or recognition in the European Union. This invisibility stems from the difficulty to determine and market a limited number of singular domains (due to the high fragmentation of the research & innovation effort) and from the lack of outreach strategy to promote effectively such expertise.

Third, La Réunion presents a distinctive difficulty to capitalize on preexisting collaborations into effective and successful projects. Though the island is connected to major national and European organizations (3 out of the 6 main partners have obtained more than 100 Horizon projects), 90% of the collaborations developed lead to only one project.

The consequences of such lack of integration are straightforward: it inhibits the attractiveness of the island and thus the creation of critical mass (as described in problem 1); negatively affects the reputation of regional stakeholders who need to demonstrate their added value and dedicate more efforts to integrate consortia ; and compromises the capacity to position La Réunion as a knowledge hub in the Indian Ocean where European stakeholders could develop expertise adapted to tropical context.

Problem 2

There is a lack of connection of La Reunion to major European networks

3) Organizations & individuals do not have the resources to build competitive projects

The third obstacle concentrates on the limited capacities of regional organizations and stakeholders to engage in FP projects.

This phenomenon is first of all the consequence of a small and recent innovation system, characterized by a low level of tertiary education and limited resources available, as well as by a limited capacity to turn new ideas into concrete, innovative and competitive solutions.

Internally research and innovation organizations present a critical lack of skills on the European Union policies, standards and priorities and have not defined a smart strategy to support their participation in Horizon 2020. Such phenomenon is illustrated by the very limited number of organization which effectively submitted proposals during the two last periods.

The third explanation has been massively and regularly pointed out by the people interviewed who deplored the lack of fertile atmosphere encouraging the participation in FP. Conversely, regional organizations may encourage individual self-selections decisions and deter potential candidate from applying because their administrative and teaching obligations leave little time for research. Interviewees also insisted on the lack of promotion and incentives to participate in FP projects, leading to a general disinterest. Those who overcome the self-selection temptation have deplored the lack of professional training and support services which reinforce the chances of success.

Problem 3

Organizations & individuals don't have the resources to build competitive projects

During the workshop, each group were encouraged to transform the problem trees into solutions trees, proposing strategic and operational orientations to address the main blocking points and causes identified (The levers identified during the workshop are presented in Annex II).

These orientations were then explored by Nexa to define a roadmap, inspired by the other European experiences and best practices, to increase significantly the participation in Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. This roadmap, or preliminary action plan, relies on three pillars: reinforce the efficiency of the regional innovation system, develop a European ambition and culture in regional organizations and make FP participation desirable and achievable. The ambition and pillars have been shared with 16 representatives of the main research and innovation organizations and public institutions of the island in a second workshop organized on the 12th November 2019.

B. Priority 1 : Increase the performance of the regional R&I system

1) Current situation

If the R&I system in La Reunion is relatively young, its rapid development has led to a fragmented system composed of a broad number of research fields gathering few researchers, redundant & nonspecialized support services, and a weak and disconnected political coordination.

In addition, despite the established belief on "small size allows easier interknowledge", cooperation among private companies, among researchers from different areas, as well as between researchers and business sector remain weak. This situation, preventing the development of comparative advantages and innovation, hinders our ambition to turn La Réunion in a resilience living lab, able to produce solutions that not only addresses local challenges to reduce our dependency and vulnerability also the needs of exterior markets.

2) Objectives and actions

In order to structure an efficient research and innovation system, 3 strategic objectives are defined :

OS1.1 Coordinate research system at regional level

- Set up a research coordinating body gathering HEI, research organisations and regional authorities
- Set up a R&I policy lab that monitor and evaluate the R&I policy, provide data and formulate independent and evidence-based propositions to European, national and local authorities to develop adequate funding instruments
- Establish an assessment mechanism for organisations receiving institutional funding, based on core principles of international peer review

OS1.2 Build critical mass and develop excellence domains in research

- Redirect ERDF to fund long-term collaborative research programmes that bring together actors from the quadruple helix and that include roadmap for infrastructures, human resources (doctoral and post doctoral fellowships), mobility and equipment
- Develop a funding scheme to allow the creation of new, distinct research group led by young scientists and dedicated to high level frontier research in excellence domains
- Support participation in European and national calls for projects which allow networking, knowledge sharing, capacity building such as ITN, Chairs, Teaming, EUR, european partnerships, ...
- Support regional infrastructures as regards their participation in the European research infrastructures network (ESFRI roadmap)
- Encourage research governance to develop European standards in research activities regarding researchers recruitment (promote the «Human Resources Strategy For Researchers» labellisation), intellectual property, knowledge transfer, open access, gender equality, integration of gender dimension in research
- Use INTERREG V to build Excellence partnerships with third countries

OS1.3 Increase the involvement of all stakeholders, notably SMEs, in R&I

- Promote research and innovation culture through competitions, awards, exhibitions, workshops with adapted actions plans targeting youth, academics, businesses, consumers, end users, policy makers
- Build a regional technology and knowledge transfer system which focuses on excellence domains and connects to world-class partners
- Promote access of the R&I community to publicly funded research groups and infrastructures
- Further enhance the collaboration between academia and businesses by increasing public aid for collaborative innovative activities involving SMEs & academics

C. Priority 2 : Develop a European ambition and culture within organisations

1) Current situation

Academic and research collaborations are well developed in La Reunion but partnerships are mainly turned towards actors in mainland and from the regional basin (Mauritius, Madagascar, Comoros, South Africa, ...).

This lack of connection with European research centers is really damaging : it increases our remoteness from decision centers, it decreases impacts of our research results and diminishes our attractiveness to world-class researchers, investors and entrepreneurs. In a world where talents and capital are concentrated in a few hubs at global scale, La Reunion is being marginalized.

2) Objectives and actions

In order to break out the vicious circle, organisations must develop a European ambition and culture. To this end, three strategic objectives are pursued :

OS2.1 Develop funding mechanisms which supports connexion to European partners

- Subject public aid to HEI et REC to a clear FP-oriented strategy with quantified objectives
- Co-design and implement a public support for researchers and entrepreneurs dedicated to "in & out" european mobility, for short, mid and long term exchanges

OS2.2 Promote excellence domains and R&I capacities to targeted audience

- Identify the most interesting networks to work with in each Excellence domain and develop a targeted outreach strategy
- Increase the visibility of capacities through a dedicated web portal and the organisation of thematic congress with targeted european partners
- Strengthen the presence of La Reunion's R&I stakeholders in European decision-making circles (ERRIN, EUA, European sectorial federations,...) and actively participate in the FP policy dialogue regarding EU-Africa partnerships
- Support participation to international brokerage events

OS2.3 Support organisations in the definition of an international strategy aiming at integrating performant European networks

- Raise desire for Europe through the promotion of positive experiences and benefits (book of projects, poster campains, ...)
- Support stakeholders in the identification of valuable partners and in a connexion strategy, notably Infrastructures, Research groups, Clusters and SMEs (through the Europe Enterprise Network)
- Train individuals to develop a European culture (European policies knowledge, networking & communication skills, on-line reputation tools,...)

D. Priority 3 : Make FP participation desirable and achievable

1) Current situation

If most of individuals have the will and the capacities to engage themselves in competitive projects, too many barriers stop them from even applying : overwhelming workload, apprehension due to previous experience of inadequate/nonexistent support, lack of incentives, preconceived ideas on opportunities, lack of knowledge on FP project cycle development... This self selection phenomenon dramatically hinders the participation of La Reunion to FP. It is therefore highly important to propose a project development pathway which improves user experience, aligned with their mission and vision.

2) Objectives and actions

To make FP participation desirable and achievable, three strategic objectives are targeted :

OS3.1 Develop and coordinate a Reunion Europe network

- Allocate in each research group a FP-skilled european project engineer
- Coordinate effort and share resources for the promotion and training for FP participation

OS3.2 Anticipate project development

- Empower actors to monitor FP consortia and calls for opportunities
- Take part to key networks to influence calls for proposals and detect emerging consortia in Excellence domains
- Capitalize on existing European networks involving partners from La Reunion to build competitive consortia

OS3.3 Make the project development cycle 100% winning

- Propose a structured, effective and engaging support service maximizing chance of success
- Encourage organisations to develop incentives to facilitate project development and implementation such as reduction of teaching/administrative activities, allowances,
- Fund with ERDF high-quality mono-beneficiary proposals which reached the "Seal of Excellence" but failed to be funded
- Offer a complementary funding to FP successful beneficiaries to be used to increase the project impacts in terms of research potential (10% of the total amount obtained from EC)

To convert this preliminary action plan into S.M.A.R.T. objectives, several redaction committees involving the local R&I community will be set up in the next weeks.

Annexes

Annex I - List of participants to interviews and workshops

AGORAH	David Daniel
ARMEFLHOR	Insa Guillaume
BRGM	Chaput Marie
Centre hospitalier Universitaire de La Réunion	Randrianaivo Hanitra
Centre hospitalier Universitaire de La Réunion	Medjane Samir
CIC-EC	Marimoutou Catherine
CIRAD	Jeuffrault Eric
CIRAD	Rouget Mathieu
CITEB	Turquet Jean
DRRT	Hiol Abel
DRRT	Conruyt Noël
IFREMER	Duval Magali
IRD	Chabanet Pascale
MEDEF	Beton Alexandre
OSU-R / UR	Cammass Jean-Pierre
OSU-R / UR	Duflot Valentin
QUALITROPIC	Grondin Didier
QUALITROPIC	Tostain Graziella
REGION REUNION	Charritat Catherine
REGION REUNION	Irissin Josiane
REGION REUNION	Pothier Jean-Pierre
REUNIWATT	Schmutz Nicolas
Université de La Réunion	Balcou-Debussche Maryvette
Université de La Réunion	Bastide Alain
Université de La Réunion	Benne Michel
Université de La Réunion	Bialecki Anne
Université de La Réunion	Brioude Jérôme
Université de La Réunion	Castaing-Lavignottes Jean
Université de La Réunion	Chabriat Jean-Pierre
Université de La Réunion	Dietrich Muriel
Université de La Réunion	Duboin Corinne
Université de La Réunion	Duret Pascal
Université de La Réunion	Geoffroy Sophie
Université de La Réunion	Lajoie Gilles
Université de La Réunion	Mora Rey Juan
Université de La Réunion	Morel Béatrice
Université de La Réunion	Payet Jean-Philippe
Université de La Réunion	Poussier Stéphane
Université de La Réunion	Roche Marjolaine
Université de La Réunion	Strasberg Dominique
Université de La Réunion	Tortosa Pablo

Annex II - List of levers identified during workshops

GROUP 1 - Increase the competitiveness of Research

Build critical mass in the domains of excellence

- Develop a university policy oriented towards research
- Adopt within the decision bodies of the research institutions clear orientations / priorities concerning research and education
- Design educational programs (especially L1) to make them rely more on teaching oriented profiles than on researchers
- Develop an internal policy with multi annual funding in line with the orientations
- Evaluate the impact of internal policies on research
- Revise the organisation of research support activities (work distribution and recruitment distribution, training in light of the evolution of professional activities etc....)
- Establish a regional organisation for scientific monitoring scientific research
- Develop a scientific strategy with appropriate means in favour of the development of excellence and critical mass
- Evaluate the impact of research policies of each research institutions in terms of contribution to the development of critical mass in the domains of excellence
- Support the development of a quality control policy for the research produced in the region
- Favour the concentration of means around a few domains of excellence
- Bring up to date the Joint-research units (JRU) development strategy and support research groups in developing excellence according to their status (local research group not integrated in a JRU, research group transitioning to integrate a JRU, established JRU)
- Inspired research group with projects examples they could have developed
- Make compulsory independent scientific councils on a yearly basis for all research groups
- Offer incentive to support concentration (administrative support if merging...) and discourage actions that will participate to the breaking up of the research effort (financial penalty on the allocated fund)

Develop attractiveness policy

- Develop collaborations with existing international excellence networks
- Develop an integrated approach to ease collaboration (short scientific exchange, then longer mobility)
- Revise criteria for the distribution of "authorisation releasing from teaching hours obligations" by integrating a priority for researchers aiming at developing European projects with excellence research centres
- Support the identification of key partners to connect with and coach local actors on networking
- Ease and encourage the recruitment of talented applicants at international level as well
- Establish several tools allowing short incoming mobility to test future potential candidates
- Integrate in the institutions strategy a human resources policy based on excellence
- Integrate more transparency and advance planning in all steps of the recruitment process
- Train and raise awareness staff from the human resources management on recruitment impacts

- Strengthen the numbers and the quality of the publications in the domains of excellence
- Increase support staff within the laboratories, offer training in relation to the evolution of the profession
- Offers solutions to researchers that are not publishing : support to come back in the research pool or adapt the position (PRAG)
- Support research via human resources policy for research (chairs, post doc, ATER...)
- Update equipment of research group to make sure we stay competitive

GROUP 2 - Increase the participation and the involvement of Reunionese actors in European Research network of excellence

Strengthen existing networks and develop collaborative projects

- Strengthen existing networks and encourage/ease the development of new collaborations
- Build adapted financing schemes that will allow researchers to meet with partners at European level to develop collaborations and projects
- Develop a support service action aiming at identifying the right networks with and for researchers, research groups and institutions in their field of expertise
- Develop networking itineraries to ensure existing collaborations are turned into long-lasting work relationships (tools guide for larger cooperation agreements with multi layers collaboration such as co-directed thesis, research projects, research exchanges (erasmus), master programs)
- Free researchers time to develop new collaborations by rethinking administrative and teaching responsibilities distribution. Build tools such as "teaching hours delegations" dedicated to give the time and opportunity to develop collaborations
- Make network development at EU level a priority for the region by integrating it as a key criterion when evaluating and attributing local funds (Open ERDF funding to European partners to initiate new collaborations, prioritise the financing of international co-supervision of thesis etc...)
- Strengthen the capacities and will to connect to European partners among local actors
- Equip institutions with long term strategies with objectives, means and incentives for the development of connections with European research excellence hubs
- Increase the will to develop one's position in network by promoting existing successful local stories (book of project, testimonies os succesful participations)
- Integrate in the contracts biding the different organisations which run a joint research unit the importance to integrate local actors in their European networks and collaborative projects
- Raise awareness and strengthen the knowledge of local actors on the necessity to be connected to international research excellence hubs and on the expected risk with systemic marginalisation (Develop networking culture)
- Strengthen knowledge of local actors about collaborative programmes and networking strategies at individuals or research groups level through trainings
- Strengthen the positioning of Reunion actors in collaborative projects and increase the participation
- Build a longer term vision for projects participation in order to be prepare, have the time to connect with the right networks and propose a qualitative lead and support service to potential partners
- Develop solutions to be more present in important decisions circles of the European institutions (Researchers enlisted as evaluation experts for the commission, or in other projects advisory board,

lobby activities for work programme and projects development, info days participations)

- In the institutions, develop a qualitative and efficient services for the management and implementation of research projects to reassure researchers and encourage them to take the lead on collaborative projects
- Locally initiate qualitative collaborative projects to actively take part in the dynamic and be invited in return
- When invited to participate in collaborative projects researcher should take a more important role (increase funding share, activities and responsibilities such as WP or task leaders)

Strengthen the perception of Reunion as high-quality partners

- Make Reunionese research more visible and attractive
- Design schemes and rethink human resources strategies to attract « key opinions leader » in local institutions
- Develop institutional strategies to promote and disseminate Reunion research capacities to the targeted excellence hubs (Infra, territoire-laboratoire, High impacts publications, flagship projects)
- Organise promotion events in a coordinated manner and according to the objectives of the strategy and ensure maximum visibility
- To increase Reunion recognition and identification highlight the participation of local institutions in collaborative projects (avoid third parties status)
- Strengthen the international reconnection of Reunionese research
- Develop a territorial and global vision for local research organised around key domain of excellence in order to create expertise centres internationally renowned
- Finance chairs of excellence increase critical mass and develop pluridisciplinary research with key project/demonstrators in the excellence research domains of the territory
- Increase the number of citable citations and projects notably from the excellence pillar (ERC, Marie Curie)

GROUP 3 - Make H2020 a public policy priority

Build a shared ambition for H2020

- Establish a “Regional Research Council”
- Concentrate public support on the most promising research priorities
- Contractualize with research organisms to orient their activity toward H2020.
- Coordinate national, regional and institutions policies
- Promote the added value of H2020 (through storytelling)
- Illustrate H2020 participation through concrete stories, testimony
- Sensibilize local stakeholders to the challenges of European integration / international connection

ERDF as a lever for Horizon 2020 participation

- Create a dedicated ERDF instrument to support the development of H2020 Projects
- Dedicate an ERDF envelope to H2020
- Finance the time needed to develop a project
- Introduce incentives and penalties on ERDF mobilization
- Align the evaluation criteria on H2020 evaluation
- Condition infrastructure support to H2020 participation
- Finance research centres and programs on a long term development plan, which includes a FP participation strategy
- Mobilize European experts / externalize the evaluation to an independent authority

Use public funds to support the integration in global networks

- Increase the synergy between local funds and H2020 (era-net)
- Increase the use of ERA-net type instruments
- Promotion Reunion island research and innovation ecosystem
- Support the mobility and networking of researchers
- Ease the stay of foreign researchers through adapted support
- Short term mobility schemes

GROUP 4 - Provide time to researchers for a better dedication to developing H2020 projects

Create a « European research projects » culture

- Develop incentive measures
- Foster the partnerships within laboratory research units towards a national and European Research & Innovation network

Develop a Human Resource strategy in order to optimise the setting-up of H2020 research projects

Administrative staff :

- An engineer in project management should be recruited
An engineer in project management should be recruited
- An executive assistant for research laboratories should be recruited
- The local funding procedures (such as the ERDF) should be reduced

Europe office :

- Increase the staff of the Europe office
- Project engineer should work within research laboratory for the writing-up of H2020 proposal and implementation

Researcher :

- The criteria in recruiting researchers should include an expertise in project write-up
- To reduce time allocated to teaching

Insure a mid to long term vision

- Allocate time to basic research while writing-up H2020 projects (as an applied research)
- To reduce administrative task (to send a request to the Regional Council)

Madeira

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems

Região Autónoma da Madeira

(RAM)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation

programme under grant agreement No 824550

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Summary	3
Introduction	4
Methodology	5
I - State of play of participation	7
II - Analysis of participation determinants	14
A - Network analysis	14
B - Regional innovation system.....	16
C - Regional organizational characteristics	27
D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level	32
III - Analysis of the representations	34
IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation	41

Summary

The Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems concerning Madeira report has been conceived by the Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation (Agência Regional de Desenvolvimento da Investigação, Tecnologia e Inovação – ARDITI) in collaboration with the University of Madeira (Universidade da Madeira – UMa) and goodwill from regional or national organisations and individuals.

This work was produced under the supervision of NEXA – Agence Régionale de Développement, d'Investissement et d'Innovation de La Réunion, as Workpackage 2 (WP2) leader.

A quantitative and qualitative evaluation on Madeira participation in European competitive funding programmes – the Seventh Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development (FP7) (2007-2013) and Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (H2020) (2014-2020) is made, shedding light on immediate and future necessities and opportunities for the next next research and innovation framework programme (FP) – Horizon Europe (2021-2027).

During the considered period, regional FP awarded projects almost multiplied and European Union contribution reached nearly the double from FP7 to H2020, suggesting a moving up into more ambitious and risk-taking scientific and/or business research and technological development projects by these regional organisations, who internalized new knowledge creation as a critical success factor.

Determinants for such growing are a higher involvement of regional stakeholders and connection with experienced FP European peers, particularly in specific scientific fields – as in Biotechnological and/or Information and Communication Technologies (ICT's) fields – consistent with the implemented regional Smart Specialization Strategy (S³).

An improvement in the research and innovation ecosystem is improving, namely if compared on a national scale, reveals a long path to reach an advanced position on the European context – with upcoming bottlenecks at sight, such as a shortage in individuals with completed tertiary education whom supply new university students and future graduates. An outline of other organizational characteristics is also advanced.

From an individual's perspective, retrieved from a regional survey and interviews, obstacles and levers are specifically identified which delivers a wider perception of existent and missing resources, infrastructures, political governance and stimulus and/or individual skills.

Madeira is currently engaging in the evaluation process and strategical design, based on comprehensive stakeholder involvement, addressing specific fields of industrial and research strengths with existent and/or potential competitive advantages for the region. This exercise shall gain from the current mapping, and its results, for an economical profitable and social prosperous access to the next framework programme and regional participation thereon.

Introduction

Since its first edition in 1984, framework programmes (FP) have been established and progressively extended to become the major planning instrument of Europe for research, to stimulate competitiveness and address technological, organizational and commercial innovation.

Promote and increase regional participation of Research and Innovation organisations in European Union, in particular on framework programmes and the European Research Area (ERA), unleashes new opportunities to strengthen territorial development, its competitive advantages and Madeira prosperity, both in national and European context.

This improvement shall be a collective endeavour to be undertaken by regional organisations, whether business firms, research institutions (including Higher Education establishments), regional government, funding and/or regulation agencies, Non-governmental organizations and well supported by islanders.

The current assessment exercise is an innovative approach to tackle recent evolution and “in the making” work, applying a European competitive lens to recognize unexplored potential and raise up exceptional promising capacities.

Aligned with ongoing discussion on future FP (Horizon Europe) and cohesion policies, this diagnostic reveals clear-cut existing obstacles that hinder regional participation and points well defined levers to a renewed ambition towards R&I policies implementation by regional, national and European authorities.

Such analysis, including R&I community mobilisation, represents a major opportunity to conceive, for further implementation, a research-based development strategy for the next programming period and ensure robustness to – and from – the regional innovation ecosystem on the new Smart Specialization Strategy (S3) generation.

Moreover, the research activity performed on the regional R&I ecosystem mapping produces a basis for further studies, catalysing an identification and description of research issues and challenges, relevant for both regional innovation potential and smart specialization priorities.

Methodology

The methodology applied follows the guidelines provided by the WP2 leader and, when applicable, resorted to international standards and/or methods used in relevant scientific literature. During the activities, different limitations were faced regarding the execution of the regional diagnosis.

Data sources came mainly from databases related with the information required:

- CORDIS, the European Commission data base that compiles the results of EU research and innovation framework programmes;
- The H2020 dashboard, that gives an interactive consultation of data on H2020 projects.

Related to other funding schemes, there were methodological limitations that have been, in most cases, surpassed. For European support programmes, it was conducted a search for the respective public repositories. To each programme, data collection generally followed a) access to programme site; b) search for data archive with approved projects; c) selection of information, and d) evaluation of accuracy and/or feasibility towards the data required by project needs.

Specifically, in European Territorial Cooperation schemes a verification and validation procedure was developed and applied. A comparison from the programme supported projects with the main aggregated database provided secure and reliable data of Interreg Europe (<https://www.interregeurope.eu/>) 2014-2020 and its former 2007-2013 programme.

Also relevant are the projects themselves and whose “priority axe” belong to. There are specifically measures for research and development support – which would be of direct relation with FP – while others, even if might involve partial scientific and/or technological research work, are not suitable in that thematic goal.

Data provided relates with approved applications and budget which may differ from physical and financial execution thereof (for example, an entity present in proposal but who further leaves the project and consortium before the subvention agreement contract).

Another hindrance comprises last calls for projects and subvention budgets treatment. The period covered by the analysis considers all the funded projects from 2007 until 2018 – leaving these last projects, approved in 2018, in an open border.

For instance, a call was in place by the middle of the year and the approval came almost at year end. The project has a 24 months duration. Should it be considered and if so, the whole budget – is an open question. Following the current example, the operation and its activities will be carried forward and executed in the upcoming years (in 2019 and 2020). An estimation based in a fractional count could be applied, dividing the project budget by the number of months and consider only 2018 part.

From a network perspective on FP participation, which is one of the primary mapping targets of the current work, an imbalance has been verified between collaborative / mono-beneficiary projects. As these last ones bring inconsistency upon a realistic context evaluation, caution shall be taken on the present analysis (three projects in FP7 and four on H2020 – from the “SME Instrument”).

In other funding schemes for research at European scale, namely EUREKA network and EUROSTARS, it has been detected at least one supported project for a Madeiran established

stakeholder. The accessible public information did not provide an explicit budget for regional participation. This awarded project has been excluded, for the sake of OR's comparison, given that these initiatives are not covered.

In consideration of trustable, complete, representative, reliable and verifiable data, regarding all funding schemes detected and entities involved, the participation of an "Associated Partner" or "Third party" has been recognized and identified even if there is no EU funding allocated. These brings bias on later treatment, since averages (e.g. of euro per project or euro per regional entity) suffer influence from these.

The conduction of interviews and survey followed the protocols established within the work package. A major bottleneck was to capture individual opinions from unsuccessful proposals to framework programmes – which revealed itself of troublesome identification and are missing in the interviewed panel. Considering the survey, the query on relative importance of "attractiveness towards foreign researchers of the regional research system" as a determinant factor in Horizon 2020 regional participation was not introduced.

Regarding information and data for regional profile of "RDI mapping", it was extensively used Eurostat, national statistical office (Instituto Nacional de Estatística – INE) and the regional statistical office (Direção Regional de Estatística da Madeira).

Subjective identification of INTEREG "strong research and innovation content projects implemented" with third countries goes along with considerations of (1) projects who shown continuity between programmes – as a reinforcement of their expected results and outputs, (2) allocated budget – as a demonstration of higher commitment and (3) sectoral approach, concerning the variety and types of organisations in consortium.

For research system analyses in "Regional Figures" there were real obstacles: scarce sources, actual data without historical information, data which unfulfilled the requisites or not data at all. Contacts have been established with local and national departments and institutions to recover existing data, which has been partially successfully. Data and/or information shortage is extensive to other tools outside regional scale. For example, in Regional innovation system performance, the recommended 'engine' developed by the Joint Research Center (JRC) lacks a Regional Benchmarking tool the Portuguese OR's. An internal method was developed as proxy to identify European regions for further comparison.

Another example concerns regional academic spin-offs. By the best available knowledge, there is no current measure of regional entrepreneurship considering research results. An internal procedure was developed for mapping economic exploration of science and technology knowledge outputs and new firms' creation. There is a wide and growing knowledge base about research commercialisation and the definition of academic spinoffs in scientific literature. At this date, we have taken a broader identification which, by no means, represents regional reality (which has not been studied in depth) and is expected to bring bias in further OR comparison. Also, the lack of a consensual definition and/or the indication of a standard to be followed predicts future contrast between OR results in this indicator.

I - State of play of participation

1) Evolution of regional participation

Global performance of Madeira participation in European research projects has grown from the Seventh European Framework Programme for Research and technological development (FP7) to EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (Horizon 2020). Indeed, it has almost multiplied the number of projects (11 to 20) in which, at least, an organization established in the region is present.

Even if total number of FP7 proposals submitted is unknown, for Horizon 2020 in almost each two proposals one has been granted (41% of global success rate).

The increase in number of researchers per project, from 0,05 to 0,07, shows that a wider participation does not reflect proportional growing in human resources dedicated and give a contained improvement for enlarging research pool in general population (from 0,02% to 0,03% of researchers per 1000 inhabitants).

As regards to EU contribution, total FP funding awarded to regional partners reached almost than 12 million euros in Horizon 2020 which represents nearly the double from previous FP7 (from 5 868 384,47 € to 11 724 696,35 €) where the budget allocated per FP project had a slight increase (around fifty thousand euros).

Figure I.1. Beneficiaries by EU funding and Contribution.

Although a growing participation in FP programmes, total of other EU competitive funding awarded to regional partners decreased from 2007/2013 period to 2014 until today. The awarded amount dropped more than a half (from 4 411 015,17 to 1 715 954,05), as shown above (Figure I.1). This clearly indicates the rise of FP programmes between the two periods, measured by the share of FP7/H2020 in the total EU funding, which boost from 57% up to 87%.

Resident companies, research institutes, university and regional government owned laboratories awarded with European competitive research funding perform a rise in FP7/H2020 and their relative weight in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from 0,14% to 0,26% as percentage of GDP in regional economy.

Taken the total number of projects supported, including other EU competitive funding, the average EU contribution per project has reduced, from 513 969,98 € to 407 292,44 € which relates positively with a lower average EU contribution to each regional partner (331 593,54 € to 305 469,33 €).

Regardless the decrease verified both in EU contribution per project and support to regional partners, the average share of total EU contribution awarded has increased ten pp. – 65% to 75% – from 2007/2013 period to 2014 until today, demanding a lower ‘effort rate’ for total expenditure (current and capital) carried out.

2) Participation to the different programmes and funding schemes

Observing the types of FP programmes and funding schemes mobilized by Madeirean stakeholders on H2020, the distribution of projects by “FP Pillar” shows hole coverage of research and innovation goals promoted by EU – with exception of projects on the specific objective 'Spreading excellence & widening participation'.

Figure I.2. H2020 Specific programmes - N.º Projects.

Topmost awarded projects are present in ‘Societal Challenges’ with nine (9) projects. Industrial Leadership has six (6) projects and with four (4) projects the ‘Excellent Science’ pillar. With only one occurrence is 'Science with and for society' – concerning the current project “Fostering Research Excellence in EU Outermost Regions” (FORWARD), as shown above (Figure I.2).

By applied funding schemes, ‘Innovation actions projects’ had the highest number of investment operations awarded (6) while ‘Research & Innovation actions’ and ‘SME

instrument' (new Enhanced European Innovation Council – EIC pilot) have each four (4) supported projects. 'Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions (MSCA)' and 'Coordination & support actions projects' had either three projects (as depicted in Figure I.3).

Figure I.3. H2020 Funding Schemes - N. ° Projects.

There is none **European Research Council (ERC) grant** or other measures, namely 'Procurement actions', 'Inducement Prize', 'Recognition Prize' and/or 'Debt and equity facility' mechanisms, which can potentially demonstrate a communication failure and/or that they simply do not have traction in regional research and innovation system.

3) Thematic distribution

FP funded projects with Madeirean participation cover all fields of science (Physical Sciences and Engineering, Life Sciences and Social Sciences and Humanities with total 12, 7 and 12 projects respectively). Top major scientific domains are mostly stable according to number of projects and/or amount of funding attributed.

For both periods, setting at least two or more projects, comes first research work focused on application of marine organisms, like algae and sponges, in biotechnological processes. This field had the highest grow, between FP7 and H2020. Secondly, activities related with management and organizational aspects of environment and climate change (from Social Sciences). Computer science and informatics and systems and communication engineering projects are, taken as a group with Earth System Science, the most prolific thematic on H2020 with eight (8) projects, as in Figure I.4.

Figure I.4. N. ° of Projects in FP per Scientific domain.

Financial budgeting and commitment generally indicate more ambitious and risk-taking projects. Within H2020 with an amount above 1 million euros, four scientific domains similar with projects distribution represent themselves 89% (10 421 660,10 €) of all approved funds of the programme in Madeira (Figure I.5. below).

Figure I.5. EU funding in FP per Scientific domain (Million €).

Results steadiness show an existing crossbreeding with Regional Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS³) priorities, namely with ‘Sea Resources and Technologies’, ‘Energy, Mobility and Climate change’ and ‘Information and Communication Technologies’ by different angles of science and technology work.

4) Stakeholders mapping

The type of organizations active in FP, measured by the number of participations, show business enterprises as main sector in both programmes. Research organizations are in second place. On the bottom, Higher education reflects the lowest relative importance in regional participation (Figure I.6. below), while the category “other organisations” (Non-profit institutions) emerge in H2020.

Nevertheless, Research organizations and Higher education establishments combined represent more than one third from all participations in the programme.

Figure I.6. Madeira participation in FP by organisation type.

There are nineteen (19) organizations participating in FP (which an average of 0,61 project participation per entity). Most represented in H2020, with at least three (3) participations each, are one higher education establishment, two research organisations and another organisation, from the private non-profit sector.

Together, these organisations (Table I.1. below) reap almost half (40%) of the sixteen active participating organisations, showing a highly concentration of H2020 participation relying on few (a quarter) of all the organizations presented.

Name of the organisation	N. ° H2020 participations
Universidade da Madeira	3
MITI - MADEIRA INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES INSTITUTE - ASSOCIACAO	3
AGÊNCIA REGIONAL DA ENERGIA E AMBIENTE DA REGIAO AUTONOMA DA MADEIRA (AREAM)	3
ARDITI - AGÊNCIA REGIONAL PARA O DESENVOLVIMENTO DA INVESTIGACAO, TECNOLOGIA E INOVACAO – ASSOCIACAO	3

Table I.1. Top Madeira organisations participation in FP.

These represent the most advanced and leading research organisations in the regional ecosystem, directly linked with new scientific knowledge production.

5) Participation profile

The participation profile as an indicator of regional relative influence in the networks they are part in H2020, show that Madeiran entities act as project Coordinators on ten (10%) percent in all projects (excluding mono-beneficiary projects). Same proportion presents on Third Party invitations (i.e. participating without any dedicated budget). Performing as a Workpackage leader has a higher number, as it acted in charge on 6 projects¹ (Table I.2).

Madeira organisations role in H2020	N. °
Coordinator	2
Mono-beneficiary	7
WP Leader	6
Third Party	2

Table I.2. Madeira organisations status in H2020.

6) Regional collaboration

There are 5 projects (25%) which include a partner from another OR. Top-3 outermost regions and countries with which Madeiran entities share the greatest number of projects are Açores, Portugal (5 projects), Canarias, Spain (4 projects) and Guadeloupe (2 projects having Antilles University as partner in the consortium).

There is one current project (INSULAE - Maximizing the impact of innovative energy approaches in the EU islands²) which has a participation from a Netherland entity established in Bonaire, in the Caribbean Sea (near to Curaçao and Venezuela) that, together with Saint

¹ Workpackage leader results are based in 10 of 20 projects performed.

² <https://bit.ly/2HzQMqQ>.

Eustace and Saba, make up an Overseas Country and Territory (OCT) of Netherlands in the region.

Projects with neighbouring third countries are absent. Considering third countries itself (non-European Union countries), without geographical proximity, there are (by descending order): China (3 projects), Norway (3 projects), Argentina (1), Canada (1), Israel (1) and Switzerland (1).

II - Analysis of participation determinants

A - Network analysis

1) Global connectivity

The average rank of regional partners ¹, excluding Madeiran positions, had an escalate from 4262 in FP-7 to 974 in H2020. Consequence of the enlargement of participations, the enhancement established links with more “qualified” partners (Table 3. below).

In H2020, regional stakeholders integrate “clubs” that dominate FP scene, having participation with organizations from the TOP 100 Ranking (upper then 105 projects, inclusive).

Name of the organisation coordinating the project	Country	Nr. of projects	Ranking
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	France	160	45
WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	Netherlands	137	61
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS - NTUA	Greece	121	79
NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	Norway	117	81
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TRENTO	Italy	83	132
RINA CONSULTING SPA	Italy	64	170
FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS	Spain	37	329
UNINOVA-INSTITUTO DE DESENVOLVIMENTO DE NOVAS TECNOLOGIAS-ASSOCIACAO	Portugal	28	429
HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM FUR OZEANFORSCHUNG KIEL	Germany	27	447
UNIVERSIDAD DE CASTILLA - LA MANCHA	Spain	25	486

Table II.1. Madeira Top partner organizations in FP.

2) Thematic connectivity

Integrating all partner institutions, including regional ones, major thematic connectivity appears associated by far with the field of Life Sciences, in ‘Marine biotechnology’. ‘Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy’ represents the second highest “club”, sharing with ‘Marine biotechnology’ the topmost networks. Both emerge twice in different work programmes.

‘Computer Science and Informatics’ (web and information systems) and ‘market and organisational change towards innovation and research’ also come out on two work programmes. ‘Energy, transportation and mobility’ ends scientific domains derived from the average ranking of Madeiran partners in Horizon 2020 projects (as in Table 4. below)².

¹ Results are based in project Coordinator partners in which at least one organisation from Madeira is present, excluding themselves.

² For 22 organizations, the Ranking data did not deliver any result. We attributed 1 to the Number of H2020 projects and 9864 Ranking to calculate the averages.

Scientific domain	Work programme	Average Nr. of H2020 projects	Average Ranking
Marine biotechnology	EXCELLENT SCIENCE - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	48	5781
Web and information systems, database systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP - Leadership in enabling and industrial technologies	17	4389
Technological change, innovation, research & development	INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP - Innovation In SMEs	8	3055
Web and information systems, database systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Health, demographic change and well-being	17	4880
Marine biotechnology	SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine, maritime and inland water research, and the bioeconomy	63	5917
Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy	SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Secure, clean and efficient energy	26	5864
Energy, transportation and mobility	SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Smart, Green And Integrated Transport	4	7136
Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy	SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials	22	3620
Technological change, innovation, research & development	SCIENCE WITH AND FOR SOCIETY	4	5689

Table II.2. Madeira Top thematic networks in FP.

3) Relative position

Assessing relative position of Madeiran stakeholders and their role in Horizon 2020 projects, by scientific domains and RIS3 priorities, show that scientific domains of ‘Energy, transportation and mobility’ and ‘Digital social research’ directly connected with RIS priorities ‘Energy, Mobility and Climate change’ and ‘Information and Communication Technologies’ respectively, are the ones where regional organizations acted as “Coordinator”, recognizing influence and a value proposition of these stakeholders.

4) Neighbouring countries participation

There are four projects bridging together partners from neighbouring territories, namely Canarias, from Macaronesia islands in Spain.

According with available data, Canarias has 168 participations in Horizon 2020. The share of projects that include partners from both regions (Madeira and Canarias) represents 2,4% of integration between the two ecosystems.

B - Regional innovation system

1) Mapping the regional innovation system

Madeira archipelago (situated in the Atlantic Ocean to the west of Morocco) is an autonomous region of the Republic of Portugal with an autonomous political and administrative status under the Portuguese Constitution since 1976, having a regional government and parliament responsible for political and administrative decisions in all sectors, except defence and foreign affairs.

It consists of two main islands, Madeira (742 km²) and Porto Santo (43 km²), surrounded by six inhabited islets (Ilheus da Cal, Cenouras, Cima, Fora, Ferro and Fonte de Areia) which form a nature reserve, three small islets known as Desertas (Ilhéu Chão, Deserta Grande and Bugio, uninhabited nature reserve of 14 km²) and the small sub-archipelago of Selvagens (uninhabited nature reserve of 3.6 km²), with its two small islands (Selvagem Grande and Selvagem Pequena) and several small islets (Ilhéu de Fora, Ilhéu Comprido, Ilhéus do Norte).

Madeira archipelago (like the Portuguese outermost region Açores) was uninhabited at the time of its discovery by the Portuguese: the current population descends, mainly, from the these¹. With an increase of over 100 000 inhabitants since 1900, its present population is of 254 876 inhabitants mainly concentrated in Funchal (41%), the capital of Madeira island².

Madeira has been a tourist destination since the XIXth century and the tourist industry mobilized 1 323 million international tourists in 2017 (DREM, 2018). The economy is dominated by the tertiary sector, where (1) accommodation and food service activities, (2) wholesale and retail trade and (3) transportation and storage has nearly 45% of the employed population and represents 50% of total value added generated in the region in 2017.

2) Regional innovation system performance

For a national assessment of Portuguese regional innovation systems performance, we used a set of four indicators from the Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2019: scientific excellence and intellectual assets, described here as products of research and innovation inputs and scientific and economic impacts of these, namely their *bang* in science communities and markets.

Normalised scores for the most recent year indicate diverse results considering the region in the national context (Figure II.1 and II.2).

Madeira has the lowest openness in scientific publications, with at least one co-author based abroad, almost half of the first place (Lisboa) with Açores being second to last and below Alentejo in research collaborations.

¹ In *Regional ecosystem profile–Macaronesian Region. 2016. EU Outermost Regions and Overseas Countries and Territories*, Luisa Madruga, Francisco Wallenstein, José Manuel N. Azevedo. BEST, Service contract 07.0307.2013/666363/SER/B2, European Commission, 233 p + 10 Appendices.

² In *Estatísticas Demográficas da Região Autónoma da Madeira / Direção Regional de Estatística da Madeira - Funchal: D.R.E.M., 2018.*

From an innovative proprietors’ perspective, Madeira firms are on the podium in number of trademark applications at the European Union Intellectual Property Office – EUIPO, topped by ‘Norte’ and ahead of ‘Lisboa’, the third place.

Figure II.1. Portugal Regional Innovation output.

Figure II.2. Portugal Regional Innovation Impact.

Data on highly cited scientific publications shows that, by far, Madeiran scientific production enables higher quality than regional and European peers¹. This indicator discharges

¹ There are only three regions with a higher number of publications among the top-10% most cited publications worldwide: Zürich, Nordwestschweiz and Région lémanique, all from Switzerland.

considerations about the ‘quality of scientific research’ and productivity¹ since, even if some closure in the research system might be present, it can deliver remarkable science products with worldwide excellence and global positioning in given scientific fields.

Economic effects reveal lower returns from innovation efforts in comparison with national average (74,32) being the third lowest region. Although, if a relation between trademark applications and ‘innovation sales’ is made, Madeira has nearly the same proportional turnover as ‘Norte’ region, meaning that market success rate might result from other explanatory variables than by outermost conditioning.

For a European regional correlation, it was internally developed a method to define a benchmark coverage. Results delivered six European regions, plus Madeira (Table II.3). Estonia and Malta are included at the country level, as in these countries, NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 levels are identical to the country territory.

The choice of this group considers the combination of various criteria namely size, financial effort in Research and Innovation along with other economic, demographic or geographical factors.

Region	Country	Population - Eurostat (2015)	GDP - Euro per capita (2015)	Total ESIF Research & Innovation per capita per year	Total H2020 per capita per year	Ratio H2020/ESIF
Kriti	EL	631 513	13 900	16 237 886	31 525 833	1,94
Midtjylland	DK	1 282 750	42 900	4 497 187	24 984 567	5,56
Friesland	NL [*]	1 718 775	33 800	8 634 984	22 049 806	2,55
Eesti	EE	1 314 870	15 400	100 711 236	18 139 877	0,18
Madeira	PT	258 686	16 100	30 577 007	12 837 243	0,42
Malta	MT	439 691	21 500	26 287 042	11 248 182	0,43
Sardegna	IT	1 663 286	19 600	15 072 282	3 639 322	0,24

* Friesland is here based in (NL1) Noord-Nederland data. Further data reflects specific indicators of the region (NL12).

Table II.3. European regional benchmark.

There are differences between European funding (descending order by Total H2020 per capita) in research and innovation projects and activities on a regional basis. Madeira is below average (17 774 976 €) together with Malta and Sardegna region. The highest disparities come from the proportion of European competitive grants in community funds, which passes from one quarter (Sardegna) until almost sixfold (Midtjylland, in Denmark).

Using the “Regional Innovation Index” classification scheme, there are all categories present, excluding “modest innovators” (Table II.4). In addition, for an analysis of regions research and innovation systems evolution, we have run the three subgroups exercise for each performance group (introduced in RIS 2017) to detect subtle evolutions at regional level since 2011².

¹ « International scientific co-publications are a proxy for the quality of scientific research as collaboration increases scientific productivity. » as in RIS 2019 database description.

² A comparison of the Regional Innovation Index at the country level with the Summary Innovation Index in the European Innovation Scoreboard shows that, due to a more restricted set of indicators in the RIS and, for several indicators, slightly different definitions, countries’ performance relative to the EU average in the RIS is different from that in the European Innovation Scoreboard. As such, countries were removed.

Region	Performance group	
	2011	2019
Kriti	Moderate	Strong -
Midtjylland	Leader -	Leader -
Friesland	Moderate +	Moderate +
Madeira	Moderate -	Moderate
Sardegna	Moderate -	Moderate -

Table II.4. European regional benchmark by performance group and sublevel classification.

In the selected regions, only Kriti had a catching up to the above group, from ‘Moderate to Strong’ (minus), and Madeira had a moving towards the subgroup upper level (from ‘Moderate –’ to ‘Moderate’). Other regions maintained each one their positions, having smaller growing variations in performance, with exception of a slightly lagging behind of Midtjylland (Figure II.3).

Figure II.3. European regional benchmark by performance group – score relative to EU 2011.

According with the selected regions, Madeira falls into the lowest scores regarding human resources (only Sardegna has a worst mark). Regional existent third-level education provides reduced supply of advanced skills to university in the population aged between 30-34, with completed tertiary education. With respect to population between 25 and 64 years, in education or training activities to improve knowledge, skills and competence, Madeira gets an equal result (second lowest). For both indicators, the Danish region (Midtjylland) takes, by far, an unbeaten stance (Figure II.4).

Public Expenses in R&D (PERD) and Business Expenditure in R&D (BERD) reflects an identical scenario. Madeira position is in second to last and as lowest score respectively.

Although, classical knowledge postulates governmental budgets as the largest source of funding for R&D activities (Caraça, 1993)¹, recent analysis add that their still mostly of a fundamental nature, too concentrated in the State and its effects are felt especially in non-market sectors (Heitor et al, 2014)².

Comparatively, all regions have nearly the double or higher of Madeiran R&D financed by the government (with the astonishing exception of Friesland) and Madeira is the least in business firm’s investment. The analysis of these sectoral expenditures shows that different development stages of research and innovations systems are present with distinct ‘recipes’ and ‘prescriptions’ for technological progressiveness and commitment to knowledge creation. By no means, should a “one-size-fits-all” be addressed, since even well-developed science and technology regions shows practically an equilibrium or a staggering imbalance between PERD and BERD in advanced performance groups (namely, Midtjylland and Friesland).

Figure II.4. Human resources.

Figure II.5. Research expenditure.

Towards economic knowledge explorers and/or users some special features arise. Madeiran SMEs with house innovation activities stands in second place, ahead of Midtjylland and Friesland (who are, by large, the BERD champions within the chosen regions). This might represent some misunderstanding of research and innovation efforts. “Errors in this respect are particularly significant: while many innovations may require costly R&D, the costs of preparing for production are often higher still” and some overlap will appear in consequent report of these activities”³.

¹ Caraça, J. (1993). *Do saber ao fazer: porquê organizar a ciência*. Lisboa: Gradiva.

² Heitor, Manuel, Hugo Horta and Joana Mendonça (2014) "Developing Human Capital and Research Capacity: Science Policies Promoting Brain Gain," *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Vol. 78, No. 8, pp. 1299-1309.

³ OECD (2015), *Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development*, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>

Co-operation agreements on innovation activities with other enterprises or institutions, lay Madeiran SMEs in regions tail (being Sardegna the last position). The score for upper regions reveals deeper linkages in firm’s co-operation activities ¹, with Kriti scoring the toppest value.

Intangible investment of technical knowledge and services (for this purpose, intellectual propriety) enlightens fertile trademark activity in Madeira – as in national context – which correlates positively with its economic specialization on a regional market scale, since trademarks are seen as an important innovation indicator, especially for the service sector.

Regions score in patent applications, even if low anywhere (excepting Midtjylland), has his minimum record in Madeira. This might be reason of (1) weakened evaluation (or not evaluation at all) of patentable results coming from research projects, (2) lack of support in patent filing (including patent literature and all administrative and legal work connected) or that (3) research products are too far from a “state-of” technological invention ² or, even, (4) related with too dynamic technological sectors (for example, software) in which property rights does not reveal direct value added (because the speed-up and obsolescence that characterizes these products and/or services).

Figure II.6. Innovation activities.

Figure II.7. Intellectual assets.

Regarding aesthetic creations, Midtjylland is the winner as other regions perform lower – with Kriti, Friesland and Madeira getting roughly the same score – and Sardegna showing the minor score in industrial design.

¹ This indicator excludes pure contracting with no active co-operation and activities done for others on a pure contract base without active co-operation.

² Related with a somewhat “fundamental nature” of scientific outcomes.

3) Regional research performance

Madeira public higher education system is composed of one institution – Universidade da Madeira. It is divided into six teaching units, four corresponding to research programmes in Physical Sciences and Engineering, Life Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities and the other two follow professional programmes, namely Health and Management.

There are also in the region two private higher education institutions – Escola Superior de Enfermagem São José de Cluny and Instituto Superior de Administração e Línguas, being the former oriented to graduates and advanced studies in nursing care services, such as medical assistants and therapists, while the second concedes first cycle learning (known as Licenciatura) in (a) Organization and Hotel Management and (b) Tourism without providing post formation (Master and/or PhD).

According with best available knowledge there are currently nineteen research organisations (from research centre's to research units) in these Higher Education establishments. They cover scientific domains like Engineering, Biological Sciences, Clinical Medicine and Health Sciences, Economics, Management and History, among others.

Two of these, Madeira Chemistry Research Centre (Centro de Química da Madeira – CQM) and the Research Centre in Education (Centro de Investigação em Educação – CIE), are included in the 305 national research units which receives funding from the national Science and Technology Foundation (Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia – FCT).

Between 2013 and 2018, from an average of 73 PhD students enrolled in doctoral programmes 1,2% came from abroad (measured by the share of foreign PhD students in total PhD scholars). In the same period, foreign career scientists represent, in average, 46% of the active scientific community (measured by the annual share of foreign post doctorates in total post doctorates in the region).

As to new knowledge spill over from academic and research organisations, economic exploited results gave rise to, in average, one spin off (1,33) created in the considered period (2010 until 2018), which is in line with international results of new firm creation across OECD countries¹.

4) Private sector implication

Portuguese outermost regions, Açores e Madeira, had in recent years an upsurge in firm's expenditure after economic and financial crisis which has not been fully overcome at the country level (Portugal currently still spend less on R&D than it did in pre-crisis period, in 2009).

¹ OECD. Publishing, & Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development Staff. (2010). *OECD Studies on SMEs and Entrepreneurship*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Since spin-off measurement is absent at regional level, an internally method has been developed, according with reference concept of academic spin-off (ASO) in 'OECD (2003), Entrepreneurship and Local Economic Development: programme and policy recommendations' and 'European commission (2003) Green Paper: Entrepreneurship in Europe', extended at Portuguese national landscape.

NUTS 2	Business expenditure in R&D (BERD) - € (thousands)				
	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Açores	1 659,20	733,40	1 319,90	873,50	1 645,72
Madeira	3 759,10	3 786,90	3 739,00	3 071,20	4 573,17

Table II.5. Portuguese outermost regions R&D expenditure (BERD) by Business enterprise sector.

The recovery is on track for the last year of the series, with an annual growing rate of 88,4% and 48,9% for Açores and Madeira respectively (the highest's in national context), between 2016 and 2017 (Table II.5). This clearly illustrates a reinforcement in engagement of business R&D into new scientific and technological and innovative projects and activities.

NUTS 2	R&D expenditure (GERD) – percentage GDP			
	Government	Business enterprise	Higher education	Private non-profit
Açores	0,03	0,04	0,23	-
Madeira	0,09	0,10	0,17	-

Table II.6. Portuguese outermost regions gross expenditure in R&D (BERD) by performance sector.

Provisional data for last known year (2017) shows sectoral distribution between classical R&D division (Table II.6). There are differences between the two regional systems, being most highlighted the ‘Government’ expenditure, with Madeira having threefold Açores investment.

Even if considered the higher education as the central R&D performer in Açores, a joint analysis of the public institutional expenditure (i.e. sum of Government and Higher education expenditures) demonstrates the same proportional GDP investment in R&D, of 0,26, for both regions. Regarding the private sector, the contrast represents more than double expenditure from Madeira firms than their Açores counterparts.

5) RIS3 priorities

Smart specialization strategies aim concentrating regional resources on a limited number of innovation priorities to reach a critical mass and build competitive advantage that must contribute to the transformation of the economy and the development of new, diversified sources of prosperity and jobs.

Current regional smart specialization strategy, established in 2014, is in an undergoing review for the next generation of priorities. The number of H2020 projects (Table II.7) in each RIS³ priority indicates a highly concentration in given specific priorities, especially in Sea Resources and Technologies, Energy, Mobility and Climate Change and Information and Communication Technologies.

RIS³ Priorities	N. ° H2020 Projects
Bio-sustainability	1
Energy, Mobility and Climate change	6
Information and Communication Technologies	5
Sea Resources and Technologies	6
Transversal to all RIS ³ Priorities	2

Table II.7. Madeira number of H2020 projects by RIS³ Priority.

A joint matrix, produced by a cross search of economic and scientific domains together with policy objectives, from Madeira RIS³ priorities and their counterparts around Europe shows convergence in specific scientific and technological domains (Table II.8) and, also, some widely chosen trends.

RIS3 priority	N. ° of Regions /Country
Health-and-well-being	142
ICTs	155
Tourism	4
Sustainability	42
Quality of Agrofood	21
Marine	69
Energy	136

Table II.8. Number of European regions by Madeiran RIS³ Priority.

There are common endeavours which represent ‘Societal Challenges’, such as ICT’s, Health and Energy, priorities which are partially addressed across European regions. Targeted areas are, on a lesser scale, Marine and Sustainability and – with only a few – Tourism¹ and/or Quality of Agrofood. These later ones represent “priority niches”, attesting existent competitive advantages for and from Madeira in European regions context. On the other side, represents scarcity² – at least using a European research competition “length” – in other strategical priorities such as Infrastructures Sustainability, Management and Maintenance, Health and wellness or Agro-Food Quality.

Chosen regions in Research innovation system performance benchmark share with Madeira some of RIS³ priorities (Table II.9), prevailing (as above) ICTs, Health and Energy as widely European focus in scientific and technological development towards economic specialization.

¹ The four regions are, including Madeira, Algarve (Portugal), Illes Balears (Spain) and Swietokrzyskie (Poland).

² This exercise applies an “headcount” attributing to each project “one” priority, considering the «major» impact of the scientific and technological outcomes.

Region name	Health and well-being	ICTs	Tourism	Sustainability	Quality of Agrofood	Marine	Energy	N. °
Friesland	✓	✓					✓	3
Kriti							✓	1
Midtjylland		✓					✓	2
Madeira	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	7
Sardegna	✓	✓						2

* Friesland is here based in (NL1) Noord-Nederland information.

Table II.9. European regional benchmark by Madeiran RIS³ Priority.

The approach also delivers a clear difference for future research prospects: while, in part, ORs specificities and their challenges (for example, Sustainability and/or Marine) should be explored and enacted mainly by their own stakeholders', other priorities are better suited with an engagement of regions outside outermost territories.

6) Public policies

The amounts presented reflect planned investments using European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) exclusively related with research, technological development and innovation intervention field at regional level and include data from regional Operational programme (OPs), but also shares of national and transnational cooperation programmes (Table II.10).

Operational programme	Estimation
Regional Operational Programme "Madeira 2014-2020"	29 000 000,00 €
National Operational Programme "Competitividade e Internacionalização"	26 000 000,00 €
Cross-border Cooperation programme "Interreg V-A - Spain-Portugal (Madeira-Açores-Canarias (MAC))"	3 000 000,00 €
Total	58 000 000,00 €

Table II.10. European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) for Research and Innovation.

Since all programmes started on track after 2014, the covered duration on calculus goes from 2015 until 2020, inclusively, which gives an average of € 9 666 666,67 per year.

On the considered period, 2016 was the closest of a leverage effect (a more than 1 ratio) which means that performed R&D activities in Madeira took higher advantage from the H2020 programme (Table II.11).

Besides the late implementation of the regional operational programme, the instability verified should (or can) also be combined with other cycles, such as governmental (regional elections in 2015) or business investment for instance.

Indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
H2020 funding	615 556,00 €	5 055 735,55 €	2 656 289,05 €	1 097 169,00 €	2 299 946,75 €
Population	258 686	256 424	254 876	254 368	253 936 <i>p</i>
H2020 funding intensity	2,38	19,72	10,42	4,31	9,06
Leverage	0,06	0,52	0,27	0,11	0,24

p: provisional data based in 2018 effective growth rate. Source: National Statistics Office.

Table II.11. H2020 leverage effect.

From the analysis of the instruments deployed at the regional level, there are missing measures who directly support R&D internationalization, particularly addressing the participation of companies and other entities from the R&I System in research and innovation programmes (namely H2020) which are available at national thematic Operational Programme "Competitividade e Internacionalização".

C - Regional organizational characteristics

1) Review of higher education and research organizations' participation determinants

Higher education system in Madeira is composed both of public and private organizations (as discriminated above in “Regional research performance”).

Madeira university has, proximately, 502¹ staff employed which, according to literature (Lepori et al. 2014) serves as explanatory fact of a limited participation in the FP programmes – i.e. when the size of the institution has less than 500 full time equivalent academic staff.

In perspective, Portuguese outermost regions present significant differences in their regional higher education systems². Data from the last available year of reference (2017/2018 academic year) in Table II.12. shows, in each level, a larger number of students who have completed their studies in Madeira except for those awarding degrees at the doctorate level, where Açores has twofold newly qualified doctoral graduates.

Academic year 2017/2018	Açores	Madeira
Higher education graduated students	547	720
Professional Higher Technical Course	14	55
1st Cycle (Bachelor)	436	514
2nd Cycle (Master)	83	144
3rd Cycle (PhD)	14	7
Higher Education Teachers	303	349

Table II.12. Portuguese outermost regions higher education graduated students and Teachers.

These correlates positively with the verified expenditure in R&D for the Higher Education (on Table II.6), since research activity performed by doctoral students is included in the overall R&D performed by Higher Education (even if there are difficulties in identifying the borderline between the R&D and education and training activities of doctoral students).

NUTS 2	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Açores	0,002	0,008	0,022	0,020	0,025	0,032
Madeira	0,014	0,039	0,036	0,017	0,014	0,014

Table II.13. Portuguese outermost regions higher education establishments research orientation.

¹ Proxy estimation based on 2018/2019 national statistics on Higher Education Teachers for the public establishment in Madeira (315) plus 59% (or 187) of non-teaching personnel, which assumes data provided in Council of Rectors of Portuguese Universities - <http://www.crup.pt/universidade-da-madeira/>, last access on 22/10/2019.

² Açores does not have a private higher education establishment while in Madeira there are two of such institutions.

On this regard “research orientation”, measured by the ratio between the total number of graduated PhD students and the total number of graduated first-degree students ¹, gives an evolution of both regional Higher Education systems. In recent years (Table II.13. above) Açores has been directing more resources towards conducting research when compared to other activities (such as teaching and increased internationalization).

As measurement units of researcher’s recognition and reward, scientific publications – and bibliometric sources as a powerful field within science studies – deliver a handful approach to estimate scientific excellence.

Scientific productivity (here, measured by the number of publications per full time equivalent researcher in Institutional sector²) shows an increase of scientific production, almost doubling the number of published outputs during the considered period, reaching a one-by-one basis in 2017.

Together with the number of publications, most used proxies to measure impact upon research communities of such products are citations to articles and share of the top 10% most cited publications. This last indicator delivers an insight on the efficiency of a research system, since “highly cited publications are assumed to be of higher quality”³ where (Table II.14) regional performance is above average.

Indicator per year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Total number of researchers (FTE)	215	241	199	195	204	219	244	265
Total of scientific publications (all fields)	137	191	188	206	207	291	262	323
<i>Research productivity</i>	0,64	0,79	0,95	1,06	1,02	1,33	1,08	1,22
<i>Top 10% most cited publications</i>	13,14	17,28	14,89	14,56	13,53	9,62	14,50	12,69

Table II.14. Madeira research productivity and impact.

As for international openness of a research system, coauthorship of scientific products and foreign researcher’s mobility allow observations on cooperative science and access global knowledge pools. On this determinant, Madeira regional research and higher education systems has a growing path towards a higher and stronger quality of its scientific research (Table II.15).

Indicator per year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
% of international scientific co-publications	34%	47%	51%	66%	60%	71%	68%	72%
% of foreign PhD	0%	0%	67%	0%	0%	29%	17%	200%

Table II.15. Madeira international research openness.

¹ Simen G Enger, Closed clubs: Network centrality and participation in Horizon 2020, Science and Public Policy, Volume 45, Issue 6, December 2018, Pages 884–896, <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scy029>.

² Institutional Sector includes all units from regional public administration, such as hospitals, Higher Education establishments and private non-profit institutions.

³ Values above 10 are considered above average performance and below 10 are considered below average performance.

According with public grant information from all funded projects by the European Union under the sixth framework programme for research and technological development (FP6) – from 2002 to 2006 – there is none regional participating organisations¹. This demonstrates that in recent years (covering FP7 and H2020) regional institutions, as newcomers, developed capacities and accumulated resources to their competitive advantage, reputation and capacity in terms of both collaborative and competitive research nature.

2) Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions

An unsuccessful attempt to collect these data was driven.

Absent standardised available information.

3) Analysis of institutional strategies

Conducted interviews reached five institutions with the following profile: business firms (1), research unit (1)², regional and/or local public administration (2)³ and a private non-profit institution (1)⁴. Their representative's positions are, respectively, Chief Executive Officer, Coordinator, Heads of Division and Chairman of the Administration Board.

All organisations have current or previous participation in framework programmes, three of them in one project on Horizon 2020 and two with 4 to 5 participations, in both programmes (FP7 and Horizon 2020).

Research units recognize the existence of implemented internal strategies, along with the organisation development for FP programmes participation and its improvement.

One institution has its strategic research and technological programme according with FP calendar and plans to redirect “efforts from local or regional EU support to FP programmes for financial and scientific/technical reasons”. Although, any of these have monitoring procedures implemented to follow organisation's participation.

Concerning lobbyist activities, none of the organisations have members acting at European Level (Brussels). However, representatives are deployed in experts' groups for advisory in European Institutions.

No organisation commits efforts on internal actions to promote and foster FP participation, although they provide incentives, such as financing trips abroad for proposal consortium meetings.

One interviewee indicates the existence of a local office dedicated to the support of FP Programmes project development and internally proposes Horizon 2020 trainings to research

¹ There is one manufacturing SME established in Madeira – description in database refers that some fields of 'FP6 Organisations' dataset are not populated.

² MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre, Pólo da Madeira.

³ Centro de Maricultura da Calheta (CMC), under ‘Secretaria Regional do Mar e Pescas’ and Divisão de Mobilidade e Trânsito from ‘Câmara Municipal do Funchal’.

⁴ AREAM - Agência Regional da Energia e Ambiente da Região Autónoma da Madeira.

staff. In all cases, other staff (such as administrative and support) is not trained in FP programmes specificities and there is not any mentoring system between peers in relation to FP participation within the interviewed organisations.

For drivers that led SMEs, public bodies and agencies to engage in FP programs, the interviewed panel drawn attention on available financial features (i.e. funding rate), “an excellent way to feed” and foster networking (with “world class partners” is mentioned) and coordination of R&D activities, including learning experiences and good practices transfer. Also, by the nature of the organisations themselves, is seen as a mean for compliance with regional policy goals (such as sustainable energy, environmental and/or territorial management).

They all agree on delivering innovative solutions and actions towards regional economy and society as a primary benefit from FP participation. Pursuit for financial support, incorporation of new skills and know-how are indicated and, also, partnering advantages whereas should “make sure the partnerships established within the consortium are more than just a way to get funded and that they will remain long after the project’s end”, as one interviewed reveals.

There are two main properties interviewees rely on to increase their participation: first “added value” where it relates to scientific, technological, organisational and/or commercial expertise (all abilities together or just part of) that one must bring for the project and/or consortium or – not dependent on organisations’ internal competitive advantages – inherent natural conditions as worthy assets, since islands own characteristics provide unique ‘living laboratories’ for innovative solutions experimental development to replication in large scale coverage. Second, prior collaborations and networking, which in addition to FP increase can also activate new funding schemes (usually, leveraged by previous partners).

Regarding good practices, emphasis is given to strategic orientation of potential engagement – to be “sure about your goals and have them aligned with the proposed project” and “regional importance of the tasks”. A deeper insight adds importance on “coherence between the tasks foreseen and the budget allocation”. As someone sets out, the “success of the participation in the FP programmes is related with quality and not quantity of applications”.

Concerning the perspective of non-participating institutions to FP programmes, it was not possible to capture their institutional strategies and main characteristics. These are missing from the interviewed panel.

4) Analysis of Support Services

FP dedicated support services is seen as an asset to increase regional participation in FP programmes. These act as facilitators, providing assistance to local stakeholders in building, manage and reporting of funded projects.

There are eight (8)¹ organisations and one (1) individual established in Madeira whose activities are driven to administrative and support services towards funding procedures. These are mainly oriented to European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) operational programmes (5) without explicit mention to research and technological development (RTD) thematic priorities.

¹ Information’s on two (2) of these firms are missing, since a proprietary website was not found.

From the ones who specifically address “Research and Innovation”, the individual presents herself as “international Innovation consultant and Technology Transfer expert” who assisted “different types of stakeholders (Large and Small Enterprises, Universities, Research centres) and has extensive experience as proposal evaluator for the European Commission (VI FP; VII FP, H2020 and Energy Intelligent Programme).

Two firms (2) refer to RTD. One – I.T.B. - INVESTIGAÇÃO E TRANSFERÊNCIA DE BIOTECNOLOGIA, LDA.¹ – is dedicated to technical and scientific services in areas such as biology, biotechnology, quality, environment and tourism, where also has performed research activities under regional and transnational cooperation programmes. It expressly communicates “building and management of R&D (Research and Development) projects for Products and Services”, but no mention is made to FP programmes.

The other – CONHECIMENTO INTENSIVO - CONSULTADORIA EM INOVAÇÃO, LDA² – states “structuring and execution of applications and simplification of projects’ administrative process” but no mention is made to FP programmes (except an image of Horizon 2020 logo).

The search undertaken is based in informal knowledge. Considering all potential FP assistance providers, including public bodies and structural funds managing authorities or private organisations, no in-depth study has been attempted.

¹ <https://bit.ly/36bOatY>.

² <https://bit.ly/32WsFve>.

D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

1) Patterns of success and failure

The group composed by a total of nine individuals, belong to companies (2), research units (2), government (1) and private non-profit institutions (1).

Research profiles are unequal. Two of these have a PhD degree awarded in the considered period (2008 and 2016) where only one works in the same institution were has been graduated.

Almost half (4) have published scientific publications, mainly scientists who work in research units. From these, only two (2) identified productivity and citation impact of the publications (*i.e.* h-index).

In terms of mobility experience, the majority developed their professional career at regional and international context and only two had national mobility experience (between 1 and 2 years). Part (4) had an international experience for 1 and 2 years while one individual has an extensive international background with more than 5 years of experience.

Three (3) of these were involved in FP projects on their international mobilities abroad.

With reference to international networking, one (1) individual admits occasional and/or weak links with external partners and other (1) mentions regular interactions – even if those do not result in new collaborative projects or co-publications. One third (1/3) recognizes strong network collaborations (in the form of past or on-going projects and/or co-publications) although working together occurs occasionally. Four individuals sign strong and regular collaborations with partners.

FP projects experience and involvement during individual professional careers shows that more than half (5) have participated in four or more projects and the rest (4) have been implicated in one or two FP projects.

Two individuals are registered as experts in the European Commission and have assisted in grant applications, projects and tender's evaluation.

From chosen supported research activities, three individuals had experience and participation in FP Programmes only in the scope of that same projects, while four individuals were involved in other FP projects, prior to the selected ones. Two individuals show higher experience and participation in FP programmes since they joined other projects, before and after, the selected ones.

In view of Consortium formation, most participations came from invitation by the core group thanks to previous collaboration with one of the consortium members (6) and, in less extent (2) without pre-existing collaboration. Only in one case an individual initiative took place, mobilizing pre-existing network and contacts to join a consortium.

These results show that mostly individuals have not built any consortium and have not initiated a proactive partner's search process to look for new collaborations as well.

During project development cycle, there was in one case a relevant intervention during project conceptualization – since the individual was part of the core group – whereas in most cases (5) participants where invited at an early stage and kept in charge of some key parts of projects drafting. A lesser part (3) declare a later stage invitation, with few involvements in the proposal development process.

Lobby activities *i.e.* dialogue and interaction backing between research communities and institutions to common challenges identification aligned with real scientific and socioeconomic needs, were applied in three cases through interaction with EU project officer (2) and/or informed political support of the submission of the project (1). Other alternatives, such as propositions during the Work programme drafting or involvement with a national expert group (National Contact Points – NCP) are absent.

Six (6) individuals acknowledge that approved projects proposals were granted in a first submission and three (3) refer to support services, using private consultants and/or regional services for proposal writing, being absent other services such as partner's search, financial & administrative support and/or external review of proposals before submission.

Concerning the perspective of unsuccessful candidates to FP programmes, it was not possible to capture individual opinions and main characteristics from their failed proposals – revealing itself of troublesome identification. These are missing from the interviewed panel.

2) Analysis of self-selection determinants

Information provided by one (1) FP non-applying researcher does not reach a minimum significance level established – constitution of a panel representing at least 5% of their global R&I community and/or a minimum of 10 individuals.

III - Analysis of the representations

1) Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders

A survey was launched in 7 of June of 2019 and remained active until 25th. Target population is based in three institutions internal databases (mailing list) – ARDITI - Agência Regional para o Desenvolvimento da Investigação, Tecnologia e Inovação, Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute (M-ITI) and Universidade da Madeira – and have been disseminated in social media platform (ARDITI). Final data collection considers fifty-seven (57) valid answers from 392 inquiries, corresponding to an answer rate of 14,5 %.

Respondents are mainly researchers (49,1 %) and employees of regional administration institutions (17,5 %) representing to two thirds (2/3) of all answers. The reminiscent came from manager/project engineers who work as innovation intermediary in clusters or transfer centres (15,8 %), CEO's of private companies (8,8 %), a private company's employee (1,8 %) and 'other' (7 %).

Knowledge and/or experience about European framework programmes (FP) for Research and Innovation differ, although unfamiliarity with the subject is residual (3,5 %).

Most respondents (40,4 %) are aware of FP, having assisted to public conferences and/or contact with the subject threw other channels (e.g. email) or in dedicated training sessions (33,3 %). Around one third (38,6 %) had already drafted, or at least tried to produce, a proposal while part (33,3 %) have previous participation in a FP-funded project. A minority were currently conceiving a project (12,3 %).

Figure III.1. Regional perception on H2020 funded projects with Madeira participation.

Regional research and innovation ecosystem perceptions differ. A small part of respondents (8,8 %) recognizes lack of information's about the subject. On other side, almost half (47,4 %) have heard about regional smart specialisation strategy (S3) and/or about their institutions. The same proportion declares to be working in a research/innovation institution.

Impressions about regional participation in framework programmes for Research and innovation (FP7 and Horizon 2020) are mainly perceived as having between one to ten (1-10) participant (as coordinators, beneficiaries or third parties) or, closely, from ten to fifty

cooperation in research projects. A short part (3 respondents) believes that regional presence is of fifty or more partnerships (Figure III.1. above).

When compared with other European regions number of FP funded projects, two thirds express their opinion as Madeira being below average (“very low” – 14,0 % and “low” – 52,6 %) while part indicates a regular participation – as much as their counter peers – and a minority (5,3 %) believes that regional presence is “high”.

Region	H2020 Net EU Contribution	H2020 Participations	Average EU contribution per project
Midtjylland	203 570 288,00 €	468	434 979,25 €
Kriti	111 095 423,00 €	315	352 683,88 €
Sardegna	29 133 932,00 €	101	288 454,77 €
Friesland	15 922 097,00 €	36	442 280,47 €

Table III.1. Number of project participations and Net EU Contribution by benchmark region.

Regarding relative importance of potential factors and their influence in regional participation on FP, namely Horizon 2020, considerations on “Very influent” – with higher than one third (1/3) of all answers are “Regional research performance (Scientific excellence) – 35,1%” and “Connection to the most Horizon 2020 successful institutions/networks” – 33,3%.

Potential factors	Influence	%
Regional research performance (Scientific excellence)	Influent	36,8%
Implication of business sector in R&D expenditures	Influent	54,4%
Connection to the most Horizon 2020 successful institutions/networks	Influent	40,4%
Use of ERDF or regional policies as a lever for encouraging and building capacities for Horizon 2020 participation	Influent	43,9%
Size of research/innovation organisations	Some influence	40,4%
Local organisations strategy and tools to encourage and ease the participation of candidates	Influent	43,9%
Quality of support services to develop and manage H2020 projects	Influent	40,4%
Scientific productivity of individual researchers	Influent	38,6%
International connections of individuals	Influent	40,4%
Knowledge of candidates about framework programs	Influent	38,6%
Relative attractiveness of Horizon 2020 compared to other available funding	Influent	54,4%

Table III.2. Potential factors and their influence in Madeira participation on FP.

Chosen “Influent” factors which received more than half respondent’s opinion (and given same relative importance) are “Implication of business sector in R&D expenditures” – 54,4% and “Relative attractiveness of Horizon 2020 compared to other available funding” – 54,4%. Both represent the highest relative importance between all factors addressed.

With “some influence”, aggregating more than one third (1/3) of all expressed opinions, are “Size of research/innovation organisations” – 40,4%. Even if low anywhere, factors with “No influence” at all pointed a higher share to “International connections of individuals” – 14,0%.

Highest answers (%) per factor are depicted in Table III.2 (above), which received all “influential” relative importance with notably exception of “Size of research/innovation organisations”.

Factors assessment	Evaluation	%
Regional research performance (Scientific excellence)	Good	33,3%
Attractiveness towards foreign researchers of the regional research system	Insufficient	43,9%
Implication of business sector in R&D expenditures	Insufficient	73,7%
Connection to the most Horizon 2020 successful institutions/networks	Insufficient	43,9%
Use of ERDF or regional policies as a lever for encouraging and building capacities for Horizon 2020 participation	Sufficient	45,6%
Size of research/innovation organisations	Insufficient	45,6%
Local organisations strategy and tools to encourage and ease the participation of candidates	Insufficient	56,1%
Quality of support services to develop and manage H2020 projects	Insufficient	45,6%
Scientific productivity of individual researchers	Sufficient	42,1%
International connections of individuals	Sufficient	49,1%
Knowledge of candidates about framework programs	Sufficient	47,4%
Relative attractiveness of Horizon 2020 compared to other available funding	Sufficient	42,1%

Table III.3. Potential factors and their evaluation in Madeira participation on FP.

Considering an evaluation of the same factors¹ as “Very satisfying”, answers (6 or 10,53%) shown “Relative attractiveness of Horizon 2020 compared to other available funding” as main element. Although this appreciation, it represents a small proportion of total respondents if compared with its relative importance representation, which concentrated a top mark. One respondent even expressed that he became aware of “this program through this

¹ It has been added one question concerning the evaluation of “Attractiveness towards foreign researchers of the regional research system”.

survey”, where other also enlightened “lack of information and/or dissemination” of such programs.

Achieving a “Good” assessment, with one third (1/3) of answers or higher, “Scientific productivity of individual researchers” – 35,09% – and “Regional research performance (Scientific excellence)” – 33,33%, are in stable correlation with relative importance results, for both factors. These might be influenced by the inquired respondents, since they belong majorly to the research community.

“International connections of individuals” and “Knowledge of candidates about framework programs” were established as the leading “sufficient” factors (with 49,12% and 47,37% respectively).

An “Insufficient” evaluation has been given to “Implication of business sector in R&D expenditures” – 73,68% – and “Local organisations strategy and tools to encourage and ease the participation of candidates” – 56,14%. The first, related with private for-profit sector involvement in science and technology gathered, by far, the consensus of all respondents, as it represents the highest share of answers. Though this, business firms collected a substantial different representation as potential factor for participating in Horizon 2020, of one fifth lower (1/5 or 31 versus 42 answers). Highest answers (%) per factor are depicted in Table III.3 (above).

From the assessment of representations on FP participation and evaluation of their determinant factors, respondents agreed (*i.e.* lowest differential share) upon the “use of ERDF or regional policies as a lever for encouraging and building capacities for Horizon 2020”.

2) Analysis of the concordance or gaps

A feature captured by the analysis of interviews and survey (two open-ended questions) relates with private and public sectors.

Some register low private investment on scientific and technological activities (or even its indifference towards the subject) and lacking a Research and Innovation (R&I) culture in business firms. Still, as someone concludes, FP is “too far from SMEs”.

Wide opinions targeting institutional sector refer an under optimal investment in Research, where is missing ambition and political will. A consequent regional joint vision and strategy (addressed both for government and Higher Education sectors) follows for an effective implementation of a R&I culture, including FP participation.

Focusing on the research system, identified barriers are associated with research units and groups (small) dimension and fragmentation. For some, missing scientific cohesion – aligned with FP key-areas – hinders research sustainability and its scientific teams. One sharper viewpoint indicates the absence of competition on scientific production (among teams and/or individual researchers) and potential neglected linkages with, more competitive, mainland research units. As corollary, considers that lacks an institution who promotes the advancement of knowledge in science and technology.

Qualified human resources availability – full time dedicated – and their attractiveness weakens, an already perceived as, existent low critical mass. Besides, the willing to participate in FP is a time-consuming endeavour which may, or may not, deliver the expected benefits (*i.e.* funding) – as one noticed, there is inexperience and weak openness to Science Management.

Financial resources were related to mobility aspects, mainly subsidies for partnership prospecting abroad. Lacking facilities or well-equipped infrastructures (research laboratories) is also mentioned, added with an “outermost” barrier while carrying research work (for example, for organism’s transportation or mailing of samples during experimental activities).

Obstacles identified by individuals – interviews (1) and survey (2) on Figure III.2 – goes straight along with different angles and stages of a FP project, from applying for funding, grant evaluation to grant management.

Project development cycle	Obstacles	
	(1)	(2)
Call identification		• Knowledge and/or experience on FP
Idea generation		
Consortium Formation	• Establish a consortium and/or accepted as a partner in the best consortia	• Join established networks (national and/or European)
Proposal drafting	• Excellency of applications • Target evaluators perspective	• Absence of support services • Requirements complexity
Contract Negotiation		
Project management	• Partners commitment • Changes during project’s lifespan	

Figure III.2. Regional obstacles on Madeira participation in FP.

In both extremes there are who do not foresee any obstacle while others mention that these projects “can be quite complex”, specifying language proficiency (English) as an additional difficulty.

From survey results, lack of information and diffusion or even complete unawareness of FP programme is one of the highest obstacles identified. Some added precise issues, such as participation requirements and/or addressing specific economic sectors (e.g. SMEs).

Interviewed individuals (2) rise considerations on high level of competition at European scale as a handicap for regional participation. The main obstacle (herein as the one who collected more comments, *i.e.* 3) relates with “Consortium formation” and their establishment (no mention is made as it relates to project Coordinator) or acceptance as partner “in the best consortia”. Survey results also emphasise this factor, signaling existent blockages on partnership and networking that hinders an increased participation.

Proposal drafting is underlined in two (2) interviews, considering the “excellency of applications” and the necessity to target “evaluators perspective”. As a factor widely repeated in survey, it enhances non-existent support services – technical, financial and administrative – and highlights applications complexity and/or requirements.

Only one interviewed individual expressed his concerns about “different degree of commitment” between partners during project implementation and on survey results there is no reference to this stage. In both forums, “idea generation” as well as “contract negotiation” were not mentioned.

Identified levers gather consensus around individuals in interviews. Organizational widening threw collaboration and/or cooperation with European and international partners (third countries), outermost specific context for scientific and technological development work and/or financial factors enlists the major attributes for engaging in H2020 participation.

Levers	
(1)	(2)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Credibility among pairs, professional reputation and network • Cooperation with European and international partners (third countries) • Island singularity to societal problem-solving and learning environment • Financial features 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination actions • Regional government political and organizational innovation (towards FP) • Support services (technical, financial and administrative) • Training sessions

Figure III.3. Regional levers for Madeira participation in FP.

From survey results, one defends higher investment in R&I (both public and private sectors), more acute when specifically addresses government funding for private (for profit) innovation. This sector is seen as a non-negligible player from and in the research system since there is a claim for “scientific and technological development application in industry” but also importance on “knowledge and technology transfer towards the market”. Relevance is made to “Private R&D performers enlargement” and different business characteristics namely “early stage funding for disruptive ideas and start-ups” and more “opportunities for SMEs (“with scarce resources”, is written)”.

A wide majority mentions necessary governmental change towards R&I, demanding “political will for Research and Innovation uptake” with a newly institutional vision aligned with FP and based on a strategic policy for rising regional participation – with instruments and “real goals”, beyond merely raising up European funding.

One sets the need upon institutional disclosure of regional smart specialization strategy (S3) in European and international fora to capture strategic partnerships while other reflects his concerns on the investment in strategic and promising technologies to become "value added" partners. To this regard, disparity views are in place: departing from efforts concentration to a broader coverage of performing areas – expressly an “addition of new scientific areas within Madeiran S3, such as Education and Arts (for Tourism offer enrichment)” and/or investment in research areas other than Tourism, such as agriculture and environment.

Particularly to the research system, declared higher cooperation and pro-activity between Research organizations is expected and organizational solutions are hypothesized such as “Research groups consortia for further constitution and/or integration in R&D Units and Associate Laboratories, evaluated and funded by the National Science Foundation (Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia - FCT)” and even their potential affiliation to supranational Research Organizations. Others advance the need for a dedicated coordination team, responsible for FP management (perhaps, as written, “within the Agência Regional de

Desenvolvimento da Investigação, Tecnologia e Inovação – ARDITI”) for proposal drafting and partner prospecting support.

Towards human resources in science and technology, advantages should consider focus on medium and long-term outlook for researchers and research teams (behind short-term concerns) while promoting higher quality scientific products from new researchers and highly reputed Professors hiring (Higher Education).

Financial aspects target funding for institutional participation in information sessions and partners prospecting (contacts) – namely in “the” decision center, *i.e.* Brussels – and proposal drafting meetings abroad. On a regional context, expectations consist on the use of a specific instrument for ERDF support to H2020 financed projects and positive discrimination for research projects, regardless of links with R&D institutions.

Going further then only assemble a team for FP coordination and management, two respondents explicit mention the “creation of an Institute which gathers human and financial resources, aligned with S3 priority areas” and the need “of a specialized office dedicated to firms support in FP”.

A synthesis from major levers in interviews (1) and survey (2) that should be activated to facilitate and increase Horizon 2020 participation are identified on Figure III.3.

IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation

Madeirean FORWARD partners are currently engaged in a wider process for conducting a broader discussion with regional stakeholders to present the main uncovered necessities and opportunities for the future development of strategies and priority actions to increase participation on framework programmes for research and innovation and beyond.

Martinique

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems

MARTINIQUE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

under grant agreement No 824550

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction	3
Methodology.....	4
I - State of play of participation.....	5
1) Evolution of regional participation.....	5
2) Participation to the different programs and funding schemes	8
3) Thematic distribution.....	10
4) Stakeholders mapping (type of stakeholders).....	11
5) Participation profile (coordinator, partner, third party, WP leader ...)	13
6) Regional collaboration (with other Outermost Regions & Third Countries)	13
II - Analysis of participation determinants	16
A - Network analysis	16
1) Global connectivity.....	16
2) Thematic connectivity	18
3) Relative position	18
4) Third countries participation	19
B - Regional innovation system.....	21
1) Mapping the regional innovation system.....	21
2) Regional innovation system performance (French OR)	25
3) Regional research performance	25
4) Private sector implication	27
5) RIS3 priorities.....	28
6) Public policies.....	32
C - Regional organizational characteristics	33
1) Review of higher education and research organizations' participation determinants	33
2) Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions	34
3) Analysis of institutional strategies.....	34
4) Analysis of Support Services.....	34
D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level	35
1) Patterns of success and failure.....	35
2) Analysis of self-selection determinants.....	35
III - Analysis of the representations	36
1) Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders (analysis of survey; analysis of interviews)	36
2) Analysis of the concordance or gaps between survey results and the data	39
IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation.....	40
<i>A - Major obstacles</i>	<i>40</i>
<i>B - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP</i>	<i>40</i>

Introduction

The analysis of the results of the 7th Framework Program (2007-2013) and data on the ongoing Horizon 2020 program shows that overall participation reflects a low trend towards participation in the Framework Programs (FP).

Although insufficient on both programming periods, there is a modest growth margin. Indeed, although low, the success rate improves on H2020. This is a sign of greater ownership of the H2020 program and the beginning of a dynamic participation in calls for projects.

An analysis, based on the findings of the interviews and surveys conducted, highlighted several determinants of participation.

According to the actors, it is necessary to deal in the first place with the information deficit. At least one in two actors interviewed knows the existence of the program. However, they feel they are not well informed and poorly trained.

To improve and increase participation, the goal is to increase the number of applications. To do this, all the stakeholders were unanimous in setting up incentive effects. Laboratories and research organizations that have never applied for a position, mention obstacles such as complexity, the level of editorial and scientific requirements, as well as the important time devoted to the submission and implementation of the project. These incentive mechanisms will have to be specific for each actor, as the brakes on submission differ according to the type of actor.

Other determinants of participation:

- lack of dedicated support structure
- the lack of human resources within the laboratories, research organizations and companies to be trained at H2020 and also to strengthen the management and monitoring of the project,
- the size of calls for projects. The H2020 calls for projects are characterized by a strong scientific competition between European actors. Resizing calls for projects, especially for the Outermost Regions, could encourage partners to apply more.

The definition of an effective and coherent regional action plan could remove these barriers to participation. To begin, proposals for action to quickly remedy the information deficit. It will take the form of a communication in the broad sense (media, inter site, training session, workshops, meetings with the socio-professional world ...).

To increase the number of applications, the deployment of incentive mechanisms could help mobilize stakeholders. These mechanisms are, in addition, H2020-specific support mechanisms (mechanism for scientific profit sharing, valuation of salaries, valorization of research units, career development effect, etc.).

In addition, in order to take into account the specificities of the outermost regions and the search for a sizing of calls for projects, representativeness of the outermost regions is essential within the EU bodies or structures in charge of drafting the AAPs. The proposal is to appoint a referent in the OR unit for the drafting of the AAP....

Finally, for the regional plan of action, a reflection should be carried out jointly on a clearer articulation of the RDI financing schemes.

The multiplicity of funding mechanisms for research and development can often be ambiguous for the project leader.

Methodology

In order to establish the diagnosis of the ecosystem and following the shared methodology defined by NEXA, the partners were invited to take ownership of the project, its issues and its impact. A time of communication and explanation was necessary to obtain the involvement of all the actors. Also, to collect our data, FORWARD project referents conducted interviews, surveys and workshops with RDI actors.

As the RDI ecosystem in Martinique is small, the sample of stakeholders interviewed was limited to 25 (8 research organizations, 8 research laboratories, technology transfer actors, incubators, local partners who participated in calls for projects H2020, ...).

The Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique (CTM) working group composed of Tania REMY, Maguy MARIE-JEANNE and Murielle ALEXANDRINE relied on the following bibliographic data and resources:

- STDEII, Territorial Scheme of Economic Development, Innovation and Internationalization
- SRESRI, Regional framework for Higher education and Research
- S3, Smart specialization strategy,

This analysis is based on the CORDIS databases of the European Commission and Eurostat, as well as on various conducted by the CTM. Local partners have been mobilized to share their data and statistics on their structures, projects and others. There has been a real difficulty in mobilizing partners, given the time and schedule of each one.

For the most part, interviews were conducted virtually from an online platform. The survey was transmitted by Google drive.

Some data were difficult to collect in the absence of a regional scorecard for research and innovation and a comprehensive mapping of research and innovation. Our research and difficulties have allowed us to understand the need to set up this monitoring tool.

I - State of play of participation

1) Evolution of regional participation

The state of play of Martinique's participation in FP7 and in the fifth year of the 8th H2020 framework program shows a low participation of the actors. Indeed, there have been few projects submitted and funded on both programs. The bar of the ten files is not reached as well in submission as in retained.

However, there is an upward trend for the H2020 Framework Program in view of the number of projects submitted in evolution compared to the FP7 Framework Program.

Projects funded by the EU framework Programs		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Winds-Caribe ▪ NETBIOME ▪ EUCARINET 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ PEEI (2015-2016) ▪ GREEN BLADE ▪ PEEI (2017-2018) ▪ SOCLIMPACT ▪ CONNECTCARIBBEAN ▪ FORWARD

The success rate of FP7 projects is 100%, as there were only three projects submitted and funded. However, for the H2020, only six files on the eight draft applications were selected and funded.

Although modest, a dynamic participation in calls for projects is observed for the H2020 program.

The increase in the number of applications and the maintenance of the success rate require specific support and better representation in terms of the influence of the ORs.

	FP7	H2020
Global Success Rate	100%	75%
Number of projects / number of researchers		0,045
Number of projects / number of researchers per 1000 inhabitants		44,78

The ratio "number of H2020 projects / number of researchers" corresponding to 4.5% reflects the lack of involvement of researchers.

▪ *EU Contribution*

Overall participation in the framework programs did not generate a significant financial volume of credits for the projects of the territory.

Total funding provided to regional partners under H2020 is significantly higher than FP7. The financial return of the framework programs to Martinique in particular for H2020 is improving. The balance sheet remains modest but positive.

At the same time, RDI actors have become involved in collaborative projects funded by other EU competitive funds. The EU contribution is much larger than the total share of FPs.

These competitive funds do not present as selective criteria as FPs. The degree of involvement (application file, administrative and financial management, competition between researchers and others) is lower. In addition, these funds make it possible to meet the research and development funding needs for projects or thematic actions.

Total EU funding programs	
Total FP7 funding awarded to regional partners	€ 133 931,00
Total H2020 funding awarded to regional partners	€ 649 763,16
Total of other EU competitive funding awarded to regional partners (Life+, BEST RUP, BEST 1, Life Biodiv'OM, GROW RUP, Interreg Europe)	€ 5 738 158,00

	Horizon 2020
Ratio between H2020 and other EU competitive funding	11,32%
H2020 funding as percentage of GDP 2017	0,08

H2020 financing represents 0.08 of 2017 GDP. This ratio shows that there is currently no effect on the economy. H2020 is part of the culture of financing research and innovation in Martinique.

2) Participation to the different programs and funding schemes

Regional partners have positioned themselves better for H2020 territorial cooperation programs than FP7. These calls for projects respond to local issues and common and shared problems of the Outermost Regions. They have preferably chosen to respond to the calls of the following pillars:

- "Scientific excellence" dedicated to "human resources and the development of the careers of public and private researchers". Only one project was identified on the action for which a Martinican research laboratory is included (MSCA Funds). On this pillar, LC2S captures a significant share of funding (this is the largest EU contribution allocated to the Region).

- "Primacy industrial" especially with the tool "SME Instrument", implemented and coordinated by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Martinique. This tool has enabled a Martinican company FIB & CO, specializing in the transformation of pseudo-trunks of banana trees into design products, to solicit H2020 funding.

- "Societal challenges" for research and innovation actions to anticipate, reduce or adapt to climate change. A research laboratory of the University of the Antilles -Pole Martinique participates to the selected project. He is the leader of one of the workpackages of this project.

3) Thematic distribution

Calls for projects targeted by local actors focus on priority themes, answering some of our issues across the ORs and Europe. The research effort focused on the Social sciences and Humanities for both programs.

Total number of financed FP7 projects: **3**

FP7	SH2_Institutions, Values, Environment and Space	PE6_Computer Science and informatics
Number of projects for this thematic	2	1
Share of projects for this scientific domain	66.67%	33.33%
Total Amount of EU contribution for this scientific domain	100 633,50€	33 298€
Share of total EU contribution for this scientific domain	75.14%	24.86%

The 7th Framework Program has provided funding opportunities for regional partners for "cooperation" programs. These programs have supported research conducted in international partnership on one of the EU's thematic priorities. For the projects in Martinique, the actors favored partnerships on thematic priorities such as biodiversity and sustainable development.

Total number of financed H2020 projects: **6**

H2020	SH1_Individuals, Markets and Organizations and Infection	SH2_Institutions, Values, Environment and Space	PE8_Products and process Engineering
Number of projects for this thematic	3	2	1
Share of projects for this scientific domain	50%	33.33%	16.67%
Total Amount of EU contribution for this scientific domain	268 001,15€	251 370€	50 000€
Share of total EU contribution for this scientific domain	41.25%	38.69%	7.70%

Calls for projects on the Social sciences and Humanities are still favored by regional actors for H2020.

- *RIS3 domains analysis*

The scientific domains targeted for the Framework Programs correspond to the domains of specialization of S3. The European Commission, thus shares the same investment priorities as the outermost regions.

Also, the targeted effort on some priority themes has allowed the number of applications to be improved.

<i>Data</i>	FP7	H2020
Total number of RIS3 priorities in the region	2	2
Total number of RIS3 priorities with a minimum of 1 FP project	1	2
Share of RIS3 priorities with at least 1 FP project	2	1

4) Stakeholders mapping (type of stakeholders)

Organization types	FP7	H2020	Name of organizations
Number of Higher education establishments participating in FP	1	1	Université des Antilles - pôle Martinique
Number research organizations participating in FP	1	0	CIRAD
Number of public bodies participating in FP	1	2	PNRM (FP7) CCI Martinique (H2020)
Number of companies (PRC _ Private for Profit)	0	1	FIB AND CO
Number of SME participant to FP Projects participating in FP	0	0	
Number of FP beneficiaries as coordinator	0	1	CCI Martinique
Number of FP beneficiaries as WP leader	0	1	Université des Antilles - pôle Martinique (1 beneficiary for two projects)

The most active organizations for the H2020 program are the Higher education and research establishment and the public organisms (Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Martinique). They participated in at least two projects. They have both a share of 33.33% of total of H2020 projects.

The highlight is the under-representation of research organizations and the University (although the latter is very small). For Martinique, only one laboratory of the University (LC2S) is mobilized and active on projects of excellence scientific research.

The LC2S research laboratory is the largest partner with the most number of successful and funded research projects. He is the most offensive player for participation in the Framework Programs.

The concentration of participation at organization level is 50%.

However, the improvement of participation is noted.

It should be noted that a company via the "SME Instrument" tool has benefited from H2020 funding for its individual project.

5) Participation profile (coordinator, partner, third party, WP leader ...)

The LC2S research laboratory, the local beneficiary of the SOCLIMPACT project, is leading a workpackage for this project.

6) Regional collaboration (with other Outermost Regions & Third Countries)

	FP7	H2020
Number of projects involving a least a second partner from OR	1	3
Number of projects including a neighboring third country	2	0

OR Collaboration

The framework programs promote regional cooperation and strengthen relations between ORs, neighboring countries and third countries. For Martinique, H2020 does indeed strengthen its relations with some ORs.

Top 5 third countries, partners of Martinique

Regional cooperation is a strategic pillar for the outermost regions. They are linking more and more with Third Countries' scientific partners. Indeed, Third Countries are more involved in programming and joint project planning. Cape Verde, Jamaica and the Dominican Republic are the three most involved third countries alongside Martinique.

II - Analysis of participation determinants

The data collection made one of the following observations: the low participation of ecosystem actors in the framework programs is due to poor knowledge of the program. The actors often stated this observation during the polls. For companies and research laboratories, it is necessary to deal first with the information deficit.

Research laboratories strongly expressed the need for incentives to participate in the program. This implies that there is a strong willingness to participate in FPs and to put in place efficient and coherent incentive mechanisms.

In addition, statistical resources are often unavailable because a region cannot have enough specific data essential for an in-depth analysis of the ecosystem (examples of indicators: public sector research and development expenditure as a percentage of GDP, innovation expenditure SMEs excluding R&D as a percentage of total turnover, scientific co-publications, etc.) This can be explained by the absence of a tool for centralizing the territory's economic data.

Other observations made it possible to emphasize that:

- the tools available to ecosystem actors do not sufficiently encourage participation in the framework programs;
- organizations are not critical enough to apply because of their internal organization and the degree of autonomy of these structures.

At the individual level, the lack of involvement depends on several reasons:

- Some actors operate in structures that depend on organizations at the national level,
- the other actors show a lack of interest.

A - Network analysis

1) Global connectivity

The number of FP participation is very low, as the number of common projects selected and funded does not exceed ten projects.

Martinique has two common projects with some partners. Among the top 20 most active organizations identified, they have a project in common with the Region.

Number of top 10 partners having between 50 and 100 FP projects	3	Partners : - JOHANN WOLFGANG GOETHE-UNIVERSITATFRANKFURT AM MAIN - UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
---	---	---

		- GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITAET HANNOVER
Number of top 10 partners having between more than 100 FP projects	3	Partners : - AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS - ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA - AGENZIA NAZIONALE PER LE NUOVE TECNOLOGIE, L'ENERGIA E LO SVILUPPO ECONOMICO SOSTENIBILE

TOP 3	2 organizations are involved in 2 with Martinique :
	They have less 50 H2020 projects : INSTITUTO TECNOLOGICO DE CANARIAS, S.A. UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA
TOP 20	18 organizations are involved in at least 1 project with Martinique (between 10 and more than 100 H2020 projects) :
	3 have more than 100 H2020 projects : - Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas - Alma Mater Studiorum - Universita Di Bologna - Agenzia Nazionale Per Le Nuove Tecnologie, L'Energia E Lo Sviluppo Economico Sostenibile
	i.e. 3/18 (16,67%) have more than 100 projects
	3 have more than 50 H2020 projects : - Johann Wolfgang Goethe - U. A. M. - Universidad de Sevilla, - Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz U. H.
	i.e. 3/18 (16,67%) have more than 50 projects
	12 have between 10 and 50 H2020 projects :
	i.e. 12 out 18 (66,67%) have between 10 and 50 H2020 projects

Martinique is connected with good actors, very successful in research and innovation. These organizations are very present in H2020, because of their participation rate and the success rate of the projects.

It seems that Martinique does not capitalize enough of these collaborations for future partnerships and the advantages of belonging to collaborative networks at the best European level of research and innovation. These collaborations only remain punctual, because it is difficult to know the professional relationships that have developed.

2) Thematic connectivity

Thematics	Average number of projects of the partners	Average ranking of the partners	Number of organizations involved per thematic
SH1	25	5127	17
SH2	24	4992	43
PE8	1	10743	1
Global	17	6954	61

SH1 and SH2 thematics allow Martinique to be connected with at least three partners having more than 50 H2020 projects.

3) Relative position

Thematics	Name of Local Partner	Number of projects as coordinator	Number of projects as WP Leader
SH1	Chamber of Commerce and Industry	2	
	Université des Antilles – LC2S		1

4) Third countries participation

	Name of project	Name of Third Countries	Number of projects including a neighboring third country	Share of projects including a neighboring third country	Number of projects involving a least a second partner from OR
FP7	Winds-Caribe Eucarinet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Belize ▪ Curaçao ▪ Dominica ▪ Guatemala ▪ Haïti* ▪ Jamaïca ▪ Mexico ▪ Porto Rico ▪ Dominican Republic ▪ Trinidad and Tobago ▪ Argentina ▪ Cuba* ▪ Saint Lucia** ▪ Turks and Caicos Islands *** 	2	33.33%	1
H2020			0		3
Interreg Caraïbes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ OSAIN ▪ PREST* (Plateforme Régionale de Surveillance Télurique) ▪ CARES** ▪ CARI'MAM*** Réseau de gestionnaires d'aires marines protégés de la Caraïbe pour la préservation des mammifères marins ▪ MYCONOVA 		5		

FP7 projects that are mainly cooperation projects have encouraged the participation of third countries in two projects. The peculiarity of these projects is the experimental basin, often limited

to the ORs and the Third Countries. They fit little or nothing into the H2020 approach and projects. They are focusing more on regional cooperation programs, such as INTERREG Caribbean.

Indeed the existence of the “INTERREG Caribbean program” fosters cooperation in the Caribbean between the outermost regions of Guadeloupe, French Guiana, Martinique, Saint Martin and more than 40 other states and/or countries and/or territories. These countries are members of the three main Caribbean organizations, namely ACS, OECS, CARICOM, which are partners to the INTERREG Caribbean program.

For the record, Martinique is an associate member of these regional organizations:

- ACS: Association of Caribbean States
 - OECS: Organization of the Eastern Caribbean States,
- and will be soon admitted to CARICOM (Caribbean Community)

The participation of third countries in EU funding programs is more representative in the 2014-2020 "INTERREG V Caribbean" cooperation program. This is explained by one of the eligibility criteria is the participation of at least one Third country.

This program facilitates the participation of third countries, contrary to the H2020 program.

For Martinique, two research and innovation projects, OSAIN and PERST are supported by regional partners, leaders of these projects: PNRM and IPGP-OVSM

The thematic of these projects are environment and resource efficiency (OSAIN) and climate change and risk prevention (PREST).

These themes are common to RIS3 priorities. As well, Interreg thematic priorities are Education and training, SMEs competitiveness, Low-carbon economy, Climate change and risk prevention, Environment and resource efficiency and Social inclusion.

B - Regional innovation system

1) Mapping the regional innovation system

Research System Overview

➤ Research organizations

There are eight research institutes in Martinique. They represent 302 FTEs, including 39 in support of research. The permanent staff consists of 174 FTEs and the additional temporary research staff are 204, including 180 doctoral students. (2013 figures)

Number of public researchers in 2013 - ETP (Sources Sies)	Université des Antilles	CIRAD	INRA	CNRS	IRD	IFREMER	BRGM	IPGP-OVSM	Total
Research Organization	-	24	0	4	4	3	0	1	36

The available data are from the year 2013 and do not allow to have an exhaustive vision of the reality of the regional research and innovation ecosystem.

An update of the mapping of RDI actors is in progress.

The structuring of research in Martinique can be represented by the diagram below (from STRATOM 2018 Antilles and modified to specify the existing structures intervening in Martinique).

➔ *The companions of innovation: Main support structure*

<p>The PARM (Agri-Resources and Research Center of Martinique), unique Center of Technological Resources (CRT) labeled Caribbean, supports the development & innovation of the agri-food sector and contributes to the development of the development of bio-plant resources in Martinique .</p> <p>The missions of PARM are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ conduct collaborative research & development programs ▪ provide companies with technological services and resources to strengthen their competitiveness ▪ Accompany the training of professionals, students, doctoral students and trainees ▪ Supporting the development of innovative projects: from idea to marketing ▪ Support the emergence & development of strategic sectors, clusters of companies. 	<p>The CACEM Technopole, an incubator labeled European Center for Enterprises and Innovation (CEEI), supports innovation projects by offering an incubation space and a business incubator for young entrepreneurs. The Agglomeration Community of Central Martinique - CACEM supports this technopole.</p> <p>The missions of Technopole are :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accompanying innovative projects, ▪ Reception of young innovative companies through its nursery, ▪ Animation of a network of innovation actors called CAP-INNOVATION in order to bring out a true culture of innovation.

➤ *Tools for financing research development and innovation*

ESIF	Interreg Caraïbes Interreg Europe	National and regional calls for projects
ERDF Axis 1 Innovation for growth: € 11,000,000 EAFRD Measure 16 Cooperation /Sub-measure 16.1 Innovate in Agriculture and Forestry for Better Sustainability and Productivity: € 9,000,000	<i>Interreg Caraïbes</i> Global amount ERDF: € 64,292,905 Total OP budget: € 85,723,873 Total EU contribution: € 64,292,905	
FINANCING RDI		
EU Competitive programs COSME, LIFE, BEST, INTERREG Europe & Caraïbes		BPI - Future Investments Program (PIA) - Martinique Territorial Innovation Fund (MTIF)

➤ *Existing RDI policy tools*

- Absence of structuring tools classically present in France: SATT, competitiveness clusters, Carnot Institute, Regional Innovation Agency ...
- The Computing Center - C3I of the University of the West Indies gives access to a calculator whose primary purpose is to support the research axes of researchers in

the Antilles requiring intensive computing; Technopole Martinique's business incubator enables innovative start-ups to start their business in a privileged and tax-efficient setting because of its presence in the Urban Free Zone;

- An agro-transformation incubator project currently underway, supported by the CACEM-Technopole CACEM (in the construction phase).
- A Technology Resource Center (TRC) - PARM.

2) Regional innovation system performance (French OR)

	ERDF	Other financers
Number of beneficiaries supported	18	In 2016, 40 innovative projects were supported by the Technopole including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 19 concerned new projects - 72% were industrial type projects - 67% were projects in the agri-food sector - 90% were projects concerning product innovations
Total amount of grants awarded	€ 3 696 892	

From 2015 to 2018, the support of the CTM is mainly for projects or actions of technology transfer and support for innovative companies. For the ERDF, there are 18 supported companies. These innovations are mainly product innovations, industrial-type projects and projects in the agri-food and agri-processing sector. Calls for thematic projects are programmed to boost the consumption of the financial envelope of axis 1 "Innovation for growth".

In addition, this small number of supported RDI projects can be explained in part by the modest RDI ecosystem. Other economic variables are also to be taken into account.

As regards the H2020 program, the local partners interviewed in the context of the interviews and surveys, declare that they devote more of their efforts and means to ERDF aid. They highlight the important administrative burden of monitoring the project, the time and the financial and human resources to be spent over a long period.

3) Regional research performance

The research potential in Martinique is to develop, despite the limited number of researchers, only one higher education and research institution for the territory.

	2018
Total number of higher education establishments	1

Total number of research organizations	8
Total number of research groups	8
Total number of UA researchers (Pôle Martinique)	134

➤ *Research effort*

R & D staff and expenditure in 2013 (source Sies)			
Martinique	DIRDA M€	Public Researchers Staff (FTEs)	Research Support Staff (FTE)
	22,2	82	90

NB: DIRDE / Private Search Staffing is not available

➤ *Scientific production*

<i>Data 2018</i>	University of the West Indies Martinique pole
Number scientific publications -all fields	173

The University of the West Indies - pole Martinique presents a specialized scientific profile in Social Sciences, Medical Research and Humanities. She appears unskilled in Basic Biology, Applied biology-Ecology, Earth Science and Engineering.

Despite its small size, the university has a good publishing activity.

➤ *Research funding*

EU Contribution Université des Antilles - pôle Martinique		
Programms	ESIF	H2020
Number of projects	5	2
Total Amount awared	€ 103,000	€ 369 620

The University has decided to seek funding for operational programs and for the H2020 program.

The number of projects in the structure is larger under ERDF (5) than for H2020 (2). But the EU Contribution is more important.

This difference could be explained by the following arguments:

- the ERDF offers the possibility to the actors to make several requests for aid for low budget projects. The selection process does not require an application file to integrate a consortium. In the absence of overly selective criteria and for the sake of simplicity, the actors favor the use of ERDF funding.

They do not require scientific excellence and therefore no administrative rigor for the implementation and monitoring of the project.

- H2020 addresses projects of scientific excellence with multiple partners. The budgets of these projects are evaluated according to all the financing needs of the actors, they generally amount to millions. Thus, each partner can obtain a significant contribution from the EU.

Ratio H2020/ESIF amounts	3,53
Ratio ESIF / H2020 amounts	0.28

The ratio between H2020 funds and ESIF funds is **3.53**.

H2020 funding is higher than ESIF allocation. The intensity of R & I is also higher, even if the allocated funds do not exceed one million euros.

4) Private sector implication

Martinique (2015 à 2019)	Filers	Beneficiaries
Research tax credit	9	7
Innovation tax credit	6	3

From 2016 to 2018, only 7 companies are beneficiaries of the EIF. Of these, nearly 90% of beneficiaries have fewer than 50 employees. They evolve in the agri-food, natural risk management and digital sectors. Service firms perceive innovation tax credit more. The total amount of research expenditure declared is € 2.083M (2016-2018 period). Total innovation expenditure amounts to only € 383,000.

Martinique's economic system, composed mainly of small-sized companies, does not always dare to innovate or even develop them on their own funds. Some companies are reluctant to use this tax system for reasons of complexity of the tool or for lack of knowledge or sufficient information.

5) RIS3 priorities

➔ Presentation Priorities RIS3

<p>Biodiversity-Environment</p>	<p>Agro-food industry and terroir</p>	<p>The agri-food sector, linked to that of agriculture, plays a strategic and structuring role in Martinique. The agri-food industry IAA is the densest in the industry in terms of units and jobs (2350) and the 2nd sector of Martinique in terms of turnover (270 companies including 85% TPE and 48 SMEs in the industrial sector). Some 40 companies that are reputed to be innovative benefit from the support and support of the research community. Martinique's ambition for this sector / market is the creation of new integrated sectors on flagship products, particularly the cocoa, coffee, local starchy and maritime species with high potential. The objectives pursued for the region and which constitute differentiating segments and niche markets, include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the wider influence of Martinican products on international markets, - the transformation of traditional sectors into organic production (for example, research into the cultivation and production of organic sugarcane and processed products - spirit drinks AOC organic), - the valorization of the terroir
--	---------------------------------------	--

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the transformation of the fruits, vegetables, rare medicinal plants of Martinique , - the valorization of techniques / modes of production or construction method of the Martinique industrial heritage.
	<p>Biomolecules and co-products, agro bio-resources/ Innovation Markets : health, Pharmacology, Cosmetology, Cosmetics</p>	<p>A real dynamic of innovation stands out around the economic valorization of products from endogenous resources and integrated sectors. The main goal is to build marketing channels from endogenous resources, requiring the development of extraction techniques, production processes, and innovative marketing approaches. The main challenge is to improve production and services for the population (food, health, environment and well-being) while respecting the sustainability and protection of resources. The emergence of new projects around biomolecules and green chemistry and the creation of new agricultural micro-channels (including transformation) illustrates the new niche market segments for the region. One of the research axes of the valuation of plant biodiversity is the production of medicinal plants developed in Martinique by PARM, some of which are now listed in the national pharmacopoeia.</p>
	<p>preservation and enhancement of biodiversity</p>	<p>At a time when biodiversity and marine ecosystems in general are subject to human actions, growing pressure and permanent, marine and terrestrial, the issue of preserving biodiversity is crucial. The erosion of biodiversity is today a scientific reality that threatens the diversity of life; this reduction is one of the two major environmental issues of the 21st century, with climate change.</p> <p>Today, the scientific community intervenes and can be force of proposals to limit the loss of biodiversity. To this end, means of conservation are implemented including the creation of protection zones for threatened species (fauna and flora) and the creation and preservation of the genetic heritage of the species.</p> <p>This specialization can provide answers to environmental and ecological issues, particularly by restoring environments and ecosystems conducive to the reintroduction of marine and terrestrial species and the restocking of ecosystems. The economic valuation of this research can give rise to niches of activities such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the development of new ecological services and thus the creation of new jobs, - the rise of economic sectors: the development of sustainable tourism, - the creation of a sector for the reintroduction of certain terrestrial and marine species.

<p style="text-align: center;">Management and prevention of major risks</p>	<p>green building, analysis, control, prevention and adaptation of products to natural elements, health</p>	<p>Risk prevention is imperative for our society, as citizens aspire to live in increasingly secure and comfortable environments. Applied to Martinique (and the Caribbean), it is first and foremost about capitalizing on and valuing expertise acquired in a potentially dangerous area given the convergence and accumulation of natural hazards. The territory can also rely on interesting academic skills with differentiating lines of research and real will to valorize the economic fabric. Beyond the notion of management and prevention of major risks, the <i>innov'actors</i> have highlighted a great diversity of applications and translations on the economic level: means of analysis, sensors, warning systems, training of international influence, treatment solutions, crisis management, ...</p> <p>A particular focus is also made on the theme Eco3-construction. The eco-construction suggests for Martinique prospects and spin-offs, which will obviously be important in the building sector. Innovative construction methods that respect the environment or use natural plant materials should be sought. These materials, services or processes must be aligned with regulatory constraints (seismic risks) and above all have a better competitive price than the market price.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">ICT</p>	<p>Service publishing, digital applications and software</p>	<p>The digital sector in Martinique has around 2240 establishments for 3.3% of the regional economic fabric, a percentage rather lower than that observed in the other outermost regions. The Martinican ICT sector is structured around "mature" companies, from the field of IT services, networks and software development and "younger" companies, from the new economy, developed largely on a service innovation. Several fields of application draw the sector in the territory and consist of developing technological or non-technological innovations in the fields of other areas of specialization, notably ICT and tourism, ICT and health, ICT and education, ICT and food-tech...</p> <p>The challenge for the field is to promote and energize the digital ecosystem by supporting all innovative initiatives and projects that address strategic economic issues critical to the development of the economic fabric.</p>

<p>Renewable energies</p>		<p>The share of renewable energies in Martinique's final energy consumption is around 7% in 2016. Electricity production is mainly dependent on fossil fuels. The law for the Energy Transition for Green Growth (TEPCV) provides for an energy autonomy of Martinique by 2030. The Multiannual Energy Program (EPP) plans by 2023 a strong development of renewable energies to reach 58 % of electricity production (photovoltaic, wind and biomass). Martinique must, in terms of energy, move from a status of experimental territory to that of territory creating wealth and jobs implementing technological solutions that can be spread around the world. The territory has many assets to succeed in this conversion. The potential of renewable resources that can be mobilized, the stability of consumption and the ever-increasing cost of current electricity production are all factors that will encourage the search for innovative technologies and accelerate the dynamic process to reach its goals.</p>
<p>Silver economy</p>	<p>health, tourism, home automation, transport</p>	<p>According to a study by INSEE, 40% of Martinique will be over 60 in 2040 (against 21.5% in 2011) while this rate will be "only" 31% for the whole of France. Martinique will then, just behind Corsica, the oldest region of France with an average age of 48 years. The management of the demographic phenomenon clearly appears as the societal challenge n ° 1 in Martinique with the question of employment and associated precariousness. During the elaboration of the S3, this topic was in incubation to allow the realization of studies allowing to analyze and to validate the creative and innovating potential in the field in order to decide on the advantage effect of an intervention of the S3 in the sector. Today, this theme is elevated to the rank of area of smart specialization, with regard to initiatives and emerging projects in this sector. It is for Martinique to turn an apparent handicap into an asset by the constitution of a specific sector "Silver Economy" which will provide the advantage of meeting the social needs of Martinique but also to create activities (direct and indirect), value and jobs, and strengthen the intergenerational link. In addition, emerging companies and startups interested in this potential market to develop are moving towards the search for solutions, services, digital processes in the health sector, tourism, tourism and tourism. specialized housing, home automation, transport, leisure and well-being, ...</p>

Social and societal innovation - methods and regulations of social relations	advice, expertise, training	<p>The social and solidarity-based economy is generating a growing interest in the overseas territories, as well as throughout the country, in promising initiatives and a real development of innovative structures. Today, it represents 15.2% of local private employment in Martinique. In addition, Martinique's social economy employment grew by 11.7% in 5 years, while local private employment grew by 3.5%. In Martinique, the associative sector accounts for just over 85% of employees in the social economy. The S3 Martinique targets mainly for this area, methods and tools of social regulations. Based on scientific expertise developed by certain actors in the region, particularly methods of analysis and understanding of social relations, the objective is to improve social dialogue and the social climate within companies and organizations.</p> <p>This DAS occupies essentially the field of services with more specific variations on the professions of the council and the formation. The applications and opportunities are mainly in the professional markets. The desired and expected products and services are, in addition: initial training and continuing education, ecosystem of interconnected and nomadic applications for labor analysis (ICT). The technologies and scientific fields underpinned are psychology, negotiation techniques, sociology, and ergonomics, work psychology, SI, database management.</p> <p>Thus, the dissemination of good practices would help to amortize and resolve conflicts within organizations and companies, this being a major stake in Martinique (indirect job creation).</p>
---	-----------------------------	--

6) Public policies

Public policies	RIS3	Regional framework for Higher education and Research
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ RDI awareness: developing the culture of innovation ▪ Supporting innovative projects ▪ Pursue the construction of the innovation ecosystem 	Support research in private sector by promoting the employment of doctoral students

It is clear that there is no link between the participation of laboratories, universities and companies in H2020 calls for projects and research and development strategies (STDEII, SRESRI and S3).

As such, the Community wants to establish a culture of European calls for projects within the regional RDI ecosystem. A regional policy that would not be limited to supporting individual initiatives but encouraging synergies.

C - Regional organizational characteristics

1) Review of higher education and research organizations' participation determinants

Higher education and research organizations' participation determinants	 Université des Antilles	Comment
Size of the institution	< 500 equivalent academic staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Modest size that does not reach a critical mass of researchers to develop research excellence ▪ Very few researchers are integrated in networks to date, however some have kept a collaboration with some previous networks in the framework of previous projects, co-publications, ... ▪ Casual collaborative work ▪ No integration into EU expert groups but into ANR expert groups ▪ No administrative support service dedicated to H2020
Orientation	Analysis research intensity : n.a (ratio between the number of PhD students and the number over undergraduates)	
Scientific Excellence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Scientific productivity (measured by the number of publication per full time equivalent) : : n.a ▪ Impact (determined by the average number of publications' citation) : : n.a 	
Degree of international openness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ number of international co-publications : n.a ▪ Share of foreign PhD : : n.a ▪ number of foreign researchers : : n.a 	Lack of international openness, cooperation to build
Prior participation	LC2S, under the supervision of the CNRS, benefits from the scientific and technical expertise of this research organization, ranked among the world's leading research organizations for its excellent results in research and innovation.	

Many data are not available because they are aggregated in a global Overseas, which argues for a differentiation by territory, with the obtaining of own statistics.

2) Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions

UA intends to encourage research teams to become involved in the framework programs. A support device is under construction.

3) Analysis of institutional strategies

Higher education establishment: Université des Antilles

The training and research teams present in Martinique and Guadeloupe are specialized in issues that are singular for at least four reasons:

- Firstly, belonging to highly anthropised tropical island environments, interacting with many countries and territories (Caribbean, Americas, Europe)
- Then, the genetic characteristics of the populations present in Martinique and Guadeloupe are at the origin of the prevalence of genetic diseases such as sickle cell disease, diabetes or certain cancers. Aggravating circumstance, the change in eating habits associated with a reduction in physical activity leads, as in many countries, to increased obesity, diabetes and cardiovascular events;
- In addition, past anthropogenic activity has resulted in significant residual environmental pollution of island territories, with dreadful consequences for human health, as revealed by the problem of chlordecone;
- Finally, by 2040, Martinique and Guadeloupe will constitute the French regions where the average age will be the highest involving appropriate care of a growing population of older people. As for people suffering from chronic diseases, management by physical activity seems to be a good lever to improve the quality of life of older people. However, the tropical climate present throughout the year is a stress that forces the establishment of physical activities adapted to the environment.

All of these characteristics lead to the development of a "Health in tropical environment" cluster, whose activities revolve around four axes:

- Prevalent and emerging infectious diseases
- Cardiovascular vulnerability, metabolic and endocrine pathology.
- Chronic diseases, aging and physical activity in tropical environments
- Health and nutrition

4) Analysis of Support Services

UA intends to encourage research teams to become involved in the framework programs. A support device is under construction.

Supporting units are being structured the University Hospital Center of Martinique and the Chamber of Commerce and Industry.

D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

1) Patterns of success and failure

Projects	FP7	H2020
Patterns of success	Wind-Caribe NETBIOME-CSA EUCARINET	PEEI GREEN BLADE SOCLIMPACT CONNECTCARIBBEAN
Patterns of failure	PEEI	ZIKALLIANCE

2) Analysis of self-selection determinants

The analysis makes it possible to identify the motivations of the RDI actors who position themselves on the calls for projects:

- Build or join a network;
- Promotes inter-OR relations at research organization level;
- Have a better knowledge between the research institutes present in the ORs;
- Promotes exchanges on topics covered by calls for projects.

III - Analysis of the representations

Activities for the realization of the regional diagnosis

Number of survey respondents	Number of interviews conducted with research organizations	Number of interviews organized with non-respondents at H2020	Number of interviews held with people who failed	Number of interviews organized with people who obtained an H2020 project	Number of workshops organized	Number of workshop participants
4	11	7	2	3	1	12

1) Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders (analysis of survey; analysis of interviews)

ANALYSIS OF SURVEY

➔ Obstacles to H2020

Lack of support	Sizing H2020 calls for projects	Lack of information and structuring of networking
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • no support cell • no qualified human resources for file mounting • team size • insufficient critical mass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty connecting to the most successful institutions / networks • Relative attractiveness of Horizon 2020 AAPs given island realities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • standby failure • no effective transparency and information sharing • no network identified

➤ *Levers to H 2020*

Training	Networking	Strategic watch
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• support desk with a device mapping actors, assistance with editing and monitoring• Political leadership for setting up consortia	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Facilitate the connection to the most successful institutions / networks• Support strong project dynamics to enhance performance, attractiveness and publicize teams at the regional, European and international levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• visibility of projects• transparency of projects

ANALYSIS OF INTERVIEWS

➤ *Levers to H2020*

Network structuring	Training
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• To federate the actors of research.• Involve students on local issues shared with other regions.• Create a network with other universities and researchers• Experience sharing• Partnership organized with research teams for better responsiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• integration of the entrepreneurial approach in the programs especially for the SME instrument program• support to innovation• Support for H2020 accompaniment• Work to raise awareness among researchers about the benefits of participating in H2020• Proposal of tools ex: detailed guide of the type "recipe": what steps to realize in which order• pooling resources

➤ Obstacles to H2020

Scale	Project sizing	Human resources
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem of size and scale.• Size of research laboratories• Mixed research units are better recognized internationally. Non-tutorship laboratories are much more limited for involvement at the European level.• critical mass "insufficient for sufficiently ambitious projects"	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Themes not sufficiently related to local issues• Definition of innovation in small island market• Access to technology transfer means, to international markets• Distance from decision-making economic centers in major markets• Inadequate objectives for island territories• Not taking into account the economic fabric• Failure to support innovation in the island market• Difficulties accessing international markets• Distance from decision-making economic centers in major markets• Investment demanding compared to the chances of success	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Very important mobilization for the drafting of the PAA.• The University is not sufficiently sized• No support cell for project leaders• Lack of experience and engineering (administrative and financial management)• Complicated tracking of PAA and projects• No adequate supervision in the internal organization• Misunderstanding of the articulation between H2020 and ERDF.• lack of technicality• Weakness of the engineering of the support

2) Analysis of the concordance or gaps between survey results and the data

There is a concordance between the identified perceptions and the observed reality.

The same causes produce the same effects: the obstacle ratings for the survey and the interviews are the same as those examined in the workshops.

IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation

A - Major obstacles

Obstacles perceived and observed include: the lack of support, the sizing of calls for projects, the lack of information and structuring of networks but also the skills that are inadequate in relation to needs, the sizing of structures.

Two problems different from those identified in the survey and interviews emerged from the workshops: the lack of management and monitoring of calls for projects and the small size or the small feeling of the ecosystem.

The various levers proposed in response to the obstacles observed include:

strategic monitoring, training, networking, improved support to encourage the submission of projects, control of the management and monitoring of calls for projects, a better adaptation of calls for projects to the outermost regions, improvement of the capacity and the culture of the porting of calls for projects by the RDI actors.

B - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP

The two actions sheets requested by RUP are based on suggestions for solutions suggested during the workshops.

PROPOSED ACTIONS

➤ IMPROVE SUPPORT TO ENCOURAGE THE SUBMISSION OF PROJECTS

LEADER: ALL Ors

OPERATIONAL CONTENT:

- ❖ Identification and identification of local skills
- ❖ Setting up of training of consultants and actors
- ❖ Creation of networks for territorial information
- ❖ Creation of a platform dedicated to the rup accompanying network
- ❖ Targeted regular workshop
- ❖ Newsletter, strategic watch, dissemination and information tools
- ❖ Creation of a support cell
- ❖ Creation of a reflex culture AAP
- ❖ Adaptation of financial means

➤ APPOINTMENT OF A REFERENT IN THE OR UNIT FOR DRAFTING CALLS FOR PROJECTS

LEADER: RUP UNIT

OPERATIONAL CONTENT:

- ❖ Proposal for adapted financial rules
- ❖ Collaboration in the preparation of specific calls for projects
- ❖ Identification of a RUP Unit representative in the drafting phase of the AAPs
- ❖ Lobbying actions
- ❖ Choice of themes related to the needs of the ORs
- ❖ Proposal of methods
- ❖ Creation of a specialized unit for proofreading before submission
- ❖ Concertation of the actors

➔ EXCEL TOOLS

1. RDI Mapping
2. FP Participation
3. Regional Figures

TABLE OF ANNEXES

Annex 1: Interviews Protocol _ Research organisation Strategies

Annex 2: Interviews Protocol _ Other participating organisations

Annex 3: Interviews Protocol _ Keys to Success

Annex 4: Interviews Protocol _ Failor Factors

Annex 5: Interviews Protocol _ Self-Selection determinants

Annex 6: Workshops Protocol

Annex 7: Problem-Solution tree Poster

Annex 8: Template for the preliminary diagnosis*

Annex 9: Template for reports on surveys and workshops*

Annex 10: Template for the Regional Diagnosis and strategic plan*

Annex 11: Calendar deadlines

Mayotte

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems

[MAYOTTE]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Contenu

TABLE OF CONTENTS	2
Summary	3
Introduction	4
Methodology	5
I - State of play of participation	7
II - Analysis of participation determinants	12
A - Network analysis	12
B - Regional innovation system	13
C - Regional organizational characteristics	21
D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level	22
III - Analysis of the representations	24
A - Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders (analysis of interviews; analysis of survey)	24
B - Analysis of the concordance or gaps between survey results and the data	24
IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation	26
A - Major obstacles	26
B - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP	27

Summary

One of the specificity of Mayotte which has to be highlighted is the fact that, Mayotte is an outermost region of the European Union only since 2014. So the stakeholders did never benefit the FP Programmes, neither the credits of the Horizon 2020 programme.

Since then, Mayotte is facing an unprecedented development pace. More and more projects are financed by the EU and especially with ESF.

Stakeholders from Mayotte cannot count on basic facilities such as research labs. This situation lead to the lack of basic analysis of samples, for instance in medicine, chemistry or biology.

The lack of material and immaterial infrastructures impose local companies trying to cooperate to research centers from other networks on other overseas territories or in mainland France. Companies from Mayotte cooperate in particular in the Indian Ocean with La Réunion, those networks may punctually provide business-research partnerships in certain sectors.

Mayotte is definitely different to other OR in terms of readiness to participate to FP Programmes. However, local institutions try and set up measures and actions to cope with this situation with micro-loans, a Technopole project or the creation of business incubators.

Introduction

Mayotte has strongly restrictive features, the small size of the territory, its remoteness and its isolation from the European area, 374 km², 230,000 inhabitants, 8000 km from Paris.

Unlike other ORs, Mayotte does not have regional economic accounts. In this context, it is difficult to measure gross domestic product on a regular basis. In November 2018, a GDP update was carried out for 2016. GDP per capita was EUR 9,220.

The economic fabric is composed mainly of small entities with less than 5 employees (90%) and an economy marked by the weight of informal activities, which find very few opportunities in a narrow local market and heavily dependent on a small number of products.

The economy is mainly structured around traditional activities, and not very industrial, with a broad predominance of the tertiary sector. The sectors that produce the most value added are: trade, business and real estate activities, industry and energy (including agri-food activities), building, transport, financial activities.

Agriculture, fishing, aquaculture and maritime activities, constitute traditional sectors of activities culturally important and whose extension are source of added value and innovation. These sectors remain unstructured and currently face significant export difficulties.

SMEs are struggling to cope with exorbitant production and transport costs. This is a hindrance to the development of exports. In addition, there is a difficulty in bringing out high value-added sectors outside traditional sectors.

These factors impact the development of the economy and the capacity of research, development and innovation.

Since 2016, the Department Council of Mayotte supported the creation of the development and investment agency. The main goal of this agency is to promote the development and the investment in Mayotte. The agency instructs the investment aid files for the account of Department. It works on improving the attractiveness of Mayotte abroad. Each year, it organizes an event in Paris to promote investment in Mayotte.

Moreover, during the 2014-2020 programming, a smart specialization strategy (S3) has been adopted but this one is not animated.

In addition, the chamber of commerce and industry (CCI Mayotte), in partnership with the Department Council (CDM), works for implement the technopolis project.

So, in the absence of a research ecosystem profile, it's interesting to work for a creation of a network and accompanied the actors to integrate national and European networks and also improve the participation in innovation and research projects.

In this context, research, development and innovation activities deserve special attention to lay the conditions for success and the levers for the development of the territory.

Methodology

At the beginning, only one person was in charge of the FORWARD project in Mayotte. During the administrative phase, he had occasional help for some tasks.

First of all, we started by sending an email to all stakeholders of research and innovation to explain the project and the methodology developed by NEXA to release the diagnosis.

The contacted institutions were:

- INRA - National Institute of Agronomic Research,
- BRGM - Geological Research Mining Bureau,
- ADIM - Development and Investment Agency,
- CCI - Chamber of Commerce and Industry,
- CHM - Hospital Center of Mayotte,
- University of Mayotte,
- DRTM - Maritime and Land resources Division of the Department Council,
- ARS - Regional Health Agency
- Fahoullia MOHAMADI, chemistry researcher, researcher of PhytoKeyz
- and CIRAD - the Agronomic Research International Cooperation Centre for the development.

Afterwards, we organized a work meeting with the stakeholders to explain the Excel tools, and we asked their involvement to provide the data and to realize the diagnosis. Only five of them showed up to the meeting.

We transmitted the Excel tools to all partners. However, we had only one filled Excel tool. After several reminders, we didn't have other responses.

Despite few raises by mail and call, it has been difficult to mobilize the stakeholders. In June 2019, a single entity sent the Excel tool.

In order to stimulate the stakeholders, the new method was the "door to door". As result, we had few filled Excel tools.

On October, the FORWARD team for Mayotte grew up with two more agents among with the future correspondent in the project.

As previously with the door to door method, we went back to the different stakeholders for interviews and surveys in order to reactivate the interest to the project and to collect more information.

The particularity of Mayotte about getting appointment is that you have more chances by doing door to door than sending emails or phone calls. The fact that no one in the team was dedicated to FORWARD project only makes it difficult. Thus, it was highly time-consuming for this step. Adding to that, the person who conducted the previous contacts and meetings with stakeholders was out of Mayotte for the whole month of October and the new correspondent took over the FORWARD project during October and had only few days to reach the partners.

The main difficulty was to have time to approach the different stakeholders for a short period of time.

- In the big organizations: The first difficulty is to determine: who is the right person to prospect. Once identified, in big organizations such as CHM or ARS, they couldn't receive us for the short period announced.
- In the smaller organizations: Most of time, the project manager is also responsible of several topics which makes him/her hardly available. It has been very complicated to have them.

Unfortunately, some of the appointments for interviews have been cancelled for different reasons except five of them.

The fact that innovation concept is something new in the territory; most of the actors don't see the importance to dedicate efforts in it yet.

I - State of play of participation

1) Evolution of regional participation

The situation of Mayotte regarding the ecosystem of innovation is different from the other 7 Outermost regions and quite similar to Saint-Martin. Mayotte is located in the Indian Ocean which contributes to isolate the territory to the European research ecosystem. In addition, the economic activities are supported only by small enterprises with less than 5 employees (90%) and by an informal economic activities (20% to 60% employment are concerned). Department of innovation are inexistent within the SMEs located in Mayotte.

In order to better understand these specificities, it is also necessary to point out the legal status of Mayotte. Mayotte's main characteristic is related to its recent recognition as an integral part of the European Union territory in 2014. Article 349 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) recognizes Mayotte like an Outermost region; the rights and obligations of the European Treaties apply fully to Mayotte.

Prior to 2014, Mayotte was a French region (Département) with no access to the European structural funds neither the horizontal European programmes. This situation can explain the fact that Mayotte has no experience under the FP7 (2007-2013).

Moreover, Mayotte will need to gain more experience in terms of management of project in order to be able to submit a proposal under the H2020 European programme.

For the first time since the new legal European status, Mayotte is fully involved as partner of the ongoing project FORWARD financed under the H2020 European programme.

Given these regional particularities, the data collected, which are related only to the unique experience of Mayotte on Forward Project, cannot state *the evolution of regional participation* in the case of Mayotte. Equally, it was not relevant to fill up “the two first categories of the “RF-1 Participation data”: “ Global performance” which presents general indicators and “EU Contribution” which measures the funding obtained by regional stakeholders and their relative weight in the GDP”¹.

2) Participation to the different programmes and funding schemes

ORs can benefit from other horizontal European programmes that offer direct to their SMEs, their stakeholders in research and innovation when the priorities and eligibility criteria of the European call for proposal are in line with ORs needs.

In the absence of a research unit in Mayotte, stakeholders have not yet been able to mobilize the Horizon 2020 programme. However, the partners were able to draw on other European programmes outside Horizon 2020.

¹ WP2 guidelines, page 7

In fact, besides its unique participation on behalf of the regional authority of Mayotte, under the H2020 (current FORWARD project), stakeholders from Mayotte were involved in instruments such as BEST RUP, DG MARE call for proposal and ERASMUS +.

BEST RUP

BEST RUP is pilot project dedicated to the French ORs that was submitted in 2015 by a member of the European parliament. It was launched by the European commission on 15 January 2017 with duration of 3 years. This initiative is based on the previous programme BEST and aims at achieving an “inventory of species and habitats in the French Outermost Region”.

The main objective is “*to foster the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystems as well as sustainable use of ecosystem services including ecosystem-based approaches to climate change adaptation and mitigation and nature-based solutions, in the 6 French Outermost Regions (Guadeloupe, Martinique, Saint Martin, French Guiana, Mayotte and Réunion).*”

- **Activity 1:** Diffusion of species and habitats lists for the French ORs using the existing available data.
- **Activity 2:** Explore the implementation conditions of Mapping and Assessing Ecosystem Services (MAES) in the context of ORs, capitalizing on the Amazonian Ecosystem profile elaborated in French Guiana.
- **Activity 3:** Carry out one dedicated call for proposals for “swift small grants” of up to EUR 50,000. The call will be launched in the 3 Regions where the ORs are located (Amazonia – Caribbean – Indian Ocean) with the aim to empower and strengthen local stakeholders, including civil society organisations committed to local development, biodiversity conservation and sustainable use of ecosystem services in the ORs¹.

Under the BEST RUP programme, 3 Mahoran² projects were funded:

- 1) Carried out by **Mayotte Nature Environnement**, the project entitled "Inventory and status of echinoderm populations in Mayotte", for a budget of €6,000. This project started in May 2018 for 12 months. Among the main results of the project: an atlas of the echinoderms of Mayotte as well as action sheets. The project was also very useful because it enabled the discovery of new species for Science.

¹ Official description of the pilot project: <https://www.iucn.org/theme/marine-and-polar/our-work/eu-overseas/best-rup-project>

² From Mayotte

- 2) The second project carried out by the **Botanical Conservatory of Mascarin** is entitled "Knowledge and conservation of the unknown and threatened flora of Mayotte", for a budget of €50,000. It started in June 2018 for 12 months. Among the reports, there is a scientific report and recommendations in terms of species management. This project uncovered new species.
- 3) The third project carried out by **Les Naturalistes de Mayotte** and **ECOMED Indian Ocean**, is entitled "*The realization of an atlas for the distribution of Mayotte reptiles and amphibians and guidelines for conservation*", for a budget of €50,000. This project has also received CEPF funding in order to be extended to the Comoros. It started in May 2018 for 12 months. The main result is a species distribution atlas and a presentation of trends in species distribution in relation to climate change forecasts (modeling), and thus advocating conservation measures.

In the case of Mayotte, stakeholders concentrated their effort on less competitive calls for proposal. In fact, this initiative is tailored to fit the specific needs of the potential project's leader by offering them small grants with no constraints in terms of partnership. In addition, the beneficiaries benefit from less administrative burden and do not have to co-finance the project. This small grant scheme offers the flexibility required to support very small organizations that don't have a large view of the funds opportunities at the European level. They are also able to realize small study such as feasibility studies to fuel their day to day activities.

ORFISH PROJECT

The other strategy was also to engage in a European project with a role to play as partner which is in line with the operational capacity of Mayotte. This approach may allow Mayotte to benefit from the expertise of other European regions and ORs. At this stage, Mayotte does not have sufficient capacity to be involved as a leader of a European project. For instance, CAPAM (Chamber of Agriculture Fishery and Aquaculture of Mayotte) was partner of the ORFISH project led by Guadeloupe Regional Council. This project was funded in 2015 by the DG MARE and aims at providing a platform for exchange of knowledge on low-impact offshore fishing techniques among fishers from the outermost regions.

The project pursues three main objectives: developing and optimizing fishing techniques in order to alleviate fishing pressure on coastal fish resources; raising awareness of the opportunities to develop innovative low-impact fishing techniques for small-scale fisheries; and creating alternative sustainable fishing opportunities that will help consolidate jobs in the fishing industry. Coordinated by the Guadeloupe Region, ORFISH partners come from French, Portuguese and Spanish outermost regions.

3) Thematic distribution

The project funded under other European programme than the research program focused on 3 main areas: Biodiversity, Fishery and youth mobility.

Due to the lack of capacity and the absence of research ecosystem in Mayotte, it is difficult to define the thematic distribution. However, the smart specialization strategy defined specific investment priorities that can be also used as guidelines for any relevant future H2020 projects to be implemented in Mayotte.

Given the main potentialities of Mayotte, research projects could be developed in the future on specific areas such as aquaculture, biodiversity and agronomy.

4) Stakeholders mapping (type of stakeholders)

First of all, in Mayotte there isn't any organization active in H2020. Local research capacity is very limited in Mayotte with the exception of the interventions of national public bodies such as CIRAD and BRGM, whose regional offices are most often based in Reunion Island (BRGM and ADEME).

However some original research projects related to the natural resources of the territory were developed by the few stakeholders based in Mayotte but the approach is often limited to transposing metropolitan research programs.

The main stakeholders who might have the capacity to submit proposal under the European research program are the following:

CIRAD is specialized in international research on food security, sustainable development and adaptation of agriculture to climate change. 55 researchers are located in Reunion Island only one is located in Mayotte. CIRAD is a French research centre institution operating in over 90 countries around the world.

BRGM is a geological national service created in 2001. BRGM's activity is organised around 6 major societal issues: Geology and knowledge of the subsurface, data, digital services and infrastructure, risks and spatial planning, groundwater management, mineral resources and the circular economy, subsurface potential for the energy transition

Its programmes focus on scientific research, supporting public policies and international cooperation.

The main office in the region is located in Reunion Island and they have an office in Mayotte.

ADEME is a French agency active in the implementation of public policy in the areas of the environment, energy and sustainable development. ADEME provides expertise and advisory services to businesses, local authorities and communities, government bodies and the public at large, to enable them to establish and consolidate their environmental action. As part of this work the agency helps finance projects, from research to implementation, in its areas of action. Their work in Mayotte is dedicated to energy and waste.

ADIM (Development and innovation agency of Mayotte) is a recent entity (created in 2016 and started activities in 2017) that aims at contributing to the economic development of Mayotte. The innovation department is engaged in raising awareness on innovation, identifying innovative projects and mobilizing the entities in charge of training. ADIM organized the second edition of the Innovation days in Mayotte on 9 and 10th October 2019. They also promote the Made in Mayotte concept.

University center for training and research was created in 2011 and aims at developing a project research focusing on maritime environment and Afro and arab-muslim civilisations. The university offers courses on mathematic, literature and law up to the licence diploma (bachelor). This center could be in the future a strong lever in terms of connection with research European or regional network and capacity buildings in order to develop project under the European research programme with huge economic impact in Mayotte.

IUCN is a membership Union composed of both government and civil society organisations. It harnesses the experience, resources and reach of its more than 1,300 Member organisations and the input of more than 15,000 experts. This diversity and vast expertise makes IUCN the global authority on the status of the natural world and the measures needed to safeguard it. The IUCN French National Committee set up one representative in Mayotte.

Some original research projects related to the natural resources of the territory were developed by the few stakeholders based in Mayotte but the approach is often limited to transposing metropolitan research programmes.

The few participants registered, were mostly working on punctual project through the research national networks, public or private research organizations.

5) Participation profile (coordinator, partner, third party, WP leader, ...)

Most of partners are a part of a regional unit (Reunion Island) or national unit. They are under their policies and influence. As a result, their links with the different networks are generally through their core organization.

Under the BEST RUP, stakeholders were able to be leader as this kind of small grant does not require the involvement of partners. As far the other project mentioned in this report, the stakeholders from Mayotte were just partner.

6) Regional collaboration (with other Outermost Regions & Third Countries)

ORFISH and FORWARD project mobilized regional collaboration, in particular with ORs. For instance, the Orfish project enabled to identify the challenge of small fishery sector in Mayotte and the other ORs. This project aims also at facilitate the setting up of the Consultative European body on fishery within the ORs.

So in both projects, there were collaborations with the other Outermost Regions. Projects with the other ORs are helping a lot Mayotte in networking and taking experience in FP.

II - Analysis of participation determinants

A - Network analysis

“Newcomers to European research, seeking funding without well-developed networks and with no prior experience, are likely to fail” this quote from Simen G. Enger seems to be written for stakeholders from Mayotte.

Indeed, Mayotte is an Outermost Region since 2014. Thus H2020 is the first FP in which stakeholders from Mayotte can take part of.

Not any stakeholder from Mayotte has experience in European research program even less in FP Programmes. The networks in which they are integrated are the core organization of their structure.

1) Global connectivity

Local organizations are not implicated in any FP Programme so they can't be compared with others at European level or global. Very few organizations have the financial and structural capacities to be implicated in such projects.

So there is no any ranking list on H2020 participation which can be presented.

However, it can be noticed that some organizations like CIRAD, IUCN or BRGM work with organizations from La Réunion or mainland France thanks to their status. Indeed, all of them are branches from national unit or from La Réunion as said above.

2) Thematic connectivity

Like the global connectivity, the connection between local organizations and regional, European or global organizations by thematic is very limited or even inexistent.

3) Relative position

The relative position of stakeholders from Mayotte cannot be analyzed because of the inexistence of participation in H2020. This aspect will be relevant for the next programme: Horizon Europe.

4) Third countries participation

As for the previous parts, the inexistence of H2020 project from Mayotte makes this section very light or empty in terms of information.

However, collaborations under INTERREG programme have to be cited. Indeed, there is a programme between Mayotte, Comoros and Madagascar.

Mayotte has a foot in the region thanks to cooperation agreement with Seychelles, Comoros, Madagascar, Tanzania, Djibouti, Mozambique, Kenya and Mauritius

B - Regional innovation system

1) Mapping the regional innovation system

Since 2014, Mayotte is the 101 department of France. Mayotte is located in the northern Mozambique Channel in the Indian Ocean, 295 km from Madagascar, 1435 km from Reunion Island and 8000 km from France. Mayotte is made of two main islands and about 30 islets which represents 374 km².

There are 17 municipalities composed of 80 villages and 256 518 inhabitants in Mayotte (in 2017), among them, 84% lives below the poverty line.

This outermost region faces many challenges:

- A specific demographic trend: the population is highly composed of young people.

The graph below depicts the trends between 2002 and 2017. One out of 2 inhabitants are less than 20 years old. The fertility rate is also high: 4,9. In addition, the migratory movement is growing up with the arrival of women and children and the departure of young active person of students.

The

unemployment rate is high, in particular for the young people (57,3%). Mayotte is also facing immigration pressure with the massive arrival of young non-qualified people from the regional area.

eurostat									
European Commission > Eurostat > Regions and cities > Regions and Cities Illustrated (RCI)									
Regions: Cities Metropolitan Urban-rural Degree of urbanisation Border Coastal Island Mountain Outermost Statistical domains: Labour market									
▼ Employment rate, From 20 to 64 years, 2017									
Region	Employment rate, From 55 to 64 years	Unemployment rate, Females (% of labour force aged 15-74)	Unemployment rate, Males (% of labour force aged 15-74)	Unemployment rate, Total (% of labour force aged 15-74)	Youth unemployment rate, Females (% of labour force aged 15-24)	Youth unemployment rate, Males (% of labour force aged 15-24)	Youth unemployment rate, Total (% of labour force aged 15-24)	Long-term unemployment share (% of labour force aged 15-74)	Young people neither in employment nor in education and training (% of population aged 15-24)
Mayotte	i)	33,5 %	26,4 %	29,6 %	(u)	55,2 % (u)	57,3 % (u)		24,9 %

Source: Eurostat 2017

As far as the GDP of Mayotte is concerned, it reaches less than one third of the EU average. Mayotte is one of the lagging and least developed region of Europe. The table below depicts Mayotte's GDP per capita in 2017 was among the lowest (34%).

Regional GDP per capita in the EU in 2017
(in PPS, EU28 = 100)

The highest:			The lowest:		
1	Inner London - West (UK)*	626	1	North-West (BG)	31
2	Luxembourg (LU)*	253	2	North-Central (BG)	34
3	Southern (IE)	220	-	Mayotte (FR)	34
4	Hamburg (DE)	202	4	South-Central (BG)	35
5	Brussels Region (BE)*	196	5	North-East (BG)	39
6	Eastern & Midland (IE)*	189	-	North-East (RO)	39
7	Prague (CZ)*	187	7	South-East (BG)	43
8	Bratislava (SK)*	179	-	North Great Plain (HU)	43
9	Upper Bavaria (DE)	177	9	South Transdanubia (HU)	45
-	Île-de-France (FR)*	177	-	South-West Oltenia (RO)	45
11	Inner London - East (UK)*	168	11	East Macedonia, Thrace (EL)	46
12	North Holland (NL)*	167	-	North Hungary (HU)	46
13	Capital (region) (DK)*	166	13	Epirus (EL)	48
-	Stockholm (SE)*	166	-	North Aegean (EL)	48
15	Stuttgart (DE)	159	-	South Great Plain (HU)	48
16	Darmstadt (DE)	157	-	Lubelskie (PL)	48
17	Bremen (DE)	155	17	Western Greece (EL)	49
-	Utrecht (NL)	155	-	French Guiana (FR)	49
19	Warsaw-Capital (PL)*	152	-	Warmińsko-Mazurskie (PL)	49
20	Vienna (AT)*	151	-	Podkarpackie (PL)	49
-	Salzburg (AT)	151	-		

* Capital region

Source: Eurostat 2017

Regarding the distribution of employment in Mayotte, the most recent data are related to the years 2002 and 2007 (source: INSEE).

Répartition des emplois par secteur d'activités (2002 et 2007)

Source : INSEE

The economic activities are concentrated at the North-East of Mayotte and distributed around 5 areas : Nel Industrial zone of Kawéni (45 ha), the Port of Longoni, the valley of Longoni and Koungou (where the industrial and logistic activities are based), the Badamiers zone where the thermic central is located and the Majicavo zone for commercial activities. The rest of the region is dominated by informal activities with no structuration of the real estate for enterprises. (see next image)

Mayotte has great natural and cultural assets which are an excellent base for developing tourism. Agriculture, fisheries and aquaculture are traditional sectors, still poorly structured. So Mayotte has strongly restrictive features, the small size of the territory, its remoteness and its isolation from the European area, 374 km², 256,518 inhabitants, 8,000 km from Paris.

A fabric of companies composed mainly of small entities with less than 5 employees (90%) and an economy marked by the weight of informal activities, which find very few opportunities in a narrow local market and heavily dependent on a small number of products. As a result, the trade balance of Mayotte is -545.6% which clearly show the monumental gap between imports and exports.

Indeed, the almost inexistence of local production and even less exports is a real indicator of the lack of openness of local stakeholders to foreign countries.

Regarding RDI in Mayotte, in the absence of research entity and a team dedicated to the smart specialization strategy, weakens the capacity of stakeholders to mobilize the Horizon 2020 programme.

There is no research lab in Mayotte. Local researchers have to send their samples to Reunion Island or mainland France for analysis. Cooperation between companies, companies and research actors is relatively limited. The partnership between public authority, research center and company tries to structure itself by the regrouping of operators and the creation of cooperative under the aegis of the chamber of commerce and industry.

There is a lack of innovation in Mayotte's businesses. If we can say so, innovation in companies is rarely high in technological content. Moreover, the culture of innovation is not sufficiently developed to allow the development of reasoned valuation approaches. In fact, the “innovation” word is commonly misunderstood or unknown.

The development and investment agency (ADIM) has been identified as the main partner for the implementation of the smart specialization strategy. There was no dedicated team for this purpose. However, it has set up a network of innovation actors but essentially composed of services that deal with the financial and technical support of companies such as the management shop, the microcredit agency. Dynamism is underway to promote the development of innovative projects. In 2018, they organized a training course on innovation for network players. In 2018 and 2019, they organized an event in Paris entitled “Invest in Mayotte” to promote the Mayotte brand and promote the emergence of project leaders. Likewise, in 2019, they organized an Innovation Day to promote the culture of innovation.

2) Regional innovation system performance

Although not very connected to the economic fabric, some innovative projects, especially around renewable energies (first region with regard to the number of days of sunshine):

- Reflections initiated within the framework of the PADD on the orientations of development of the strategic sites of tourist development.
- Rural Pole Project

Strengths: Business sectors with potential for the future: aquaculture, fishing, agriculture, tourism, personal services, home help, social and solidarity economy, animation sector, ICT ...

Opportunities: Projects in progress: Opera, electric mobility powered by solar energy linked to the smallness of the territory.

Weakness: Innovation in ultra-marine companies is low in technological content, business cooperation is relatively limited, businesses suffer from a deficit of local skilled labor, support for companies in their innovation projects is almost non-existent, low amount or lack of innovation structure, no or few public collaborative research project

Threats: limited number of structures in capacity to be a European project leader, a banking sector very cautious on supporting projects, Continuity of innovation projects financing

in overseas regions facing a double constraint: cash flow difficulties and the possibility of commercial outlets

The Regional Competitiveness Index (RCI) is a tool provided by the European Commission in order to compare the performance of the NUTS-2 level regions across the European Union. The RCI report published this year includes 74 indicators to compare how European regions offer a strong ecosystem for socio-economic growth. This data allows citizens and stakeholders to analyze the progress made by their region and the whole European regions.

The scorecards of Mayotte

RCI scorecards facilitate the comparison of each region with its peers. Mayotte’s performance is compared to the average performance of 15 regions which are considered like economic peers in terms of average 2015-2017 per capita or regions with similar level of economic development. There are 11 pillars and 3 sub-indices. In this specific graph below, none of those regions are outermost regions. Nonetheless, due to the lack of data related to Mayotte, taking into consideration the sub-indices “Innovation” seems relevant for the purpose of this document. The sub-indices related to innovation clearly indicate that Mayotte overperformed with respect to its peers in particular in “technological readiness” and “business sophistication” pillar while the underperforming in “innovation pillar” is highlighted.

It is also known that implementing actions simultaneously in all the 11 pillars rather than 1 or a few of them can clearly contribute to a region’s economic growth. In the case of Mayotte, even the innovation’s sub-indices is higher in comparison to its peers, the graph shows very low performance in all the pillars related to “efficiency dimension” : “higher education and lifelong learning”, “labour market” and “market size”.

Source RCI report, European commission 2019

The spider graph below provides a general overview of the 11 pillars. It shows Mayotte's performance in comparison with an outermost region in its own geographical area (Reunion Island) and the European average.

Source : European commission, RCI 2019

The analysis of this figure provides some insights on Mayotte's situation. For instance, the basic education, institutions, Macroeconomic stability are the strongest scores and technological readiness is even above the EU average scores. Only 4 pillars out of 11 are high, the other ones in particular innovation is one of the lowest with respect to Reunion Island and the EU average scores.

3) Regional research performance

Currently, the regional situation leads to a lack of research performance. No research based or located in the territory, so there are no available figures to evaluate this aspect.

4) Private sector implication

The private sector is not really active in the regional innovation system. As the diagnosis data reflect it, very few projects emerged from EU funding system.

In 2017, according to INSEE Mayotte, 2,070 companies generated €1.79 million in turnover, including €587 million in added value (an increase of 12% compared to 2016). Their investments represent €124 million. 39% of the companies were not employing anyone, 48% were employing between 1 and 9 people, 13% were employing between 10 and 249 people, no company has more than 250 employees. The 2,070 companies were employing 12,450 people.

60% of the added value came from the retail, industry and construction sector which represent 5% of companies.

5) RIS3 priorities

The smart specialization strategy was elaborated on partnership governance between the State and the Departemental Council of Mayotte in coherence with the development of operational programs. The implement of this S3 comes from the prefecture of Mayotte, managing authority of European funds.

Unlike the other Ors, there is not a team dedicated to the implementation of this one. However, since the creation of the development and innovation agency in 2016, this one has been in charge of implementing it. Otherwise, some projects related to innovation are included in axis 3 of operational program, to develop new products about S3. The implementation is not yet concrete and no assessment has been made.

There are two types of areas selected:

Section 1. Areas of strategic innovation concerning the "knowledge, enhancement and sustainable exploitation of the natural and cultural heritage of Mahorais."

6 areas that could lead to the creation of new activities or diversify existing activities have been identified.

- 1. Sustainable exploitation of the sea and development of maritime activities;*
- 2. Agriculture and agro-processing;*
- 3. Recovery of primary resources (forest, water, "terrestrial");*

4. *Economic enhancement of natural and cultural heritage (including sustainable tourism);*
5. *Production and energy efficiency (solar) including in construction and transport;*
6. *"Social and Solidarity Economy (ESS) and Personal Assistance*

Section 2: Cross-cutting areas: three areas supporting the development of identified areas:

7. *Social innovation;*
8. *Information and telecommunications technologies and creative and cultural industries;*
9. *Mobility and logistics services related to maritime, land and air transport issues.*

6) Public policies

One of the Departmental Council (CDM) division was created in 2016, the Economic & Innovation Development Division in a reorganization process. This division works with ADIM in several actions. Most of their actions are based from RIS-IS.

These two institutions organize different events in order to promote innovation in the territory:

- Innovation Regional Fund: 1.500.000€ grant for companies, associations, researchers for innovating activities. This grant was created to financially support companies in their research activities. The idea came from the fact that financing innovation projects usually face two constraints which are both financial: mobilizing enough cash-flow to start the innovation process. The second constraint is the amortization of investment costs.
- **Technopolis**: Project in progress supposed to provide research labs, aquaculture centre, ICT labs, agro transformation, applied research lab.
- **Innovation days** are organized to
- **“Ecole de Code”** (Coding School): programme for young people (14 to 25 y.o) in coding, web development. The budget allocated for this project is over 320.000 € and should start in January 2020.
- **Innovation conquests**: 100.000€ each year to reward innovative solutions created in Mayotte.
- **Clusters**: The Economic & Innovation Development Division and ADIM work with CCI to put forward clusters which will be able to integrate the different markets of the nearest territories of the region. The locally most famous is the GEMTIC (ICT Mahoran Companies Group) with 88 companies.
- **Innovation Network**: The objective of this organization is to structure and support between partners in the innovation process. The different partners exchange ideas in R&I.

All of these measures are not specialized in one field or a specific type of innovation. For the moment, they try to promote any type of innovations.

None of these actions are dedicated to FP Programmes. So, the current policy does not create a specific interest to FP Programmes yet.

C - Regional organizational characteristics

1) Review of higher education and research organizations' participation determinants

As far as the university centre is concerned, there is no research entity yet. The Masters of Lectures are all attached to Metropolitan Units or Reunion. As the university's research teachers are attached to Mayotte's outdoor laboratories, there are no publications. There is no Master's degree in research in Mayotte, nor is there a doctoral school. However, the university centre's research teachers supervise M2 trainees and PhD students from other universities.

2) Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions

The CUFR makes significant efforts to adapt the offer of higher education to the demand for training. There is a strong dynamism of the demography generating an increasing number of graduates of secondary school likely to pursue in third cycle. There are about 20 training organizations really active in the territory.

The CUFR intervenes in partnership with the universities of Nîmes, Montpellier 2, Aix-Marseille and Rouen. Nevertheless, the goal is ultimately to obtain full university status. The launch of an in-depth sectoral study on investment and the training and skills needs of a dozen sectors is part of the prospect of a better understanding of the needs of companies, especially innovative companies, of a adaptation of the training offer and a monitoring system adapted to the evolution.

The offer of initial and in-service training does not cover all the needs and offers limited higher education while being developed at the CUFR. Moreover, there is no Master degree in the CUFR so far neither PhD programmes.

The low overall level of qualifications and local labor shortage is obviously a hindrance to the conduct of an innovation process

3) Analysis of institutional strategies

One thing to notice is that, there are very few projects financed by H2020 programmes. However, since 2014, more and more projects are financed by other Structural European Funds. The project of the Technopole (Science park) is one the very few project about researches and innovation financed by ERDF: 35% of the project. Local institutions have noticed that without these kind of resource, it will be difficult to develop R&I in Mayotte.

More and more information sessions are organized by the different institutions in order to sensitize on different European Funds and Programmes. The most active in this process are the Chamber of Commerce with the Innovation Division and the Department Council with its European Affairs Division.

- The Innovation Division of the Chamber of commerce has specialized innovation advisers who offer specific expertise in strategic watch, development and diversification strategy, standards and regulation and financing of innovation.
- The Division of European Affaires of the Department Council (DAECR) manages some European Funds so they have to inform the different potential stakeholders in different fields. Thus, a unit is dedicated to manage and inform stakeholders on Horizon 2020 programmes. In 2018, they organized a training session on Horizon 2020, ERASMUS+, LIFE, COSME, AMIF with 15 participants among with potential stakeholders. Seminars were organized in order to sensitize the stakeholders on the subject.

4) Analysis of Support Services

Local stakeholders can rely on some organizations such as ADIE which can provide financial support by giving micro-loans for SMEs.

The Development and Innovation Agency supports stakeholders as well on financing as on project management. Since 2018, on person is dedicated to innovation in the organization, he is the one coordinating all actions

Some non-governmental organizations play a role in supporting stakeholders on managing projects and entrepreneurship, in Mayotte. BGE is one of them, most of small structures work with BGE, as the economic structure is mostly composed of SMEs and VSEs.

D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

Capital information to have in mind: among the interviewees, only 2 are researchers or business entrepreneur. The others are agents in public institutions and are in charge of innovation in their organization.

1) Patterns of success and failure

First of all, there is no any candidate or participant on FP proposals.

The interviews were realised with stakeholders who could be concerned by FP programmes but never participate.

According to interviewees, Mayotte is a very small territory in which the big majority of companies is composed of very small enterprises in terms of financial capacity. Very few of the participants have heard of HORIZON 2020 even if since 2014 some of them are used to benefit from European structural funds.

2/3 of the interviewees thing that one of the reasons, innovations don't emerge is the lack of high education programmes nor research programmes. This situation is caused by the fact that there is

no student interested in research programmes. The students in high school don't know anything about research fields.

All of the interviewee considers that "innovation" is a word which is locally misunderstood by the majority of stakeholders. Most of people think that innovation is only about ICT. This is a general problem of information circulation which lead to this misunderstanding or lack of knowledge of "innovation" word.

Thus, local stakeholders are not informed about FP. Then there is no research structure based locally.

2) Analysis of self-selection determinants

In general, most of stakeholders find themselves unable to fulfil all the conditions and follow the procedures. The first argument mentioned by local stakeholders is the "complexity of European funds and programmes". It requires a certain level of English.

The second argument is that a certain financial stability is necessary which is quite difficult to obtain for the majority of the stakeholders. "Since you have to finance the project by your own before getting refund, the majority of local stakeholders are not able to participate". Adding to that, one stakeholder reported during a workshop that local banks are reluctant to give loans. So, there is a real problem about financing capacities of local stakeholders.

The third reason is the lack of links between local companies and European companies and research centres. "We can only get small work packages in big project, the bigger European companies get first", according to a CEO of an ICT company. Behind this argument, he points out the lack of visibility and recognition of local stakeholders outside of Mayotte.

This feeling leads to the lack of knowledge on the opportunities offered by the FP. According to a worker from local support company, local stakeholders say: "Since it is difficult to obtain those funds, it's not worth it to look for information about it".

III - Analysis of the representations

A - Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders (analysis of interviews; analysis of survey)

Five interviews were realised among them researchers, public institutions agents, and entrepreneurs.

- **According to 3 interviews realised, the main obstacles are that there are :**
 - No (technical) resources for research or organization to host research projects: research centres.
 - No specific infrastructure dedicated to R&I.
 - Not enough experiences in European Funds. Stakeholders from Mayotte can benefit FP only from 2014. It is only five years to experience those programmes.
 - Local small companies don't have enough financial resources to participate in FP programmes

- **The local stakeholders (during workshop) point out the following main levers :**
 - The awareness of R&I in academic streams and the attractiveness of Mayotte. In order to develop R&I and FP success stories, both of the subject have to be improved. "Mayotte as a whole has to work in innovation management mood" said one person during a workshop. It all starts with the animation of the FP and all European funding programmes.
 - Education, sensitization to R&I first. Currently, Mayotte doesn't have many researchers also because few students took this route.
 - Complexity of European funding programs could be simplified for example not systematically requiring spending before refund.
 - Companies support in innovation management
 - Technopole project

B - Analysis of the concordance or gaps between survey results and the data

With only 3 surveys collected, analysing the results was quick and they match with the collected data.

In Mayotte, there is a lack of knowledge on FP or H2020 which makes stakeholders fear to do the necessary procedures to obtain European Funds in general.

The fact that the resources are limited, in terms of needs for R&I, don't help stakeholders. Thus, very few projects are financed by European funds even less by H2020.

As a result, only five projects from the contacted stakeholders were financed by European funds. Among them, there isn't any project in H2020.

IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation

A - Major obstacles

There are these main obstacles:

- The shortage of human resources, the weak structuring of economic sectors and the lack of critical mass are a real obstacles.
- A small number of players in Mayotte with expertise in financial engineering, particularly those mobilizing European funds.
- Insufficient financial resources: most of the companies don't have sufficient cash flow to face with the needed investment before getting refund. This is true for ESIF as well.
- Low capacity for access to government procurement.
- Weak networks and support actors (means not enough to meet the demand for support, especially post-creation),
- Lack of innovation in terms of research in the territory: Mayotte suffer from "basic" structures necessary for R&I. For instance, for simple analysis, samples are generally sent to Reunion Island or sometimes to mainland France. This process makes any analysis, expensive and extends processing time.
- Most of the public researchers in the area are located in Reunion. Just like for research labs, if the different public institutions has set those researchers in Mayotte, they, probably have done the necessary to make them equipped. Some branches of the national research centres: BRGM, Energy Control Agency, CIRAD. The latter has 180 permanent employees, including 55 researchers, 125 technicians and employees who are based in Réunion, and one researcher is based in Mayotte.
- Limited research capabilities in all areas of the territory

B - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP

The treatment of downstream of the innovation chain (from idea to commercialization) is conditioned by the following points:

- The creation of masters and doctoral programmes: It is really important to locally have such programmes, without these, it will be difficult for the university to have publications attributed to it.
- The creation and strengthening of networks of actors capable of pooling and densifying innovation forces in the territory. One of the criteria of FP is the partnership requirement. As shown with the figures, local actors are mainly small companies; the idea is to evolve by groups in order to pool individual resources.
- The creation of thematic skills centres and transfers of competence in the territory (marine centre of excellence, agricultural centre of excellence, technopole...)
- Internationalization of partnerships: working with the entire scientific community in the Indian Ocean and even further. Mayotte is a small territory and need to open the opportunities on the region but not only. Certain issues have been already or are experienced in other territories, collaborating with others will help finding solutions.
- Developing collaborations with every research centre which has a branch in Mayotte. Collaborating with them will certainly lead to anticipate the needs of the territory.
- And, in any case, the establishment of a node of relations with the resources of R & D present in the other Overseas Departments and Regions (DROM) and in the hexagonal regions.

EXCEL TOOLS

1. RDI Mapping
2. FP Participation
3. Regional Figures

TABLE OF ANNEXES

Annex 1: Interviews Protocol _ Research organisation Strategies

Annex 2: Interviews Protocol _ Other participating organisations

Annex 3: Interviews Protocol _ Keys to Success

Annex 4: Interviews Protocol _ Failor Factors

Annex 5: Interviews Protocol _ Self-Selection determinants

Annex 6: Workshops Protocol

Annex 7: Problem-Solution tree Poster

Annex 8: Template for the preliminary diagnosis*

Annex 9: Template for reports on surveys and workshops*

Annex 10: Template for the Regional Diagnosis and strategic plan*

Annex 11: Calendar deadlines

Saint-Martin

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

Regional Diagnosis of OR's R&I ecosystems SAINT-MARTIN

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
innovation programme
under grant agreement No 824550

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS2

Introduction4

Methodology5

I - State of play of participation7

II - Analysis of participation determinants13

A - Network analysis14

B - Regional innovation system17

C - Regional organizational characteristics24

D - Analysis of participation determinants at individual level25

III - Analysis of the representations27

IV - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation29

A - Major obstacles30

B - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP30

Introduction

Saint Martin is a binational island of 87 km² (34 sq mi) located in the northern part of the West Indies, surrounded by the Atlantic Ocean and the Caribbean Sea. Since the Treaty of Concordia of 1648, the island has been divided between the French part, located in the north (56 km²) and the Dutch side, in the southern part (31 km²), by an open border.

In 2007, Saint-Martin, formerly a municipality of Guadeloupe, became a “*Collectivité d’Outre-mer*”. It therefore exercises competences conferred to Municipalities, Departments and Regions, as well as those transferred by the State.

Saint Martin is also characterized, on one hand, by its geostrategic positioning, being located not far from the American continent and within the Caribbean regional environment, and on the other hand, by its geopolitical and institutional singularity on a European scale, with two distinct European statutes: in the North an Outermost Region (OR) and in the South an Overseas Country and Territory (OCT).

The latest figures established in 2016 sets the population at about 35,746 inhabitants on the French side. The island counts more than 100 nationalities and is marked by a strong multilingualism (English, French and Spanish, among others).

The tourism sector is the local economic pillar, agriculture and fisheries representing a smaller part of the economic dynamic but whose structuring is underway.

In September 2017, Saint-Martin suffered the violent passage of Hurricane Irma, worsening its structural backwardness. This deficit of "basic" investments is also present in the social field, in particular in terms of infrastructures linked to employment, education and training and the medico-social field. As well as other ORs, the local job market is marked by a high unemployment rate, especially among the younger population.

The natural wealth, both land and sea, which is one of the island's major assets, is today seriously threatened by the adverse effects of climate change, the impact of which also affects social and economic dimensions. In addition, there is a persistent delay in waste management and treatment in Saint-Martin, hence the desire to establish a real strategy in favor of a circular economy, as part of a global green and blue growth perspective.

In such a context, research and innovation can constitute an important lever for socio-economic development in order to meet the needs of the territory and also allowing the emergence of new sectors with high potential. Encouraging participation in EU framework programs for research and innovation within the territory is therefore essential.

For the time being, research and innovation actions are, nonetheless, extremely limited, even non-existent, mainly due to a lack of infrastructures (no research centers, no universities, no centers of excellence, etc.) which thereby generates a lack of attractiveness (researchers, academics, etc.). This explains, in fact, the almost zero participation of Saint-Martin in research programs, also linked to the lack of expertise, information and collaborations to be reinforced to boost a real RDI ecosystem.

The approach undertaken within the framework of the Forward project, aiming to carry out a diagnosis accompanied by a regional action plan responds in this sense to a real need, which is that of identifying flaws, gaps but also solutions that can be brought in phase with the elements gathered in this diagnosis, in order to increase the capacities of the territory and its actors (private and public), in a local and regional approach and allow, in this sense, a better overview in the long term.

Methodology

The starting point for this exercise raised some difficulties for Saint-Martin, notably stemming from the absence of an R&I ecosystem, to which was added a serious shortage in terms of human resources.

In the framework of WP2, the CCISM proceeded as follows for the constitution and the implementation of the working group.

Identification of current and potential actors working on RDI thematics

Given the specificities of the territory's entrepreneurial tissue, it was necessary to identify actors from the private and public sector involved in domains related to RDI thematics. Naturally, this does not mean that these actors have necessarily benefited from Framework programs funding. As a reminder, the island of Saint-Martin is characterized by an essentially tertiary economy oriented towards tourism, with marginal development of the fishery and agriculture sectors, and an entrepreneurial tissue composed essentially of very small businesses (VSE) at almost 90%.

It seemed therefore pertinent to start this task based on existing tools. An RIS3 strategy had been defined for the territory of Saint-Martin in the framework of the ERDF-ESF operational program managed by the local national authority (*préfecture*). However, the RIS3 strategy has not been implemented by the managing authority of the program.

Its content remains, nonetheless, relevant and contains valuable information, all the more so given that the document required the conduct of a diagnosis, the mobilization of institutional and private actors and the definition of areas of strategic activity.

The following strategic activity areas identified were:

- Sustainable and intelligent utilities, construction and planning;
- Information and communication technologies and information society;
- Management and enhancement of natural and cultural heritage.

This information was a starting block to guide us in our work process towards the development of a diagnosis on the potentialities of our territory in RDI.

Obtaining access to data sources in order to assess the participation of local stakeholders in any framework programs was not a simple task and this can be explained by the following elements.

- Multiple window access points

The European structural funds are essentially the type of EU funding mobilized in the territory by economic actors: ERDF, ESF, the European fund for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries and EAFRD funding for rural development and agriculture. These funds are managed by different managing authorities.

The local national authority (*préfecture*) is in charge of the ERDF, ESF, funds for maritime affairs and fisheries and the Cross-border cooperation program between Saint-Martin and Sint-Maarten.

The Collectivité of Saint-Martin is in charge of a part of the ESF envelope and the EAFRD funds.

Therefore, the managing actors are diverse and each have their own data.

- Beneficiaries

Information on beneficiaries is not easily accessible and there's a lack of awareness and knowledge on other EU mechanisms and funds mobilizable by economic actors.

However, we did make use of the European database "CORDIS", which is the main source of information and results made available by the European Commission on projects funded by EU framework programs for research and innovation (from FP 1 to Horizon 2020) , in order to identify possible projects in which Saint Martin participated.

No projects were found, with the exception of a "*Desalination plant using recycled heat in Saint-Martin-Guadeloupe project*" which ran from December 1st, 1985 to December 31st, 1987. Unfortunately the content of the project is no longer available on the CORDIS database. We therefore do not have access to a more detailed presentation of it or knowledge of the partners that composed it.

Interviews and Surveys

Having very little information concerning the participation of actors in Framework programs, because there were no projects, interviews were carried out. The first step that seemed necessary to take was to get closer to relevant local private and public stakeholders in an informative and pedagogical approach allowing them to better understand the project and its objectives. This process was first done by email in coordination with the CCISM as a local partner of the project.

After initiating a first contact, interviews were conducted via physical meetings, by telephone and/or by email.

Below is the list of stakeholders interviewed:

- National nature reserve of Saint-Martin (*Réserve Naturelle de Saint-Martin*)
- Dauphin Telecom (private sector)
- Computech (private sector)
- Saint Martin Initiative (Initiative Saint-Martin)
- Cloud 97 (private sector)
- 3W Academy (private sector)
- ADIE (Association)

Services within the Collectivité and the CCISM were also interviewed.

I. State of play of participation

1) Evolution of regional participation

Saint-Martin's participation in Framework programs is inexistent. European projects implemented on the island are mostly financed by ESIF funds (ERDF, ESF...). Though we did not have any H2020 projects to analyze, we adapted our scope to projects that are currently being financed by the EU in order to better understand our ecosystem and its participation to European programs, as well as the key thematic interest points for the region. To date only one local actor, the Natural Reserve of Saint-Martin (NRSM), was able to successfully be a part of 2 competitive projects under the BEST initiative.

2) Participation to the different programmes and funding schemes

With the participation of the NRSM, we were involved with the BEST project in 2015 in collaboration with other outermost regions and today, this same stakeholder was also able to join the BIODIV'OM LIFE project.

BIODIV'OM LIFE

Natural Reserve of St-Martin (RNSM)

budget -

In terms of research and innovation, the region of Saint-Martin was able to participate in the two INTEREG projects:

Graph 1 - Distribution of the these INTEREG CARAIBE budget in Saint-Martin.

The CARIBIX project that is led by a private company was only funded up 50% of the total budget, the RADAR project was funded at 75% of the budget and the local government is the lead partner. Both projects aim to accommodate better facilities in areas such as fiber optic and meteorological monitoring systems.

Because of its specificity Saint-Martin shares its territory with its counterpart Sint-Maarten. Naturally this has led both sides to cooperate and mutualise resources. This context has indeed led to the establishment of a cross-border OP with a 10-million-euro budget, focusing on three major projects.

Graph 2 - Distribution of the Cross border OP on the island

To sum up, here's the main EU programs / projects in which Saint-Martin has taken part in :

EU PROGRAMMES	NUMBER OF PROJECTS	FUNDS
LIFE	1 Project - LIFE BIODIV'OM	LIFE
INTERREG Caraïbes	5 Projets – <i>CARIBIX – RADAR - Odyssea - Cari Mam - Cares</i>	FEDER-COOPERATION
Cross border PO	3 projects – collaboration projects with Dutch Sint-Maarten	Specific funds given to the island

In comparison, Sint-Maarten (Dutch part), as an OCT doesn't benefit from ESIF but has access to several sectoral European programmes.

To date, Sint Maarten has taken part in three programmes:

- Erasmus +: 3 projects
 - Caribbean Education and Culture Foundation: Youth mobility
 - Erasmus caribbean: Youth mobility
 - St. Dominic High School: Strategic partnerships for schools only
- Interreg Caribbean: 3
- Best 2.0

In the region however, the neighboring OCT's are more actively involved in H2020 projects:

Territory	Projects	
Anguilla	H2020 – 3 projects	Offshore navigation limited: SPLASH (Sail Plan service for energy efficient SHipping - innovative and revolutionary sail planning) & EONav (Earth Observation for Maritime Navigation) LADAR limited (Smarter 2)
	Erasmus for young entrepreneurs	1 new entrepreneur from Anguilla participated in a 4-month exchange in Finland (end date 09/12/2018)
British Virgin Islands (BVI)	H2020 – 1 project	Lancaster Exploration Limited: Sea Change
	Erasmus+: 6 projects	Sail Caribbean Ltd: VET learner and staff mobility (1) The Stay Academy: School education staff mobility (4) et VET learner and staff mobility (1)
	Best 2.0:	The National Park Trust of the Virgin Islands is involved in the cooperation project Securing pockets of paradise in the Caribbean
Saba	Erasmus+: 1 project	Foundation Social Workplace Saba: Youth mobility
	Best 2.0: 2 projects	
Saint-Barthélemy	Interreg: 3 projects	Association Saint-Barth Essentiel: Priority axis 6 - Cultural and natural environment Collectivité de Saint-Barthélemy: Priority axis 2 - Competitiveness of enterprises & Priority axis 6 - Cultural and natural environment

In comparison to other regions who are OCTs, we can note that the participation to European programs and more precisely H2020 projects are much more important. These regions are all members of the OCTA organization.

In total, two neighboring OCTs stand out having the most H2020 projects: Anguilla and the BVI.

3) **Thematic distribution**

The thematic distribution of funds for the island is not very even, the focus has been on upgrading infrastructures. Indeed, the territory of Saint-Martin is lagging behind for almost 10 to 20 years on certain aspects such as :

- Undergrounding communication networks;
- Wastewater treatment equipment;
- The deployment of optical fiber;
- Adapting structures to climate change;
- Public infrastructures abilitation.

Other EU projects were identified:

- **Biodiversity:** LIFE BIODIV'OM, CARI MAM
- **Climate Change:** Radar and Sea Level Station
- **Health:** CARES
- **Economic development :** CARIBIX and Odyssea
- **Infrastructure:** PO CTE
- **Field of sanitation:** PO CTE

Graph 3 -
Thematic distribution
taking all
programmes together

4) Stakeholders mapping (type of stakeholders)

The NRSM has been the only stakeholder that has been able to participate as a partner to a LIFE program project. In this project the NRSM, is the local coordinator.

However, we still wanted to understand who were the main stakeholders that participated in EU programs and what potential could they have participating in framework programs. With 90% of SME's, we've analyzed the profiles of stakeholders and partners and have concluded the following:

- Stakeholders are, for most, organizations from the public sector mostly because they have the necessary financial, structural and human resources to carry out such projects.
- Partners:
 - o NRSM: The Natural Reserve of the Island;
 - o Regional Health Agency;
 - o COM: The collectivité of Saint-Martin;
 - o EEASM: Establishment of water and Sanitation of Saint-Martin ;
 - o Dauphin Telecom (private sector in telecommunication) ;

Taking into account the specificities of Saint-Martin, in particular, the narrow nature of the territory shared by two distinct national entities, resulting also in :

- two different legal and institutional systems (OCT & OR);
- two local currencies (euros and guilders) adding to that a third currency for economic exchanges - US dollars
- two different models of governance leading to two distinct visions of economic development.

It seems relevant for the Collectivité of Saint-Martin and the CCISM to seize the FORWARD Project as an opportunity to take an overall vision of the territoire's actual equipment.

The idea is to optimize/ create partnerships with some potential partners that have been identified due to the specificities of the island. Such as,

- University of Saint-Maarten;
- The Coast Conservatory;
- Sint-Maarten Nature Foundation.

5) Regional collaboration (with other Outermost Regions & Third Countries)

Given its location and specificities, Saint-Martin cooperates with neighboring countries through EU projects. The major partners are:

- The other French territories: *Guadeloupe, Martinique, St-Barthelemy and French Guiana*;
- Surrounding regions: *The Dominican Republic, Jamaica, Puerto Rico, Dominica, Trinidad & Tobago, Cuba, St-Lucia, Turks & Caicos, Antigua and Barbuda, Barbados, Saba, Anguilla, the British Virgin Islands, Saint-Kitts-and-Nevis, United States Virgin Islands.*

PROJET	OR COLLABORATION	OCT /NEIGHBOURING THIRD COUNTRIES
CARIBIX	- Guadeloupe	- St Barthelemy
CARES	- Martinique - Guadeloupe	- Dominican - The Dominican Republic - Jamaica - Puerto Rico - Trinidad and Tobago - Cuba - Saint Lucia
CARI MAM	- Guadeloupe - Martinique - French Guiana	- St Barthelemy
RADAR	- Guadeloupe - Martinique	- Antigua & Barbuda - Barbados - Saba - Porto Rico - Sint Maarten - Anguilla - The British Virgin Islands - Saint Kitts & Nevis - The US Virgin Islands
ODYSSEA Blue Growth	- Martinique - French Guiana	- Colombia - Mexico - Cuba

II. - Analysis of participation determinants

A. - Network analysis

1) *Global connectivity*

Within this territorial diagnosis it was noted that stakeholders were not able to access framework programs. However, the Natural Reserve of Saint -Martin seems to have better capacities to access sectoral EU programs and therefore FPs. The interviews conducted with this actor made it possible to determine that the main factors enabling them to position themselves are the following:

The Natural Reserve: an actor belonging to a national and international network

The NRSM was created in 1998 and covers 3,060 hectares north-east of the French part of the island. The marine area, covering 2,900 hectares, is located on the plateau which stretches between the islands of Anguilla, Saint Martin and Saint-Barthélemy. On the land area, 154 hectares, or 11 kilometers of coastline, have been allocated to the *Conservatoire du Littoral* and are now managed by the NRSM, as well as 198 hectares of wetlands, distributed throughout the island.

It belongs to a national network: the network of French National Reserves. Nature Reserves exist throughout France (continental and overseas). They are managed respectively by the State, the regions or even local authorities as in Corsica. They pursue 3 inseparable missions (specific themes that we find in framework programs):

- Protect natural environments, as well as animal and plant species and the geological heritage;
- Manage sites;
- Raise public awareness.

Belonging to a national network,

- Facilitates the sharing of experiences;
- Allows skills development;
- Ensures the sharing of knowledge and expertise, in particular on the mobilization of funds and partnership networks in order to respond to project calls within framework programs.

Having solid human resources

The NRSM is a structure with a team of 7 main employees and 2 scientists working on projects. They frequently welcome trainees to complete the team and work on specific projects.

Through this analysis, it was possible to identify in parallel the blocking elements of the participation of other actors working on the similar thematics :

- Lack of participation in a national or international networks;
- The absence of internal resources / capacities oriented towards research and of expertise on mobilizing financial resources on an international scale other than "common" tools such as banks, structural funds (ERDF, ESF) etc.
- Lack of knowledge on FP : Clearly, there's not enough information about these financial opportunities;

All of these elements explain the low or even non-existent participation of actors in FPs.

2) *Thematic connectivity*

Saint Martin has no FP participation history, the Forward project being its first. This however doesn't mean that possible connections can't be taken into consideration for a future strategic RDI plan. The challenges of Saint Martin are notably identifiable in the cooperation axis.

Public policies are a vector to encourage the participation of economic and institutional actors of the territory to FPs. However, Hurricane Irma did not facilitate the development of a strategic action for RDI on the territory. On the contrary, it reinforced its structural delay.

3) *Relative position (As Saint Martin has no FP projects except FORWARD and no research institution, these informations cannot be analyzed).*

4) *Third countries participation*

Despite the absence of RDI projects on the island, there is still potential networks that can be utilized in a future approach to develop a RDI ecosystem. Indeed Saint Martin has always collaborated with several partners in its regional basin.

INTERREG CARAIBE & LIFE

Through these programs, Saint-Martin has collaborated with regional partners.

High Potential on innovative programmes

		OR Collaboration	OCT/Neighbouring third countries
	CARIBIX	Guadeloupe,	Saint-Barthelemy
	CARES	Martinique, Guadeloupe	Dominican republic, Jamaica, Dominica, Puerto Rico, Trinidad and Tobago, Cuba, Saint-Lucia
	CARI MAM	Guadeloupe, Martinique, Guyane	Dominican Republic, Turks and Caicos Islands, USA, Saint-Barthélemy

B. - Regional innovation system

1) *Mapping the regional innovation system*

The landscape of research and innovation in Saint Martin is unstructured. Initiatives are essentially individual or carried out by public bodies / institutions. The main actors that compose this landscape are:

Public institutions / bodies: The actors in this category consist mainly of providing support services for project development.

- Interprofessional Consular Chamber of Saint-Martin (CCISM);
- Regional Cooperation Service, Contractual Policies and European Funds service of the Prefecture of Saint-Barthélemy and Saint-Martin (ERDF Management Authority on the territory);
- Service in charge of Contractual Policies of the Community of Saint-Martin, European affairs and regional cooperation service (COM).

On the territory, innovation tends to be developed or emerged from individual initiatives or from the civil society which consists of private companies and associations:

Private companies

- Dauphin Telecom: Telephone and digital company
- Computech: Digital Business
- Associations:
- Initiative Saint-Martin Active, a support platform
- Nature reserve
- 3WAcademy
- CloudCom 971

Dutch side Mapping Research and innovation capacities:

- University of Saint-Maarten
- The Coast Conservatory
- Sint-Maarten Nature Foundation

This is largely explained by:

- A priority given to rehabilitating infrastructures, particularly after hurricane Irma, which led to very weak public policies on RDI and not being able to encourage the development of innovative projects and mobilizing a high degree of research capacity.
- The absence of a resource center: research institutions, agencies or actors oriented towards the development of knowledge and talents.
- The main economic promising actors and drivers of the territory are not big or structured unlike stakeholder's responding to calls for projects and being able to position themselves on FPs.
- The definition of territorial innovation is not necessarily nor directly developed and oriented in favor of the industry that drives the economy of the territory: Tourism.

The organization of the Workshop made it possible to reveal that the actors of the territory are aware that diversification is necessary, that research and innovation can allow a better positioning on the regional chessboard in particular within the tourism industry, given the island's advantages:

- Multicultural;
- Experience in terms of climate change and lessons learned from the passage of previous hurricanes;
- An open border with another legal and political entity;
- Optimization of resources in a cross-border logic;

The experience of the territory and its actors deserves to be valued and can be a source of inspiration or model for other territories.

2) *Regional innovation system performance*

OCT's neighbours,

"The Overseas Countries and Territories of the European Union (OCTs) make up a group of currently 25 countries and territories, which, despite a certain number of differences, have a lot in common, e.g. remoteness, insular micro-economies, a rich biodiversity, etc. The OCTs depend constitutionally on four European Union (EU) Member States: Denmark, France, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom.

Although the OCTs do not form part of the territory of the EU, they benefit from an associate status conferred on them by the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). The OCTs' 'eligibility by principle' to EU programmes other than the European Development Fund (EDF) was granted by the 2013 Overseas Association Decision (OAD) that came into force on 1 January 2014....

...., the OCTs are eligible 'by principle' for participation in and funding from EU programmes such as the research and innovation framework programme, the programme for the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises, the education and training programmes, the cultural and audio-visual programmes, etc., reflecting their status as members of the European family....."

(Report on the participation of the Overseas Countries and Territories in the European Union programmes during the period 2014-2018)

Although we cannot compare performances on framework programs in general, we can analyse two major neighbours of Saint Martin and think of future possibilities of partnership.

The first one is our natural partner St Maarten, who as an OCT has been able to participate in 2 EU programs for the programming period 2014-2020: Interreg Carribean (6 projects) and Erasmus+ (36 projects).

This exercise permits them to work on a certain number of key sectors for innovation on Sint-Maarten:

- Tourism: for management decisions - tools for reputation management and digital branding and analysis of real-time data for decision-making;
- SMEs: creation of a website as a one stop shop for all information pertaining to SMEs- from the start up point to the operational phase;
- Education: Enhancing existing educational institutions to offer online professional certificates especially in the hospitality sector;
- Research and development: research on which food commodity can be produced locally through the use of technology (greenhouse and drip irrigation technological system), renewable technologies;

The second possible partner is the British OCT Anguilla, the second closest territory to Saint Martin at a distance of 15 km.

In the 2014-2020 programming period, Anguilla has answered so far to 4 H2020 project calls for a total of 879 763€, this figure places the region as the 3rd best OCT performer on the H2020 program behind Greonland (8 projects) and New Caledonia (7 projects).

Although OCTs only used 1.9% of H2020 funding, it is clear that OCTs are performing better on FP program in general (**109 306 327€ total H2020 EU fund - Total for OCT used on**

the envelop 2 047 537€- Report on the participation of the Overseas Countries and Territories in the European Union programmes during the period 2014-2018).

We do not have relevant data to explain this , however we did notice that for Anguilla, Stakeholders were big private sector companies.

3) *Regional research performance* – (As Saint Martin has no FP projects except FORWARD and no research institutions these information cannot be analyzed).

4) *Private sector implication*

The peculiarities of the economy of Saint-Martin and more specifically of its entrepreneurial tissue, comprising almost 90% of Very Small Enterprises (VSEs), appears to be a determining factor in the low participation of local businesses in:

- European sectoral programs;
- Framework programs;
- Research and innovation projects though ESIF funding (ERDF-INTERREG Caribbean projects, INTERREG Cross-border cooperation V-A Saint-Martin, Sint-Maarten).

Few companies respond to calls for projects from European funding (Structural Funds) and even fewer from Framework programs.

Only two private companies have the capacity to do so:

- Dauphin Telecom: Telephone and digital company
- Computech: Digital company

5) *RIS3 priorities*

Ever since Saint Martin became a Collectivité, it has managed its ERDF-ESF funding.

In 2014, a RIS3 strategy had been defined for the territory of Saint-Martin when preparing the operational program (OP).

The managing authority was given to the Prefecture of Saint-Barthelemy and Saint-Martin (State) and the defined RIS3 strategy has not been implemented.

Its content still remains valuable and interesting. We can only analyze its results as future elements to take into consideration to develop an innovation ecosystem.

Setting up a RIS3 for Saint-Martin revealed two highly binding features that are still relevant for the establishment and development of RDI on the territory:

- The very small size of the territory (with nearly 40 000 inhabitants) having an essentially touristic and artisanal economy makes it difficult to multiply and diversify the national schemes.
- The absence of any public or private research organization (in addition to any institution of higher education) as well as any interface on innovation, both in the French and the Dutch part of the island.

As a reminder, the main areas of strategic activities forming the heart of the RIS3 and corresponding to major issues (socioeconomic as well as environmental) of the territory identified were :

- **Sustainable and intelligent equipment, construction and planning;**
- **Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) / Information Society;**

- **Management and enhancement of natural and cultural heritage.**

Within these main areas of strategic activities, some innovation focal points on which ERDF funds would be concentrated had been identified, even if the allocation of European funds was not entirely done in order to meet the identified challenges in the RIS3. Adding to that the structural delay of the territory impacting strategic choices of institutional actors and public policies:

- A priority given to upgrading infrastructures and equipments (earthquake, submersion ...) and post-IRMA reconstruction;
- R&D put in second place on a territory in reconstruction;

Keeping in mind that the allocation of EU funds was based on 11 objectives for the 2014-2020 programming :

- Strengthening research, technological development and innovation;
- Improving access, use and quality of information and communication technologies;
- Strengthening the competitiveness of SMEs;
- Foster the transition to a low-carbon economy;
- Promote adaptation to climate change as well as prevention and risk management;
- Protect the environment and promote the rational use of resources;
- Promote sustainable transport and improve network infrastructure;
- Promote sustainable and quality jobs, and promote labor mobility;
- Promote social inclusion and fight against all forms of discrimination;
- Investing in education, training and lifelong learning;
- Strengthening the efficiency of public administration;

The passage of Hurricane IRMA reminded us, however, that the issues previously mentioned are still current and could be tackled within framework programs to help develop “innovative” solutions.

6) Public policies

As there are no defined public policies in terms of RDI, no analysis in that sense can be done. However this does not constrain present issues tackled in other strategic policies that are being implemented .

The territory faces 2 main issues. The first comes from the lack of RDI policies even before hurricane Irma. With no university and research institution, the public body struggles to grasp challenges in terms of RDI as it can be for another OR. Also, RDI has always been interpreted by the idea of something “new”, or “innovation” as in something “different”. This idea doesn't match what FP program requires.

The second factor is indeed the structural delay. With 95% of the island infrastructure damaged, priorities were focused on reconstruction, cleaning, health, economy and survival needs.

However, three (3) main strategic action plans were defined before and after Irma.

- The Economic Development Action Plan 2014-2020

This document highlighted the areas on which the Collectivité will have to concentrate its efforts. It already revealed that the territory suffers from a considerable delay in terms of basic infrastructures accentuated by a strong demographic growth.

Therefore, development necessarily implies structural catching up such as the construction and adaptation of public facilities. This meant that the objectives of the Europe 2020 strategy could not be implemented as it is but rather to align investment priorities with the real needs of the region.

- The Digital layout diagram (State mandatory - undergrounding of the entire electrical and digital network by 2022);
- The Tourism strategy 2017 - 2027 ;

Written after Irma, the action plan for tourism focuses on building back the tourism economy, reconstruction of the high-end accommodation park, sustainability policies for future generations, promoting and supporting the development of high potential sectors etc.

The challenge today is identifying how can RDI contribute to pursue the reconstruction.

2020 New Year interview of Daniel Gibbs, President of the Collectivity of Saint Martin

“The future of Saint Martin lies in tourism but not only... economic diversification, economy 2.0, new technologies, but also economy 5.0, green and blue, agriculture, fishing, organic, environmental protection projects are great economic niches. Our actions to support investors and our active partnership with business support platforms and their creation makes it possible to support innovative business projects ...”

C. - Regional organizational characteristics

1) **Review of higher education and research organizations’ participation determinants**

Without any University on the French side, these analyses are impossible to make. The highest level of schooling on the territory is high school and two (2) BTS on the island:

- Tourism
- Manager assistant

2) **Analysis of the characteristics of higher education and research institutions** - (As Saint Martin has no FP projects except FORWARD, no University and therefore no research institutions these information cannot be analyzed).

3) **Analysis of institutional strategies** (As Saint Martin has no H2020 programs except FORWARD, no University and therefore no research institutions these information cannot be analyzed).

4) **Analysis of Support Services**

The importance of allowing a balance in the choices of future projects must be sought between a logic of excellence (which presides in the selections for calls for projects in FPs) and the logic of structuring the island's research and innovation ecosystem.

The expectations of local stakeholders, in addition to leaning on:

- The implementation of public policies allowing the development of research and innovation on the island;
- Creating a smart specialization strategy approved and implemented (S3) ;

... is to benefit from support and expertise services on RDI and FP programmes thematic.

The actual support is carried out by the Collectivité and is mainly focused on structural funds.

They do understand the need for more support services but they lack a strategic vision on the long term and resources. In the interviews carried out, the director of rural and maritime affairs revealed the need of human resources and trainees to support stakeholders in answering EU project calls in general.

It seems even more difficult for them to manage new calls when there is already a need for existing ones.

D- Analysis of participation determinants at individual level

There cannot be a clear analysis on the participation determinant to compare as it was revealed earlier on the Network analysis, as there's no participation of local actors as partners in FPs.

Being part of a national, european or international network helps in sharing of experiences and good practices, skills development, knowledge and expertise, in particular on the mobilization of funding and finding other potential partners.

These factors play a major role determining FP participation.

The absence of researchers, research institutions and more over the absence of a dedicated channel of communication - informing on FP calls for projects are clearly failure factors.

III. - Analysis of the representation

1) Main obstacles and levers according to regional stakeholders

The interviews and surveys allowed us to highlight stakeholders point of view of what the main obstacles and levers were:

- **Obstacles :**

- **Lack of coordination with local policy makers**

Throughout interviews that were conducted, the lack of a clear general plan for the territory has been mentioned many times. Today, it is important for stakeholders to understand the island's direction for innovation and research projects in order to plan projects that fit the needs and to facilitate their funding. The lack of follow-up of the RIS3 strategy played an important role in this regard.

- **Misconception of what funds are for lack of communication**

Sometimes, local actors do not fully understand that they can benefit from funds, and especially what funds can be targeted. Many continue to believe that it is impossible for SMEs to receive funding unlike larger corporations. This misconception stops them from positioning themselves and they tend to focus only on smaller projects, thus somewhat hindering the true growth and potential of their businesses.

- **Irma - The reconstruction of the territory**

The passage of hurricane Irma in September 2017 is a major obstacle to be considered. This major hurricane has changed a large part of funding demands over the past two years. Our territory being based solely on a touristic economy, hotels and restaurants urgently needed support. Funds and offers have been launched for such projects, rather than research and innovation. However, interviewees admitted that the reconstruction process could have been used to rebuild more efficiently and with more innovative ways. Unfortunately, this aspect was not investigated, and the window of opportunity seems somewhat closed for them. We could consider looking into alternative ways to continue developing our infrastructures and try to still use the momentum we are into going forward.

- **Financial capacity of companies to invest (banks)**

Companies wishing to receive some funding are now faced with the fact that local banking institutions do not consider the difficulties of the past two years that have affected their investment capacity. They now need to be supported to carry out key projects, but their financial situation does not permit them to do so on their own. New innovative financial schemes are necessary.

- **Size of the island and lack of collaboration with other operating rooms on projects of the same calibre**

Although there's joint projects between ORs, this process is not yet completely ingrained enough and entities sometimes forget that they can contact other ORs for help and support. Also, the island is small and does not have a developed ecosystem allowing it to understand larger projects. Our lack of collaboration in comparison with other regions around us is, as well, a factor as we could partner up with them on them and benefit from mutual exchanges and grow our expertise. Today this is becoming even more important in the competitive era we are in, if we do not work together.

Levers :

- **Economic and strategic plan for the island**

Having a shared clear long-term vision for the territory would allow all parties to align their strategies to move forward together. The size of the territory requires more strategy and planning to move forward accordingly and successfully. With defined objectives and goals, it would be easier for stakeholders to align themselves and be able to work together more effectively. This would boost the ecosystem and allow it to grow tremendously.

- **Organise and pull resources**

Working together and with other ORs is a lever that should not be neglected. There is a strength in numbers and ability to capitalize on pre-existing knowledge and ways of doing things can allow the island to catch up in terms of research and innovation. Mutualizing knowledge and

infrastructures could permit them to increase capacities and be able to overcome certain challenges that they currently face thus allowing greater participation.

- **Strengthening communication and access to information**

A greater effort in terms of communication and access to information and details should be considered to better understand the different funds available and share with the public where and how they can gain access to this information.

2) Analysis of the concordance or gaps between survey results and the data

When comparing the survey results and the data we can analyze that replies from respondents are in direct concordance with the findings that we were able to identify.

The absence of a R & D-friendly ecosystem to position Saint-Martin on FP programs can be explained by:

- The absence of quantitative data (scientific publications ...);
- Difficulty accessing qualified resources ;
- Absence / insufficiency of instruments likely to support innovative projects across the board and the need for mechanisms to support tangible and intangible investments of companies engaging in innovative projects;
- The lack of a business incubator, which can welcome in good conditions innovative project leaders;
- The generational gap between youth who are returning from their studies and are able to create such an ecosystem and the older generation. This gap can create a conflict in terms of vision for the long term.

IV. - Identification of major obstacles & levers to FP participation

A. - Major obstacles

The major local challenge to which innovative activities must be able to respond:

- Undertake efforts to catch up the backlog of basic infrastructures accentuated by a strong population growth;
- Preserving the environment in a global way;
- Optimize the connections within the regional area and the rest of the world;
- Revitalize and diversify the tourism sector;
- Reduce food dependency;

B. - Preliminary action plan, describing the operational objectives & instruments to increase the participation in FP

The 4 action sheets requested are based on suggestions for solutions which result from the workshop.

Operational objective n°1 : PROMOTE ECONOMIC DIVERSIFICATION

Expected impacts :

- 1 - Propose training adapted to the needs + training (university campus)
- 2 - Rehabilitation of public infrastructure, improvement of roads, landscape, lighting...
- 3 - One-stop shop englobing physical & digital;
- 4 - Identify sectors complementary to tourism (service dependent on food ...);

Actions to be implemented

- 1- Propose partnerships to create a University course on the island. Use the multilanguage assets to encourage international partnerships;
- 2- Prioritize the rehabilitation of infrastructures to be able to start a strategy to communicate on the island's economic potentials;
- 3 – Educate the population on digital economy, promote training on the digitalization/ digitalise the administration usage;
- 4- Develop long term businesses around the tourism economy (housing, etc.);
- 5- Capture big investors into the island;

Beneficiaries

- 1- The business owners in the island;
- 2- The young population that are growing with digitalization;
- 3- The government;

Stakeholders involved

- 1- local government;
- 2- Chamber of Commerce;
- 3- local businesses, infrastructures;

Existing tools to capitalize on

- 1- Actual rehabilitation projects on the island (FIBER installation in all sectors can favor the digitalization for public services and other sectors);
- Partnerships between both Dutch and French government ;
- EFSI funds.;

Resources needed

- Human resources to manage these actions;
- Government approval and understanding of these impacts;
- Long term strategy for the public and private sector;
- Big investors;

Timeline

Most of the infrastructure rehabilitation is underway. However a social plan preparing the population for change (training , digital economy, developing other economic sectors) needs to be put in place . This can be done in 2 to 4 years.

Indicators

- Evaluation of public infrastructures;
- Numbers of training and local appreciation;
- Data on business development;

Operational objective n°2 :

(RE)STRUCTURE THE R&I ECOSYSTEM

Expected impacts :

- 1- Create a real innovation strategy plan on a political basis- to build an INNOVATION VISION.
- 2- Build adequate infrastructures (observatory, research centers...);
- 3- Have a consortium group with SME's and public stakeholders to promote H2020 projects;

Actions to be implemented

- 1- Communication actions to present and explain FPs to SME's and innovation project holders;
- 2- Create a support cell to help build FP projects;
- 3 – Have local policies promoting R&I development for the island and a « HOW TO » contribute;
- 4- Clearly identify actors that can be of help;

Beneficiaries

- Local stakeholders and project managers;
- Local economy;

Stakeholders involved

- Consortium stakeholders;

Existing tools to capitalize on

- There is no existing tool to rely on. FOWARD being the first H2020 project.

Resources needed

- Human resources for training and support cells;

Timeline

This can be done during the Foward project (12 months);

Indicators

Create a time table for communication Policy and création of support cells

Operational objective n°3 :

EMERGENCE OF AN ACTION PLAN / MANAGEMENT PLAN AND R & I DEVELOPMENT

Expected impacts :

- 1- Attract researchers in the territory to work on projects;
- 2- Have a real knowledge on all the EU funds that can be used;
- 3- Have more young locals coming back to the island to work on R&I;

Actions to be implemented

- 1- Create a support cells/ One stop Shop to inform and help project holders;
 - 2- Work on Tax policy to attract R&I investors;
 - 3 – Have local and international existing on R&I opportunities;
 - 4- Create a report on Innovation, R&I for Saint Martin.
- ...

Beneficiaries

- Local SME's;
- International researchers;
- International investors;

Stakeholders involved

- Local government ;

Existing tools to capitalize on

FOWARD

Resources needed

Human resources for communication actions and support cells;

Timeline

Indicators
Number of H2020 projects
Operational objective n°4 : Increase project support for R&I development
Expected impacts :
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ 1- Have a real climate change awareness policy for the island; ❑ 2- increase the answers to the various EU call for project in the island (EU FUNDS OPPORTUNITIES (H2020, FESI etc); ❑ 3- Easy access to those information;
Actions to be implemented
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ 1- Define innovation for Saint Martin and what is expected; ❑ 2- Deliver training for the project holders and support cell services to understand FP projects; ❑ 3 – Make a state of play about the different instruments that can be used; ❑ 4- Have a dedicated infrastructure for Innovation;
Beneficiaries
The population
Stakeholders involved
Local government
Existing tools to capitalize on
Support cell on FESI and INTERREG project in Saint Martin
Resources needed
Employees able to manage a “Guichet Unique” to increase project calls respond
Timeline
12 months

Number of EU project in the island for innovation

EXCEL TOOLS

1. RDI Mapping
2. FP Participation
3. Regional Figures

TABLE OF ANNEXES

- Annex 1: Interviews Protocol _ Research organisation Strategies
- Annex 2: Interviews Protocol _ Other participating organisations
- Annex 3: Interviews Protocol _ Keys to Success
- Annex 4: Interviews Protocol _ Failor Factors
- Annex 5: Interviews Protocol _ Self-Selection determinants
- Annex 6: Workshops Protocol
- Annex 7: Problem-Solution tree Poster
- Annex 8: Template for the preliminary diagnosis*
- Annex 9: Template for reports on surveys and workshops*
- Annex 10: Template for the Regional Diagnosis and strategic plan*
- Annex 11: Calendar deadlines

PART III

Joint strategy

FORWARD

Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

(GA No 824550)

***Co-creation of the Joint Strategy
for OR's R&I ecosystem performance***

WP2 - Task 2.5

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550

Project Acronym	FORWARD
Project name	Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions
Grant agreement n°	824550
Project type	Coordination and Support action
Start date - End Date	01/01/2019 - 31/12/2021
Work package	WP2
Responsible partner for the WP	NEXA
Responsible partner for the deliverable	FRCT
Authors	FRCT: Lina Silveira Luz Paramio Gisela Nascimento Phillippe Holstein (NEXA) Lucio Quintal (ARDITI)
Contributors	All other Forward partners
Delivery date	15.11.2019 (first draft)
<p>The FORWARD project – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions” (GA N° 824550/952727405) is result of the call SWAFS-22-2018 “Mobilizing Research Excellence in EU outermost regions (OR)”¹, a coordination and support action (CSA) financed by the framework program Horizon 2020. The Regional Fund for Science and Technology (FRCT – Azores, Portugal) is responsible for Co-creation of the Joint Strategy for OR’s R&I ecosystem performance, Task 2.5, “Co-creation of the Joint strategy for ORs R&I ecosystem performance” (M08-M34). This task is part of the Work Package 2 (WP2), dedicated to the “Diagnostic of OR’s R&I ecosystem”, led by NEXA (Reunion Island, France).</p>	

¹ Articles 349 and 355 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU).
<http://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/100/outermost-regions-ors->

The need of a joint strategy

As foreseen in the Grant Agreement of the Forward project the Workpackage 2 “Diagnostic of OR’s R&I ecosystem” includes the Tasks 2.5 Co-creation of the Joint Strategy for OR’s R&I ecosystem performance that aims to “*present a common vision, mission and values for the OR’s to improve, promote and support their R&I ecosystem in the participation of the EU Framework Program*”.

The co-creation process starts from the beginning of the project focusing on the developments and results from the OR’s R&I² ecosystems mapping, Task 2.1. led by NEXA. The methodology used for the co-creation process collects the gathering of information, from the nine OR’s mapping diagnosis, consultation and validation process with regional partners. In this sense, the Task 2.5 foresees:

- ✓ An initial approach from the partners to design a document including the mission, vision and values of the OR’s R&I and propose orientations in fields such as capacity building and training, networking actions, policy making and communication;
- ✓ An analyses of the individual OR mapping and a follow-up of the comparative analyses to gather the information to include at the joint strategy;
- ✓ A consultation and validation from the project partners in peer-learning and validation the actions to be cover under the joint strategy.

The co-creation of a joint strategy arises as an orientation roadmap, which needs to be understood as an iterative process, a living document that should to be adapted and complemented along the project and be feed by the main four operational WP’s, namely

- WP2 “Diagnostics of OR’s R&I ecosystem”
- WP3 “Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans”;
- WP4 “Capacity building and training activities”;
- WP5 “Network activities”;
- WP6 “Connecting research and policy making: next generation policy tools”.

² Outermost Regions (OR’s); Research and Innovation (R&I)

Beyond the differences, a common vision and recommendations

An emerging transformation process is changing and shaping the world, as Europe, at an unprecedented speed: digital revolution, a “*post crisis*” financial system, climate change, social and demographic pressures, political changes in the world map, etc. These transformations, which crystalize social, economic and territorial inequalities, have to be taken in to account and tackled by governance efficiency, supported by equity measures and regulated frameworks to concentrated effort covering all territorial levels inside the EU. It’s fundamental that the OR’s join effort in a common strategy to show their R&I potential and assets as European living labs.

The article 349° of the Treaty on European Union, points out that the inherent, structural characteristics of the OR’s., minimize the opportunities of the realizations of their exceptional potential, through their differentiated characteristics. Limited critical mass, as well as limit and fragment research and innovation capacities, with no network alignment, inhibits their participation on collaborative and competitive, calls for projects. These characteristics although may be perceived as determinist “handicaps” they can be mitigated and approached in a positive light trough Forward project and show OR’s capacities and potential. The project Forward should be an opportunity to increase the participation of each region in the FP projects, as a mean for R&I development and reduce the gap with the mainland, as between the OR’s. This an opportunity for OR’s to demonstrate to the European Union that by improving equity measures it is possible to increase OR’s access to the FP and projects.

The message is that OR’s, despite its “handicaps and heterogeneity”, can contribute with their differentiated characteristics and add value to FP programs and in R&I ecosystems in Europe. Together, by having a better view of their challenges and opportunities, and putting in to place a joint strategy towards a common development strategy, OR’s can *showcase* their added value to the EU and globally. By creating conditions to improve infrastructure’s, human resources qualifications and promote the international networks, in order to increase critical masses, the OR’s, can mitigating the effects of the challenges of their permanent conditions by turning their limitation in to assets and show the added value of their unique characteristics.

The co-creation conditions

This document is dedicated to the “Co-creation of the Joint strategy for ORs R&I ecosystem performance” (M08-M34), starts from a bottom-up process, approaching the nine Outermost Regions (OR’s) Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystems under the WP2 - an intense process of co-design since the beginning of the project (January 2019). The main development process covered an ecosystem mapping, and diagnostic, which culminated with a strategical macro analysis applied to the OR’s. A consultation process that preceded the development of this document was the common exercises that took place during the Mutual Learning Event (MLE) in Brussels at the Regional European Week, 8th to 10th of October. This MLE allowed to validate by the partners the mission, vision and values of the OR’s R&I and to propose orientations.

The application of a strategic approach to the elaboration of the OR’s Joint Strategy includes an adaptive and **interactive co-creation process** that will developed under this following steps:

Figure 1. The stages of an *iterative co-creation process* for a common joint strategy.

The design of a common Joint Strategy for the 9 Outermost Regions (OR) R&I ecosystem has the ultimate goal to contribute to higher participation on FP projects³ through and in the international value chains. This goal implies an effective integration of the OR's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the European Research Area (ERA)⁴. The question that opens the Strategy construction should be:

How the OR's could together increase the integration of the OR in the ERA and take in to account OR's specific conditions?

AMBITION – Inclusive growth through knowledge-based economy

The goal is to accompany the transformation of the OR's toward a knowledge and innovation based economy to support an inclusive growth as expressed by the Memorandum of the Presidents⁵. In this constructive process, Forward aims to increase our capacity to attain and manage framework-financing programs in the EU and focus OR's position on of the European Research Area (ERA).

Also the increasing of the OR's participation at a national and European level networks and initiatives will allow to achieve key the improvement and empowerment of their R&I ecosystem, between others actions as free circulation of researchers, exchange and promotion of scientific knowledge and access and knowledge regarding technology.

VISION – Common goal to achieve excellence in the OR's R&I ecosystem

To reach the Forward's ambition a clear definition of what the OR's aims to achieve together identifying a specialization from the global competition, developing a distinctive expertise and value proposition i.e. being recognized as the resilience living labs. The vision is the backbone to the project and a single, clear direction, fostering synergies between OR's.

The starting of this process starts by defining a vision that sets strategic positioning of differentiation for OR's Research and Innovation ecosystem to address the challenges related

³ Since 1984, European Community research and technological development activities have been defined and implemented by a series of multi-annual Framework Programmes (FP); The Framework programme have been the main financial tools through which the European Union supports research and development activities covering almost all scientific disciplines. More information on research programmes and funding: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cros/content/research-projects-under-framework-programmes-0_en

⁴ The European Research Area (ERA) is a unified research area open to the world and based on the internal market. The ERA enables free circulation of researchers, scientific knowledge and technology. Source: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/era_en

⁵ Las Palmas, 2019

to the global transition toward more sustainable development mode. This mean to address the major ecological, economic and social challenges they face, transform their vulnerable development models and turn their unique assets into new sources of prosperity, the transition toward knowledge economy constitutes a major opportunity.

To attain this OR's need to have a clear conscience regarding their present conditions: common shared obstacle and levers. In this, regard the OR's need to foster critical mass of stakeholders and resources. The cooperation, especially in the context of OR's may be the answer: to reinforce the potential of their "outermostness" characteristics and use the OR's capacity for added value.

The results of the diagnostics and mapping allowed the OR's to identify the added values, as well as challenges, namely some that could be turn in to opportunities, as the European living labs with global resilience. Despite the heterogeneity identified within the OR's, due to its regional characteristics (human resources, geography, population, political situation and R&I characteristics) and different levels of maturity of their R&I ecosystem, there is space to find a coordinated joint strategy that is focused the OR's common features.

VALUES – Common principles respecting the regional specificities

In the context of OR's, designated by the same concept within EU Treaties, we have regions with very different levels of maturity, regarding the R&I ecosystem, the FP participation and experience, as well as different political system that requires adjusted approaches within the 9 OR's. Although, and having in to account this diversity, there are common needs, goals, and potential - a set of common values should address those pillars to sustain and advance toward a shared vision within the Forward project.

Taking in to account the conclusions that came out of the WP2 in one hand and searching for a common OR' strategic positioning of differentiation for OR's Research and Innovation ecosystem it was defined 3 main values for OR's R&I in Forward project context:

1) Synergies; 2) Integration; 3) Participation.

Synergies open and amplifies opportunities, reinforcing also the alignment between OR's, namely in FP participation in R&I and other development areas. The **Integration** is a main point identified as the missing link to promote the OR's R&I ecosystem. The **Participation** on Framework programs as H2020 and Horizon Europe increase the circulation of ideas, stimulate collaborations, reach and promote the growth of critical masses.

These three values intend to be the levers to lead the vision and inspire action for the OR's empowerment toward excellence in R&I.

ORIENTATIONS- Towards an action plan

The kick off for the action plan is a set of recommendations for OR's R&I, including the actions that will be proposed along the WP's to implement within a roadmap, on a step-by-step process.

Forward joint strategy aligns its goals and promote connections between OR's awareness to the State-members and European Union regarding to the OR's potential on specific I&R specialization. The joint strategy aims to identify concrete actions to empower the R&I potentiality and capacity to competitive framework programs, as well technical support for political, scientific and business investment contexts. These actions intend to contribute to tackle the effects of the permanent challenges that OR's face and determine objectives as future goals and actions, within and beyond the project timeline, as start of a new mindset, a transformational change for OR's, from the way they perceive themselves to the strategic positioning of the R&I in Europe.

AMBITION: Inclusive growth through knowledge and innovation based economy

The common ambition for the OR's R&I ecosystem has to be in line with the challenges of global competition and be able to promote OR's competitive advantages; therefore to build differentiated know-hows/expertise based on innovation for R&I is critical.

Based on the results of the regional diagnosis and the comparative analysis, Forward partners co-designed a common ambition for the OR's become the European worldwide network of living labs of global resilience (in a real open innovation playground mindset). The ambition aims to turn the critical challenges faced into innovative solutions in several fields as biodiversity conservation and restoration, energy transition, circular economy, multicultural society, tropical agroecology and biodiversity valorization, etc. This ambition will be achieved through an action plan that contribute for the integration of the European Research and Innovation Area, more involvement on the Framework Programs and increasing participation to international value chains. To that end, the Forward project needs to foster the condition to achieve some determinants as political will and synergies between the outermost regions.

The competitive advantages can come out of the OR's R&I specifics being approached as economic accelerators and step stones to reach an OR's sustainable development, in such fields as biodiversity conservation and restoration, ocean services, sustainability models, energy transition, circular economy, multicultural society, etc.,.

The ambition question was launched to the OR's R&I ecosystem as a question: **“Where do the ORs aims to achieve?”**

The reflection process arisen from the results of the comparative analyses and built along the WP2 consultation to the R&I ecosystem stakeholders in the nine Outermost Regions including the Mutual Learning event (MLE). The ambition pave the way towards a successful and full participation in the European framework programs as Horizon 2020 and the new framework Horizon Europe.

A more involvement at the ERA will display and empower the OR's expertise on the valuable research and innovation ecosystem's changing the awareness and perception of several determinants as **“handicapped” toward “differentiated” regions**. This premise will be crucial on the integration of competitive *consortia*. An effective involvement on the European Research and Innovation Initiatives promoted by the European institutions and

other key players implies efforts at networking and capacitation level in order to position the OR's expertise as differentiated and specialized.

Promoting a common strategy for OR's in the ERA sphere, within the Forward project, should **to incorporate individual regional goals for each OR articulated under a common umbrella the joint strategy, as a way to respect the heterogeneities and aligned vision from the nine outermost regions.** This Forward alignment helps to gain strength and highlights the creation of a unified research area for OR, with better visibility and access to the world and based on the internal markets characteristics. Moreover, the application of a **common strategical approach from the OR's to the ERA will allows:**

- ✓ Access to scientific knowledge transfer;
- ✓ Exchange of good practices;
- ✓ Access to a strong international network, namely to key player in the FP
- ✓ Promotes the creation of critical mass;
- ✓ Amplify OR's influence in the research/scientific world;
- ✓ Contribute to the increase of the (successful) participation of the OR's R&I ecosystem in framework programs.

VISION: Common goal to achieve excellence in the OR's R&I ecosystem

A definition of the vision will provide a way to be achieved, arising a perception and expectation about work developments and future targets, as well as, the power of anticipating and foresight needs and challenges.

A vision should be grounded on positive, realistic, attainable, challenging and target on self-effort, not dependent on third parties actions, that we do not control, as well as a desirable and achievable ambition for all regions, which overcomes the diverse characteristics, performances and aspirations.

A Forward project vision was designed taking in consideration the ORs development context and R&I policy framework including the Smart Specialization Strategies. The vision construction identified research excellence as based and the way to increase of participation of the OR's in FP. To attain these common goal it is essential to integrate research and innovation stakeholders in a common path and discussing at the same language towards a common clear vision. Instead of focusing heterogeneities, Forward provided the favorable conditions under the WP2 implementation support the construction of robust common vision. A paradigm shift on the OR's assets and potentials implies a new conscience regarding OR's conditions, based on diagnostic improvement, prospective, visualization, introspection and definition of the realistic ambition.

Under several dynamic discussion, Forward partners reached a consensus on the following common pre-vision for the OR's for the project:

“Foster political will and synergies between OR's to turn them into global resilience living labs through the integration into international value chains and increased participation in European research and innovation area.”

By Forward partners during the MLE in Brussels, October 2019

VALUES – Common principles respecting the regional specificities

The values are silent guides to mobilize and inspire the OR's and lead to a common roadmap. The heterogeneity of the OR's is a fact that Forward project, through WP2, diagnose and mapping, confirmed. Each OR has its own specificities that determined different levels of conditions to reach the vision. We can even identify natural differences by one side, from archipelagos, to islands, to enclaves, to tropical to Atlantic, to volcanic, etc. To another level of specificities, due to its natural conditions but mainly not only, as its maturity at the level of research development, critical mass, level of capacitation of the R&I Officers, FP participation, etc, The joint strategy is an exercise of finding common ground for OR's and the values are the orientation guides that sustain the vision. The Forward vision is supported on three common values, mandatory targets for the OR's R&I, as a central goal to attain in the project, within the actions of the workpackages:

Figure 2. Interactive dynamic of the highlighted three vision dimensions

SYNERGIES

Synergies open and amplifies opportunities, reinforcing also the alignment between OR's, namely in FP participation in R&I and other development areas.

The identification of R&I synergies between OR's is the first step to identify a common vision under Forward. These synergies will be capitalized by networking giving to the OR's a perfect platform to showcase their added value, namely as living labs and enhance these regions attractiveness for multi-sectoral knowledge-based policies. In addition, the networks

and partnerships based on sharing principles will allow increasing resources, human, financial and material as open access to equipment, infrastructures and investment. The synergies with European centers of excellence in order to address the needed solutions to the present and future global challenges.

These objectives will be also cover under the Forward WP3 approaching the main R&I areas under the thematic working groups and as well as in WP 5 specific in establishment of networking.

INTEGRATION

The integration is a main point identified as the missing link to promote the OR's R&I ecosystem.

The integration of Outermost Regions in ERA is fundamental key for the construction of a common vision, since this may enable OR's to reach the needed critical masses, that all OR has identified as a challenge to be overcome. Being perceived as a step that can lead the OR's to the knowledge economy and a lever of development the capacity to participate in Framework programs (FP).

To attain this goal it is important to take in to consideration the conclusion of the WP2 regarding the perception on the H2020, as FP is overlooked as a more sustainable funding. This identified challenge regarding the perception of H2020 restrains and limits the submission of projects and this minimizes the change of OR's to participate in FP projects in a fair and efficient way.

Another challenge that the integration in networks can help the OR's is to boost the condition for increase their critical masses to engage the OR's R&I for a knowledge economy. That can be achieved through strengthening the capabilities of the R&I human resources, as well as its infrastructures as was proposed under the Forward WP4, with training and capacity building actions.

The Forward can implement this point within the WP3, on the thematic working groups, in WP4, on capacitation and training actions, as well as under the Forward WP5, on the networking activities.

PARTICIPATION

The participation on Framework programs as H2020 and Horizon Europe increase the circulation of ideas, stimulate collaborations, reach and promote the growth of critical masses.

By engaging OR R&I ecosystem f in FP and projects, also allow to increase a global visibility, reputation and capability. It is crucial to attain excellence the increase of OR's FP participation as the mean to achieve R&I development and valorization.

Other structural funds should be promote identifying synergies to support the development of R&I following an effective model based on multifunds scheme. The mutual engagement in the funds hiring by synergies exploration will bring benefit, namely, between for European Structural and Investment Funds⁶ and FP, combined with the Smart Specialization Strategies (S3/RIS3) and internationalization process for the OR's. However, another question raised in the co-creation process of the Joint Strategy during the Mutual Learning event was the need to include EU standards evaluation criteria for PO (R&I) for a matter of normalizing rules. In this regard the overall OR's indicated in the mapping process that the national funds were seen as easier to access, therefore the FP was pulled to second plan, since it's perceived as more demanding, in terms of technical skills, and time consuming.

This operational step should be inforce under the WP3's thematic working groups, WP4's capacitation and training actions under the WP5 by the networking activities. The WP6 will provide the bridges and connecting actions between researchers and decision makers at regional, national and European level.

⁶ Article 174 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) provides that, in order to strengthen its economic, social and territorial cohesion, the Union is to aim at reducing disparities between the levels of development of the various regions and the backwardness of the least favoured regions or islands, and that particular attention is to be paid to rural areas, areas affected by industrial transition, and regions which suffer from severe and permanent natural or demographic handicaps.

ROADMAP – Recommendations

Following the **Forward previous priorities**, the roadmap aims to be an incentive to mobilize partners, engage stakeholders and provide guidelines to fit the next question:

How can OR's attain the desired ambition and reach their vision?

The proposed actions and steps comply with the following 4 SMART conditions:

Figure 3. Smart condition for the construction of action plan

This timeline and their specific objectives will be used to monitor and evaluate the results under the WP7 (Monitoring, evaluation and performance)

A set of proposal actions, in table 1, was validated by the OR's participants on the MLE Workshop, following the following the classification:

- **PRIORITY (P)** - to be implemented in the next 6 month – **determined by importance** (therefore the numbers next to the letter “P”);
- **IMPORTANT (I)** – to be implemented in the next 12 months;
- **RELEVANT (R)** - to attain during the next 26 months of the project and beyond Forward project.

OR'S PRIORITY ACTIONS

ACTIONS	PRIORITY LEVELS
Build a common OR training program for trainers and experts	P1
Include EU standard evaluation in the criteria for OP for R&I	P2
Showcase for regional policy makers	P3
Networks of regional established offices / equivalent	P4
Promote a common communication campaign on successful projects / individuals	P5
Launch calls for interests to build common roadmap for areas of interests	P6
A training program for policy makers	I
Training program for Researchers and SMEs on how to apply, how to communicate on their research	I
Financial support and schemes design for networking	I
Train/mentor researchers, students and companies for innovation action and knowledge transfer	I
Dedicate a part of INTERREG for common R&I program for OR's	I
Prize to give visibility to research	I
Establish a regional office to support FP participation	R
Interreg Europe project to improve ERDF management	R
A European representation in Brussels for R&I of OR	R
Launch calls for proposals for participative science projects	R
Launch calls for proposals for multidisciplinary projects	R

Table 1. List of actions by time frame and priority, defined by Forward partners in the MLE, following the result of the WP2 mapping and diagnose

This approach may fall within the context of the operationalization plan in the Forward Workpackages, namely carried out in the context of the actions provided for in WP3 (thematic working groups); WP4 (training and capacity building); WP5 (networking) or

through WP6 (connecting research to policy makers) and WP8 (Communication and Dissemination). By implementing synergies between the WP's of the Forward, the OR's can promote a more effective approach and reinforces OR's collaboration, enabling joint actions.

PRIORITIES FOR FORWARD JOINT STRATEGY

The identification of Forward priorities had as a starting point the Solution Tree analyses – that were applied to each OR's R&I.

During the MLE event in Brussels the results of the OR's diagnostic were presented compiled the Solution Trees from the OR's workshops. A common solution tree was created for OR's Forward representatives during the MLE working event. The objective of this work was having them validate and suggest actions/solutions/orientations in order to support the joint strategy construction. These stakeholders approach within the co-creation methodology provide to the joint strategy more weight from two angles of action: from OR's actions (aligned vision and ambition; roadmap and actions orientations) to EU actions, in order to the adjusted conditions for OR's access to FP.

Figure 4. Priority 1 - Design and implement more effective policies and funding schemes to increase the performance of the regional R&I system and FP participation. Source: Comparative analysis WP2

PRIORITY N°1: Design and implement more effective policies and funding schemes to increase the performance of the regional R&I system and FP participation

This priority has 3 main branches, in one hand there is the need to transfer the OR's in to a knowledge economy, in another branch the focus goes to the alignment of public funds and RiS3 and thirdly it's emphasized the need to use of existing funds available for the OR's to mobilize the FP participation.

This priority highlights the role of policies and funding schemes as a leverage to reach the performance of the regional R&I ecosystem and FP participation. In this case, of policies are approach as essential to reach the needed knowledge economy. The tree, in this point, proposes initiatives in order to foster political will and align the decision makers with the

R&I system needs and potential, namely through promoting trainings for policy makers and the use of RIS3 to improve the use of public funds and improve strategic priorities regionally. Another point that is important in this tree is the suggestion to reuse existing resources, as RiS3, PO and ERDF, in order to promote its effectiveness to support and promote the FP.

Priority 1- main orientations trough the WP's

WP3 - Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plan

- ✓ To develop a influence perspective in OR, per sectors, based on technical facts – common communication campaign on successful projects / individuals.

WP4 - Capacity building and training activities

- ✓ To Create opportunities for debate and pear learning: gather decision makers and R&I stakeholders, in order to learn more on EU and FP;
- ✓ Create trainings for policy maker.

WP5 - Networking activities

- ✓ Promote network actions, per thematic (interaction with WP3), to better integrate the OR's R&I ecosystem in order to promote their integration in the European Research Area and other relevant networks at OR level, as well as European and international level - Use ERDF to integrate ERA Net and other networking projects;
- ✓ Create initiatives in order to build regional roadmaps in strategic priorities.

WP6 - Connecting research and policymaking: next generation policy tools

- ✓ Follow up on the policy making procedures already taking place within the existing political organisms and approach the technical side of the question having present the existing policies;
- ✓ Involve the *Comite of Suivi*, the Assembly of Regions; Committee of Regions; RUP Presidents assembly in the follow up of Forward procedures in order to feed them facts to promote OR's influence and debate in the national, European and international political arenas;
- ✓ Create a OR's Forum for R&I ecosystem in order to showcase island/regions success stories.

WP8- Dissemination and communication

- ✓ Create a OR's Forum for R&I ecosystem in order to showcase island/regions success stories - promote OR's know-hows and assets

Figure 5. Priority n°2 - Create a collaborative strategy to integrate major European networks and create critical masses. Source: Comparative analysis WP2

PRIORITY N°2: Create a collaborative strategy to Integrate major European networks and create critical masses

This second priority has two main subcategories, one focus on the globalization and the other on communication as a tool to promote excellence of OR's.

The first branch mentions the need of proximity to create value and impact, namely trough the mobility programs for researchers and the creation of an influence group in the in EU (Brussels). They both share the same starting point: the cooperation between OR's.

The other branch highlights the importance of strategic communication and marketing as a toll for networks and critical masses creation. The communication strategy proposed is aligned with

existing resources, network and territorial marketing, namely using Forward research label, connect and promote the existing networks (EUROAXES; Enterprise Europe Network; Interrege). Once again the collaborative strategy for OR's is the pillar of this subcategories, as for this priority.

Priority 2- main orientations trough the WP's

WP3 - Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plan

✓ Under the experts of the thematic groups, create a group of influence by the use of data and the resource of their influential network;

WP4 - Capacity building and training activities

✓ Build a common OR training program for trainers and experts;
✓ Training program for Researchers and SMEs on how to apply, how to communicate on their research.

WP5- Networking

✓ Identification of the OR's existing participation and main networks to be established

WP6 – Connecting research and policymaking: next generation policy tools

✓ Connect the Territorial Marketing with influence resources – as common toll for OR's

WP8- Dissemination and communication

✓ Image and Brand Creation
✓ Territorial Marketing using existing resources for OR research and innovation. Connect with Lobby resources

ONGOING PROCESS

Figure 6. Priority n°3 - Foster the FP-shift in R&I organizations. Source: Comparative analysis WP2

PRIORITY N°3: Foster the FP-shift in R&I organizations

This third priority has three subcategories with recommendations. The focus is on performance (1), EU culture (2) and favorable environment for FP (3) and it has at his main target organizations and R&I system. This priority targets capacity building in research, EU culture and innovation skills. Another key feature is the FP strategy, namely promoting participation through smart strategy for organizations and use of other tools to encourage and participate in

FP, as incentives, skills training, disseminate about FP, as organize Open days, simplifying processes, create regional contact points to support participation, etc.,

Priority 3- main orientations trough the WP's

WP4 - Capacity building and training activities

- ✓ Promote innovation through training towards students in all OR universities
- ✓ Peer learning programs to support researchers to develop their entrepreneurial will and skills
- ✓ A common OR training programme for trainers
- ✓ Training on interpersonal skills, namely Leadership and team management
- ✓ Training on entrepreneurship, coordination skills, project proposal writing

WP5- Networking

- ✓ Develop collaboration research through a dedicated office

WP6 – Connecting research and policymaking: next generation policy tools

- ✓ Engage the regional and European decision makers in the capacity building actions, in order to engage them in the process and better know the network towards - for a clear political ambition towards research and innovation
- ✓ Identify financial support and other financing schemes design for networking, at a national and regional level
- ✓ Institute a regional contact point in each OR

WP8- Dissemination and communication

- ✓ Promote success, cases-events-campaigns
- ✓ A centralized receiver to disseminate the calls and to draw lists of valuable partners (OR association?)

ONGOING PROCESS

Next steps for the Roadmap

For the first time the OR's have access to information and created a technical project that allows to create a common vision that carries within it an ambition for the nine OR's, for their R&I ecosystem and gives a context of a project to implement actions, a common roadmap, to fulfil this vision. This vision was the result of a process that will extend along the 36 months of Forward project but also has the goal of creating the foundation for actions that can last long after the timeline of this H2020 project. It's essential to put in to place a strategic regional plan that target a mindset change, but also has concrete consequences, as the creation of a Regional Contact Point and other influence structures that should be implemented at OR's level, having the decision makers and R&I stakeholders as its target. The **added value** of the OR's should be recognized in the framework programs in order to promote the development of the OR's R&I ecosystem, involving more researchers, incentive the private sector to engage with science and technology, through training, networking and thematic actions.

The **swift of image** regarding the OR's is essential to create conscience at a national and European level on the positive contribution the OR's R&I ecosystem can give to European and global challenges. It's essential to create opportunities to promote a stronger OR R&I at EU and international level in order to move towards the creation of a common voice for OR's in the future Horizon Europe, starting with Forward and continuing with its effects beyond this context.

In the project context, it is important to create a medium, long-term vision and measure our advances in this regard. Therefore, and in the context of a joint strategy, the Forward partners should measure the evolution of the goals set by the question that the Forward has been a challenge to answers during the Forward initiatives, at many levels. In this stage, in order to continually engage the partners on the co-creation process under the construction of a joint strategy. The figure 7. challenges the Forward partners to reflect on contributions for the next roadmap steps per Workpackages.

Figure 7. Future scenarios, questions to gain insight on the Forward WP's

What are the possible scenarios that can come out of the implementation of a joint strategy; this is something that should be embodied in the ambition, reflected in the vision and be a starting point for a roadmap that integrates action plans. During the implementation of the Work-packages the strategy will be completed by the design of scenarios, this will allow the partners to along the work packages monitor the efficiency and adjustment the process. This process should be made within the WP7 (“Monitoring, evaluation and performance), and also as a joint process, were all partners from Forward, namely Work Package leaders, and OR’s can take in to their hands the follow-up of project and invest in strategic co-alignment of the OR’s R&I to ensure that Forward reach its vision and ambition.

Bibliography:

- SWD - “Communication from the committee to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, the Committee of the Regions and the European Investment Bank - A strengthened and renewed strategic partnership with the EU's outermost regions”, European Commission, Strasbourg, 24.10.2017; (source:http://www.cdep.ro/afaceri_europene/CE/2017/COM_2017_623_EN_ACTE_f.pdf)
- COM, “Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council amending in order to maintain the current limitations on the scope of aviation activities and to prepare for the implementation of a measure based on the global market from 2021”, amending Directive 2003/87/EC (2017), Strasbourg, February 207, (http://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-8-2017-0258_EN.html)
- Grant Agreement n° 824550/952727405, Forward project, Horizon 2020, January 2019
- Comparative analyses, WP2, Philippe Holstein, NEXA, Réunion Island (France), 2019
- COM, “Regulation of the European parliament and of the council On specific provisions for the European territorial cooperation goal (INTERREG) supported by the European regional development fund and external financing instruments”, Strasbourg, 29.5.2018
([http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/docs_autres_institutions/commission_europeenne/com/2018/0374/COM_COM\(2018\)0374_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/docs_autres_institutions/commission_europeenne/com/2018/0374/COM_COM(2018)0374_EN.pdf))
- Mutual Learning Event Report, Forward project, 2019
- Consolidated versions of the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) [2016] OJ C202/1.

Sites

- https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/era_fr
- <https://cor.europa.eu/>
- <https://aer.eu/>
- <https://cpmr.org/>
- https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/era_en
- https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cros/content/research-projects-under-framework-programmes-0_en

PART IV

Annexes

Annex I - Mapping tools and dashboards

To conduct their analysis, OR first collected data from database and interviews in mapping tools ("RDI mapping tool" and "FP participation") and produced dashboards ("Regional figures") gathering indicators of performance.

These tables are available online on the following links :

Name of the region	Links to mapping tools and dashboards
Azores	http://bit.ly/Forward-WP2-Azores
Canary islands	http://bit.ly/Forward-WP2-Canary
French Guiana	http://bit.ly/Forward-WP2-FrenchGuiana
Guadeloupe	http://bit.ly/Forward-WP2-Guadeloupe
La Réunion	http://bit.ly/Forward-WP2-LaReunion
Madeira	http://bit.ly/Forward-WP2-Madeira
Martinique	http://bit.ly/Forward-WP2-Martinique
Mayotte	http://bit.ly/Forward-WP2-Mayotte
Saint Martin	http://bit.ly/Forward-WP2-SaintMartin

Annex II - Quality report of the nine regional diagnoses

24/03/2020

forward

WP2 – State of progress of pending diagnoses

Nexa – Regional development and innovation agency - La Réunion

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824556.

Nexa - WP2 – Methodology

1

The slide features the 'forward' logo at the top left, which includes a stylized sun and a bird. Below it, the text 'WP2 – State of progress of pending diagnoses' is centered. Underneath, 'Nexa – Regional development and innovation agency - La Réunion' is written. A grid of 24 small logos representing various regional partners is displayed in the bottom right. The European Union flag and a funding notice are in the bottom left. The slide number '1' is at the bottom right.

Context

forward

The slide features the 'forward' logo at the bottom right. The European Union flag and a funding notice are in the bottom left. The slide number '1' is at the bottom right.

1

1. To respect WP2 deadlines, each region had to provide by November 29th 4 completed documents :
 - 3 excel files (FP participation; RDI Mapping; Regional figures)
 - 1 regional report covering the different sections described in the methodology.
2. On December 11th, the SC validated the integration of 5 diagnoses into deliverable 2.2. 4 regions were asked to complete their analysis : Guadeloupe, Guyane, Mayotte and St Martin.
3. The 4 regions were to deliver the actualized diagnoses by January 30th.
4. On February 13th, the 4 regions committed to provide the full analysis (report + excel files) by February 28th.
5. The only elements received were from Guyane.

Actualized documents received

	Guadeloupe	Guyane	Mayotte	Saint Martin
FP participation	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow
RDI Mapping	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow
Regional Figures	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow
Regional report	Green	Green	Green	Yellow

Elements needed

- Revised version of the regional figures
- Actualize the EU contribution obtained without the 15% principle
- Complete network analysis

NEXA - WP2 - Methodoly 12

Elements needed / next steps

- « Clean » the interviews in FP participation to avoid duplication
- Complete the analysis on regional R&I policies
- Organize a workshop
- Elaborate a more detailed analysis and action plan

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 801001

NEXA - WP2 - Methodology

Saint Martin

RDI Mapping

Period	Extensive and checked data	Corrections needed	No data provided
November 29th	7	1	3
January 31st	7	1	3

FP participation

Period	Extensive and checked data	Corrections needed	No data provided
November 29th	3	3	2
January 31st	3	3	2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 801001

Elements needed / next steps

- Complete the analysis on regional R&I policies
- Elaborate a more detailed analysis and action plan
- Translate the whole report in English

NEXA - WP2 - Methodology 18

Annex III - Summary of the mutual learning event report

From October 8 to 10th, the first mutual learning event of the FORWARD project took place in Brussels at the Canary Island Brussels Office, gathering 22 representative of the members of the project consortium from 8 European outermost regions (OR).

FORWARD is a European Coordination and Support Action funded under the H2020 Swafs 2018-2020 call. The aim of the project is to support European outermost regions to improve their research excellence and innovation capacities and develop their capacities to increase their participation in current and future European research and innovation Framework programmes (FP).

Organized under the workpackage 2 dedicated to the diagnostic of OR's R&I ecosystems and participation in FP, this event aimed at sharing knowledge and experiences among OR on the major obstacles and levers that influence their participation in FP, and at drafting a common vision and roadmap for a joint strategy to increase the participation of ORs in Framework programmes.

The mutual learning event began with a presentation of the main results of a comparative analysis which was built on the diagnoses performed by each region according to a common methodology, designed as a replicable approach to assess regional participation in FP and analyse the main determinants identified by the literature (quality of the European networks, performance of the regional innovation system, R&I organizations characteristics and policies, individual determinants). Such analysis based on the data provided by partners and European sources (CORDIS and Eurostat) proposed a state of play of the participation of the outermost regions in FP, a comparison with other regions that share close characteristics and an analysis of the main determinants that influence the participation.

Based on the results of the regional diagnosis and the comparative analysis, partners were then mobilized to design a common ambition for the OR: become the European worldwide network of living labs of global resilience (in a real open innovation playground mindset), by turning the critical challenges faced into innovative solutions in such fields as biodiversity conservation and restoration, energy transition, circular economy, multicultural society, tropical agroecology and biodiversity valorization, etc. This ambition will be achieved with, and contribute to, an increased integration in the European Research and Innovation Area, more FP projects and the participation to international value chains. To that end, the FORWARD project needs to foster political will and synergies between the outermost regions.

To turn the vision into a roadmap and capitalize on peer-learning, the participants discussed in small groups the main obstacles for an increased FP participation and collectively defined realistic & impactful levers that will be integrated in a common action plan for FORWARD and beyond.

- The work between OR continued with an in-depth exercise on two decisive levers: fostering OR's collaboration through interregional thematic groups, dedicated to the major research and innovation fields of expertise of the regions

- bridging research and policy making in OR. Participants were, once again, able to share their knowledge, experiences and vision of these key issues.

The results of the mutual learning event fed the final diagnosis of OR performance and the FORWARD joint strategy.

The full report is available online here : <http://bit.ly/FORWARD-WP2-MLEreport>

